

**INVESTIGATING THE DIMENSIONS OF
PERCEIVED ATTRIBUTIONS IN MAKING
SENSE OF FAILURE: AN EXPLORATORY
STUDY OF LEBANESE ENTREPRENEURS**

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Table of Contents

List of Figures	7
List of Tables	9
Abstract	10
Declaration	11
Acknowledgment	12
Dedication	12
Abbreviations	13
1 Chapter One: Introduction	14
1.1 Research Background	14
1.2 Research Context - Lebanon.....	15
1.3 Research Problem	17
1.4 Rationale for the Study	19
1.5 Research Aim and Objectives.....	20
1.6 Research Questions.....	21
1.7 Research Structure	22
2 Chapter Two: Learning Process from Failure	23
2.1 Introduction.....	23
2.2 Process of Learning from Failure	23
2.2.1 Defining Entrepreneurial Failure	24
2.2.1.1 Entrepreneurial Exit.....	25
2.2.2 Entrepreneurial Learning	26
2.3 Failure and Entrepreneurial Learning	28
2.3.1 Learning from Failure.....	28
2.3.1.1 Levels of Learning	29
2.3.2 Approaches of Entrepreneurial Learning.....	30
2.4 Timeframe of Reflection Outcomes	35
2.4.1 Aftermath of Failure	35
2.4.2 Long Term outcomes	37
2.4.2.1 Cognitive and Behavioural	37
2.5 Influencers of Learning from Failure.....	39
2.6 Challenges of Learning from Failure.....	41
2.7 Summary.....	43
3 Chapter Three: Attribution in Learning Process	46
3.1 Introduction.....	46
3.2 Attribution Theory in Reflecting on Failure	46

3.3	Coping with Failure	52
3.4	Dimensions of Attribution	58
3.4.1	Internal Dimensions	60
3.4.1.1	Rationalising Failure with Decision-Making.....	60
3.4.1.2	Entrepreneurial Competencies	64
3.4.1.3	Networks and Social Skills	67
3.4.1.4	Marketing Skills.....	70
3.4.1.5	Human Capital Management	72
3.4.2	External Dimensions.....	74
3.4.2.1	Finance.....	74
3.4.2.2	Government and Ecosystem	78
3.5	Summary.....	81
4	Chapter Four: Literature Gap.....	93
4.1	Introduction.....	93
4.2	Entrepreneurial Learning Frameworks	93
4.3	Contributions and Research Gaps.....	96
4.4	Research Conceptual Framework	99
5	Chapter Five: Research Methodology	102
5.1	Philosophical Stance	102
5.2	Approach to Theory Development	105
5.3	Data Collection	107
5.3.1	Qualitative Approach.....	107
5.3.2	Data Collection Techniques.....	110
5.3.2.1	MMR Adoption	110
5.3.2.2	Semi-structured Interviews	112
5.3.2.3	Narrative Inquiry	114
5.3.3	Data Collection Design.....	120
5.3.3.1	Semi-structured Interviews	120
5.3.3.2	Narratives.....	122
5.3.3.3	Pilot Study	122
5.3.3.4	Research Quality.....	123
5.4	Sampling.....	124
5.4.1	Sample composition.....	125
5.4.2	Sample Size	127
5.5	Qualitative Data analysis	130
5.5.1	Thematic Analysis	130
5.5.2	Narrative Analysis	131
5.6	Ethics	134

6	Chapter Six: Findings	135
6.1	Experts' Interviews.....	136
6.1.1	Demographics of Experts.....	137
6.1.2	Analytical Process of Interviews	138
6.1.2.1	Availability, Access, and Management of Funds	140
6.1.2.2	Entrepreneurial Competencies	143
6.1.2.3	Emphasis on Strong Networks.....	146
6.1.2.4	Ineffective and Insufficient Marketing	149
6.1.2.5	Availability and Ability of Human Capital.....	151
6.1.2.6	Unsupportive Ecosystem	153
6.2	Entrepreneurs' Narratives	156
6.2.1	Demographics of Entrepreneurs	160
6.2.2	Reflection Process on Failure	165
6.2.2.1	Stage 1: Establishing the Venture.....	167
6.2.2.1.1	Initial Entrepreneurial Motivations.....	168
6.2.2.1.2	Availability, Access, and Management of Funds	169
6.2.2.1.3	Level of Preparedness and Failure.....	173
6.2.2.2	Stage 2: Managing the Venture	175
6.2.2.2.1	Social Skills and Networks	176
6.2.2.2.2	Marketing: Planning and Execution.....	180
6.2.2.2.3	Capacity of Recruiting and Managing Human Capital.....	183
6.2.2.2.4	Role of Culture and Ecosystem on Persistence.....	188
6.2.2.3	Stage Three: Exiting the Venture.....	191
6.2.2.3.1	Motivation and Exit Decision	192
6.2.2.3.2	Ascriptions of Failure	196
6.2.2.4	Entrepreneurs' Responses to Failure	203
6.3	Summary.....	208
7	Chapter Seven: Discussion	214
7.1	Introduction.....	214
7.2	Reflection on Foundation Stage.....	216
7.3	Reflection on Survival Stage	217
7.3.1	Reflection on Individual Level	217
7.3.2	Reflection on Business Level	219
7.4	Reflection on Exit Stage	221
7.5	Emotional Reflection.....	222
7.6	Learning Generated	223
8	Chapter Eight: Conclusion.....	227
8.1	Introduction.....	227

8.2	Revisiting the Research Aim and Objectives	227
8.3	Contributions to Knowledge	228
8.3.1	Theoretical Implications	228
8.3.2	Practical Implications	229
8.4	Limitations of the Research	232
8.5	Potential Areas for Future Research	234
8.6	Reflection on the Doctorate Journey	236
	Bibliography	239
	Appendix A: Experts' Interview Guide	265
	Appendix B: Narrative Inquiry Guide	267
	Appendix C: Sample Thematic Analysis.....	269
	Appendix D: Sample Narrative Analysis.....	270
	Appendix E: Ethical Clearance.....	273
	Appendix F: Evaluation of Learning Frameworks	274

List of Figures

Figure 1: Levels of TEA Activity by income group (%).....	16
Figure 2: Main reasons for venture discontinuation in Lebanon	16
Figure 3: A summary of the various definitions of entrepreneurial learning.....	27
Figure 4: Experiential learning by Kolb (1984).....	31
Figure 5: Learning process according to life after failure.....	35
Figure 6: Problem-focused strategies	55
Figure 7: Emotion-focused strategies	56
Figure 8: Rationale for each reasoning mode	61
Figure 9: Four major areas of competencies.....	65
Figure 10: Four categories of entrepreneurs' competencies	66
Figure 11: Financial landscaping in Lebanon.....	77
Figure 12: Factors constraining entrepreneurial activity in Lebanon (%)	79
Figure 13: Self-perceptions of Lebanese adults in terms of capabilities and opportunities..	81
Figure 14: Research Conceptual Framework.....	101
Figure 15: Comparative diagram of the five main research philosophies	103
Figure 16: Contrasting the deductive approach with the inductive approach.....	106
Figure 17: Comparative analysis of qualitative and quantitative research methods.....	108
Figure 18: Qualitative Research Design	119
Figure 19: Process of formulating the interview questions	120
Figure 20: Classification of narrative analysis	132
Figure 21: Summary of the themes from the thematic analysis (I denotes internal, E denotes External)	140
Figure 22: Key findings of Section 6.1.2.1	143
Figure 23: Key findings of Section 6.1.2.2.....	146
Figure 24: Key findings of Section 6.1.2.3.....	149
Figure 25: Key findings of Section 6.1.2.4.....	150
Figure 26: Key findings of Section 6.1.2.5.....	153
Figure 27: Key findings of Section 6.1.2.6.....	155
Figure 28: Scheme outlining the heterogeneity of entrepreneurs interviewed	165
Figure 29: Nature of attributions of the lack of funds and their impact on the venture.....	172
Figure 30: Nature of attributions of the market study and their impact on the venture.....	174
Figure 31: Nature of attributions of the networking skills and their impact on the venture	179
Figure 32: Nature of attributions of the marketing function and their impact on the venture	183
Figure 33: Nature of attributions of the human capital and their impact on the venture	188
Figure 34: Comprehensive scheme of perceived internal attributions.....	212

Figure 35: Comprehensive scheme of perceived external attributions	213
Figure 36: Representation of the sequential process of Lebanese entrepreneurs' learning from failure	222
Figure 37: Comprehensive Learning Process from failure (CLP)	226

List of Tables

Table 1: Narrative Attributions.....	50
Table 2: Internal Attributions concluded by attribution studies	59
Table 3: External Attributions concluded by attributions studies.....	60
Table 4: Key contributions into the literature since 1999 (by chronological order).....	92
Table 5: Entrepreneurial learning models.....	96
Table 6: Categorisation of the relevant literature on learning from failure	97
Table 7: Detailed summary of the MMR design	111
Table 8: Guidelines for semi-structured interviews in qualitative studies.....	122
Table 9: Probabilistic versus non-probabilistic sampling.....	125
Table 10: Summary of qualitative studies on entrepreneurial learning from failure	128
Table 11: Criteria for selecting participants of both samples	130
Table 12: Process of Thematic Analysis.....	131
Table 13: Process of Narrative Analysis.....	133
Table 14: An informative summary of the interviewed experts	138
Table 15: Summary of findings from experts' interviews	156
Table 16: An informative summary of the demographics of entrepreneurs interviewed	164
Table 17: An informative summary of entrepreneurs.....	166
Table 18: Attributions of failure by each entrepreneur.....	202
Table 19: Comparative summary of experts' and entrepreneurs' attributions of failure.....	210

Abstract

By challenging the anti-failure bias and contributing to the theoretical territory of the attribution theory, this thesis develops a comprehensive process for entrepreneurial learning from failure. The practical implication of the findings suggests assisting entrepreneurs (current, failing, and nascent) in effectively anticipating and reflecting upon failure. Additionally, the process is suggested to enhance the level of institutional and private (accelerators and financiers) support provided to entrepreneurs; the implications of which may improve future opportunities of entrepreneurial success. Henceforth, exploring learning from failure is argued to impact the potential survival of future ventures, subsequently, revitalising the economic contribution of entrepreneurship. This learning process can be enhanced with the cognitive development of causal ascriptions for failure, which eventually impacts learning outcomes. However, the mechanism with which entrepreneurs make sense of failure, reflect on the journey, and transform experience into knowledge is still under-researched. More specifically, the cognitive process of failure attribution is under-explored, majorly in the context of developing economies, calling for a more insightful understanding on how entrepreneurs ascribe failure. Responding to the call for more thorough research in such cultural contexts, this study expands the understanding of the dimensions of failure attributions as perceived by entrepreneurs and the impact of these dimensions on learning outcomes in the Lebanese context.

The research adopted the exploratory interpretivism paradigm and collected data from interviews with industry experts first, followed by narratives of entrepreneurs using the qualitative multimethod approach. The holistic and categorical content analysis of narratives, preceded by the thematic analysis of interviews, unveiled how entrepreneurs ascribe failure by developing minor and major dimensions of each failure attribution. The findings have also revealed how each dimension impacts the learning from failure when accompanied by emotional resilience. The thesis concludes that exploring in-depth the dimensions of failure attributions significantly determines the level of learning generated. Moving beyond the simple categorisation of ascriptions as primary internal or external unveiled how learning may occur with each attribution at the individual, venture, and ecosystem levels. This has further accentuated that an internal major attribution of failure combined with a minor external attribution generated the highest levels of transformative and double-loop learning, emphasising the role of personal blame and responsibility on enhancing learning outcomes.

Keywords: attribution, entrepreneurship, reflection, sense-making, emotions, learning outcomes, failure, exit

Declaration

I hereby declare that no part of this work has been submitted for any other degree, neither at this university nor at any other institution of learning. As the author of this research, I own copyrights of this dissertation (including appendices) and has given the University of the West of Scotland the right to use such Copyright, including administration purposes. Any copies of this research shall be made only in conformity with the Copyright, Designs and Patents Act 1988 (as amended) and its regulations, or, the licensing agreements of UWS, wherever appropriate. All copies made should have this page.

I further declare that this research is completely my personal work and is, hence, based on my own efforts to conduct the research. I also declare that the process of collecting and presenting information has been conducted in conformity with academic policies and ethical behaviour.

Ghiwa A. Dandach

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Dedication

To my youngest sister, Farah, my precious dreamer whose eyes carry huge dreams and boundless potential for this world, and to my charming niece and nephew, Medina and Ali, my cherished twins, who filled our hearts with unprecedented happiness and love, and whose tiny hands will grow to write countless achievements,

I dedicate this work to you, to tell you to dream high and achieve even higher.

Abbreviations

AET	Affective Events Theory
BDL	Banque Du Liban [Central Bank of Lebanon]
BLOM	Banque du Liban et D'Outre Mer
CLP	Comprehensive Learning Process
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GEM	Global Entrepreneurship Monitor
MET	Ministry of Economy and Trade
MMR	Multimethod research
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
SCT	Social Cognitive Theory
SME	Small and Medium Enterprises
TA	Thematic Analysis
TEA	Total Early-stage Entrepreneurial Activity

“The secret of life is to fall seven times and to get up eight times”
– Paulo Coelho

1 Chapter One: Introduction

1.1 Research Background

Start-ups contribute significantly to the global economy (70% to international employment and 90% to local employment) (Page and Söderbom, 2015), but the rate of mortality of these ventures is worrying as the vast majority of entrepreneurs is failing (Turner and Endres, 2017). However, the extant understanding of these failures is still very basic (Wennberg and DeTienne, 2014), calling for more insightful studies on learning from failure (Walsh and Cunningham, 2017) as a worthy subject for future examination (Ucbasaran *et al.*, 2013). Therefore, the growing literature on understanding failure, although limited, expands the academic and practical comprehension of business failure and the process of learning from these failures (Benson and Han, 2011; Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015). However, the existing entrepreneurship research holds an anti-failure bias (Rasmus and Laguna, 2018), concentrating majorly on successful businesses. Learning does not only occur from successful endeavours, but also from failing ventures (Gong *et al.*, 2009).

Learning from failure improves the effectiveness of entrepreneurs' behaviours via correcting inappropriate practices and expanding knowledge and capabilities (Cope, 2011). Despite the increasing number of studies on failure, the process by which experience is translated into knowledge-learning is still incomplete: rather a compilation of scattered contributions with the absence of a definite system (Wei *et al.*, 2019). Therefore, exploring the business failure and its consequences, as well as the learning that emerges of it, exhibits a crucial need for future research, given its impact on future entrepreneurial activities (Boso *et al.*, 2019).

In examining the reflection on entrepreneurial failure, various learning theories were adopted, such as the social cognitive theory (SCT), experiential learning, configuration theory, organisational learning and population ecology (Wang and Chugh, 2014), with the experiential learning mostly adopted by recent research (Fust *et al.*, 2017). According to this theory, reflecting on failure enhances the individual stock of knowledge derived from learning from entrepreneurial experiences (Cope, 2005a; Politis, 2005), and is influenced by the personal reflection and direct action of

entrepreneurs (Politis and Gabrielsson, 2009). The critical nature of experiences affects the whole process of learning, mostly the resulting outcomes (Lattacher and Wdowiak, 2020). Consequently, the experiences that are critical or higher in level (Cope, 2003) result in deeper reflection, which may ultimately result in substantial behavioural and cognitive changes (Cope, 2003; Pittaway and Thorpe, 2012). Another commonly adopted theory in explaining the reflection of entrepreneurs on failure is the attribution theory (Heider, 1958; Weiner, 1985) that develops causal explanations for failure as perceived by entrepreneurs (Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015). This study, hence, builds on Eggers and Song's (2014) recommendation that future research should focus on understanding how the process of attribution affects learning outcomes, more specifically on "*the trade-off between trying to remedy the cause of the previous failure and the ability to learn from failure experience*" (Eggers and song, 2014, p. 29). Therefore, the focus of this study is on the processes with which entrepreneurs embrace their sense-making of previous experiences and identities, by generating narratives (Gartner, 2007) and creating attributions.

1.2 Research Context - Lebanon

Saleh (2014) highlighted the importance of SMEs (family businesses) for the Lebanese economy, given the high level of entrepreneurial initiatives as statistically reported by the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM). Measuring entrepreneurship levels in Lebanon according to the TEA (Total Early-stage Entrepreneurial Activity), GEM (2017) reported Lebanon the first for embracing TEA entrepreneurs within the Middle East region, and eighth internationally in 2017. According to statistics, Lebanese adults have exhibited a high tendency to entrepreneurship, as 38% of surveyed candidates reported their intention to pursue business ventures in a three-year time and more than 14% were already engaged in entrepreneurship (GEM, 2015). Entrepreneurship for Lebanon, like for any other country, constitutes the building block for the economy (Saleh, 2014), employing 72% of the national workforce (Mezher *et al.*, 2008) and contributing the most to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP).

Figure 1: Levels of TEA Activity by income group (%)

Source: GEM (2018)

Figure 2: Main reasons for venture discontinuation in Lebanon

Source: GEM (2016)

Nevertheless, only a few studies were conducted on entrepreneurship in the context of Lebanon and focused on examining: the barriers of entrepreneurship in Lebanon as psychological, political, and environmental (El Nemar *et al.*, 2016); the impact of the hybrid nature of governance and its corruption on entrepreneurship (Stel and Naude, 2016); statistically the level of entrepreneurial activity (GEM, 2017:2018); international entrepreneurship in Lebanon (Ahmed and Julian, 2012); the rooting causes behind failure (Mezher *et al.*, 2008); challenges and opportunities facing Lebanese entrepreneurs (Charafeddine, 2013); a roadmap for promoting and improving the activity level of entrepreneurship (MET, 2014); women entrepreneurship (Lichy *et al.*, 2020); social entrepreneurship (Jamali and Kreidie, 2014); and corporate entrepreneurship (Hejase *et al.*, 2014). Relying mostly on the quantitative approach in investigating the entrepreneurial context in Lebanon, no single study has so far explored the learning process of Lebanese entrepreneurs from failure or employed a narrative approach that embraces the perceptions of entrepreneurs. Therefore, the failure of Lebanese entrepreneurs needs to be more insightfully investigated in terms of attributions developed and the learning generated from their experiences.

1.3 Research Problem

Start-ups usually face a high exit rate in the first few years of their establishment (Page and Soderbom, 2015), justifying the focus of scholars on explaining the reasons for failure. However, this dominant concentration on the causes of failure diverts the emphasis from more insightful dimensions such as the learning dynamics. The process of entrepreneurial learning emerges from understanding entrepreneurial mistakes and errors (Cope, 2011). Henceforth, a need emerges to move beyond the failure causation inquiries (Cressy, 2006), to investigate learning from failure and its impact on future venturing activities (Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015). If exploited properly, the learning process of entrepreneurs from failure provides a rich addition to their stock of knowledge and may facilitate and enhance the opportunities and survival of another entrepreneurial emergence (Boso *et al.*, 2019). In other cases, it assists in dealing with subsequent critical occurrences and other professional contexts (Lattacher and Wdowiak, 2020).

Extant research on entrepreneurial failure investigated aspects of the learning process via qualitative studies that specialised in single factors, such as the personal stock of knowledge (Politis, 2005; Huovinen and Tihula, 2008; Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015), personal emotions (Shepherd, 2003; Shepherd *et al.*, 2009; Dias and Teixeira, 2017), the impact of traits such as narcissism (Liu *et al.*, 2019) and attribution of failure to specific factors (Eggers and Song, 2014; Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015; Walsh and Cunningham, 2017). However, this focused and specialised territory resulted in fragmenting the field (Nogueira, 2019) and limiting the development of entrepreneurial research, given the difficulty of continuing the work of other researchers in a way that identifies directions for future research (Lattacher and Wdowiak, 2020). Additionally, research on entrepreneurial failure is still considered a newly emergent field, although the number of studies in this field has increased recently (Lattacher and Wdowiak, 2020). However, with the need to answer many unanswered questions yet, research on the subject of entrepreneurial failure still constitutes an interesting discussion, intending to improve the academic and practical comprehension of failure and its impact on entrepreneurial learning (McGrath, 1999; Ucbasaran *et al.*, 2013). Eventually, researching failure provides a more dynamic perspective on the entrepreneurial field (Cope, 2005).

As this learning process does not occur automatically (Shepherd, 2003), it depends significantly on the sense-making undertaken by entrepreneurs (Kolb, 1984), and the ascribed explanations developed to rationalise failure (Mandl *et al.*, 2016). However, the majority of research on learning from failure did not consider how the ascriptions of failure by entrepreneurs affect this learning process and its outcomes (Cardon *et al.*, 2011; Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015). Therefore, adding to the shortage in empirical studies that focus on attributions on the entrepreneur's level (Ucbasaran *et al.*, 2013; Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015), this study focuses on investigating the failure attributions developed by entrepreneurs in reflecting on failure, and the impact of its dimensions on learning outcomes. Henceforth, the interest of this research paper will focus on the learning process (in terms of attributions), content and outcomes from entrepreneurial failure, classified as a critical event of the entrepreneurs' journeys (Espinoza-Benavides and Diaz, 2019).

1.4 Rationale for the Study

The relevance of exploring learning from failure emerges from its improvement of the entrepreneurs' stock of knowledge about their personalities, ventures, connections established with the outer environment, and ability to deal with critical events (Boso *et al.*, 2019). These learning opportunities are therefore argued to improve the performance of subsequent venturing (Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015; Boso *et al.*, 2019). However, the focus of these studies on the outcomes of the learning process from failure has overlooked the process itself (Fang He *et al.*, 2018). The outcomes argued to result from failure will only generate from an active, engaging, and deliberate learning process that transforms knowledge from previous experiences of failure (Fang He *et al.*, 2018). Henceforth, the study of learning behaviours constitutes a critical step to achieve its perceived outcomes on subsequent entrepreneurial activities (Lin *et al.*, 2019). As a result, understanding the impact of individual learning on entrepreneurial behaviour necessitates a thorough study of the ways with which entrepreneurs develop entrepreneurial approaches and attitudes from failure.

Entrepreneurial learning has been perceived as a constant and continuous process, during which entrepreneurs evolve their identities by narrating these critical experiences (Bruner, 1990; Weick, 1995). Despite revealing the manner with which entrepreneurial minds work with regards to information (from a cognitive perspective), the nature and process of entrepreneurial learning in an academic format is still under-researched, calling for the employment of a more socially constructive approach that collects narratives (Gergen, 1994). Through narratives, entrepreneurs try to retrieve meanings from their past experiences (Harre and Gillett, 1994), to provoke profound insights into the entrepreneurial experience (Steyaert and Bouwen, 1997). When entrepreneurs account for this learning experience using their own discourse, their subjective reflection provides an in-depth perspective of their learning (Rae and Carswell, 2000). In parallel, the cognitive theory of learning, contributing to the understanding of entrepreneurial learning, considered the entrepreneurial brain as a processing system of information (Gagne, 1977; Rae and Carswell, 2000). According to this theory, entrepreneurs acquire, store, and use knowledge as a problem-solving process that defines operational learning through entrepreneurial experience (Young and Sexton, 1997). Similarly, the theory of social cognition as

developed by Bandura (1986) had its contribution to understanding the learning process of entrepreneurs.

Despite these contributions onto the subject of learning from failure (Minniti and Bygrave, 2001; Cope, 2005; Parker, 2013), the impact of failure attribution into the proceedings of learning (Cardon *et al.*, 2011; Jenkins, 2012; Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015), the process of attribution (Kelley and Michela, 1980; Brockner, 2002) and the impact of both, attribution and learning, on the success of regenerative entrepreneurship (Parker, 2013; Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015) are still under-researched. Therefore, this study aims to address this gap by exploring the learning process of entrepreneurs in terms of attributions, and the impact of the nature and dimensions of these ascriptions on the reflection process on failure. Another apparent gap in the conceptual territory of business failure and entrepreneurial learning is that a significant portion of research has been conducted in the context of developed countries, overlooking the turbulence in the developing contexts and their impact on the sustainability and growth of start-ups (Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015). As a result, the Lebanese context for this study will add to the scarce conceptual territory of entrepreneurial reflection on failure in developing contexts.

1.5 Research Aim and Objectives

This study aims to explore in-depth how entrepreneurs develop failure attributions (Homsma *et al.*, 2007) during the process of reflecting on failure, in order to understand the impact of these attributions and their dimensions on the expected learning outcomes. The purpose of such an exploration is not to identify the actual reasons for failure, but rather to understand the various ascriptions of failure as perceived by entrepreneurs. Consequently, this study expands the work of Yamakawa and Cardon (2015), Yamakawa *et al.* (2015) and Walsh and Cunningham (2017) by uncovering the minor and major attributions of failure, beyond the notion of primary attributions. The study then argues that the in-depth expansion of the dimensions of attributions is suggested to promote further the understanding of the various learning outcomes generated from each level of attribution. The exploration of these processes led to the formulation of a comprehensive entrepreneurial learning model from failure. Additionally, the process developed provides practical implications to entrepreneurs, institutions and the private sector (mostly financing organisations) on the importance

and relevance to understand entrepreneurs' individual perceptions of failure, argued to enhance the future sustainability and survival of subsequent ventures (Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015).

Henceforth, the researcher has defined the following objectives to achieve the above-mentioned aim:

- a- To examine the nature and association between entrepreneurial failure, exit and learning;
- b- To understand the relationship between the reflection process on failure and entrepreneurial learning;
- c- To examine the role of attribution in the reflection process on entrepreneurial failure;
- d- To explore the mechanism with which entrepreneurs develop failure ascriptions with respect to internal and external factors by employing cognitive attributions; and
- e- To investigate the impact of expanding the dimensions of attributions on the process of reflecting on failure and on the outcomes of learning generated.

1.6 Research Questions

In order to accomplish the specific aim and objectives highlighted above, the following research questions will be addressed:

- a- How does the experience of failure generate entrepreneurial learning? (How do entrepreneurs process learning from failure?)
- b- What levels of learning outcomes are generated by the sense-making/reflection process of entrepreneurs of the failure experience?
- c- What is the impact of failure attributions as perceived by entrepreneurs on their reflection and learning processes?
- d- How do entrepreneurs ascribe failure to internal and external factors by employing cognitive attributions?
- e- How can the understanding of entrepreneurial learning (outcomes) be enhanced by insightfully expanding on the dimensions of the entrepreneurial attribution approach (process)?

1.7 Research Structure

This research is organised into eight main chapters, divided conceptually into two main parts: the theoretical part and the practical part. The first part involves Chapters 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5, as the researcher was founding a sound, theoretical base for the study before moving into the practical part. The second part involving the rest of the chapters constitutes the processes of collecting, analysing, and discussing the empirical data in relation to the literature. Therefore, the study is structured as follows:

Chapter 1: presents a background on the research, the rationale for the study, the research context and problem, the research aim, objectives and questions, and the structure of the study.

Chapter 2: examines the extant literature on the process of entrepreneurial learning from failure in relevance to the first two research questions.

Chapter 3: discusses the attribution theory as an essential part of the learning process, in terms of internal and external dimensions in relevance to the third research question.

Chapter 4: evaluates the learning models developed and highlights the knowledge gaps in the literature.

Chapter 5: justifies the methodology adopted in this study in detail, emphasising on the relevance of adopting the interpretivism exploratory paradigm and the qualitative multi-method approach in collecting and analysing the data.

Chapter 6: analyses and interprets the primary data collected through the in-depth interviews of experts and the narratives of entrepreneurs. The analysis aims into answering the last two research questions and achieving the aim of the study.

Chapter 7: presents the discussion of the findings, by linking inferences from the literature review, leading to the development of the entrepreneurial learning model.

Chapter 8: summarises the study, extracts conclusions, highlights the contributions of this research, acknowledges its limitations, underlines its practical implications, and offers recommendations for future research.

“It’s fine to celebrate success, but it is more important to heed the lessons of failure” – Bill Gates

2 Chapter Two: Learning Process from Failure

2.1 Introduction

This Chapter of the literature review considers the learning process from failure by focusing on the elements of this process, the various approaches developed to explain learning, the definition of failure adopted by this study, the learning outcomes from making sense of failure, and the challenges and influencers for achieving these outcomes.

The field of entrepreneurial learning, though not new in concept and been attracting researchers’ attention since the 1980s, has in fact started to emerge more insightfully over the last fifteen years. Henceforth, the researcher has considered the time span of the last fifteen years to analyse the key contributions onto the field, given that research on entrepreneurial failure has emerged more than 15 years ago, with an emphasised focus since 2015 (Lattacher and Wdowiak, 2020). The earlier significant contributions to the field were presented as well, as these form a robust ground for further explorations, and establish a solid base for defining and understanding the construct of entrepreneurial learning from failure.

2.2 Process of Learning from Failure

In favour of researching failure rather than success (as a result of the anti-failure bias in entrepreneurial research) (McGrath, 1999; Peng *et al.*, 2010; Razmus and Laguna, 2018), Ellis *et al.* (2005) believed that learning from success confirms only extant theories and assumptions, whereas failure urges the need to enrich existing knowledge and beliefs (Cope, 2011). Learning from failure occurs when entrepreneurs have gone through trials and errors, testing themselves in solving problems and exploring solutions (Cope, 2003). Just as failure has its own preconditions to occur (Pretorius, 2008), learning has also failure as a prerequisite to reaching a fundamental form that re-shapes entrepreneurs’ cognition (Cope, 2003). Failure may hold various definitions according to the criterion of evaluation; hence, the next subsection will outline the definition adopted in this study.

2.2.1 Defining Entrepreneurial Failure

Failure had been defined differently in various studies. Cope (2011) and other earlier scholars (McGrath, 1999; Politis and Gabrielsson, 2009) have defined failure as “*the termination of a business that has fallen short of its goals [...] thereby failing to satisfy principle shareholders’ expectations*” (Cope, 2011, p.4). Consequently, the exploration of entrepreneurial failure depends on the objective or the subjective lenses (or criteria) adopted by researchers to judge the failure: either objectively, through the economic ability of the venture to sustain (Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015); or subjectively, through entrepreneurial goals and expectations versus facts (Jenkins and McKelvie, 2016), which may happen even when the business is economically viable and profitable (Fang He *et al.*, 2018). As this study focuses on understanding the failure experience as lived by entrepreneurs through adopting a qualitative narrative approach, a more comprehensive definition that involves both criteria, the financial struggle and the goals of the main shareholders, will be adopted. Given the difficulty to find respondents matching one criterion in the designated context under study, this research will define failure as the termination of a business venture that either did not achieve the initial goals of its main shareholders (entrepreneurs) or has not been economically viable.

According to this definition, the failing notion of ventures involves the closure of businesses as decided by entrepreneurs rather than a bankrupt situation¹. These decisions could have resulted from a struggle in financial sustainability, in growth potential or inapplicability of the business idea. Therefore, the adoption of this definition of failure necessitates a connecting discussion to the exit decision undertaken by entrepreneurs. Given the direction of this study towards failure as a decision taken by the entrepreneur, the researcher agrees with Coad’s (2014) argument that the word failure is too pejorative to be used in researching entrepreneurial failure, and hence, the word death is more reflective. Therefore, even when used throughout this research, the notion of failure does not mean that the business was a failing project for the whole period of its existence (Coad, 2014).

¹ Excluding the bankruptcy definition of failure relates to the dominance of the informal economy for business ventures (more will be elaborated in Chapters 5 and 6). The informal economy in Lebanon is a stand-alone case that combines perspectives from the old and new definition of informal economy, mainly including a wide range of informal occupations rather than simple street vendors or illegal activities (Rossis, 2011).

2.2.1.1 Entrepreneurial Exit

The exit decision impacts the economic environment of any country; hence, scholars have focused on understanding the entrepreneurial exit and its linkage with entrepreneurial learning (DeTienne, 2010). Historically, entrepreneurial exit was considered as an indication of failure, while business continuation indicates entrepreneurial success (Brudler *et al.*, 1992). However, not all continuing ventures imply being economically successful (van Witteloostuijn, 1998), and similarly, many exits cannot be judged as an outcome of a failing venture (McGrath, 2006; Coad, 2014). Consequently, the approach to understanding the exit decision may be rather explained as a career choice (utility maximization theory), or as insolvency of an earlier investment (prospect theory).

Exit may be conceptualised with a utility-maximisation perspective, where entrepreneurial exit may be defined as a resolution for the venture's opportunity costs that have excessively increased (Wennberg *et al.*, 2010). In this case, entrepreneurial exit is a career choice (Becker, 1964), where entrepreneurs seek to optimise the returns from their skills (Wennberg *et al.*, 2010). In parallel, following the prospect theory (Kahneman and Tversky, 2013), entrepreneurial exit may be the result of a venture liquidation, when entrepreneurs assess their ventures' profitability with reference points that weigh the gains versus the losses (Parastuty *et al.*, 2016). From a financial behavioural perspective, entrepreneurs do not always seek to maximise utility, but mostly care about short-term profits even when the long-term profits are greater, hence called 'hyperbolic discounters' (Grenadier and Wang, 2007). Other forms of exit may include discontinuation or stewardship (selling it to another individual) (DeTienne *et al.*, 2015).

Entrepreneurial exit cannot be detached from entrepreneurial decision-making, which embraces two main issues: assessing the opportunities for the pursuit of business ventures; and adopting the entrepreneurial career, including the decision to exit and terminate this career. Under this aspect, Shepherd and Patzelt (2017) argued that organisational traits such as success, employees, and associated identity affect entrepreneurs' decision to exit business ventures (either by discontinuation of the venture or by selling the shares) (DeTienne, 2010). Nevertheless, other reasons (such as linkage of business to personal identity) may also influence the entrepreneurs' exit

decision, development of an exit plan, and impact of this decision on their careers and/or lives (Shepherd and Patzelt, 2017). Among these factors comes the initial motivations of entrepreneurs to pursue an entrepreneurial career. Though Parastuty *et al.* (2016) did not find any clear connection, initial motivations are suggested to affect the level of persistence of entrepreneurs (DeTienne *et al.*, 2008). Additionally, these motivations for venture creation impact the entrepreneurs' mode and exit plan. More specifically, entrepreneurs with aspirations for growth tend to develop exit plans (i.e. creating new ventures) before exiting their current venture (DeTienne, 2010). Such factors, therefore, affect the probability, timing, and mode of entrepreneurial exit. Subsequent to presenting the connection between the entrepreneurial exit and business failure, and how the decision taken by the entrepreneurs to exit the venture leads to the notion of business failure, the following section moves into defining entrepreneurial learning and its levels.

2.2.2 Entrepreneurial Learning

Researchers have attempted to define entrepreneurial learning according to its purpose and nature. The most popular and common distinction was the first attempt undertaken by Argyris and Schon (1978): the adaptive (single-loop) learning that occurs frequently, and the corrective (double-loop) learning that creates new theories of actions, and forces entrepreneurs to re-evaluate their usual behaviours (Cope, 2003). All definitions, despite the varying dualist terminology adopted, distinguished between a lower level of learning and a higher level of learning. The former implies the repetition of past actions, whereas the latter assists in developing new actions (Fiol and Lyles, 1985). Further definitions and elaborations emerged throughout the years by various researchers, who contributed to the development of this field as shown in Figure 3 below. Though transformative and double-loop learnings are considered higher-order learning, both terms still differ in essence, not in purpose. Transformative learning induces a modified understanding of the self and thus has a personal aspect; whereas double-loop learning implies a reflective understanding of the business processes and plans and thus, has an organisational perspective (Cope, 2003).

Contributing Theorist(s)	Lower-level learning	Higher-level learning
Gibb (1995)	Learning in order to cope with change and survive	Learning that involves the capacity to 'bring forward' experience
Huber (1991)	Learning within a 'frame of reference'	Learning a new 'frame of reference'
Argyris and Schön (1978)	'Single-loop' learning regards routine, immediate tasks	'Double-loop' learning regards the questioning of underlying values which guide action; implies an awareness of long-range outcomes
Senge (1990)	'Adaptive' learning involves coping with the current environment in new and better ways (cited in Sadler-Smith et al., 1999) ^a	'Generative' learning moves beyond adaptation, requiring individuals and organizations to develop new ways of looking at the world (cited Sadler-Smith et al., 1999)
Mezirow (1990, 1991)	'Instrumental' learning is involved in task-oriented problem solving—how to do something or how to perform. Regards developing an understanding of the procedural assumptions guiding the problem-solving process	'Transformative' learning has the capacity to transform an individual's 'meaning perspectives'—perceptual and conceptual frameworks that form, limit and distort how individuals think, believe, feel and what, when and why they learn
Pask (1976)	' <i>Serialist</i> ' strategy involves detailed, step-by-step approach from one idea to the next without necessarily considering the whole picture	' <i>Wholist</i> ' strategy involves learning in relation to the whole
Fiol and Lyles (1985)	Occurs through repetition and routine, short-term outcomes	Has long-term effects; more of a cognitive process that involves skill development and new insights
Appelbaum and Goransson (1997)	'Adaptive' learning involves more mundane, everyday, incremental learning	'Transformational' learning involves radical change; learning that requires a shift in 'mindset'

Figure 3: A summary of the various definitions of entrepreneurial learning

Source: Cope (2003)

This research concentrates on both of these types of higher-level of learning, due to their impact on shaping and modelling the process and outcomes of entrepreneurial learning. Such higher levels of learning require first reflecting on failure and making sense of the experience, as discussed in the next section.

2.3 Failure and Entrepreneurial Learning

Extant research has explored entrepreneurial failure from numerical, psychological (Artinger and Powell, 2015) lenses and resulting behaviours (Politis and Gabrielsson, 2009) perspective, suggesting that the failure experience may generate knowledge that guides entrepreneurial decisions in pursuing future business ventures (Shepherd, 2003; Mantere *et al.*, 2013; Ucbasaran *et al.*, 2013; Jenkins *et al.*, 2014; Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015). The next sections will explain how learning is generated from failure and the various approaches for understanding this process.

2.3.1 Learning from Failure

The learning process from failure cannot be described as planned learning, as this form of learning occurs with pre-determined learning goals and methods. On the contrary, emergent learning, as in the context of entrepreneurial failure, allows entrepreneurs to reflect on their experiences and develop a new understanding (Williams, 2001), especially in uncertain and unpredictable environments (Shane and Venkataraman, 2000). The engagement of entrepreneurs in emergent learning encourages a deep reflection and analysis on the actions taken previously, in order to understand how the failure occurred (Ucbasaran *et al.*, 2010:2013). The high level of learning expected to result, hence, necessitates a deep evaluation of prior decisions and behaviours (Shepherd, 2003).

Standing out differently from the planned learning, much of entrepreneurial learning is usually unplanned and experiential by nature, which can happen through an active and complex reflection. Thus, learning is not automatic; it requires a curious soul and an active approach with the purpose to learn from failure (Pretorius and Le Roux, 2011). This process allows entrepreneurs to understand more effectively themselves and their experiences, for more informed decisions and pursuits in the future (Rae, 2013). Strategically, the failure experience induces learning on the effectiveness of strategies adopted, and the need in the future to change the previously implemented options. This change stems from the entrepreneurs' transformation in their understanding and perceptions of the environment and existing opportunities (Lin *et al.*, 2019). More specifically, by experiencing failure, entrepreneurs shake their commonly embraced assumptions, mental models, extant beliefs, and frames of references that normally direct their behaviours. This radical inquiry of the

entrepreneurs' blind spots generates a higher form of reflective learning than success would do (Cope, 2011). On another level, entrepreneurs who experience failure tend to exhibit more positive attitudes towards it (Politis and Gabrielsson, 2009), and feel motivated as well as prepared for another business endeavour (Stokes and Blackburn, 2002). However, it is significant to emphasise at this stage that the learning process of entrepreneurs is a constant and continuous process over the daily usual management experience of ventures, rather than the strict result of critical events such as failure (Hines and Thorpe, 1995; Costello, 1996).

Entrepreneurial learning from failure can be described as a journey of three stages: reflection on aftermath costs, critical reflection, and reflexive action (Cardon and McGrath, 1999). In the first stage, entrepreneurs seek to remove the emotional pain resulting from the social, financial, and psychological costs associated with failure. In the second stage, the focus of entrepreneurs is directed into making sense of and learning from failure, before moving to the last stage where entrepreneurs recover and consequently employ behavioural and cognitive processes to pursue and assess new venturing opportunities. The effectiveness and success of the last stage therefore depend on the criticality of the first two stages (Dias and Martens, 2019). Henceforth, this research will emphasise the stages preceding the reflexive action, whilst recognising the argument that entrepreneurial learning cannot be completed without the practical implementation of that generated knowledge (Shepherd, 2003). Both reflection stages trigger learning at various levels, with the aim to enhance the entrepreneurial profile post-failure.

2.3.1.1 Levels of Learning

As argued by Cope (2005), entrepreneurial learning can occur at four main levels: personal; venture; networks and relationships; and venture management. At the personal level, failure provides an opportunity for a deep, transformative learning about weaknesses, beliefs, skills, strengths, and attitudes, as well as areas for improvement (Walsh and Cunningham, 2017). More specifically, in learning about themselves, entrepreneurs enhance their managerial capabilities including know-how skills, tactical and theoretical knowledge, and behavioural attitudes (D'Amelio, 2011), and develop a more "*resilient behaviour and a proactive attitude*" (Dias and Martens, 2019, p. 117). At the venture level, the entrepreneur seeks to understand the reasons for failure, by assessing the strengths and weaknesses of the venture (Cope,

2005). This learning level about the business involves evaluating the strengths of the venture, while recognising the need to separate between the individual identity as a person, and the entrepreneurial identity as a founder (Ucbasaran *et al.*, 2013).

At the social level, failure allows entrepreneurs to reflect on the type and management of networks and relationships, whether within or outside the business (Cope, 2005). As part of reflecting on networks, entrepreneurs tend to share the meaning created from the experience with several stakeholders, which involves conflicts with partners (Rae, 2004; Dias and Martens, 2019). Finally, at the venture management level, entrepreneurs overcome failure and acquire the necessary skills for managing business ventures (Cope, 2005).

The initial three categories of learning lead to the generation of knowledge in the fourth category (business management), in terms of developing more awareness, knowledge and maturity in reacting to critical incidents (Walsh and Cunningham, 2017). This learning process is argued to be incomplete if the knowledge acquired is not implemented in a new business context (Shepherd, 2003). This re-entry allows for a greater understanding of the learning process acquired from the previous entrepreneurial experience (whether a success or a failure), as entrepreneurs are very likely to start new ventures (Nielsen and Sarasvathy, 2011). Emphasising on the relevance of investigating the subsequent implementation of knowledge developed from failure in the shape of new venturing, the discussion of subsequent venturing will be beyond the scope of this study, limited to re-engagement rather than an assessment of the performance of these ventures recommended by Lin *et al.* (2019). Exploring the reflection process of entrepreneurs requires an understanding of the various approaches adopted in explaining the sense-making mechanism, as will be explained next.

2.3.2 Approaches of Entrepreneurial Learning

Entrepreneurial learning from failure was investigated through various theories from the psychology disciplinary starting with the cognitive approach (i.e., Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015). This approach in exploring entrepreneurial learning has had its contribution into the field, yet, limited by narrowing the learning process to the ‘processing of information’ concept (Gagne, 1977; Bandura, 1986). Following a more social approach, the experiential and social theories of entrepreneurial learning (Kolb,

1984; Mumford, 1995) integrated action and social practice into the conceptualisation of learning through language and discourse (Harre, 1989). A recognisable theory of learning was later developed by Wenger (1998), who integrated the dimensions of “*meaning, practice, identity and community*” (Rae, 2005, p. 324), and represented a solid foundation that

“*accommodates social participation and human action as well as cognition, enabling advanced learning theory to be applied to entrepreneurship. It also enables progression from individual conceptions of entrepreneurial learning*” (Rae, 2005, p. 325).

This integration of psychology into the study of entrepreneurship has proposed three main sources for learning (Petkova, 2008): memorising the information needed subsequent to training or educational context (i.e. Glaser and Bassok, 1989), which follows the concept of planned learning (Williams, 2001); learning by repeating the most effective and efficient actions and decisions (i.e. March, 1991), which relates to the concept of exploitation (Minniti and Bygrave, 2001); or replacing wrong information with more correct ones, subsequent to a negative evaluation (i.e. Stiso and Payne, 2007). Out of these, the most influential and considerate source is the learning by doing in accordance with the experiential learning theory (Kolb, 1984), a widely common and famous approach in the field of entrepreneurial learning.

The experiential learning theory by Kolb (1984) involves four stages and constitutes a significant assistive theoretical framework in comprehending the learning mechanism of entrepreneurs (Morris *et al.*, 2012). The first stage defined as the *concrete experience* involves the initial reactions of the learner (in this case the entrepreneur) to a significant experience, setting the stage for the learning process.

Figure 4: Experiential learning by Kolb (1984)

Source: Lattacher and Wdowiak (2020)

The notion of experience *per se* has to bear some level of significance to the subject (the entrepreneur) (Hegel, 1953). This initial assessment of the experience with the existing abstract concepts allows for a deeper evaluation in the second stage, *reflective observation*, also considered as the most extreme challenge for learners. The

deliberate and multi-angled nature of this stage adds to the challenge (Duley, 1981), before reaching a deep sense of the event and its outcomes, usually achieved in the third stage of *abstract conceptualisation*. Through this stage, individuals employ creativity in rationalising the experience or the event and develop new beliefs and attitudes (Politis and Gabrielsson, 2009). These developed theories are therefore implemented at the final stage of *active experimentation* for testing their adequacy. This can create another learning process if an unexpected outcome or experience emerges (Kolb, 1984), giving this process the notion of a cycle rather than a sequence (Kolb and Kolb, 2018). The adoption of cognition in the transformation mechanism of Kolb's (1984) experiential process improves the theoretical, as well as the practical understanding, of entrepreneurial learning from failure. Each entrepreneur's cognitive processes impact their capacity in transforming failure into knowledge (Mueller and Shepherd, 2016). However, despite its influential contribution to the field of entrepreneurial learning, the experiential theory of learning reflects only on few factors that led to the failure, besides decontextualizing the learning process (Politis, 2005).

In exploring the process of making sense from failure, researchers (Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015; Walsh and Cunningham, 2017; Fang He *et al.*, 2018) sought to understand the entrepreneurs' cognitive process of transforming experience into knowledge, via either exploration or exploitation. The selection of one process over the other depends to a great extent on the level of experience of entrepreneurs. More specifically, entrepreneurs may either adopt the same or similar actions taken before, hence, exploiting their pre-existent knowledge; or might take completely different actions (Minniti and Bygrave, 2001). Being confronted with various experiences and situations, entrepreneurs have to decide on courses of action and thoughts connected to one of these two distinct, yet correlated modes (March, 1991). By implementing the exploitation mode, entrepreneurs refine and re-implement the knowledge acquired from previous experience, thus building higher credibility in these experiences. On the other hand, the adoption of exploration creates a variety in these experiences, motivating entrepreneurs to explore new prospects (Holmqvist, 2000).

The predominance of one mode of transformation over the other is essentially impacted by three main factors: the consequences of prior entrepreneurial experiences

(Minniti and Bygrave, 2001); the principal underlying logic (Sarasvathy, 2001); and the career orientation and motivation (Katz, 1994). The previous experience of entrepreneurs, if successful, highlights the judgment that actions taken or decisions made previously were successful, hence, entrepreneurs tend to replicate them. However, in the case of failure, entrepreneurs tend to avoid the decisions that led to failure (Minniti and Bygrave, 2001; Politis, 2005). The trade-off between both modes is the tolerance towards the degree of specialisation. In other words, the exploitation allows for a higher degree of specialisation, but at the cost of diminished exploration and the opposite is true (Cohen and Levinthal, 1990). Therefore, no mode is considered superior to the other, as both mechanisms are deemed necessary for the most effective learning, within the constraints of the limited resources (March, 1991). Henceforth, the predominant mode of individuals explains the variance in entrepreneurial knowledge developed by two entrepreneurs possessing the same exact nature and quality of experience (Politis, 2005).

Behaviourism is also another early approach adopted for the investigation of entrepreneurial learning from failure. By examining the behavioural decision-making of entrepreneurs, Rae (2004) adopted the concept of practical theories of behaviour under the social constructivism approach. These practical accounts, emerging from entrepreneurs' success stories, have expanded the understanding of entrepreneurial learning, by linking theoretical knowledge to entrepreneurial action (Rae, 2004). This approach assists in understanding how entrepreneurs generate meanings from their experiences and reflect on their previous actions (Shotter, 1993; 1995). Therefore, the significance of these theories lies in the entrepreneurs' establishment of connections between their lives and their courses of action, while accounting for their behaviour and decision-making (Rae, 2004). However, these theories are bounded to the practitioner's experiences, in other words, to specific cases. Therefore, Rae (2004) has proposed the concept of practice-based theories to construct more general findings and theories that "*retain the qualities of practicality and of being formed from and relevant to lived experience, yet, which are also useful and valid in a scholarly sense*" (Rae, 2004, p. 196). An interesting note on this approach is the intuitiveness and intangibility of these theories in entrepreneurs' minds until explicitly produced through discussion. Building on this concept that was previously applied to successful

experiences, the analysis of data later in this study will borrow this notion to generate practice-based attributions from the individual cases.

A third perspective for the study of entrepreneurial learning from failure involves the affective events theory (AET), arguing that entrepreneurs seem to exhibit different emotional responses to failure. These differences originate from the individual dispositional traits, mainly the level of activating emotional responses (negativity versus positivity) and the personal capability to control these emotional responses (Fang He *et al.*, 2018). Interestingly, though it was argued that a certain level of homogeneity exists for personal characteristics among entrepreneurs (e.g., optimism, confidence, passion, higher dispositional positive affect) (Baron *et al.*, 2012), a substantial difference still exists in their propensity to control the affective responses (Shepherd, 2009), as will be elaborated in the next Chapter, Section 3.3.

Reflecting on failure is a critical step for the learning process to occur, especially with the crucial deliberate and voluntary action of entrepreneurs (Lattacher and Wdowiak, 2020). In reflecting on their actions and the failure, entrepreneurs consequently identify weaknesses to improve and capabilities to enhance. Among these capabilities is the counterfactual thinking, which implies a retrospective thinking that speculates different outcomes for adopting different behaviours in a past event (Baron, 2004). Yamakawa *et al.* (2015) argued that the relationship between internal ascriptions of failure and counterfactual thinking is direct and positive. More specifically, entrepreneurs who attribute failure to their behaviours and decisions are more likely to reflect on their mistakes and the possible behaviours that could have been taken to correct them. When the problems reflected on are perceived to be solvable, counterfactual thinking may assist entrepreneurs in developing useful business strategies with promising outcomes (Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015). Interested in investigating the reflection process with which entrepreneurs cognitively ascribe failure, this study will adopt the cognitive theory in understanding the learning from failure. Among the cognitive approaches, this research will adopt the attribution theory (as elaborated in the next Chapter) to understand the resulting learning outcomes. However, these outcomes vary according to the time elapsing after failure and range from the short-term to the long-term, as will be discussed in the next section.

2.4 Timeframe of Reflection Outcomes

The learning process from failure depends on the stages and timeframes of the entrepreneurs' lives after failure: immediately after failure (called the aftermath); a valuable period after failure (sense-making and/or reflection); and the future frame of long-term consequences (on the individual level – outcomes) (Ucbasaran *et al.*, 2013), as shown in Figure 5 below.

Figure 5: Learning process according to life after failure

Source: Dias and Teixeira (2017)

2.4.1 Aftermath of Failure

During the aftermath, psychological, financial, and social costs arise immediately after failure. As for the psychological costs, entrepreneurs may witness it on either the emotional or the motivational level (Shepherd *et al.*, 2009; Ucbasaran *et al.*, 2013). In narrating their stories of failure, entrepreneurs recurrently mention the painful experience of failure, revealing affection as a main theme. However, this affection was not only personal towards oneself, but also towards others as a socially responsible feeling (Heinze, 2013). As a result of feeling guilty, the affection of entrepreneurs after months of failure was probably intensified by the feeling of isolation and solitude (Cope, 2011). These feelings tended to be stronger when entrepreneurs retained these feelings for themselves. For instance, subsequent to the deterioration of a familial bonding (such as marriage) (Singh *et al.*, 2007),

entrepreneurs felt less able to share their feelings of stress and frustration with others as a reassuring mechanism of the stressful situation experienced (Cope, 2011). Among the feelings expressed by entrepreneurs subsequent to failure (such as grief, despair, and frustration) was the disappointment feeling (by others), resulting in a feeling of distrust (Heinze, 2013), which can be threatening for successful business connections in future endeavours (Huntsinger, 2011). However, after recovering quickly from failure, the entrepreneur's emotional and physical states are argued to be enhanced (Shepherd, 2009).

Despite these negative emotions faced, the experience of failure was not always judged as a bad episodic event (Cope, 2011). Entrepreneurs, in describing their entrepreneurial journeys, used the word passion to reflect on the attachment created with the business career (Cardon *et al.*, 2005). Such metaphoric images are used to describe entrepreneurs' goals from the entrepreneurial pursuit (Clarke and Halte, 2010). Additionally, the failure was not perceived as imposing a lasting negative effect on their professional and career levels (Cope, 2011). On the contrary, entrepreneurs reflected on their venture's failure as an enriching learning experience that could be exploited for future success. Accepting it as an inherent risk for pursuing entrepreneurial careers, entrepreneurs believed that the best strategy to adapt to failure would be to live with the event and learn from it (Politis, 2008). Therefore, novice entrepreneurs are highly recommended to consider failure seriously, and perceive it as a learning experience when it happens, while being rationally prepared for it (Dias and Teixeira, 2017). By perceiving the scenario of failure and anticipating the grief, the level of the actual grief to be experienced subsequent to the actual failure may be moderated. This process of anticipating the probable grief encourages entrepreneurs to postpone their business failure, as a mechanism that balances costs emotionally and financially when the failure finally occurs, for the sake of an optimum recovery (Shepherd *et al.*, 2009).

The financial costs arise basically from losing a stream of income and from incurred possible debts that need to be settled (Cope, 2011). However, these costs are less impactful than the social costs considered to be devastating for entrepreneurs at the personal and professional levels. Researchers of this aspect (Ucbasaran *et al.*, 2013; Nielsen and Sarasvathy, 2016), by adopting concepts from the institutional theory and network theory, suggest that the entrepreneurs' personal relations suffer after failure

mainly because of stigma. Developing stigma after failure was concluded to be the most frequent consequence of failure (Dias and Teixeira, 2017), whereas Singh *et al.* (2015) considered it a process that even starts before failure, and hence affects the exit decision (Vaillant and Lafuente, 2007).

The second timeframe (reflection and learning from failure) involves a social psychological endurance that starts with grief (Jenkins *et al.*, 2014), moves into ascribing failures to factors (Mantere *et al.*, 2013; Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015), and finally generates learning from failure (Cope, 2011; Singh *et al.*, 2015). Through this process of learning (explored in more detail in the next Chapter), entrepreneurs make sense of their failure by assigning meaning to their experiences, while integrating the individual cognitive and emotional mechanisms (Ucbasaran *et al.*, 2013). The generated learning outcomes impact entrepreneurs over the long-term as elaborated next.

2.4.2 Long Term outcomes

The long-term outcomes of failure depend on the experience *per se*, the costs associated with it, and the sense-making conducted thereafter (Mueller and shepherd, 2016). These long-term consequences are exemplified in advanced business practices that highlight the significance of failure in individuals' lives (Cope, 2011), and can be categorised as behavioural or cognitive (Ucbasaran *et al.*, 2013). In most cases, it is difficult to delineate and segregate the emotional, behavioural and cognitive responses resulting from failure (Ucbasaran *et al.*, 2013; Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015), as the responsive cycle of individuals involves embracing (cognitively), understanding (emotionally), and responding (behaviourally) to the failure experience (Shepherd and Cardon, 2009; Ucbasaran *et al.*, 2013). Therefore, the interconnection between these responses requires an aggregate consideration, which will be this study's approach in analysing the outcomes of the reflection-attribution process of failure in Chapters Six and Seven, arguing that these outcomes occur at more than one level at the same time.

2.4.2.1 Cognitive and Behavioural

Learning from failure induces long-term outcomes (in the third timeframe) at the level of cognitive models, i.e., optimism (Ucbasaran *et al.*, 2013), and the underlying assumptions of entrepreneurs about themselves and the world around them (Dias and Teixeira, 2017). In the same vein, an interesting finding concluded by Mantere *et al.*

(2013) involved the contrast and comparison that entrepreneurs clearly exhibited between their old and new identities and personalities, whilst accepting responsibility for the failure. The new personality, being superior to the old one, is believed to have gained insights from the whole experience in general, and the failure in particular (Mantere *et al.*, 2013). In connection comes an equally important outcome that is related to the fourth level of learning process suggested by Cope (2011), the dimension of business management (explained later in Chapter 3, Section 3.4). The resulting learning outcomes at this level can be hence classified as either retrospective or prospective. The former, also known as adaptive, equips entrepreneurs with a reservoir of cognitive knowledge that can be used in future similar contexts and events. However, the latter increases the sensitivity of entrepreneurs to probable, critical future events, when controlling and managing the business (Cope, 2005).

On another level, failure experience impacts behavioural intentions, such as re-embarking in entrepreneurial venturing after revising current venturing practises (Dias and Teixeira, 2017); or even re-embarking as angel investors (Nahata, 2019). Surviving failure raises the confidence of entrepreneurs as well as their self-awareness, in line with Shepherd's (2003) argument that self-awareness of negative emotions arising from failure may lessen the level of stress experienced. These changes can be mostly exhibited in subsequent business activities, such as the appointment of the managing team; selection of financing resources; and strategic venturing concentration (Dias and Teixeira, 2017). In the same vein, Nahata (2019) found that serial entrepreneurs who experienced failure received better venture capital contracts than novice entrepreneurs, which adds further significance to learning from failure.

However, learning from past failure does not always result in the common practical application of subsequent venturing (Ucbasaran *et al.*, 2013; Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015; Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015; Mandl *et al.*, 2016). More specifically, almost every entrepreneur believes that another individual with a higher level of capabilities and skills would be probably more suitable to pursue business activities. This type of fallacy, labelled as Type 1 error, occurs when entrepreneurs possess these capabilities required to pursue future venturing (mainly social and human), but refrain from doing so due to a lack of self-confidence. On the contrary, Type 2 error occurs when entrepreneurs lacking the human and social capital necessary for the venturing

activities engage in entrepreneurship again and launch another business venture as a result of overconfidence (Nielsen and Sarasvathy, 2016). However, focusing on the performance of new ventures as an examination of the effectiveness of learning may not be simple or straightforward. Entrepreneurs might have different motivations and aspirations for the new businesses; hence, the comparability would be problematic (Ucbasaran *et al.*, 2013). Nevertheless, Ucbasaran *et al.* (2010) found higher reporting of business opportunities for entrepreneurs who experienced failure than novice counterparts. Interestingly, the attitude of entrepreneurs towards risk did not entail any reduced impact. More specifically, Dias and Teixeira (2017) found that entrepreneurs' approach towards risk did not decrease after a business failure. In other words, entrepreneurs after failure still tried to search for and assess new venturing opportunities, with an augmented reporting of such opportunities as well as of self-confidence. Consequently, the behavioural change (attitudes towards risk) was accompanied by a cognitive change (confidence level), emphasising the interconnection between both outcomes.

The experience of failure can be as insightful and valuable as successful experiences, leading to double-loop and transformative levels of learning. Entrepreneurs who faced negative experiences in the past (failure), and yet were able to embark again in subsequent ventures (so-called resilient entrepreneurs) are perceived to perform better than novice entrepreneurs (Cartwright and Cooper, 2009). Such learning resulting from failure is represented by a greater level of cognition, and a subsequent effective implementation of this enhanced cognition by adopting new strategies. Resilient entrepreneurs were able to overcome their emotional challenge (thus, improving their emotional capabilities) and create new ventures (Corner *et al.*, 2017), with even substantially higher orientation for international expansion than their novice counterparts (Lafuente *et al.*, 2019). However, this positive outcome of learning may be influenced by internal moderators and behaviours, which influence the insight and depth of the reflection process, as elaborated next.

2.5 Influencers of Learning from Failure

Making sense of experiences implies first observing the environment to accumulate relevant information, and then decrypting this information to retrieve meanings. This information eventually leads to developing behaviours that correspond with comprehending the meaning derived (Gioia and Chittipeddi, 1991). The initial

motivation of individuals to pursue an entrepreneurial career plays a significant role in facilitating this sense-making process of failure (Heinze, 2013). More specifically, the intrinsic motivation of entrepreneurs to start a business venture in the first place impacts their decisions and feelings subsequent to failure. Entrepreneurs who are intrinsically motivated for entrepreneurship and invest a significant amount of resources in their ventures are suggested to overcome failure and move forward (Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015). On another level, intrinsic motivation is also proposed to impact the sense-making of failure, as entrepreneurs refer to motivations to elucidate their reflection and emotions from failure (Heinze, 2013).

Another influencer of learning from failure involves the feeling of responsibility toward employees after the discontinuation of the business and the subsequent affection to assist others (Savitsky *et al.*, 2001). Entrepreneurs may be concerned with the impact and consequences of their decisions and actions on the feelings and lives of other people, be it family or employees. Interestingly, even grief, as a main personal affective outcome that entrepreneurs mostly expressed, was expressed in conjunction with the suffering of others subsequent to failure (Heinze, 2013). Henceforth, in their active process of making sense of failure, entrepreneurs consider the feelings and attitudes of people they care about while taking decisions. These feelings for (and of) others interfere in the entrepreneurs' learning process, and subsequently in their future decision-making, including the decision to pursue another endeavour (Shepherd *et al.*, 2016). In summary, the sense-making process adopted by entrepreneurs is on many occasions multidimensional, impacted by the perspectives and opinions of others on failure (Cardon *et al.*, 2011), even when these are contradictory to the personal opinions of entrepreneurs.

Another factor suggested to influence learning from failure is related to the nature of the exit decisions taken (Dias and Teixeira, 2017). Entrepreneurs seemed to undertake a conclusive and quick closure believing that such a decision helps in moving forward from failure, especially when the closure stems from the entrepreneurs' perception of probable failure before the occurrence of the actual failure. This anticipation of failure agrees with Shepherd *et al.*'s (2009) argument that anticipating failure facilitates the subsequent recovery from grief. However, personal biases can act as obstacles against this effective process of reflection and moving forward, hindering the learning process (Chen *et al.*, 2018) as will be elaborated in the next section.

2.6 Challenges of Learning from Failure

The process of reflecting on and learning from failure is not automatic (Pretorius and Le Roux, 2011), and hence, faces many challenges and barriers before its successful completion (Lee and Miesing, 2017). Extant research has already explained the role of biases (heuristics) in entrepreneurial decision-making, but little is still explored as to the impact of these biases on the learning process from entrepreneurial experiences within uncertain environments (Navis and Ozbek, 2016; Chen *et al.*, 2018). Among these biases comes first overconfidence. This bias might interfere with the learning process from failure, as entrepreneurs who are overconfident with their skills and abilities attribute failure to external factors (Eggers and Song, 2014). Consequently, entrepreneurs exhibit less motivation to learn on the individual level (Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015; Walsh and Cunningham, 2017).

Apart from overconfidence, an inevitable challenge to learning involves the reflection *per se*, as entrepreneurs avoid the confrontation of failure and the emerging feeling of culpability (Rogoff *et al.*, 2004). This cognitive process of self-justification is argued to interfere with the reflection on failure and the learning ought to be generated (Mantere *et al.*, 2013). In order to maintain their self-esteem (Aronson, 2011), individuals might employ two mechanisms in reacting to the past event (failure) that has challenged their positive perceptions about themselves (Shepherd and Cardon, 2009). One technique involves changing beliefs in order to embrace the challenge (internally), while the other technique implies understating the impact of their previous actions or behaviours (Mantere *et al.*, 2013).

In conjunction with this theory of self-justification, another challenge for learning emerges, narcissism (Chatterjee and Hambrick, 2011). Failure usually motivates entrepreneurs to collect relevant information, analyse it, and consequently, revise personal (emotional and cognitive) processes and attitudes (Shepherd *et al.*, 2014). However, narcissistic entrepreneurs employ some defensive mechanism for their ego and self-esteem (Aronson, 2011) in order to maintain their perceived superiority. Henceforth, these entrepreneurs will disregard objective signals about failure, and select only the information that defends their state, exhibiting consequently less motivation to learn from failure (Liu *et al.*, 2019). Additionally, narcissistic entrepreneurs tend to undermine any external assistance to understand their own failure, likely to be provided through others' experiences and perspectives.

Correspondingly, among the costs associated with failure, social costs were concluded as the most threatening to the ego of narcissistic entrepreneurs, while the financial and psychological costs threaten more their self-esteem (Liu *et al.*, 2019).

Among the social costs of failure, stigma stemming from the social context of entrepreneurs (Canon and Edmondson, 2005) is another challenge for effective learning, if entrepreneurs could not manage it properly. The trauma exhibited as an aftermath of failure is mostly related to stigma (Cardon *et al.*, 2011), defined as a stain on the individuals' reputations. Singh *et al.* (2015) found that, interestingly, stigma is experienced even before the venture actually fails. When entrepreneurs perceived stigma during the episode of failure anticipation, subsequent behaviour attempting to avoid further stigmatisation contributed to the venture failure. Being affected by the criticism received, entrepreneurs develop further feelings of shame, which, in extreme situations, may hinder subsequent venturing and waste the knowledge acquired (Politis and Gabrielsson, 2009). Though this might not be very common across all entrepreneurs as individuals exhibit different sets of emotional reactions, stigma is a negative emotion that prevents reflective observation (Cope, 2011). However, this feeling of stigma can be transformed into an epiphany, which is an impulsive and profound insight into the role played by the entrepreneur towards failure. This shift in the emotional state from stigma to epiphany allows the reflective observation to occur. Entrepreneurs may further challenge the stigma experienced due to failure and share their entrepreneurial learning with other individuals, minimising its future impact on society (Singh *et al.*, 2015).

A final challenge to entrepreneurial learning is time. The knowledge to be generated from entrepreneurial learning from failure is suggested to be time sensitive. Therefore, time elapsing after the experience is of high importance (Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015): the shorter the period of learning subsequent to failure, the more effective the outcome will be, and the greater the impact on future venturing (Parker, 2013). In the same vein, Yamakawa and Cardon (2015) found that a shorter time span between the failure and the decision for re-entry maximises the learning outcomes from failure. By re-engaging quickly in launching another business, entrepreneurs believed that they learned better from failure, in contrast to Shepherd's (2003:2009) assumption that longer cooling periods before entrepreneurial re-engagement assist better in recovering from grief and learning from failure. On the emotional state, when time

elapses after the failure experience, the activation of negative emotions drops in level with time. Therefore, the motivational attitudes of entrepreneurs to learn from failure decrease (Eggers and Song, 2014). Similarly, the shorter the time between the failure and the learning behaviour, the more salient the motivation of entrepreneurs to learn. However, an extremely shorter time can trigger a strong affective reaction that will be disadvantageous to the learning behaviour of entrepreneurs. In this case, the activation level of emotions is still high, which might create the risk of diverting intellectual resources away from the learning behaviours (Fang He *et al.*, 2018).

Following this discussion comes an interesting challenge to entrepreneurial learning which is the notion of perceived learning. Learning from failure depends significantly on the entrepreneurs' personal reflections and conceptualisation. Therefore, the learning perceived by entrepreneurs differs from the actual learning that they went through, and variance in both concepts might arise, especially with biases, such as failure ascription, and strong emotions, like stigma and optimism (Bacon, 2016).

2.7 Summary

This Chapter reviewed earlier contributions into the process of entrepreneurial learning from failure, by defining, first, entrepreneurial failure as adopted in this study. The definition combined earlier notions implemented by Cope (2011), Yamakawa *et al.* (2015) and Jenkins and McKelvie (2016) to identify failure as the termination of a business venture that either did not achieve the initial goals of its main shareholders (entrepreneurs) or has not been economically viable. Therefore, this definition implies that failure could be a decision undertaken by entrepreneurs to exit the business, though not every exit is attributed to failure (McGrath, 2006). It may involve in other instances an evaluation of reference points or a better perceived opportunity.

Entrepreneurial learning took various notions and definitions over years according to its purpose and nature (e.g., Brown, 2000). For this study, the transformative form of learning (on the individual level) and the double-loop learning (on the business level) (Cope, 2003) will be of utmost significance. Learning from failure takes the emergent unplanned (Williams, 2001) form, which assists in a deep reflection and analysis on the actions previously taken, in order to understand the reasons for failure (Ucbasaran

et al., 2010:2013). However, this learning is conditioned by the curious and active soul to take place effectively (Pretorius and Le Roux, 2011), and is initiated throughout the life of the venture, rather than strictly after failure (Costello, 1996).

Learning from failure starts intense, by embracing the resulting costs from failure: financial, psychological, social, (Cardon and McGrath, 1999; Shepherd *et al.*, 2009; Ucbasaran *et al.*, 2013), and physiological (Latack *et al.*, 1995). Among these costs, stigma, as a negative social cost, was considered detrimental especially on subsequent venturing (Ucbasaran *et al.*, 2013; Nielsen and Sarasvathy, 2016). Overcoming these costs and subsequently making sense of failure determine the effectiveness (Dias and Martens, 2019) of the reflexive action undertaken later (Cardon and McGrath, 1999). The learning that results, hence, occurs at four main levels (Cope, 2005): personal (skills and knowledge), venture (weaknesses and strengths), networks and relationships (business networks and partnerships) and venture management (skills of managing the venture). The effectiveness of the process and these learning outcomes were hence argued to be evaluated by the performance of subsequent ventures (Shepherd, 2003; Nielsen and Sarasvathy, 2011:2016; Lin *et al.*, 2019), which does not seem to be always reflective (Ucbasaran *et al.*, 2013).

The study of entrepreneurial learning adopted an experiential (Kolb, 1984; Mumford, 1995), social constructivist (Rae, 2000, 2004, 2005) or a cognitive (Zacharakis *et al.*, 1999; Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015; Corner *et al.*, 2017) approach. These approaches differed in explaining the transformation process through which experience is converted into knowledge (Politis, 2005; Mueller and Shepherd, 2016): exploration and effectuation versus causation and exploitation (Minniti and Bygrave, 2001; Sarasvathy, 2001). However, none of these transformation processes proves to be superior; they are rather activated according to the constrained resources and situations (March, 1991).

The process of reflecting upon failure induces much affection and negative emotions (grief, solitude, distrust, low self-confidence, blame) (Shepherd, 2003; Cope, 2011; Heinze, 2013), yet failure is not always perceived as a negative event (Cope, 2011). Overcoming negative emotions is argued to be critical to achieving insightful learning (Shepherd, 2003) on the overlapping dimensions of the cognitive level, such as

venture management and personal aspects (e.g., Ucbasaran *et al.*, 2013) and the behavioural level, such as attitude to risk or change in career (e.g., Dias and Teixeira, 2017). However, this process of learning is affected by the initial motivations of entrepreneurs, the affection of (and towards) others (Savitsky *et al.*, 2001; Heinze, 2013), the overconfidence of entrepreneurs (e.g., Navis and Ozbek, 2016), self-justification (Festinger, 1957 as cited in Heinze 2013), narcissism (Liu *et al.*, 2019), stigma (Politis and Gabrielsson, 2009), and time passage (Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015; Fang He *et al.*, 2018). A more insightful discussion of the reflection on failure from the perspective of the attribution theory will be explained in the next Chapter.

“I have not failed; I’ve just found 10,000 ways that won’t work”
– Thomas Edison

3 Chapter Three: Attribution in Learning Process

3.1 Introduction

This second part of the literature review concentrates on the attribution approach as a critical stage of the process of learning from failure and the various entrepreneurial factors that affect the dimensions of entrepreneurs’ ascriptions of failure. In this part, the researcher discusses the cognitive reflection process on failure using the attribution theory, the various coping mechanisms with failure, and the internal and external factors influencing the dimensions of failure ascriptions. The Chapter concludes with a summary on the critical conclusions found, followed by a comprehensive summary of both Chapters, before moving into emphasising the literature gap in Chapter Four.

3.2 Attribution Theory in Reflecting on Failure

The entrepreneurs’ personal definition and understanding of failure establish the foundation to learn, as this learning stems from the process of making sense (interpreting) from the experience (Rae and Carswell, 2001; Jenkins, 2012; Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015). The failure of a business venture is a clear indication that something wrong happened, and therefore, reflecting on this experience allows for the development of causal relationships (Mandl *et al.*, 2016). The resulting causal attributions assist entrepreneurs in dealing with the so-perceived negative experience (Cardon *et al.*, 2011; Cope, 2011).

The attribution theory emerges from social psychology and is defined as the mechanism adopted by people to explain events and personal behaviours, as well as those of others’ (Martinko *et al.*, 2006). Through this process, entrepreneurs evaluate the need to develop corrective measures in future business pursuits (Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015). However, such a process of ascriptions requires an absolute voluntary and proactive initiation by entrepreneurs that stems from their own cognitive evaluation and emotional understanding of failure (Jenkins *et al.*, 2014). The attribution theory has been defined according to three aspects: *locus of causality*, identifying the causality of failure as due to internal or external (to the individual) factors; *controllability*, relating to the perception of the individual as to his/her level of control over the perceived causes of failure; and *stability*, defining the level of stability of the causes

of failure over time (Weiner, 1985). Though these three dimensions define attributions separately, they are indeed interconnected: the internal attributions of failure are often deemed as controllable but unstable, compared to the uncontrollable stable external factors (Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015). Applied in the context of business failure, the major significance of the attribution theory resides within the locus of causality dimension (Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015). Stated otherwise, determining the causes of failure allows for a subsequent assessment of the actions taken, and for a speculation of corrective measures in future endeavours (Shaver, 1985; Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015).

Comprehensive learning from failure ultimately leads to a better understanding and preparedness for managing future ventures. However, the attribution of failure to external factors (Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015), especially if accompanied by a switch in the industry, induces the least levels of learning that will be applied in new ventures (Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015). However, external attributions provide entrepreneurs with the required detachment to evaluate the failure without much personalisation. The resulting stability is suggested therefore to encourage regeneration (Mandl *et al.*, 2016). In other words, the dimensions of attributions impact the decisions of entrepreneurs to abandon entrepreneurship or undertake further business venturing. More specifically, by denying any personal responsibility for the business failure, entrepreneurs usually protect their self-efficacy (Engel *et al.*, 2014), and are hence expected to be motivated to start another venture. On the contrary, novice and serial entrepreneurs decide to abandon the entrepreneurial activity when attributing the failure to (internal) controllable events (applicable as well to a certain extent to portfolio entrepreneurs²). This suggests that entrepreneurs probably decide to quit their entrepreneurial career when perceiving themselves as unable to establish a surviving business (Nielsen and Sarasvathy, 2016). More interestingly, novice entrepreneurs would quit the idea even if failure ascriptions are partially assigned to external factors (Mandl *et al.*, 2016).

The relevance of the attribution theory as a personal reflection process was only recently highlighted, viewing the failure of ventures as a complicated process that involves more emotions and attachment than just being a distinct episodic incident

² Portfolio entrepreneurs represent entrepreneurs who engage in many entrepreneurial projects simultaneously unlike the sequence of entry and exit of serial entrepreneurs (Mandl *et al.*, 2016).

(Ucbasaran *et al.*, 2013). Subsequently, extant researchers attempted to explore more the attribution theory and how it affects individual responses to failure. The process of explaining the causes of venture failures creates individual outcomes on the cognitive, emotional, and behavioural levels (Mandl *et al.*, 2016). Therefore, Walsh and Cunningham (2017) aimed in their study to explore the impact of the different dimensions of failure attribution on entrepreneurs' responses and how this connection impacts eventual entrepreneurial learning (Shepherd, 2003). In their study, the authors revealed four layers of attributions as perceived by entrepreneurs by building on Weiner's (1985) locus of causality: internal to the entrepreneur (individual); external to the entrepreneur but internal to the business (business level); external to both (market level); and a mixture of all three levels (hybrid level).

In linking the dimensions of attributions developed by entrepreneurs to learning outcomes, the perceived instability of internal attributions is considered beneficial as it induces the belief of being able to change them. The result would be higher learning and more probable success in subsequent ventures (Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015), in contrast to the conclusion of Sserwanga and Rooks (2014) that internal attributions result in less successful future endeavours. Entrepreneurs with internal attributions usually undergo a deep learning curve that is highly personalised and individualised as entrepreneurs learn more about themselves (Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015). The consequent outcomes thus involve learning about the skills that lacked during the venture's life, while undergoing a personal growth of individual traits, such as patience, self-belief, humility, and optimism, in line with Cope's (2011) individual level of learning. In contrast, the learning that results from venture-level ascriptions is limited to generalised observations without an intensive reflection. Similarly, the market level attributions generate learning on the aspects of relationships and networks (Cope, 2011), while the hybrid ascriptions result in more comprehensive learning (Walsh and Cunningham, 2017). In the same vein, Pittaway and Thorpe (2012) emphasised the impact of internal attributions of failure on inducing the most effective form of learning outcomes. Similarly, Yamakawa and Cardon (2015) concluded that entrepreneurs who believe in their own contribution to failure are believed to learn more (Jenkins, 2012) than entrepreneurs who assign failure to external-stable factors.

On the responsiveness level, the reactions of entrepreneurs were attached to the nature of attributions assigned to failure. At the individual level, greater emotional and affective responses were exhibited: negatively such as anxiety, stress, and disappointment; and positively, such as optimism and relief (that the process of failure ended). At the business level, entrepreneurs' responses were more of a clinical-behavioural nature detaching individuals from failure, revealing a relief state (Shepherd, 2003; Dias and Teixeira, 2017; Walsh and Cunningham, 2017). Therefore, entrepreneurs attributing the failure to external factors (business and market) revealed a faster recuperation from the failing experience (Eggers and Song, 2014).

Similarly, Yamakawa *et al.* (2015) concluded that an external attribution or a limited internal attribution implies that entrepreneurs do not perceive themselves as contributory to failure, and hence, exhibit little motivation to learn from failure and amend their behaviours. The lack of shame or blame feeling is most likely to hinder an effective learning process and the development of valuable outcomes from the failing experience (Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015). A more likely explanation of this perceived attribution is related to the protection of their egos, given their overconfidence in their skills and capabilities (Eggers and Song, 2014). Therefore, entrepreneurs blame the environment instead of bearing personal liability for it. In contrast to external attributions, entrepreneurs with hybrid attributions took time in contemplating the experience and reflecting on it properly. The resulting emotional and cognitive responses integrate to assist entrepreneurs in understanding and evaluating the experience (Walsh and Cunningham, 2017).

In summary, entrepreneurs will either blame themselves, others (Heinze, 2013), or bad luck and misfortune for the failure (Cardon *et al.*, 2011), while narrating their experiences. By relying on the discourses of the main stakeholders (employees, managers, and entrepreneurs) of three ventures, Mantere *et al.* (2013) concluded their study with seven types of narratives with which entrepreneurs ascribed failure and elaborated on the emotional process of recovering from grief. The cognitive mechanism of self-justification (Aronson, 2011) revealed the perceived attributions as summarised in Table 1 below.

Narrative Type	Explanation
Catharsis	In this type of narratives, the emphasis is placed on internal attributions, while distancing the identity that contributed to the failure from the recent more mature self. Within this narrative, entrepreneurs openly declared their contribution to failure. Interestingly, cathartic entrepreneurs reported their better knowledgeable self after the failure, interpreting failure as inevitable in the entrepreneurial journey to become a good entrepreneur (Heinze, 2013).
Hubris	In this narrative, the emphasis is placed on the collective, rather than the individual sense of responsibility. Irrational behaviours that led to the failure were considered the responsibility of the group (entrepreneurs, employees, managers...) as a unit, rather than the individual's. The hubris discourse of entrepreneurs was expressed by reference to excessive conditions (e.g., raising too many investments makes them blindfolded of practical realities).
Betrayal	Under this narrative, auteurs (e.g., entrepreneurs) blamed other internal players (i.e. employees, managers) with an accusing tone. Interestingly, entrepreneurs used to blame themselves rather than their employees, but the employees blamed the entrepreneurs more for the failure.
Mechanistic	Under this narrative, the attributions of failure were assigned to the organisation itself, as an outstanding unit, though in some instances, the attribution was attached to the entrepreneurs.
Zeitgeist	This type of narratives highlights the contribution of the age/time during which the business was operating; more specifically, the limited rationality and simplicity of entrepreneurs back then. Under this narrative, entrepreneurs accepted their responsibility for the failure, while also justifying it in conjunction with acceptable practise back then.
Nemesis	This narrative usually emphasises the auteurs' main enemy, identified as the investors, in sharing the blame. The justification under this narrative relates to the investors' pressure on entrepreneurs to grow their businesses quickly, who hence, either denied injecting further funds into the venture, or forced the venture to file for bankruptcy when that growth was not feasible.
Fate	Fate was raised in attributions where unexpected events within the operational environment drive the venture out. This narrative represents the other extreme end of the narrative scale, in straight opposition to catharsis. Interestingly, for entrepreneurs who expressed Catharism, some of their narratives also expressed pure fate. In other words, entrepreneurs, while blaming themselves for the failure, believe that they could not have done anything more to save the venture.

Table 1: Narrative Attributions

Source: Adopted from Mantere *et al.* (2013)

As suggested by the literature (Ucbasaran *et al.*, 2013; Jenkins *et al.*, 2014; Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015), responses to failure differ among individuals according to their abilities, which will eventually maximise or hinder learning (Shepherd and Cardon, 2009; Jenkins, 2012). The causal attributions of failure usually differ from one person to another, as entrepreneurs configure this understanding of failure according to their

sense-making and explanation mode (Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015). This explanatory mechanism involves retrospective thinking on the event and its probable reasons, before attributing the failure to the final causes (Ford, 1985). As a result, the attributions assigned to failure induce substantial implications for subsequent recovery and learning outcomes, as well as for pursuing further venturing activities (Shaver *et al.*, 2001) and achieving future success (Shepherd, 2009). Consequently, the discussion of entrepreneurial attribution of failure emphasises the individual rather than the venture level. On the venture level, the emphasis mostly concentrates on exploring the causes for these failures (e.g., Richardson *et al.*, 1994), while the individual level research explores the attributions of failure as perceived by entrepreneurs (Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015). This latter form of failure ascriptions according to the entrepreneurs' lenses unveils a great impact on their subsequent learning (Mantere *et al.*, 2013), which might impact subsequent entrepreneurial pursuits (Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015).

Despite all these contributions to entrepreneurial learning from failure through attributive lenses, a significant gap is still to be addressed. More specifically, research exploring the ascriptions of failure as assigned by entrepreneurs relied on the attribution theory (Mantere *et al.*, 2013; Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015; Mandl *et al.*, 2016) and highlighted the relevance of failure attributions on entrepreneurial learning (Shepherd and Cardon, 2009; Shepherd, 2009; Shepherd *et al.*, 2011; Mantere *et al.*, 2013; Eggers and Song, 2015; Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015; Walsh and Cunningham, 2017). However, the mechanism behind developing attributions (Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015), and their impact on subsequent venturing (e.g., Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015; Mandl *et al.*, 2016) still need to be investigated.

Furthermore, the adoption of the attribution theory is still limited in the context of entrepreneurial failure (Franco and Haase, 2010; Mantere *et al.*, 2013; Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015; Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015), and this linkage between attribution and learning is yet to be comprehensively revealed (Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015). More specifically, the entrepreneurs' emotional, behavioural, and cognitive responses subsequent to failure are suggested to be influenced by the attributions developed. Therefore, understanding the failure and its consequences by adopting the attribution theory enhances the academic understanding of its impact on 'regenerative

entrepreneurship' (re-entry of failed entrepreneurs) (Cope, 2011; Harvey *et al.*, 2014). Recognising its relevance in: understanding the reflection process of entrepreneurs (Mantere *et al.*, 2013); revealing the impact of cognitive biases (Rogoff *et al.*, 2004); and highlighting the implications for comprehending subsequent entrepreneurial endeavours (Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015), this research will adopt the attribution theory in the subsequent analysis and discussion of the findings (Chapters 6 and 7). In line with the relevance of the attribution theory, the coping behaviour that entrepreneurs adopt to recover from failure highlights the major role of emotions in the learning process, as discussed in the next subsection.

3.3 Coping with Failure

The business failure is deemed to represent a personal loss to entrepreneurs and an extension of their own identities, and hence, results in generating negative emotions (Shepherd *et al.*, 2016). These emotions are intensified if the failure occurred in ambiguity (Kumar, 1997), which may consequently hinder the learning process (Shepherd, 2003). Entrepreneurial learning from failure is initiated by exploiting available information to explain the reasons behind the failure, in order to revise extant assumptions and knowledge about effective business management (Shepherd *et al.*, 2014). However, securing the ultimate benefit from this information, regardless of its volume, depends on the cognitive capacities of entrepreneurs. Individuals' cognitive processing can be impacted by the affective interference when faced with situations that require greater attention and intellectual analysis (Wells and Matthews, 1999).

Contributions to understanding the significance of these emotions presented mixed findings as to the impact of such negative emotions. On one hand, these emotions were argued to stimulate learning and adaptation (i.e. Lant and Mezias, 1992; Morrison and Robinson, 1997); while on the other hand, negative feelings were suggested to hinder cognitive models; limit decision making; and prevent adaptation (i.e. Barker and Mone, 1998). Entrepreneurs experience intense emotions, such as grief and despair, which consequently trigger more negative affections. These emotions are argued to obstruct the ultimate potential of entrepreneurial learning, by affecting adversely the people's capacity to learn and "*interfering with individuals' allocation of attention in the processing of information*" (Shepherd, 2003, p. 320). Therefore, when this attentive and cognitive request is pressured with the feedback

information, individuals' learning is more vulnerable to the adverse effect of grief (Shepherd, 2003).

The entrepreneurial recovery from grief occurs when the individual no longer experiences negative emotions when thinking about the events that caused the business failure. In extreme cases where recovery does not occur, entrepreneurs might end up with permanent grief that necessitates psychological treatment (Shepherd, 2003). Negative emotions decrease the entrepreneurs' motivation to move forward and engage in future endeavours (Shepherd and Cardon, 2009). Therefore, recovering emotionally from failure is critical for entrepreneurs to overcome failure and may involve one of two mechanisms: loss orientation or restoration orientation. Through the loss orientation, entrepreneurs process the failure partially and shatter eventually their emotional ties with the business ventures (Shepherd, 2003). These constructed accounts about the failure induce gradual changes in the entrepreneurs' personal perspectives of the world and of themselves, hence, assigning meaning to failure (Archer, 1999).

On the contrary, suppressing the grief rather than confronting it assists entrepreneurs to move quicker in the recovery process, recognised as the restoration orientation (Shepherd, 2003). Under this approach, entrepreneurs adopt *avoidance*, by distracting themselves from yearning over their ventures, and *pro-action*, by attending to other dimensions of their daily lives, such as family and relationships (Shepherd, 2003). In parallel, Corner *et al.* (2017) have concluded interestingly on the capacity of entrepreneurs to be emotionally resilient subsequent to failure. By undertaking an exploratory study on the narratives of 11 entrepreneurs, the authors found that most interviewees showed a stable (resilient) rather than a disrupted functionality, labelled as the process of recovery from adverse events. However, Byrne and Shepherd (2015) argued that negative emotions resulting from failure will surface in the entrepreneurs' narratives when reflecting on their experiences, similarly to how the feeling of grief cannot be suppressed for long periods.

While each technique has its own advantages and costs, the quickest route for recovery probably requires an oscillation, shifting back and forth between both mechanisms (Shepherd, 2003). As a result, entrepreneurs will minimise the disadvantages of each mode, thus easing the mental exhaustion, reducing the affective interference and its impact on distracting attention (Shepherd *et al.*, 2016), and enhancing learning from

failure (Shepherd, 2003; Shepherd *et al.*, 2009). Therefore, adopting a dual mechanism (where negative emotions can direct the entrepreneur's attention to the failure without allowing the affective interference to burden the cognitive abilities), might significantly improve the learning from failure (Shepherd, 2003). The mechanism adopted by entrepreneurs in coping with the negative emotions arising from failure assists in emphasising the argued contribution of failure to the success of future ventures (McGrath, 1999; Minniti and Bygrave, 2001; Shepherd, 2003; Sarasvathy, 2004). From a psychology perspective, the process of coping involves developing reasonable and flexible opinions and behaviours that assist in solving resulting problems from failure, and hence, in reducing stress (Singh *et al.*, 2007).

The adoption of psychology within the context of entrepreneurial failure explained majorly two main processes that individuals adopt to cope with critical negative events in their lives: the problem-focused and the emotion-focused mechanisms (Drnovsek *et al.*, 2010). A third strategy, not as popular as the previous two, is the meaning-focused mechanism. This coping behaviour is adopted by stressed individuals who attempt to attribute the discomforting situation to a more long-term meaningful outcome (Folkman and Moskowitz, 2004). The difference between the first two processes lies within the focus of each mechanism. The problem-focused coping aims to direct the individual's efforts and focus on the main causes of distress for the sake of amending the troubling subject. Singh *et al.* (2007) concluded in their study that entrepreneurs usually adopt the problem-focused coping to resolve only the economic outcomes of failures, such as searching for another source of income (see Figure 6).

Economic Problem	Coping Strategies	Supporting Quote
Lack of income (Unemployment)	Example 1: Networked with and got work to do from a contact at former workplace (Case D)	Example 1 : 'It was someone at work...I approached him.... he started giving me little bits to do, then I got more work, and eventually we became business partners. I kept going because the key to survival is to keep going, keep meeting people, and keep your social connections going.' (Case D)
	Example 2 : Networked looking for new entrepreneurial opportunity (Case A)	Example 2: 'Last year I was in China...I got so many contacts in China...I spent 4 weeks visiting factories and looking for my next opportunity.' (Case A)
	Example 3: Took a job pumping gas	Example 3: 'I am unemployable. I can only do waitressing or something that doesn't require a credit check so I pumped gas for a while.' (Case C)
Financial pressures such as debts	Example 1 : Sold assets to pay debts (Case C)	Example 1: 'I approached some friends and sold them my house for the price of the mortgage to get rid of that debt.' (Case C)
	Example 2: Borrowed money from family (Case A)	Example 2: 'I borrowed a hundred and twenty thousand (dollars) from my brother-in-law to pay creditors.' (Case A)
	Example 3: Took legal action to recover funds (Case A)	Example 3: 'I took legal action against XYZ and I am still in a battle with them.' (Case A)

Figure 6: Problem-focused strategies

Source: Singh *et al.* (2007)

On the other hand, the emotion-focused mechanism processes the emotions that resulted from a tense situation, for the sake of managing and reducing the resulting emotional distress (Drnovsek *et al.*, 2010). Emotion-focused coping is adopted to deal with the psychological aspects of the entrepreneurs' lives, including self-blame, depression, anger, as well as grief and frustration (Lazarus and Folkman, 1984) (see Figure 7). Under this approach, entrepreneurs apply many personal strategies, out of which denial and venting turned out to be totally ineffective by distracting the reality in a self-deceptive manner (Singh *et al.*, 2007). Other strategies involved positive imaging, personal re-examination, and reframing, in consistency with the loss restoration process advised by Shepherd (2003), which "*involves some avoidance of the loss and pro-activeness toward secondary sources of stress arising from the loss of the business*" (Singh *et al.*, 2007, p. 340).

Psychological Aspects	Coping Strategies	Supporting Quote
Grief	Respondents did not have coping strategies here.	'I think it is grief and you have to go through all the screaming and wailing and crying and then you come out of it feeling like you dealt with it. I haven't dealt with it.' (Case A)
Guilt	Example 1: Other-Denial of responsibility for failure with family and friends. (Case E)	Example 1: 'It took me five years not to try to dress it up as some kind of moderate success....I was not honest with anybody....I would selectively talk to different people about things.' (Case E)
	Example 2: Distraction from situation. (Case A)	Example 2: 'I avoid facing reality... I try to keep my brain as numb as possible... I live in a fantasy world... I don't want to admit that this is all over because may be I'll reach a point where suddenly I will just sit in the corner and scream and hit my head against the wall...I like betting on horses it's a distraction... I go on drinking.' (Case A)
Depression/ Despair	Example 1: Positive Imaging	Example 1: 'I always have this image of a phoenix arising from the ashes ... I am still alive you know... I started again re-inventing myself I felt like a sixteen year old starting all over again.' (Case C)
	Example 2: Personal Re-examination	Example 2: 'It (venture failure) forced me to look at myself...where my skills were and what my interests were and then eventually I got into partnership with another guy and we set up a legal practice firm after that and that business was successful.' (Case D)
	Example 3: Reframing failure	Example 3: 'I began to think of it (the failure) as a challenge.... something to get through and learn from.' (Case B)
Anger	Example 1: Venting (Case C)	Example 1: 'I would swear at him (former romantic and business partner) on the phone I'd say look at what you have left me.... how could you do this to me. I was so angry.' (Case C)
Frustration	Respondents did not have coping strategies here.	'I suppose it was more the frustration with myself for not pushing the business to the level I had dreamed of and I still have not coped with this.' (Case E)

Figure 7: Emotion-focused strategies

Source: Singh *et al.* (2007)

In the scholars' debate on the superiority of one mechanism over the other, the emotions-focused coping was criticised for generating negative emotions suggested to interfere with the problem-focused coping (Shepherd *et al.*, 2016), given the resulting perception that situations are uncontrollable. The problem-focused coping mechanism is, on the contrary, appraised for its valuable outcomes in problem-solving and decision-making, with a higher sense of controllability over situations (Folkman, 1984). However, entrepreneurs who reflected more reliance on the emotions-focused coping demonstrated considerable advancement in their sense-making efforts (Byrne and Shepherd, 2015). Therefore, the emotion-focused mechanism can be indeed positive after failure, as it provides individuals with the 'space' needed to embrace themselves and restructure their personal and environmental perceptions (Haynie and Shepherd, 2011). In parallel, cognition contributes to this reflective sense-making of failure, as entrepreneurs recalled the intellectual skills adopted back then, and

henceforth, compared and contrasted (Byrne and Shepherd, 2015) the current situation with the prior ones, building on the concept of counterfactual thinking (Baron, 2004).

The negative emotions revealed within entrepreneurs' narratives, as argued by Byrne and Shepherd (2015), would probably trigger the process of making sense from failure. More specifically, the positive emotions³ prepared an affective context for the adoption of a subsequent cognitive process. Henceforth, the emotions-focused coping mechanism (such as positive imaging, personal re-examination, and reframing) (Singh *et al.*, 2007) generated, first, high negative emotions that were followed by high positive feelings. Once processed, these emotions may contribute to an active building and engagement that triggers the consequent cognitive processes for making sense of failure. Therefore, the sequential incorporation of both mechanisms leads to a more insightful reflective process. The negative emotions *per se*, hence, neither hinder nor trigger the adoption of cognitive strategies (Byrne and Shepherd, 2015), in contrast to Cope's (2011) and Shepherd's (2003) arguments.

Following on the discussion of emotions, making sense of failure as argued by Maitlis and Sonenshein (2010) encompasses attaching meanings and emotions to the event experienced. Emotions, therefore, do not only impact cognitions but also subsequent behaviours (Shepherd, 2003; Wolfe and Shepherd, 2015). By referring to the affective theory, an emotional situation triggers in entrepreneurs two assessment approaches (Weiss and Beal, 2005): the first one aims to evaluate the influence of the situation on the entrepreneurs' well-being, hence, the *valence of the emotions*; and the significance of the event, *the activation level of emotions*. The interrelationship between these two affective dimensions determines the affective outcome. The failure as a negative event affects the wellbeing of entrepreneurs, which generates negative emotions. However, the activation of these emotions is not automatic, but rather dependent on the perceived relevance of failure by entrepreneurs. The second stage seeks to assess the event of failure in terms of content, factors, and outcomes in light of the entrepreneurs' potential coping behaviour and to generate discrete affection (Wolfe and Shepherd, 2015).

³ Positive emotions represent a person's perspective of life and include enthusiasm, joy, confidence, pride, excitement (Watson and Tellegen, 1985)

The process of regulating emotions can occur at either stage and can be antecedent-focused or response-focused (Gross, 2002). In essence, the concept of regulation involves controlling which “*emotions to have, when to have them and how to experience and express them*” (Fang He *et al.*, 2018, p. 612). When emotions are not completely developed or no behavioural change has resulted yet, the antecedents-focused mechanism works best, as it allows entrepreneurs to concentrate on certain aspects of failure and then attach meaning to these aspects. On the other hand, response-focused strategies determine the behaviour of individuals when emotions are developing (Gross, 2002). However, this depends on the level of activation of emotions which determines the impact of affection on learning behaviours (Fang He *et al.*, 2018). Entrepreneurs with higher emotional regulation would perceive failure as a temporary event, and thus, believe in their capability to cope with it (Cardon and McGrath, 1999). The outcome of this appraisal mechanism will be a dissatisfaction with what happened, which motivates entrepreneurs to embark on learning (Shepherd, 2009; Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015).

On the other hand, a low regulation of emotions will result in perceiving less controllability over failure, giving rise to further negative emotions such as depression, and generating less motivation to learn believing that this learning would not improve the situation (Fang He *et al.*, 2018). Therefore, the distinction between both appraisals refers to the triggering of emotions (antecedents-focused) and the behaviour subsequent to the triggering (response-focused) (Gross, 2002). Commenting on the significance of failure to entrepreneurs, Fang He *et al.* (2018) concluded that a moderate activation level of negative emotions creates motivational and informational attitudes, which are likely to result in more superior levels of learning behaviours. The process of regulating emotions and, henceforth, coping with failure depend on the nature of attributions developed (Weiner, 1985). The next section elaborates on the dimensions of internal ascriptions of failure followed by external ascriptions.

3.4 Dimensions of Attribution

Attributions involve developing causal explanations of why the failure happened, initiating a process of making sense from failure (Gioia and Chittipeddi, 1991). These attributions are developed according to the entrepreneurs’ perceptions of the locus of

causality (Weiner, 1985) of prior events and occurrences (Shepherd, 2003). Henceforth, failure ascriptions have to relate to either internal or external factors, following on the findings of the most influential attribution scholars in the field of learning from failure. Tables 2 and 3 below summarise the main internal and external attributions developed by entrepreneurs in making sense of failure, as concluded by these studies.

Internal Attribution	Attribution Studies
Management skills, know-how, control (deficiency, illusion, nature, capacity, and ability)	Rogoff <i>et al.</i> (2004); Arasti (2011); Pretorius and Le Roux (2011); Mantere <i>et al.</i> (2013); Eggers and Song (2014); Yamakawa <i>et al.</i> (2015); Yamakawa and Cardon (2015); Dias and Teixeira (2017); Dias and Martens (2019);
Lack of financial management skills	Yamakawa <i>et al.</i> (2015); Yamakawa and Cardon (2015); Atsan (2016); Dias and Martens (2019)
Entrepreneurial skills, tolerating incompetence, individual traits (ethics, knowledge, dedication, service), lack of ability	Rogoff <i>et al.</i> (2004); Petkova (2008); Mantere <i>et al.</i> (2013); Yamakawa <i>et al.</i> (2015); Yamakawa and Cardon (2015); Dias and Teixeira (2017)
Inexperience and commitment, underperformance, and insufficiency of efforts; lack of interest and dissatisfaction	Petkova (2008); Arasti (2011); Pretorius and Le Roux (2011); Politis and Gabrielsson (2009); Mantere <i>et al.</i> (2013); Mandl <i>et al.</i> (2016); Walsh and Cunningham (2017)
Marketing skills	Rogoff <i>et al.</i> (2004); Yamakawa <i>et al.</i> (2015); Yamakawa and Cardon (2015)
Human resources (ability to hire good human capital, HC honesty and knowledge) and partnerships	Rogoff <i>et al.</i> (2004); Arasti (2011); Atsan (2016)
Product development and characteristics	Rogoff <i>et al.</i> (2004); Arasti (2011); Mandl <i>et al.</i> (2016)
Inaccurate evaluation of the project; improper business model; business planning; strategy	Arasti (2011); Pretorius and Le Roux (2011); Eggers and Song (2014); Yamakawa <i>et al.</i> (2015); Yamakawa and Cardon (2015);
Social and business networking	Boso <i>et al.</i> (2019)
Internal lack of critical information; inconsideration of market; inconsideration of legal issues	Arasti (2011)

Table 2: Internal Attributions concluded by attribution studies

Source: Researcher

External Attribution	Attribution Studies
Competition; market size; shift in business customs	Rogoff <i>et al.</i> (2004); Politis and Gabrielsson (2009); Eggers and Song (2014); Yamakawa <i>et al.</i> (2015); Yamakawa and Cardon (2015); Boso <i>et al.</i> (2019)
Change in customer needs; excessive niche market; poor market research	Yamakawa <i>et al.</i> (2015); Yamakawa and Cardon (2015); Atsan (2016); Mandl <i>et al.</i> (2016); Walsh and Cunningham (2017)

Market for talents	Rogoff <i>et al.</i> (2004); Yamakawa <i>et al.</i> (2015); Yamakawa and Cardon (2015)
Environmental uncertainty; economic sphere; market turbulence	Rogoff <i>et al.</i> (2004); Politis and Gabrielsson (2009); Eggers and Song (2014); Yamakawa <i>et al.</i> (2015); Yamakawa and Cardon (2015); Atsan (2016); Mandl <i>et al.</i> (2016); Walsh and Cunningham (2017); Boso <i>et al.</i> (2019)
Financing issues; acquiring resources; input costs	Rogoff <i>et al.</i> (2004); Politis and Gabrielsson (2009); Arasti (2011); Mantere <i>et al.</i> , (2013); Eggers and Song (2014); Mandl <i>et al.</i> (2016);
Regulation and changes in governmental policies	Rogoff <i>et al.</i> (2004); Atsan (2016); Arasti (2016)
Technology	Rogoff <i>et al.</i> (2004)
Business profitability	Politis and Gabrielsson (2009);
Bad luck	Petkova (2008); Mantere <i>et al.</i> (2013); Atsan (2016)

Table 3: External Attributions concluded by attributions studies

Source: Researcher

3.4.1 Internal Dimensions

The ability of organisations to sustain and grow is the aggregate result of various business characteristics rather than a random outcome. Consequently, the decisions, strategic plans, and behaviours adopted define the capacity of the venture for survival and growth (Delmar *et al.*, 2003). Therefore, in reflecting on their experiences, entrepreneurs evaluate and assess past behaviours, decisions, and actions. In conjunction with counterfactual thinking (Baron, 2004), entrepreneurs visualise what options could have been taken back then and what weaknesses need to be improved in terms of skills and competencies (Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015). The adopted decision-making process generates the behaviours and decisions that impact the survival of a business (Gans *et al.*, 2017).

3.4.1.1 Rationalising Failure with Decision-Making

The decision-making process adopted by entrepreneurs affects the entrepreneurial pursuit and the performance of business ventures (Gans *et al.*, 2017). In understanding the decision-making of entrepreneurs, researchers (i.e., Mitchell *et al.*, 2002; Sarasvathy *et al.*, 2008; Hauser *et al.*, 2019) have founded their examination on two main types of reasoning: the effectuation and the causation. The effectuation reasoning represents an active and interactive mode, also classified as unstructured planning (Sarasvathy, 2001), while the causation reasoning represents the traditional school of strategic planning (Sarasvathy *et al.*, 2008). A third, unpopular reasoning

relates to the absence of strategy (Inkpen and Choudhury, 1995), which represents many ad-hoc reasoning modes, all involving the concept of not following a particular strategy. However, the absence of strategy shall not be confused with the effectuation mode, as the effectuation is more of an intentional approach, while the absence of strategy is not (Hauser *et al.*, 2019). Each mode has its own rationale as depicted in Figure 8 below, with the domination of effectuation and absence of strategy approaches in most contexts.

		Categories				
		Basis for Taking Action	View of Risk and Resources	Attitude Toward Outsiders	Attitude Toward Unexpected Events	View of the Future
Themes	Causation	<i>Goal-driven</i> Goals, even when constrained by limited means, determine sub-goals and actions	<i>Expected-return</i> Pursue new opportunities based on the expected value	<i>Competitive-analysis</i> Protecting business opportunities against potential rivals	<i>Avoiding-surprises</i> Minimizing the impact of unexpected events by prediction, planning, and focus	<i>Predictive-trends</i> Predictive logic casts the future as a continuation of the past
	Effectuation	<i>Bird-in-hand</i> Imagine new opportunities by starting from the available means	<i>Affordable-loss</i> Pursue opportunities by investing less than stakeholders can afford to lose	<i>Crazy-quilt</i> Sharing business opportunities with committed partners	<i>Lemonade</i> Imaginative rethinking transforms the unexpected into new opportunities	<i>Pilot-in-the-plane</i> The future is cocreated by willful agents
	Absence of Strategy	<i>Putting-out-fires</i> Ad hoc problem solving	<i>Blinded-by-the-light</i> Overconfidence by suppressing of risks and requirements	<i>Walking-alone</i> No analysis and no definition of stakeholder relations	<i>Dead-end</i> Surprising events cannot get leveraged	<i>No-control</i> The future is not controllable

Figure 8: Rationale for each reasoning mode

Source: Hauser *et al.* (2019)

Interestingly, the initial motivations of entrepreneurs impact the reasoning mode adopted during their ventures' early stages (Gabrielsson and Politis, 2011). The authors have found that entrepreneurs aiming for creativity, growth, and independence (with spiral and transitory minds) tend to adopt effectual reasoning, whereas causal reasoning is more adopted by linear and expert minded entrepreneurs (aiming for achievement, expertise, power and security).

A critical point of the reflective sense-making of failure is that entrepreneurs shall examine and recognise the results of their decisions and behaviours (Silkin, 1992), as these decisions determine the survival or success of the business (Minello *et al.*,

2014). Henceforth, the debate on the effectiveness of intuition compared to rationality in developing a better decision-making process reveals that knowledge processes adopted by entrepreneurs in their decision-making are argued to be more intuitive than rational (Mitchell *et al.*, 2002). Entrepreneurs tend to adopt heuristics and biases for decision-making in situations of complexity and uncertainty, under which circumstances rational and informed decision-making would not be feasible (Busenitz and Barney, 1997).

Among these entrepreneurial biases, overconfidence has earned most of the attention of researchers as a main cause for business failure (e.g., Hayward *et al.*, 2006; Astebro *et al.*, 2014; Navis and Ozbek, 2016). Entrepreneurs' overconfidence in their own skills and abilities results in an overestimation of their probable success, and an underestimation of the risks associated with the business (Eggers and Song, 2014; Singh, 2020) and of the efforts needed (Invernizzi *et al.*, 2017). From a psychological perspective, cognitive scholars (e.g., Cain *et al.*, 2015) differentiated three types of overconfidence: overestimation (exaggerated self-perception with respect to a performance aspect), over-precision (exaggerated confidence interval of a crucial factor) and over-placement (exaggerated positive self-placement in comparison to others). In conjunction with overconfidence comes the overoptimistic attribute as a related outcome⁴ (Singh, 2020). An exaggerated level of optimism of entrepreneurs is considered a common heuristic that affects not only the decision-making and leads to failure (Hayward *et al.*, 2010), but also the learning generated from failure. By realising their unfounded optimism in their previous experiences, entrepreneurs would build more realistic expectations subsequent to failure. Henceforth, entrepreneurs who displayed such 'learned optimism' are expected to recover quicker, as these entrepreneurs would view failure as a challenge and transform adverse events into opportunities (Ucbasaran *et al.*, 2013).

Given that entrepreneurs are faced more than managers with uncertainties within entrepreneurial activities, a higher probability for errors is hence expected. As a result, entrepreneurs are presented with a learning opportunity to acquire new capabilities

⁴ Overoptimism differs from overconfidence. The latter is defined as the individuals' tendency to exaggerate their actual capabilities whereas the former implies the belief that an individual has a higher probability to experience positive situations than others (has less chances to experience negative events) (Helweg-Larsen and Shepherd, 2001 as cited in Ucbasaran *et al.*, 2010).

(Petkova, 2008), and to react and pro-act effectively in uncertain situations. Additionally, entrepreneurs tend to exhibit more flexibility and less structuralism in learning about their businesses (Gartner *et al.*, 2010), by adopting the effectual mode. Along with this pursuit of learning more about the business, entrepreneurs execute informal plans that are plotted unconsciously rather than formally developed (McGrath and McMillan, 2000). Following on the informality of plans, improvisation was argued by Balachandra (2019) as a necessary element for founding a business venture. Deep planning will hinder the pursuit of action, and thus, might lead to the disengagement (discontinuation) decision. However, entrepreneurs still attributed failure to improper planning, business model, and strategy (Arasti, 2011; Pretorius and Le Roux, 2011; Eggers and Song, 2014; Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015; Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015).

In the same vein, Achtziger and Alos-Ferrer (2014) argued that the cognitive process of entrepreneurs employs both rational and intuitive modes. In other words, when entrepreneurs face an uncertain event, the information that should be supposedly relied upon stems either from their external environment or from their evaluation of past decisions in similar contexts. Ironically, entrepreneurs tend to rely more on the latter than the former in their intuitive decision-making, which was perceived as an attribute of failure (Arasti, 2011). In the same vein, the inappropriate market research and the extensive concentration on a market niche were highly attributed as causes for failure (Walsh and Cunningham, 2017). In parallel, the entrepreneurial decision-making process is found to be slowed down, due to arising conflict between these two processes (rational and intuitive) (Busenitz and Barney, 1997). However, Camuffo *et al.* (2019) adopted a more scientific approach and concluded that a scientific entrepreneurial decision-making improves the business performance of the start-up. The scientific approach is assumed to allow entrepreneurs to assess the profitability level of their business ideas, as well as for alternative projects. Accordingly, when entrepreneurs develop a better understanding of customer needs that are subsequently piloted, the resulting decisions are less likely to be biased or imprecise, hence, decreasing the probability of experiencing false signals (Hayward *et al.*, 2006; Shepherd *et al.*, 2014; Camuffo *et al.*, 2019). Such a scientific approach is suggested to enrich the linkage between strategic management and entrepreneurship (Camuffo *et al.*, 2019), given the impact of entrepreneurial decision-making on the survival of

start-ups (Mitchell *et al.*, 2002; Gans *et al.*, 2017). Entrepreneurial decision-making depends on entrepreneurial competencies as elaborated next.

3.4.1.2 Entrepreneurial Competencies

The venture failure is the outcome of the entrepreneurs' decisions and actions in managing the business (Minello *et al.*, 2014), accentuating the role of the decision-making process and competencies in leading to failure (i.e., Rogoff *et al.*, 2004; Petkova, 2008; Mantere *et al.*, 2013). Among the various definitions of competencies, the researcher will adopt Minello *et al.*'s (2014) as:

“the action which combines and accelerates capacities and intangible resources, as long as they are needed [...] competencies are not only a set of tasks related to a role, but also a set of capacities” (p.3).

Consequently, competencies stem from actions, rather than being a mere set of existing knowledge. Yusuf (2012) asserted the benefits of conducting a feasibility study, researching the market, and developing business and financial plans for entrepreneurs as well as for stakeholders. Therefore, in relation to the internal layer of failure attributions, the inexperience and lack of commitment are concluded to majorly impact the preparedness level of entrepreneurs to lead their ventures (Petkova, 2008; Arasti, 2011; Mantere *et al.*, 2013; Mandl *et al.*, 2016; Walsh and Cunningham, 2017). In conjunction, the lack of planning (Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015) and visionary direction were also perceived as the main internal attributions for failure (Dias and Martens, 2019).

Entrepreneurs are usually uncertain about their entrepreneurial skills, which can be only discovered through an entrepreneurial journey, by launching a business venture and monitoring its performance (Lippman and Rumelt, 1982). Through this experience, entrepreneurs enhance their competencies, mostly proactiveness and persistence (Priyanto and Sandjojo, 2005). Therefore, the ability of a business venture to survive depends on the entrepreneurs' ability to inaugurate regular learning processes efficiently and effectively and develop proper knowledge (Abatecola and Uli, 2016). However, subsequent to failure, entrepreneurs might refrain from engaging in another entrepreneurial venture, believing in their lack of entrepreneurial skills (Nielsen and Sarasvathy, 2016). Stam *et al.* (2008) challenged this logic of passive learning and proved that active learning from episodic entrepreneurial

experiences can augment these capabilities, encouraging nascent entrepreneurs to become renascent.

Idea identification/creation	Capitalising on ideas
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Idea generation / envisioning • Opportunity recognition and means-end analysis • Ability to acquire information about a potential opportunity, domain knowledge and associated skills • Recognition of social / market need 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness of environment and factors conducive to opportunity exploitation • Ability to garner the necessary material resources • Ability to convince others of the value of an opportunity • Networking and social embedding
Traits/behaviours	Managerial/leadership skills
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-belief, self-awareness, trust in own judgement etc. • Ability to manage risk and shoulder responsibility • Ability to endure and cope with difficulties. Energy, motivation, persistence etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ability to manage others • Ability to overcome institutional and other constraints • Ability to develop an idea as a commercial opportunity • Decision-making capability

Figure 9: Four major areas of competencies

Source: Adapted from Chell (2013) as cited in Minello *et al.* (2014)

Researchers have attempted over years to identify a set of the most important skills related to entrepreneurs, as entrepreneurial skills are proven to influence positively some metrics of a venture's success (Frederiksen and Brem, 2017). Hayton (2015) connected entrepreneurs' skills to identifying customers' needs (Hunter, 2012) and spotting or creating entrepreneurial opportunities (Alvarez and Barney, 2007). In the same vein, Michelmore and Rowley (2013) have summarized six of the main entrepreneurial competencies (among others): identifying a workable market niche; generating ideas; developing products and services; scanning the operating environment; spotting and exploiting opportunities; and developing strategies to exploit spotted opportunities. Despite the various classification by each researcher, the systems-thinking, strategic management, forecasting, and interpersonal competencies were highlighted across the various combinations (Ploum *et al.*, 2017).

Another investigation of entrepreneurial competencies was developed by Minello *et al.* (2014) (see Figure 9), who combined entrepreneurial competencies into four categories. Minello *et al.* (2014) concluded that competencies are mostly activated during and after failure, stressing the relevance of failure in enhancing the skills at the individual level (Cope, 2005). In line with Minello (2010), the actions of entrepreneurs seem to be unplanned, relying on immediate outcomes, yet, managed to transfer their enhanced competencies into knowledge and to integrate it within the business to solve new situations (Minello *et al.*, 2014). Before the failure, entrepreneurs exhibited the competency of committing to actions, knowledge, and dedication which reflected in taking responsibility for their actions during failure. As highlighted by Mussak (2003), personal responsibility is a major component of entrepreneurial competencies, where entrepreneurs admit the outcomes of their decisions as leading to failure (Minello *et al.*, 2014).

Figure 10: Four categories of entrepreneurs' competencies

Source: Minello *et al.* (2014)

On another level, the prior experience, need for self-achievement, tendency for taking risks, and self-efficacy were proven to exhibit a positive impact on venture's performance, especially in the informal economy (Al Mamun *et al.*, 2016). However, the self-efficacy and the appetite for risks (Al Mamun *et al.*, 2016), supported by a prior employment experience significantly affect the sustainability of business ventures (Baptista and Karaöz, 2006). In the same vein, the competency of identifying an opportunity based on research and proper background, of exploiting resources from internal and external resources, and of pitching and promoting the business were

concluded as critical competencies for the viability of the venture (Rasmussen *et al.*, 2011). Therefore, entrepreneurial competencies have a direct and positive impact on business survival and growth, most importantly the strategic planning and organising of the venture (Umar *et al.*, 2018). Finally, entrepreneurs are expected to possess psychological, social, and emotional skills along with the technical and managerial skills to successfully sustain the entrepreneurial career (Omrane and Fayolle, 2011). The social skills will be elaborated next.

3.4.1.3 Networks and Social Skills

Since the beginning of the twenty-first century, the success factors of entrepreneurship have greatly evolved to include networks as a critical resource for survival and growth (Lans *et al.*, 2015), and to consider the lack of social skills as an attribution of failure (Boso *et al.*, 2019). Researchers (i.e., Baron and Tang, 2009) have thus investigated the underlying quality and impact of these networks, as well as their nature and scope, under the concept of the social capital theory (Anderson and Jack, 2002). The social competence of entrepreneurs involves:

“the ability of people to interact successfully with each other within a certain position and context [...] contributes directly to success in entrepreneurial networking, rather than being the result of it” (Lans *et al.*, 2015, p. 458).

The social capital theory explains systematically the relevance of networks for entrepreneurs, by particularly embracing the influential dimensions of their quality, nature, and capacity (Bourdieu, 2008). This theory distinguishes between the structural and the relational aspects of social capital (Aldrich and Zimmer, 1986). The structural aspect refers to configuring the nature of entrepreneurial networks (who are they connected to) and the ways of building these networks (how did they reach them) (Burt, 1997; Nahapiet and Ghoshal, 1998), and can be thus classified as bridging or bonding (Adler and Kwon, 2002). The bonding nature of the structural dimensions categorizes the connections with close networks, usually friends and family, and is described as homogeneous and frequent. On the contrary, the bridging configuration represents the external networks and reflects the entrepreneurs' ability to widen and expand their connections beyond the bonding structures (Lans *et al.*, 2015).

Another differentiating characteristic in the dimensions of social networks is the relational feature (Burt, 1997). Every kind of relations induces a different set of activities among the interacting parties in any particular network. These networks

within the social capital can be constructively beneficial for entrepreneurs in supplying information about the external environment and reducing risks that might affect the business outcomes (Wang *et al.*, 2015). Additionally, these networks might assist beyond providing financial resources (Connelly *et al.*, 2011) to even provide emotional support and expertise to entrepreneurs (Soetanto, 2017). The knowledge supplied by these external networks also assists in reducing costs, increasing customer satisfaction, and operating more effectively (Perin *et al.*, 2016). One form of these networks is membership with professional organisations like syndicates, research centres, and other communities (Lans *et al.*, 2015), while another form originates from their previous experiences and backgrounds (Birley, 1985). Both types of ties, the bonding and the bridging, do not only facilitate the start-up of any new business idea, but also improve the growth opportunities of early-stage entrepreneurs by: supplying new information (through the weak bridging connections); providing access to a complicated set of implicit knowledge (through the strong bridging connections); or empowering the entrepreneurs to benefit appropriately from an arising opportunity (through the strong bonding ties) (Lans *et al.*, 2015); hence called social resources (Rooks *et al.*, 2016).

Social skills of entrepreneurs are therefore considered substantial factors for the growth of an entrepreneurial venture, through the long-term connections that entrepreneurs form with their context (Beauchamp and Anderson, 2010). According to Baron and Tang (2009), the social competence of entrepreneurs involves a diverse set of skills, each embraces a distinct dimension of social connections:

“social adaptability (i.e., being able to adjust your story and integrate ideas of others into it), social perception (i.e., the ability to accurately perceive others), expressiveness (i.e., expressing emotions and feelings clearly, to generate enthusiasm), ingratiation (i.e., the use of flattery in interaction) and self-promotion (i.e., the presentation of one’s skills and accomplishments in a positive light)” (Lans *et al.*, 2015, p. 462).

Social perception and self-promotion are immediate influencers of the venture’s performance and promote the proper execution of the main entrepreneurial activities, such as business negotiations and business partners’ identification (Barons and Tang, 2009). Self-promotion surpasses the simple meaning of promoting personal skills and achievements positively to include the ability to communicate those achievements to potential partners (Rasmussen *et al.*, 2011). This definition of self-promotion relates it thoroughly to the adaptation skill standing out as a critical factor for the growth of

entrepreneurial ventures (Lans *et al.*, 2015). Consequently, venturing opportunities and growth are increasingly affected by the entrepreneurs' social skills and their ability to develop and build networks and business relations (Watson, 2012). In other words, this competence will have a direct impact on the structure, number, and strength of networks that entrepreneurs establish with external parties (Tehseen *et al.*, 2018).

However, the development of business networks is not automatic or inherently created with the conception of a business venture, but rather necessitates an initiative behaviour by entrepreneurs (Zhao *et al.*, 2010; Soetanto, 2017). Only through proactive initiatives entrepreneurs may be able to develop rational and beneficial networks (Ismail, 2012), and overcome arising challenges when seeking to develop social networks (Zhao *et al.*, 2010). However, entrepreneurs will not exhibit similar level of willingness and preparedness to engage in networking pursuits. Bounded with financial resources or struggling economically, entrepreneurs might feel more motivated to engage in networking endeavours to secure the needed resources (Witt, 2004).

The role of networks is influenced by the environmental culture (Witt, 2004), as culture mainly affects the entrepreneurs' behaviour and reliance on social networks under the umbrella of trust (Hallam *et al.*, 2018). In individualistic cultures, more weight is placed on weak ties than in collectivist cultures, allowing for greater trust. Inevitably, entrepreneurs would feel higher levels of confidence with their networks, relying on greater interdependency with the various actors involved (Welter and Kautonen, 2005). Jaafar *et al.* (2009), surveying 54 businesses in Malaysia, concluded that business ventures referred to their strong ties in their early stages in order to access the needed capital, market information, and necessary resources (Witt, 2004). At a later stage, ventures switched to and relied more on the weak ties particularly for obtaining relevant information about the market. Consequently, Jaafar *et al.* (2009) argued that the effectiveness of strong ties is limited to the early conception stage of the SME. Once SMEs are established and operating, the impact of weak ties on sustainability and growth is more emphasized and influential (Strobl and Kronenberg, 2016). Similarly, Songini and Gnana (2014) argued that once entrepreneurs complete the conception stage and start witnessing growth, their networking approach should

move to more professional networks with the external environment. Such a shift requires entrepreneurs to strategically plan for it, allowing the venture to expand its dependence on and connections with the external environment. Among other benefits, networks significantly assist entrepreneurs in marketing for their ventures (Reijonen, 2010), as discussed next.

3.4.1.4 Marketing Skills

Marketing is a critical factor for the viability of business ventures, influencing their financial performance and subsequently their survival (Tsai and Eisingerich, 2010; Ren *et al.*, 2015; Hoque and Awang, 2016). However, the entrepreneurial context seems to exert some variance on the function of marketing (Stokes, 2000). Rather than adopting traditional marketing, entrepreneurs are more inclined to innovation, “*driven by new ideas and intuitive market feel, rather than customer-oriented, or driven by a rigorous assessment of market needs*” (Nikfarjam and Zarifi, 2015, p.334). More specifically, entrepreneurs tend to rely heavily on a classified segment of customers and to execute marketing efforts variably. Adopting less formal planning with limited competencies and the lack of entrepreneurial marketing skills can be hence perceived as an attribution of failure (Rogoff *et al.*, 2004; Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015; Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015).

Discussing the marketing function entails exploring two dimensions: the formulation of the marketing strategy and the application of that strategy, though both functions are intertwined activities that cannot be separated (Menon *et al.*, 1999). The capability of the business venture to effectively formulate and execute the marketing function (i.e., researching the market, developing the product/service, pricing it, and managing the market) influences its performance (Hooley *et al.*, 1999). However, the act of developing a proper plan has been emphasised as impacting the subsequent implementation and eventually the performance of the business (Morgan *et al.*, 2012). The formulation of marketing strategies involves developing situational analyses (among others), while the implementation depicts committing the available resources to the developed strategies (Finoti *et al.*, 2017).

With the absence of a formulated marketing strategy, entrepreneurs end up with self-marketing, undertaking various promotion activities in the actual market to create brand awareness (Shepherd, 2005). This approach of self-marketing, though criticized (Reijonen, 2008), may become an effective tool for entrepreneurs to create strategic

visibility and personify the brand with the entrepreneur (Juntunen, 2012). Entrepreneurs in such practice might refer to traditional door-to-door marketing in their pursuit to build market share (Kumar *et al.*, 2017). However, the substantial pressure exercised by the self-marketing function on the entrepreneur requires firmer work to sustain the image built of the business venture, given the lack of resources to appoint or delegate staff for the function. Without planning or understanding the marketing theory adopted, entrepreneurs rely on their interactions with clients to decide on the next step (Resnick *et al.*, 2016).

Undertaking effective marketing constitutes one of the main challenges of survival and growth for ventures aside from raising sales (Nwankwo and Gbadamosi, 2010). However, the effectiveness of the marketing function in the entrepreneurial context is influenced significantly by the personalities of entrepreneurs (Gamble *et al.*, 2011). In many instances, entrepreneurs are argued to be an obstacle to the effective execution of the marketing function (Reijonen, 2008). The extent of engagement of entrepreneurs within the marketing function affects their pursuit in applying any marketing plan (Dobbs and Hamilton, 2007). On the other hand, marketing ideas developed by entrepreneurs may be very unique and not easily copied by competitors (Resnick *et al.*, 2016).

An interesting finding undertaken by entrepreneurial ventures in relation to the marketing activities involved engaging customers and relying on effective communication processes and channels, such as networks and word-of-mouth in reaching the market (Reijonen, 2010; Resnik *et al.*, 2016). In other words, the overreliance on social networks comes as an alternative to overcome the limited financial resources available for the marketing execution (O'Donnell, 2014). This highlights again the non-traditional execution of entrepreneurial marketing, as the majority of ventures execute the marketing function based on informal, unplanned, and unstructured approaches (Musso and Francioni, 2014). The adoption of more structured strategies which yield greater performance, such as loyalty cards (Hutchinson *et al.*, 2015) is mostly unfeasible. Nevertheless, the effectiveness of marketing does not only reside in the channels and plans but also in the ability of the venture to obtain market information and utilize the relevant pieces of it that will create a positive impact on the venture's performance (Keh *et al.*, 2007).

Among the most popular advertising channels adopted by business ventures, social media ranked quite high. Indeed, more than half of business ventures believe in the effectiveness of social media as a marketing tool, especially for raising brand awareness (Schaupp and Belanger, 2014). Through the social media channels, ventures are more able to expose themselves and create a presence for their services and products (Hubspot, 2012), whilst challenged with driving human focus and traffic to business websites (Karimi and Naghibi, 2014). Indeed, social media can be a helpful tool for business ventures as it allows creating a customer base, providing ventures with good marketing for fewer costs, and creating a collaborative platform with customers (Jangogo and Kinyua, 2013). In summary, social media marketing can be just as harmful as beneficial if entrepreneurs ineffectively relied on social media (Nakara *et al.*, 2012). As a part of effectively managing the marketing function, recruiting and managing quality talents is deemed essential for start-ups and small ventures (Cardon *et al.*, 2009), as will be elaborated next.

3.4.1.5 Human Capital Management

The recruitment decisions taken by start-ups to hire human capital critically affect the growth of the venture (De Winne and Sels, 2010), as the human capital is found to impact positively and directly the venture's performance (Baptista and Karaoz, 2006). However, a limited focus has been placed on entrepreneurial recruitment (Stewart and Hoell, 2016), bounded to the formation of nascent teams prior to the conception of the venture (Klotz *et al.*, 2014). Given the impact created by the recruited individuals on the performance of the business (Wright *et al.*, 2005) and the consumption of the limited available resources (as in the form of salaries) (Powell and Baker, 2014), it is critical to examine the entrepreneurial process in early-stage recruitment.

The recruitment decision of the very first few employees differs from deciding on the foundation team members (Ucbasaran *et al.*, 2003). Team members impact the venture strategically, hold equity, and are usually selected based on either their skills or similarity and likeness by the entrepreneur (social-psychology approach) (Forbes *et al.*, 2006). Even with such a basis for team selection, conflicts arise among partners and represent a threat to the survival of businesses (Stam and Schutjens, 2005). As to its impact on entrepreneurs, recruiting the first few employees gives them space and time to be more devoted to their entrepreneurial passion (Cardon *et al.*, 2009) and the strategic direction of the venture. Therefore, the improper ability of entrepreneurs to

recruit good human capital that possesses the needed knowledge and honesty was perceived as an internal attribution of failure (Rogoff *et al.*, 2004).

However, the recruitment is highly dependent upon two main factors: an external, which is the availability of talents in the market (Rogoff *et al.*, 2004; Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015) and an internal, which relates to the social and role identities of entrepreneurs (Stewart and Hoell, 2016). The social identity represents the self-concept of entrepreneurs in attachment to the social groups to which they belong (Tajfel, 1974). This identity will influence the hiring process by selecting candidates who confirm this social identity of entrepreneurs or improve their self-concept (Stewart and Hoell, 2016). On the other hand, the role identity which signifies the inventor, developer, or founder (Cardon *et al.*, 2009), might also influence the recruitment process, by hiring employees who can take over some of the positions already managed by the entrepreneur. Consequently, entrepreneurs can concentrate and focus on their most central role identity (Stewart and Hoell, 2016).

As for the leadership style of entrepreneurs, it is crucial in managing the business. In small businesses, employees usually consider the entrepreneur as the sole instructive source for completing their tasks (Churchill and Lewis, 1983). Therefore, the leadership of entrepreneurs allows a more enhanced, informal, and unstructured communication with employees. Employees are also expected to possess the knowledge, talent, know-how, skills, and experience that allow them to undertake their transformative function of information into knowledge, which ultimately enhances the venture's performance (Bontis *et al.*, 2000). As a result, recruited human capital is concluded to directly impact the performance of business ventures (Rasmussen *et al.*, 2011). Retaining knowledgeable human capital is key for realising higher performance (Daou *et al.*, 2014), which can occur by providing continuous training and development to staff, and redesigning compensation and motivation schemes (Lyons *et al.*, 2005). However, small businesses are usually constrained with limited financial resources, posing challenges on paying proper incentives and salaries to recruit and retain the necessary talents (Salgado *et al.*, 2020). The lower salaries offered by the venture are bounded by the lower productivity of small business ventures compared to more mature companies (Burton *et al.*, 2018). Henceforth, small businesses struggle with providing enough motivation for talents to join and hence

compromise the workload with less experienced employees (Nystrom and Elvung, 2014; Ouimet and Zarutskie, 2014).

It is therefore clear that entrepreneurial decisions, competencies, and skills play a major role in the viability of the business and its future growth. However, this reservoir of motivation and individual characteristics of entrepreneurs (Simsek *et al.*, 2015) are impacted by the environment. Entrepreneurs are considered to be the influential outcome of environmental circumstances existing when founding the venture, directly imprinting on the processes, behaviours, and structures of current and future ventures (Bryant, 2014; Simsek *et al.*, 2015). Henceforth, the external environment impacts not only the skills of entrepreneurs but also the business survival (Ahmad *et al.*, 2010) as elaborated next.

3.4.2 External Dimensions

While reflecting on failure, entrepreneurs tend to explain it with causes on the internal as well as the external levels (Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015). On the market level, the turbulence in the market is considered the main contributor to failure, as the industry goes under turbulent uncertainty. On a more hybrid level, the access to capital and the timing of the business venture were ascribed as causes for failure (Walsh and Cunningham, 2017). The access to capital involves two perspectives: the struggle of entrepreneurs to raise or borrow funds needed for the business (Vos ad Forlong, 1996) and the improper management of the funds available (Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015; Atsan, 2016; Dias and Martens, 2019).

3.4.2.1 Finance

The financial resources of new ventures are usually supplied through one of two main sources: debt financing or equity financing (Beck and Demirguc-Kunt, 2006). Interestingly, the initial motivations of entrepreneurs are connected to the direction of funds sought (debt or equity). More specifically, intrinsic motivations that include ambitious and self-achievement goals rely more on non-repayable funds than on debts or personal funds (Garg and Shivam, 2017). On the other hand, entrepreneurs who pursue venturing for the purpose of increasing their profits or wealth rely more on indebted resources or exhaust personal funds (Cosh *et al.*, 2009). A third option for securing funds can be provided by strong networks such as friends or families, to compensate for the difficulty in raising external funds (Witt, 2004).

Access to finance at reasonable costs (Schmidt *et al.*, 2015) represents a major challenge for entrepreneurs (Lekhanya and Mason, 2014; Jere *et al.*, 2015). External financing involves venture capitalism or equity funds, usually available at more mature stages of the business life. Henceforth, the amounts provided for start-ups represent only a small proportion of the available equity resources, as the small amounts requested by these ventures at their early stage do not motivate venture capitalists to invest (Shane, 2012). As a result, new and small ventures divert their request of funds towards the debt financing of commercial banks as a main source, which also suffers from a limited supply for new ventures and start-ups (Abdesamed and Abd Wahab, 2014). The high risk associated with new ventures, especially with the lack of collateral creates a debt gap (Poutziouris *et al.*, 2002; Fatoki, 2014). The request for collateral serves as a protection for the financial institutions against the high risk of new ventures, informational asymmetry, and uncertain evaluation of the business projects (Abdesamed and Abd Wahab, 2014). For instance, the majority of loan applications rejected revealed that loans requests admitted by small ventures did not involve any business plan, financial forecasting, or budgeting analysis (Naimy, 2011).

Reduced cash flows, especially in times of economic downturn, decrease the financial ability of ventures to sustain their operations (Muhammad *et al.*, 2010), and to even create rewarding businesses (Gimmon and Levie, 2010). Therefore, the lack of financial resources (Fatoki, 2014) and the issues with acquiring these resources as well as the input costs (Rogoff *et al.*, 2004; Politis and Gabrielsson, 2009; Arasti, 2011; Mantere *et al.*, 2013; Eggers and Song, 2014; Mandl *et al.*, 2016) are considered among the main external attributions of failure. Interestingly, entrepreneurs might refrain from seeking debt financing if their perceptions about the potential possibility to raise debt funds is negative. Henceforth, entrepreneurs might get discouraged from borrowing funds and rely in return on internal sources of finance (Xiang *et al.*, 2015).

Sampagnaro (2013) states that, even when ventures secure debt financing, cash flows generated internally contributed most critically to the sustainability and future growth of a business venture. An important source of this internal cash flow involves collecting the outstanding receivables, which is usually a main problem for small

businesses that cannot afford to hire individuals for the follow-up process with clients as in the case with larger companies (Kestens *et al.*, 2012). These receivables compose a main source of liquidity that can assist businesses in surviving difficult financial situations. However, SMEs do not pay sufficient attention to the collection of receivables (Kubickova and Soucek, 2013). Moreover, during an economic downturn, small businesses tend to postpone the collection of outstanding receivables, granting clients extended time, which eventually results in an internal crisis of insolvency (Sobekova Majkova and Kljucnikov, 2017). In such situations, businesses that recourse to payables to finance their short-term operations, efficiently manage their assets and refer to self-financing are mostly projected to sustain and grow (Jeger *et al.*, 2016). Therefore, small ventures undergo subsequent requests for extended periods to settle off their loans, due to the diversion of available funds from payables to operations. Such requests affect the venture's financial information, usually adopted as a criterion by financial organisations to approve (or disapprove) the lending applications (Jeger *et al.*, 2016).

In emerging economies, debt financing provided by commercial banks is usually limited in its availability to new ventures, given the reluctance of these organisations to finance risky ventures. At the same time, venture capitalism is also bounded with the limited supply, which hence forces start-ups to rely more on their internal sources of funds to compensate for the lack of liquidity (OECD, 2014; Jeger *et al.*, 2016). In Lebanon, the financing support provided to SMEs and start-ups is suggested to be higher than the average in the region (the Middle East and North Africa) (GEM, 2018), with many financing initiatives according to the stage of the venture, as summarized in Figure 11 below. Public initiatives have been taken in conjunction with the central bank (Circular 331⁵) to finance entrepreneurial programmes and support new ventures (Chiofalo *et al.*, 2019; OECD, 2019). The tech field is booming in the country through venture capitalism (GEM, 2018), and equity funds are available at more mature phases of the venture's life (Rouhanna, 2018). Despite such claimed availability of funds, the majority of small business ventures revealed their dissatisfaction with these national programmes, mainly the debt financing in terms of requested capital, high interest rate, and level of collateral needed (Naimy, 2011).

⁵ This circular aims into encouraging the commercial banks to invest in start-ups by equity supporting their investment by up to 75% in case the start-ups fail (BDL, 2013)

	ICT – Knowledge economy	Agribusiness	All
USD 2 M	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ IMPACT (MEVP) (equity) ▶ MIC TelcoFund (equity) ▶ B&Y Ventures (equity) 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Lucid (debt, equity) ▶ EBRD (equity) ▶ EuroMena (equity) ▶ IFC (equity) ▶ Leap Ventures (equity)
USD 500 K	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ MEVF II (equity) ▶ Phenician Fund (equity) ▶ Impact (MEVP) (equity) ▶ Wamda capital fund (equity) ▶ Berytech I and II (equity) ▶ Cedar Mundi ((equity) ▶ B&Y Ventures (equity) 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Daher Capital (equity) ▶ iSME (equity) ▶ EuroMena (equity) ▶ IFC (equity) ▶ Theemar (equity) ▶ Libank (equity)
USD 50 K	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Lebanon Seed Fund (equity) ▶ Azure Fund (equity) ▶ Flat8labs (equity) ▶ BBEP (equity) ▶ Saned (equity) ▶ Phoenician Fund (equity) ▶ B&Y Ventures (equity) 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Daher Capital (equity) ▶ Saned (equity) ▶ iSME (equity) ▶ IFC (equity) ▶ LBA (equity) ▶ Cedar Ventures (equity) ▶ IM Capital (equity) ▶ Kafalat Plus (debt) ▶ Bader (equity) ▶ LWAF (equity) ▶ Faro Lebanon (equity) ▶ Theemar (equity)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Kafalat innovative (debt) ▶ Speed (equity) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ AEP (microfinance) ▶ Al Tamkeen (microfinance) ▶ Agrytech (grants) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Alpha capital (debt) ▶ Makhzoumi foundation (debt) ▶ LWAF (equity) ▶ CFC (debt) ▶ iSME (grants) ▶ ESFD (debt) ▶ Emkan (debt) ▶ Al Majmoua (debt) ▶ Alfamar (grants) ▶ Vitas (debt) ▶ ADR (debt)

Figure 11: Financial landscaping in Lebanon

Source: OECD (2019)

Given the shortage in funds, entrepreneurs refer to personal savings or borrowings from close networks to raise the capital needed for their ventures, whilst avoiding external debt financing (Fatoki, 2014). This limited or even lack of financial resources reveals the lack of readiness for investment also called the financing gap, which can play a major role in leading new ventures to failure (Quaye *et al.*, 2014), besides the improper management of funds (Mezher *et al.*, 2008). Attributing failure to the financing factors involves understanding the role of ecosystems as well as

governments, in supporting small businesses and entrepreneurs (Isenberg, 2011). The next subsection will discuss in more detail how ecosystems impact the sustainability of business ventures.

3.4.2.2 Government and Ecosystem

The entrepreneurial ecosystem incorporates major elements from within the local settings including finance, infrastructure, networks, culture, market, and government (Stam and Spigel, 2016). Similarly, Shirazi and Mohamadi (2018) argued that simply considering the context while studying the environment of entrepreneurship is indeed irrelevant if these studies did not consider the aggregated, as well as the individual, influence of the elements within this context. In highlighting the relevance of the entrepreneurial ecosystem, greater governmental support is emphasized for promoting an entrepreneurial culture that provides greater access to finance, information, and infrastructure (Rodriguez-Pose, 2013; Audretsch *et al.*, 2015). The relevance of governmental support was thus accentuated as a main component of the entrepreneurial ecosystem and a driver for entrepreneurial creation and growth (i.e. Stam, 2015). On the other hand, the changes in governmental regulations, environmental uncertainty, and the economic sphere were considered contributory external attributions of failure (Rogoff *et al.*, 2004; Arasti, 2011; Atsan, 2016).

Mezher *et al.* (2008) suggest that investigating the entrepreneurial ecosystem in Lebanon involves assessing three main dimensions: macro-environment, micro-environment, and institutional framework. Under the first dimension comes the decreased governmental spending, the reduction in exports, and the inadequacy in local demand faced with high foreign rivalry. The second dimension emphasizes the improper infrastructure, the high competition against small ventures (Rogoff *et al.*, 2004; Eggers and Song, 2014), defective national strategies, unstable market (Eggers and Song, 2014; Boso *et al.*, 2019), and complexity in hiring required talents (Rogoff *et al.*, 2004; Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015). The last dimension represents a huge overload on businesses, structured by high bureaucracy, complex administrative processes, lack of contractual enforcement, improper labour laws, and inadequate taxes (GEM, 2016). All of these hurdles increase the costs for entrepreneurs and, in some instances, discourage operating in the formal economy, as small ventures require an inductive and supportive entrepreneurial ecosystem to sustain and grow.

Conflicting reports and findings on the level of support provided by the Lebanese government for entrepreneurs and business ventures reveal various stances as to the actual support existing (see Figure 12). For instance, GEM (2016) reported Lebanon as providing a solid base for business ventures to be established locally, through the ISSP program and business development centres. El Nemar *et al.* (2016), on the other side, concluded that, with the absence of governmental roles, few private initiatives are undertaken, to find nascent entrepreneurs and assist them in realising business opportunities.

Figure 12: Factors constraining entrepreneurial activity in Lebanon (%)

Source: GEM (2016)

Additionally, Lebanon scored very low in terms of physical infrastructure and governmental policies and programs supporting entrepreneurial initiatives (GEM, 2017). The lack of physical infrastructure and the improper provision of essentials (water, electricity) by public institutions force small ventures to switch to private providers, a fact that makes it more expensive and costly. Furthermore, other services contribute to the struggle and ineffective operations of businesses, such as the slow internet connection and the inexistent public transportation system (GEM 2017:2018). Similarly, Naimy (2011) concluded that the role of government towards entrepreneurship in Lebanon is almost absent, where the majority of this support comes from accelerators and incubators (Goswami *et al.*, 2017). Most financing initiatives in Lebanon are undertaken by commercial banks (refinanced through the central bank of Lebanon) rather than the government. Consequently, the governmental intervention in adjusting the interest rates of supplied funds is deemed as inexistent.

Henceforth, the credit market does not really abide by the law and control of supply and demand and is rather oligopolistic, controlled by banks. Summarised shortly, the lack of governmental intervention makes debt financing barely accessible and highly expensive to business ventures (Naimy, 2011).

A further problem in the Lebanese entrepreneurial ecosystem resides in the availability of market information, as Lebanon lacks a publicly accessible economic (as well as in any other field) database (BLOM Bank, 2018). The acquisition of information that is available and accessible to businesses and sufficiently accurate and valid is considered another challenge for new and small business ventures (Farsi and Toghraee, 2014). Given that the information about the market is not available in most instances, the developed business plans suffer from weakness and reliability, with the impossibility to build projections and forecasts (MET, 2014), affecting pricing decisions and rivalry (Mezher *et al.*, 2008). Therefore, the resulting poor market research is perceived to contribute to entrepreneurial failure (Walsh and Cunningham, 2017). At another level, though the Lebanese market is judged as a free-market economy (GEM, 2017), the oligopolies within the market result in an unlevelled disadvantageous game for new and small ventures (MET, 2014). Another obstacle within the Lebanese entrepreneurial ecosystem comes with the political stability of the country, and the extent to which regional occurrences impact the local market. For instance, as reflected in the OECD report (2019), the negative contribution of the Syrian conflict added to the existing instabilities of the country. The resulting decrease in foreign direct investment, touristic levels, and economic growth affected inversely by the decrease in exports (because of the blocked trading route) reflected negatively on the economic performance of businesses in Lebanon.

A final part of the entrepreneurial ecosystem is the level of support provided by the local culture (Stam, 2015; Audretsch and Belitski, 2017). Culture has been examined and investigated significantly in entrepreneurial research as to its impact on supporting entrepreneurs and promoting entrepreneurial careers in the first place (i.e., Gupta *et al.*, 2010). In a particular city, the social settings (among others) influence the individuals' perceptions of which opportunities might result within this context. In Lebanon, the culture seems to praise the enterprise and attach the entrepreneurial identity with the self-esteem of a highly educated and qualified workforce, providing a sound and strong support for entrepreneurial careers on the political, social, and

cultural levels. Among the 66 participating countries in the GEM report in 2016, the support of the Lebanese social and cultural values to entrepreneurship ranked fifth (GEM, 2016). Interestingly, this evaluation of the social and cultural perspective revealed a low level of fear of failure among potential Lebanese entrepreneurs, where only 2 out of 10 entrepreneurs who perceived opportunities would be reluctant to pursue the entrepreneurial career due to fear of failure (GEM, 2018).

Figure 13: Self-perceptions of Lebanese adults in terms of capabilities and opportunities

Source: GEM (2016)

3.5 Summary

The learning process is essentially founded on the personal definition and understanding of failure while making sense (interpreting) from the experience (Rae and Carswell, 2001; Jenkins, 2012; Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015). Henceforth, entrepreneurs develop ascriptions or explanations for failure through the attribution mechanism (Cardon *et al.*, 2011). The perceived attributions are built according to three main dimensions: locus of causality, controllability, and stability (Weiner, 1985). Perceived attributions affect the learning outcomes, as assessing the reasons of failure determines the need for corrective measures (Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015). Entrepreneurs, then, ascribe failure internally if the failure is perceived to be caused by controllable unstable factors (Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015), which are suggested to build a higher level of learning than the external attribution attached with uncontrollable stable factors (Jenkins, 2012; Eggers and Song, 2014; Yamakawa *et*

al., 2015; Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015; Mandl *et al.*, 2016; Walsh and Cunningham, 2017).

The nature of attribution assigned to failure impacts not only the learning outcomes but also the emotional responses exhibited by entrepreneurs, who reveal a more intense emotional reaction associated with internal attribution (Eggers and Song, 2014; Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015; Walsh and Cunningham, 2017). In narrating their stories of failure, entrepreneurs will either blame themselves, others (Heinze, 2013), or bad luck and misfortune for the failure (Cardon *et al.*, 2011). However, this adoption of the attribution theory is still limited in the context of entrepreneurial failure (Franco and Haase, 2010; Mantere *et al.*, 2013; Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015; Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015), and this linkage between attribution and learning is yet to be comprehensively revealed (Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015).

On the emotional level, failure generates negative emotions (Shepherd, 2003), the activation level of which vary among entrepreneurs (Fang He *et al.*, 2018). The process of coping with failure hence involves dealing with the negative emotions (Shepherd, 2003), given their potential interference with cognitive attention (Wells and Matthew, 1999). Overcoming these emotions is best achieved through an oscillation between the mechanisms of loss orientation and loss restoration (Shepherd, 2003) that enhances the emotional recovery from failure. Similarly, by adopting a consecutive approach of emotion-focused and problem-focused mechanisms (Singh *et al.*, 2007), entrepreneurs may first embrace themselves and their emotions aftermath failure (Haynie and Shepherd, 2011), before cognitively making sense of failure and reflecting upon the experience (Byrne and Shepherd, 2015). Stated otherwise, the high level of negative feelings motivates the process of reflection, while the high level of positive emotions informs it (Byrne and Shepherd, 2015). In regulating their emotions, entrepreneurs with a high level of affective regulation will be more motivated to learn, by expressing dissatisfaction with the controllable factors of failure (Fang He *et al.*, 2018). Such regulation is impacted by the activation level of the negative emotions which eventually determines the emotional resilience of entrepreneurs (Corner *et al.*, 2017) and their motivational and informational attitudes (Fang He *et al.*, 2018).

Developing causal attributions of failure involves assessing the reasons behind the failure, by explaining and evaluating the occurrence of events and personal behaviours, as well as of others' (Martinko *et al.*, 2006), and may occur on the internal and the external levels (Weiner, 1985). Internal attributions involve evaluating and assessing past behaviours, decisions, and actions, in conjunction with counterfactual thinking (Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015). These factors include: the behavioural decision-making adopted in terms of rationality and intuition (Achtziger and Alos-Ferrer, 2014); the level of experience, preparedness, planning, and visionary direction (Dias and Martens, 2019); and entrepreneurial competencies (Chell, 2013). These competencies include: identifying customers' needs (Hunter, 2012); developing strategies (Rowley, 2013) and business plans (Yusuf, 2012); and the ability to act, communicate, take responsibilities, learn, engage and mobilise resources (Minello *et al.*, 2014).

As part of these competencies, the networking skills of entrepreneurs contribute to the survival and growth of business ventures (Baron and Tang, 2009). The reliance of entrepreneurs on their strong, bonding networks in later stages of the venture's life instead of the weak bridging networks that necessitate an initiating behaviour (Zhao *et al.*, 2010) can be contributory to failure (Jansen, 2012; Songini and Gnana, 2014; Lans *et al.*, 2015; Rooks *et al.*, 2016). In parallel, the marketing skills and approach of entrepreneurs contribute to business survival (Hoque and Awang, 2016). Executing the marketing function based on informal, unplanned, and unstructured approaches (Musso and Francioni, 2014) can hinder the venture's survival. This application depends greatly on entrepreneurial personalities (Reijonen, 2008) and can take the form of either self-marketing or reliance on social media (Schaupp and Belanger, 2014) and networks (Reijonen, 2010). In parallel, the recruitment of the very first few employees plays a crucial role in the venture's survival (Darroch, 2005; Wright *et al.*, 2005), which is highly dependent upon the social and role identities of entrepreneurs (Tajfel, 1974), though constrained by the limited resources (Powell and Baker, 2014).

On the external level of attribution comes the finance, governmental support and entrepreneurial ecosystem. The lack of funds, whether attributed to the high criteria of lending by commercial banks (Fatoki, 2014), shortage of venture capitalism (Shane, 2012), or insolvency crisis (Kestens *et al.*, 2012) prohibits entrepreneurs from

surviving and operating. The ecosystem impacts entrepreneurial opportunities of survival to a great extent (Isenberg, 2011; Stam, 2015) through providing an affordable and essential infrastructure (Mezher *et al.*, 2008), appropriate support for financing (Stam, 2015), a supportive legal framework (Naimy, 2011), accessible market information (GEM, 2016), and political stability (OECD, 2019).

Chapters Two and Three reviewed the extant contributions into the field of entrepreneurial learning from failure; the former Chapter reviewed the process of learning, while the current Chapter evaluated the attribution of failure adopted within the learning process. In Chapter Two, the evaluation encompassed the relation between entrepreneurial exit and failure and how learning can be generated from failure. This transformation of experience to knowledge involves several approaches and mechanisms through which entrepreneurs can generate higher levels of learning (on the individual level and the business level). Subsequent to discussing the aftermath costs of failure as well as the long-term outcomes, the Chapter highlighted the moderators of learning from failure and concluded with the obstacles hindering the learning process. Chapter Three discussed further a significant mechanism of this learning process from failure, the attribution theory, and the significance of its dimensions on the nature of learning generated. The Chapter then moved into differentiating the internal and the external factors that guide the development of attributions. By summarising the key contributions into the field of entrepreneurial learning in general and from failure in specific, from 1999 till present chronologically in Table 4, the study moves into highlighting the current gaps in knowledge in the next Chapter.

Author(s) (Year(s))	Research Focus	Main Contributions into the Literature	Research Type (T or E) and Methodology (Qual or Quant)
Cardon and McGrath (1999)	Attribution styles	Two attribution styles emerged: A helpless orientation whereby failure is attributed to ability and, therefore, leads to a propensity to give up and a mastery orientation whereby failure is attributed to lack of effort and generates motivation to exert additional effort. While there is a greater tendency within the sample towards a mastery orientation, there was some variation also.	E-quant
McGrath (1999)	Failure and real options reasoning	Highlights an anti-failure bias. Real options reasoning can lead to a more balanced perspective on the role of entrepreneurial failure in wealth creation. Uncertainty should be managed through pursuing high-variance outcomes, but investing should occur only if conditions are favourable. This can increase profit potential while containing costs	T
Zacharakis <i>et al.</i> (1999)	Attributions and venture capitalism	Contrary to expectations, entrepreneurs were more likely to attribute the causes of venture failure to internal factors as compared to venture capitalists who attributed their failure to external causes. Both entrepreneurs and venture capitalists were, however, more likely to attribute the causes of failure of other ventures to internal factors.	E-qual
Rae (2000)	Discourse in learning	It demonstrates the rich insights which can be gained from discursive life story research. A conceptual model of the significant themes in entrepreneurial learning is proposed. The “living theory” of entrepreneurship is a cultural, discursive resource which may be discovered and interpreted through the narrative medium	E-qual
Rae and Carswell (2000)	Education and entrepreneurial learning	Proposes a conceptual model of entrepreneurial learning, and assesses its implications for designing entrepreneurship education and development programmes. Findings indicate that there would be benefits from designing development programmes for current and aspirant business owners	E-qual
Minniti and Bygrave (2001)	Entrepreneurial learning from failure	The authors argued that entrepreneurs repeat only those choices that appear most promising and discard the ones that resulted in failure by providing a structural model of entrepreneurial learning in which failure is as informative—though clearly not as desirable—as success	T
Stokes and Blackburn (2002)	Stigma and serial entrepreneurship	The results suggest that some common assumptions need challenging in order to remove the stigma from closing down a business. The overall conclusion is that the closure process can represent a positive, learning experience. This provides further support for the concept of the serial entrepreneur.	E-mixed

Cope (2003)	Reflection on failure and learning	Discontinuous events have the capacity to stimulate distinctive forms of 'higher-level' learning—learning that is fundamental to the entrepreneur in both personal and business terms. It goes on to explore the concept of critical reflection and suggests that these learning outcomes are the result of what can be described most precisely as 'inward' critical self-reflection	E-qual
Shepherd (2003)	Grief and recovery from failure	Grief is a negative emotion that can distract the entrepreneur from objective reflection of the business failure. Thus, Shepherd suggests to oscillate between focusing on healing from the negative emotion (restoration orientation) and focusing on the failure and its causes (loss orientation) as the best path toward learning	T
Ucbasaran <i>et al.</i> (2003)	Attributions and explanatory style	The interaction between attribution of causes of failure and explanatory style (learned optimism versus learned helplessness) will influence decisions to engage in subsequent entrepreneurial activity following failure.	T
Rogoff <i>et al.</i> (2004)	Attribution biases	Provides evidence of attribution bias among entrepreneurs: Entrepreneurs tend to attribute their success to internal causes (more than entrepreneurship experts) and to identify barriers to their success as external (more than entrepreneurship experts)	E-quant
Shepherd (2004)	Education in regulating emotions from failure	Offers suggestions for pedagogical changes to help students manage the emotions of learning from failure.	T
Coelho and McClure (2005)	Definitional issues and social costs	Argues for the practical benefits of failure: It is better to pull the plug on an uneconomic venture early than to escalate commitments in hope. Perseverance and optimism are valuable entrepreneurial traits, but need to be governed by knowledge and realism.	T
Cope (2005)	Learning process from failure	Informed by qualitative empirical work with practicing entrepreneurs (Cope, 2001), this conceptual article works toward an integrated understanding of entrepreneurial learning by proposing three different yet interconnected elements of a learning perspective of entrepreneurship: dynamic temporal phases, interrelated processes, and overarching characteristics.	T
Politis (2005)	Transformation of experience to Knowledge	Politis conceptualizes learning as a process that transforms various kinds of entrepreneurial career experience (start-up/management/industry related) into entrepreneurial knowledge. This knowledge can either lead to improved opportunity recognition or superior coping capacity with the liabilities of newness. The extent to which each form of knowledge is created is influenced by the manner of transformation.	T

Rae (2005)	Process of entrepreneurial learning	It proposed a conceptual framework of entrepreneurial learning as a triadic model, including major themes of personal and social emergence, contextual learning, the negotiated enterprise, and a group of 11 related sub-themes.	E-qual
Rerup (2005)	Mindfulness and subsequent venturing	Drawing on mindfulness, he explains that in situations with high similarity between two ventures and low level of change, extended levels of (costly) mindfulness might be suboptimal. Thus, mindfulness is an important factor, however not only positive	T
Rae (2006)	Social learning and learning from experience	The paper develops a framework for analysing entrepreneurial learning through in-depth analysis of entrepreneurial experiences by using discourse analysis based on a social learning perspective. This conceptual framework includes three major themes of personal and social emergence, contextual learning and the negotiated enterprise, and 11 related sub-themes.	E-qual
Schutjens and Stam (2006)	Cognitive and behavioural outcomes	Finds that the large majority of entrepreneurs who had closed their businesses had restart intentions, and almost one in four closures was followed by the creation of a new business. Finds that the drivers of restart intentions and actual restart differ	E-quant
Singh <i>et al.</i> (2007)	Learning outcomes from failure	According to this qualitative study, business failures lead to economic, social, psychological and physiological learning outcomes	E-qual
Vaillant and Lafuente (2007)	Institutional theory, social costs, and stigma	Belief in the existence of a social stigma to entrepreneurial failure is an important constraint for entrepreneurial activity in Spain.	E-quant
Huovinen and Tihula (2008)	Portfolio entrepreneurs and learning	Examining the experiences of a portfolio entrepreneur, the authors test and confirm the conceptual framework of Politis (2005) empirically	E-qual
Stam <i>et al.</i> (2008)	Learning and subsequent venturing	The authors argue that one visible outcome of learning is the fact that even in case of failure people re-engage in entrepreneurial activity. If they did not believe in learning– from the perspective of the homo oeconomicus–there would be no reason to restart	E-quant
Pretorius (2008)	Future research on Failure	A line of enquiry firstly reviews the documented research (both theoretical and empirical) encompassing the phenomenon ‘business failure’ on a multidisciplinary basis. A conceptual framework is then proposed for categorising variables into: signs and prediction; causes and preconditions; recovery; and cognition and learning.	T
Politis and Gabrielsson (2009)	Prior entrepreneurial experience and perception of failure	The study finds that critical experiences in terms of founding and closing businesses positively impact the attitude toward business failure	E-quant

Shepherd <i>et al.</i> (2009)	Delaying failure, recovery and learning	The authors discuss the phenomenon of delaying business failure. This behaviour typically leads to high financial costs and thus harms recovery. Yet, under some circumstances, delaying a failure may help to balance financial and emotional costs. As a result, the overall recovery and subsequent entrepreneurial action can be promoted	T
Ucbasaran <i>et al.</i> (2009)	Psychological costs and behavioural outcomes	It detects an inverse U-shaped relationship between the proportion of failed businesses relative to the number of businesses owned and the number of opportunities identified in a given period. Business failure can encourage learning without dampening motivation but only when it can be placed within the context of non-failing businesses. Calls for the integration of cognitive/learning and motivational perspectives on failure.	E-quant
Hayward <i>et al.</i> (2010)	Financial costs, social costs, psychological costs, and their management	It argues that highly confident entrepreneurs are more likely to rebound from failure because they are likely to have developed greater emotional, cognitive, social, and financial resilience that can be mobilized in subsequent ventures. These forms of resilience are seen as second-order benefits of overconfidence that provide a counterweight to the more immediate costs of being overconfident (which can increase the chances of failure).	T
Ucbasaran <i>et al.</i> (2010)	Cognitive biases: optimism and failure	Ucbasaran <i>et al.</i> (2010) argue that over optimism is a specific trait of entrepreneurs and at the same time an important antecedent to failure. While portfolio entrepreneurs—through experience—become more realistic (decreasing the tendency of being over-optimistic), this is not true for serial entrepreneurs	E-quant
Cardon <i>et al.</i> (2011)	Sense-making and attributions	It demonstrates variation in how communities make sense of failure. Shows regional variation in the extent to which failures can be attributed to misfortunes or mistakes made by entrepreneurs. Examines the implications for individual entrepreneurs	E-qual
Cope (2011)	Learning process from failure, emotions and learning outcomes	Learning from failure is a process highly related with emotional feelings. Outcomes of this reflective process may be various learning contents: learning about oneself, about one's venture, about networks and about venture management	E-qual
Pretorius and Le Roux (2011)	Active learning and reflection process	The lack of learning of the interviewee is attributed to the fact that the entrepreneur never had entered a stage of reflection. Instead, following business failure entrepreneurs immediately re-emerged in another entrepreneurial endeavour	E-qual

Shepherd and Haynie (2011)	Impression management, attribution, and stigma	Entrepreneurs stigmatized by failure may use impression management strategies to align their self-conceptions with how others see them even if this means adopting a negative self-view. This counterintuitive behaviour may have positive effects on the entrepreneur's psychological well-being	T
Ucbasaran <i>et al.</i> (2011)	Serial entrepreneurs, biases and attribution	Serial entrepreneurs are found not to reflect on failures and thus do not learn from one attempt to the next. The reasons are overconfidence and wrong attributions. In fact, serial entrepreneurs (different to portfolio entrepreneurs) — potentially as a coping mechanism—attribute the causes of failures to external factors	E-quant
Pittaway and Thorpe (2012)	Emotional recovery and learning	Review and evaluation of the contribution to entrepreneurial learning by Jason Cope. Divided into three sub-chapters the paper illustrates Cope's research summarizing it into a conceptual framework	T
Heinze (2013)	Social interactions, learning and emotions	The study explores the sense-making of six entrepreneurs who experienced business failure. Particular attention is paid to the influence of the entrepreneurs' social environment. Findings reveal that social interactions triggered strong emotions that interfere with learning.	E-qual
Mantere <i>et al.</i> (2013)	Attributions of failure	The study finds attribution differences of entrepreneurial failure between entrepreneurs, hired executives, employees and the media. Further, a fine-grained set of possible attributions is provided, forming a continuum between internal and external attribution	E-qual
Parker (2013)	Learning from Serial entrepreneurship	Based on an investigation of performance trajectories of serial entrepreneurs the authors find that learning does exist. However, according to human capital theory, this positive influence depreciates over time, limiting the possibility of "cumulative learning"	E-quant
Ucbasaran <i>et al.</i> (2013)	Reflection and sense-making process of failure	Ucbasaran <i>et al.</i> (2013) argue that failure triggers sense-making, a process consisting of interrelated stages of scanning, interpretation and learning. This process is influenced by attributions and emotions. The outcome may be a change in behaviour	T
Coad (2014)	Definitional issues of failure	Critical evaluation of the tendency to see business failure—based on the assumption of being a valuable opportunity for learning—as something positive. The author reminds of the lack of large-scale empirical evidence supporting the positive effect of failure on learning	T
Eggers and Song (2014)	Entrepreneurial learning and attributions	Learning from failure is difficult due to erroneous attributions: Entrepreneurs attribute the reasons for their failure primarily to external factors. Therefore, they change these factors (namely: the sector) when opening their subsequent business while retaining other internal aspects (management etc.). Therefore, sector-specific knowledge cannot be transferred properly leading to poorer performance	E-quant

Jenkins <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Appraisal theory	It argued that how the entrepreneur interprets failure can account for the variance in entrepreneurs' response to firm failure. The findings found support that how failure is interpreted in terms of loss of self-esteem and financial loss has important implications for how entrepreneurs feel after experiencing firm failure.	E-quant
Paik (2014)	Serial entrepreneurship	According to Paik, serial entrepreneurs perform – regardless of their prior venture experience being a success or failure – better than novice entrepreneurs	E-quant
Byrne and Shepherd (2015)	Emotions and learning from failure	The authors examined the relationship between emotion and perceived learning. Most perceived learning is reported by those who initially felt negative emotions changing to positive emotional status after the failure. This implies that negative emotions act as trigger for sense-making, whereas positive emotions are important for broadening and building knowledge	E-qual
Singh <i>et al.</i> (2015)	Stigma and learning from failure	The study explores the role of stigma for learning from failure. Stigma ends when the failed entrepreneur experiences a so-called epiphany, a moment of insight. From this moment he or she sees failure as something positive and is ready to make use of learning outcomes—either in form of entrepreneurial re-engagement or alternative applications (e.g. consultancy)	E-qual
Yamakawa and Cardon (2015)	Attributions and perceived learning	Failure ascriptions (how the core causal characteristics of a failure are identified) influence perceived learning from failure. In fact, internal unstable failure ascriptions with a short time between failure and restart lead to higher perceived learning, whereas external stable ascriptions with domain abandonment further deteriorate learning potential.	E-quant
Yamakawa <i>et al.</i> (2015)	Internal Attributions and learning from failure	Failure does not automatically lead to learning and thus superior venture performance in the future. Internal attribution of failure is necessary, excessively high levels of internal attributions may lead to a sense of shame and guilt preventing the entrepreneur from re-engaging in entrepreneurial activities	E-quant
Jenkins and McKelvie (2016)	Categorisation of entrepreneurial learning	The authors discuss and map existing conceptualizations of failure. The emerging framework distinguishes between objective and subjective as well as individual-level and firm-level failures. Based on this structure, the various conceptualizations, their origins in literature and potential future application fields are discussed and links to learning provided	T

Mueller and Shepherd (2016)	Cognitive learning outcomes	The authors find that failure is linked to a specific type of thinking–structural alignment. While the main effect between failure experience and the use of structural alignment processes was not significant, this study found that when coupled with the proper cognitive tools (expert opportunity prototypes, cognitive style), failure experience can be beneficial in the long run, helping to equip individuals for success in subsequent ventures (at least in the identification of opportunities)	E-mixed
Nielsen and Sarasvathy (2016)	Active learning	Entrepreneurial learning is possible, but it does not happen automatically. It requires, in particular, a stock of knowledge – in order to allow highly educated entrepreneurs to learn from exit. On the other side, entrepreneurs who see business failure per se as a rich source for learning, might fail due to overconfidence bias	E-quant
Corner <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Emotional resilience and subsequent venturing	Applying a qualitative research approach, the authors find that the majority of entrepreneurs within their sample show emotional resilience after their failure, challenging the common assumption that entrepreneurs have to pass through a process of recovery after failure in order to learn and successfully re-emerge	E-qual
Dias and Teixeira (2017)	Process of entrepreneurial learning	This qualitative study on business failure investigates – on the basis of the conceptualization of Ucbasaran <i>et al.</i> (2013) – the aftermath of failure events. Thereby, one aspect examined was learning. The results are in line with the theoretical reasoning of Ucbasaran <i>et al.</i> (2013)	E-qual
Walsh and Cunningham (2017)	Attribution theory	The study finds that the attribution of business failure influences the entrepreneur’s response and subsequently the learning focus	E-qual
Amankwah-Amoah <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Learning and the imprinting process in subsequent venturing	Developed an evolutionary phase model to explain how prior business failure experience influences successive newly started businesses. Applying a multiple case analysis, they discovered four sub-processes: grief and despair (1), transition (2), formation (3) and legacy (4).	E – qual
Fang He <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Failure velocity and learning behaviours	The authors develop and test a model that links failure velocity and learning behaviours. They find an inverted U-shaped relationship between failure velocity and learning behaviours. Further, they investigate emotion regulation to moderate this relationship	E-quant
Boso <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Business failure experience only influences subsequent venture performance	A model is created and successfully tested that links business failure to new venture performance. Thereby, learning is found to play a mediating role. The influence of learning on new venture performance is moderated by the entrepreneur’s alertness	E- quant

Espinoza-Benavides and Diaz (2019)	Learning outcomes and subsequent venturing	The study compares personal characteristics of entrepreneurs who reengage after a prior entrepreneurial failure with characteristics of first-time entrepreneurs. Among other differences, the authors find that “failed” entrepreneurs possess significantly superior skills and knowledge, which are attributed to learning	E-quant
Dias and Martens (2019)	Learning from failure and subsequent venturing	Findings demonstrate that reflection following the failure event leads to learning that has the potential to positively influence subsequent venture emergence and performance	E-qual
Lafuente <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Serial entrepreneurial learning	The study finds that serial entrepreneurs show significantly improved cognitive capacity and increased levels of international orientation compared to their novice counterparts. These differences apply to cases of prior failure and prior success both. However, previously failed entrepreneurs were found—despite reporting rich learning—to be less likely to re-engage in entrepreneurship	E-mixed
Lin <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Entrepreneurial learning and subsequent venturing	The study links learning from failure with changes in strategic behaviour upon entrepreneurial re-emergence. Applying a perspective of strategic incrementalism, the authors provide evidence that previously failed entrepreneurs, who engage intensively in learning, exhibit in their new venturing episodes more proactive strategic actions	E-quant
Liu <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Narcissism and entrepreneurial learning	The authors find that narcissism has a negative impact on learning from failure. This particularly applies in cases when the costs of failure (especially: social costs) are high	E-quant
Nahata (2019)	Serial entrepreneurs and learning	The study reveals that on the strength of their entrepreneurial learning, serial entrepreneurs negotiate more favourable venture capital deal terms than their novice counterparts. This pattern applies to previously “failed” entrepreneurs as well as to successful ones	E-quant
Wei <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Influencers of entrepreneurial learning	Based on a literature analysis, 24 factors influencing entrepreneurial learning from failure are detected. These factors are grouped in a hierarchical order. The emerging system is subsequently empirically evaluated by one single case study	T

Table 4: Key contributions into the literature since 1999 (by chronological order)

"Failure isn't fatal, but failure to change might be" – John Wooden

4 Chapter Four: Literature Gap

4.1 Introduction

This Chapter continues with the literature review, by presenting the most contributing models of entrepreneurial learning as developed by scholars over years. Throughout the Chapter, the researcher will emphasise the gaps in the extant knowledge on entrepreneurial learning from failure from two perspectives: the practical gap of having a comprehensive learning model that integrates attribution on the individual level through business aspects, and the literature gap emerging from the shortage of studies that explore in-depth the attribution process. The learning models presented herein will be evaluated as to their focus on failure attribution, depth of exploration and the context for which the model has been developed. The researcher will justify the unsuitability of these learning models for the study, despite their significant theoretical and empirical contribution to the field. Furthermore, the Chapter continues with addressing the knowledge gaps by categorising the contributions of the most influential scholars and academics in the field according to their investigation focus.

4.2 Entrepreneurial Learning Frameworks

In their attempt to understand the learning process implemented by entrepreneurs to learn from their experiences, researchers (i.e., Rae, 2000; Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015; Walsh and Cunningham, 2017) have developed several learning models, according to the focus and scope of their research. By evaluating the content and scope of each framework and model of the most influential researchers, this section aims to highlight the shortcomings of these models for the current study (a more detailed explanation is outlined in Appendix F). More specifically, the evaluation of the extant learning models (as summarised in Table 5) revealed four main limitations:

- a) Emphasis on success rather than failure, i.e., Rae (2000) and Rae (2005);
- b) Focus overlooked the attribution process with which entrepreneurs ascribe failure to other dimensions of the learning process, i.e., Politis (2005), Cope (2011), Petkova (2008), and Wei *et al.* (2019);
- c) Primary and undetailed investigation of the internal failure attributions developed by entrepreneurs, i.e., Yamakawa *et al.* (2015) and Yamakawa and Cardon (2015); and
- d) Geographical concentration on developed contexts with rare research in developing and emerging contexts.

Despite these limitations, the reviewed models have contributed to a more enhanced understanding of entrepreneurial learning in general, and from failure in particular. However, the attribution process with which entrepreneurs develop explanations of failure and ascribe causes for the negative event is still under-explored on the individual level (Ucbasaran *et al.*, 2013; Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015; Fang He *et al.*, 2018), and hence requires deeper exploration. Therefore, this study will address the practical shortage of a comprehensive process on entrepreneurial learning from failure that integrates the attribution theory on the individual level.

Framework (Model)	Contribution	Limitation
Rae and Carswell (2000)	Process of entrepreneurial learning is revealed as an interaction between the personal theory and the known capabilities, along with the social learning from individual relationships and willingness to actively learn, and to energise the personal values leading eventually to the achievement of goals. Also, enhances the entrepreneurs' ability of reaching venture goals (Rae and Carswell, 2000)	Developed for the context of entrepreneurial success rather than failure. Furthermore, it does not embrace the peculiarities of failure as a negative event, such as the negative emotions and costs experienced aftermath. Hence, the model is not suggested to assist in recovering and learning from failure
Rae (2005)	Entrepreneurial formation occurs through negotiated connections with others, rather than by a single person. By engaging in interactive relations with others, individuals may be more able to realise their ambitions, and these social connections may include any stakeholder of the venture. For the learning to successfully happen in this case, the ability of entrepreneurs to engage with people is highly significant	This model was developed based on the entrepreneurial experience with no special consideration to the failure experience, which necessitates more of a combined approach of cognition and social constructivism, to allow for the embracing of the rational, as well as the emotional reflection on failure (Ucbasaran <i>et al.</i> , 2013; Yamakawa <i>et al.</i> , 2015).
Politis (2005)	In investigating how the entrepreneurial experience generates knowledge, Politis (2005) suggested that scholars need to understand the mode of transformation employed by entrepreneurs, and which factors influence this mode of processing. As the learning process is not acquired automatically as a consequence for having entrepreneurial experience, the transformation process holds the weight for the whole process, by generating the knowledge from that experience (Kolb, 1984).	This model is, first, built on the basis of the experiential learning theory and second, lacks the integration of attribution as a cognitive process that assists in the transformation of experience into knowledge. The experiential theory of learning reflects only on few factors that led to the failure, besides decontextualizing the learning process (Kayes, 2002).
Petkova (2008)	It outlined how errors detected in performance can be a significant source of learning for entrepreneurs. The model adopts the cognitive theory and hence proposes three processes that generate the learning: outcome	The model is essentially conceptual, focusing on the performance errors resulting from the knowledge possessed by the entrepreneurs, and limited the discussion and integration of attribution to the

	generation, error detection and error correction. By correcting their errors, entrepreneurs either specialise their general knowledge structures or refine these specialisations.	biases generated by individuals: self-serving bias and attributional style.
Cope (2011)	Cope provided a comprehensive explanatory model of the failure, outlining how the learning is processed. It started with handling the costs resulting from failure, recovering from grief, and then reflecting over the failure to generate higher levels of learning.	Despite the comprehensiveness of this framework, the attribution in its various dimensions during the reflective process associated with the loss orientation was not explored.
Heinze (2013)	It contributed into understanding the sense-making of the failure experience, apart from economic terms. Social interactions trigger strong emotions, some of them last disappear after a while (e.g. grief, confusion, worrying about financial costs), whereas more long-lasting emotions persist (e.g. distrust and betrayal).	This process mainly concentrated on the emotional dimension of the failure, and the resulting coping mechanism with these emotions. Therefore, such emphasised focus on the emotions may not be relevant to the current study that aims into investigating the attributions and their impact on the learning process.
Yamakawa <i>et al.</i> (2015)	Internal attribution generates greater learning, which ultimately enhances the performance of subsequent entrepreneurial endeavours, this benefit is dependent on the motivation of entrepreneurs positively, and on the number of previous failures negatively. In other words, the greater the motivation and/or the lower the number of previous failures, the higher the knowledge to be created from the previous experiences.	It categorises the failure as statistical single-item measures where the main variables of internal and external attribution were listed as discrete options in a quantitative survey, overlooking the linkage that may have existed among the various attributions' categories.
Yamakawa and Cardon (2015)	A learning model that outlines the impact of internal and external ascriptions of failure, as perceived by entrepreneurs, on the learning outcomes. Two moderators were considered impactful on the learning process: time taken by entrepreneurs to restart; and abandoning the domain of prior business.	It categorises the failure as statistical single-item measures where the main variables of internal and external attribution were listed as discrete options in a quantitative survey, overlooking the linkage that may have existed among the various attributions' categories.
Walsh and Cunningham (2017)	It outlines the process of learning from failure, which eventually leads to the regeneration step, defined as re-engagement in entrepreneurial activities. The model emerged from investigating the linkage between attribution and learning on three levels: internal, external and hybrid; the responses associated with each level leading to the learning dimensions and resulting from each agree with Cope's (2011) model.	This study overlooked the interaction and interconnection among the various levels of resulted learning. In other words, the learning dimensions may not possess clear-cut boundaries. More importantly, the responses of entrepreneurs focused on the primary attributions without consideration for the iterative nature of responses which could shed light on nuances between attributions and learning
Amankwah-Amoah <i>et al.</i> (2018)	In investigating how the learning and imprinting processes of entrepreneurs from failure impact the nature of subsequent ventures, the authors contributed by developing the evolutionary phase framework that	This model focuses on the imprinting processes exhibited in subsequent ventures and therefore, is less relevant to this study that focuses more thoroughly on the second phase of the imprinting

	outlines the transitional mechanisms of failure on the processes, behaviours and routines of business ventures through four phases: grief, transition, formation and legacy	process. However, in this stage, the reflective transition, the model did not take into consideration the role of attribution and its impact on conceptualising learning.
Wei <i>et al.</i> (2019)	The authors developed a structural, hierarchical model of the most fifteen impactful factors, and impacted directly only by the self-efficacy of entrepreneurs and their regulatory process of emotions.	Though this study identified the key factors affecting directly or indirectly the learning from failure, it cannot be employed in this study as it does not reflect the process with which the individual factors are elaborated, connected and integrated into the learning process.

Table 5: Entrepreneurial learning models

4.3 Contributions and Research Gaps

Under this section, the researcher has categorised the key contributions in the field of entrepreneurial learning in general (previously summarised in Chapter 3, Table 4), and from failure in particular within a four-quadrant diagram (see Table 6). The diagram in Table 6 aims into classifying the most relevant literature on entrepreneurial learning from failure according to two main criteria: the research focus (outcomes or process) and the research approach (conceptual or empirical) (adapted from Althonayan, 2003). Henceforth, four Quadrants of categorisation resulted: Quadrant I, which outlines the studies undertaken in investigating the process of entrepreneurial learning (from failure) with theoretical contributions; Quadrant II, which represents the empirical contributions of researching this process; Quadrant III, which highlights the studies conducted in exploring conceptually the learning outcomes from failure (cognitive, emotional and behavioural); and Quadrant IV, which represents the empirical inquiries on these outcomes.

Such categorisation of the existing contributions on the field of entrepreneurial learning from failure reveals two main gaps: the **limited** empirical studies conducted so far to understand the process of learning and its outcomes (Quadrants III and IV), emerging from the **recent** empirical concentration accentuated only lately. However, the outcomes of the learning process from failure emphasised in Quadrant IV will only result from an active, engaging, and deliberate learning process that generates knowledge from previous failing experiences (Fang He *et al.*, 2018). Henceforth, investigating the learning behaviours undertaken by entrepreneurs constitutes a

critical step to achieve the impact of these perceived outcomes on subsequent entrepreneurial activities (Lin *et al.*, 2019).

		Research Approach	
		Conceptual Quadrant I	Empirical Quadrant II
Research Focus	Learning Process (sense-making, attribution, reflection)	Minniti and Bygrave (2001); Shepherd (2003); Ucbasaran <i>et al.</i> (2003); Cope (2005); Politis (2005); Rerup (2005); Pretorius (2008); Shepherd <i>et al.</i> (2009); Shepherd and Haynie (2011); Ucbasaran <i>et al.</i> (2013); Coad (2014); Jenkins and McKelvie (2016).	Cardon and McGrath (1999); Zacharakis <i>et al.</i> (1999); Rae (2000,2006); Rae and Carswell (2000); Cope (2003); Rogoff <i>et al.</i> (2004); Politis and Gabriellsson (2009); Ucbasaran <i>et al.</i> (2010); Cardon <i>et al.</i> (2011); Pretorius and Le Roux (2011); Ucbasaran <i>et al.</i> (2011); Heinze (2013); Mantere <i>et al.</i> (2013); Eggers and Song (2014); Jenkins <i>et al.</i> (2014); Byrne and Shepherd (2015); Singh <i>et al.</i> (2015); Yamakawa <i>et al.</i> (2015); Yamakawa and Cardon (2015); Mueller and Shepherd (2016); Nielsen and Sarasvathy (2016); Dias and Teixeira (2017); Walsh and Cunningham (2017).
	Outcomes (emotional, behavioural, and cognitive)	Shepherd (2003); Pretorius (2008); Shepherd <i>et al.</i> (2009); Hayward <i>et al.</i> (2010); Shepherd and Haynie (2011); Pittaway and Thorpe (2012); Wei <i>et al.</i> (2019).	Stokes and Blackburn (2002); Schutjens and Stam (2006); Singh <i>et al.</i> (2007); Vaillant and Lafuente (2007); Politis and Gabriellsson (2009); Ucbasaran <i>et al.</i> (2009); Cardon <i>et al.</i> (2011); Cope (2011); Heinze (2013); Parker (2013); Jenkins <i>et al.</i> (2014); Byrne and Shepherd (2015); Mueller and Shepherd (2016); Corner <i>et al.</i> (2017); Amankwah-Amoah <i>et al.</i> (2018); Fang He <i>et al.</i> (2018); Boso <i>et al.</i> (2019); Espinoza-Benavides and Diaz (2019); Dias and Martens (2019); Lafuente <i>et al.</i> (2019); Lin <i>et al.</i> (2019); Liu <i>et al.</i> (2019); Nahata (2019).

Table 6: Categorisation of the relevant literature on learning from failure

Source: Adapted from Althonayan (2003)

As outlined in Table 6, a growing, though limited, interest in researching entrepreneurial failure has expanded the academic and practical comprehension on the process of entrepreneurial learning from business failures (Benson and Han, 2011; Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015). Despite this increasing number of studies on entrepreneurial learning, the understanding of the process with which the experience is translated into knowledge-learning is still incomplete (Wei *et al.*, 2019). So far, it

is known that this learning process does not occur automatically (Shepherd, 2003) and hence depends significantly on the sense-making undertaken by entrepreneurs (Kolb, 1984) through the ascribed explanations developed to rationalise failure (Mandl *et al.*, 2016). As a result, understanding the impact of individual learning on entrepreneurial behaviour necessitates a thorough study of the ways with which entrepreneurs develop entrepreneurial approaches and attitudes.

As a result, scholars (i.e., Zacharakis *et al.*, 1999; Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015) recommended future researchers to focus on understanding how the process of attribution affects learning outcomes. More specifically, future studies shall explore how entrepreneurs balance understanding the causes of failure and their capabilities to learn from this failure (Eggers and Song, 2014). Henceforth, the investigation of learning outcomes and the process of sense-making from failure has witnessed more recent focus, responding to the call for investigating deeper the process with which entrepreneurs reflect on and learn from failure. However, despite the expansion in the literature on the process of learning (i.e., Politis and Gabrielsson, 2009; Cope, 2011) and the impact of experiencing failure on subsequent venturing activities (Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015), only little is known on how entrepreneurs learn from failure and shape their behaviours, practices and processes assumed to be adopted in future ventures (Amankwah-Amoah *et al.*, 2018). In other words, the majority of research on learning from failure did not consider how the ascriptions of failure by entrepreneurs affect this learning process and its outcomes (Cardon *et al.*, 2011; Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015).

In summary, entrepreneurial learning and entrepreneurial failure still constitute an interesting field that needs to be investigated (McGrath *et al.*, 1999; Ucbasaran *et al.*, 2013), with the aim to explore the event, its consequences, and its learning outcomes, due to the impact of this learning on future entrepreneurial activities (Boso *et al.*, 2019). In the same vein, Ucbasaran *et al.* (2010) suggested that researchers shall understand better the process with which failing entrepreneurs develop plausible discourses about their venture failure. These explanations and attributions of failure as perceived by entrepreneurs are social constructs that result from the process of sense-making (Cardon *et al.*, 2011).

Consequently, this research responds to scholars' call (i.e., Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015; Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015; Walsh and Cunningham, 2017) to understand

qualitatively the behavioural changes in entrepreneurs, subsequent to experiencing entrepreneurial failure, by exploring in-depth the perceived attributions of failure. Adopting narratives in data collection provides the advantage of advancing the recall of entrepreneurs about these critical experiences (Flick, 2018). Therefore, this study will address the knowledge gaps within the field over four main levels: the developing context; the process of attribution; empirical evidence; and linkage between attributions and learning. More specifically, this research aims into exploring: *the causal attributions* of failure as perceived by entrepreneurs through narratives; *the dimensions and nature* of each attribution perceived by entrepreneurs; and *the impact* of these attributions on the emotional, cognitive, and behavioural outcomes generated as learning.

4.4 Research Conceptual Framework

As highlighted throughout the previous Chapters, this research paper will adopt the lens of the attribution theory (Weiner, 1985) in order to understand the reflection process undertaken by entrepreneurs to make sense and learn from their failures. This reflection process starts essentially with the occurrence of the failure event of the enterprise. Facing failure, entrepreneurs consequently exhibit a negative emotional response (Shepherd, 2003), given the personal attachment that is usually developed between the entrepreneur and the enterprise (Cardon *et al.*, 2009). Taking into consideration the potential impact of negative emotions on rationalising failure and learning from it, entrepreneurs implement a coping mechanism that allows them to deal with the event of failure.

In connection with the coping mechanism implemented, failing entrepreneurs reflect on failure and attempt to rationalise the path of the enterprise. This reflection process involves developing explanations for the event of failure according to the entrepreneurs' personal definition and understanding of failure. By re-examining what went wrong over the failure of the enterprise, the reflection process on the entrepreneurial experience allows for the formulation of causal relationships. Therefore, these attributions of failure are developed on the basis of three aspects: *locus of causality* (internal or external causes); *controllability*, (perceived controllable or uncontrollable factors); and *stability*, (perceived stable or unstable factors) (Weiner, 1985). Rationalising the causes of failure allows for a subsequent assessment of the actions taken, and for a speculation of corrective measures in future enterprises

(Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015), which in return emphasises the relevance of the attribution theory.

In explaining the event of failure and their personal behaviours, as well as those of others', entrepreneurs eventually develop minor and major attributions of failure. These causal explanations, perceived as the reasons for failure from their perspectives, affect the extent of learning from the entrepreneurial experience. In other words, the level and nature of attributions developed impact the level of learning. More specifically, the perceived instability of internal attributions induces higher learning (Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015). The result would be an opportunity for a deep, transformative learning at the individual level, as well at the venture level, by assessing the strengths and weaknesses of the venture (Cope, 2005).

At the social level, failure allows entrepreneurs to reflect on the type and management of networks and relationships, whether within or outside the business (Cope, 2005). On the contrary, the learning that results from external attributions is limited to generalised observations without an intensive reflection on the personal level and will be limited to the external learning. As a result, a high level of learning occurs when the major attributions of failure are therefore internal, while the hybrid ascriptions result in the highest comprehensive form of entrepreneurial learning (Walsh and Cunningham, 2017). Therefore, when the learning occurs on the internal level with internal attributions, the external level of learning is a consequent outcome. However, the internal level of learning does not occur with external attributions and thus necessitates the personal sense of responsibility to occur. Therefore, the resulting conceptual framework guiding the thesis is summarised in Figure 14 below.

Figure 14: Research Conceptual Framework

5 Chapter Five: Research Methodology

5.1 Philosophical Stance

The research philosophy represents the researchers' perspective of the world and is usually called the paradigm or system of beliefs that directs researchers in their investigation (Guba and Lincoln, 1994). In selecting the most suitable philosophy for answering the research questions, the researcher reviewed the most relevant ontology, epistemology, methodology and axiology (Yilmaz, 2013).

The ontological perspective embraces the philosophical assumptions made by humans to understand reality and the truth behind a social phenomenon. Ontology, therefore, questions the researchers' assumption of actuality and existence, and the system of personal beliefs employed to analyse the data collected (Scotland, 2012). Epistemology, on the other hand, is the methodology followed to understand the reality lying out there (Saunders *et al.*, 2009). In other words, epistemology is concerned with the means of acquiring, gaining, communicating, and understanding knowledge about the world.

Research-wise, epistemology relates to the researchers' acquisition of knowledge and understanding that is capable of deepening, extending, and broadening the field of the study. Subsequently, epistemology can be defined as the justification of knowledge (Schwandt, 1997), where researchers, being positioned within the context of the study, can discover new knowledge (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017). Finally, the choice of methodology represents selecting the relevant set of approaches, techniques, design, and procedures (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017). In connection with methodology, the researcher had to take into consideration axiology, which represents the ethical concerns associated with any prospective study, by determining the nature of proper and improper decisions when conducting research (Finnis, 1980).

Ontology (nature of reality or being)	Epistemology (what constitutes acceptable knowledge)	Axiology (role of values)	Typical methods
Positivism			
Real, external, independent One true reality (universalism) Granular (things) Ordered	Scientific method Observable and measurable facts Law-like generalisations Numbers Causal explanation and prediction as contribution	Value-free research Researcher is detached, neutral and independent of what is researched Researcher maintains objective stance	Typically deductive, highly structured, large samples, measurement, typically quantitative methods of analysis, but a range of data can be analysed
Critical realism			
Stratified/layered (the empirical, the actual and the real) External, independent Intransient Objective structures Causal mechanisms	Epistemological relativism Knowledge historically situated and transient Facts are social constructions Historical causal explanation as contribution	Value-laden research Researcher acknowledges bias by world views, cultural experience and upbringing Researcher tries to minimise bias and errors Researcher is as objective as possible	Retroductive, in-depth historically situated analysis of pre-existing structures and emerging agency. Range of methods and data types to fit subject matter
Interpretivism			
Complex, rich Socially constructed through culture and language Multiple meanings, interpretations, realities Flux of processes, experiences, practices	Theories and concepts too simplistic Focus on narratives, stories, perceptions and interpretations New understandings and worldviews as contribution	Value-bound research Researchers are part of what is researched, subjective Researcher interpretations key to contribution Researcher reflexive	Typically inductive. Small samples, in-depth investigations, qualitative methods of analysis, but a range of data can be interpreted
Postmodernism			
Nominal Complex, rich Socially constructed through power relations Some meanings, interpretations, realities are dominated and silenced by others Flux of processes, experiences, practices	What counts as 'truth' and 'knowledge' is decided by dominant ideologies Focus on absences, silences and oppressed/repressed meanings, interpretations and voices Exposure of power relations and challenge of dominant views as contribution	Value-constituted research Researcher and research embedded in power relations Some research narratives are repressed and silenced at the expense of others Researcher radically reflexive	Typically deconstructive – reading texts and realities against themselves In-depth investigations of anomalies, silences and absences Range of data types, typically qualitative methods of analysis
Pragmatism			
Complex, rich, external 'Reality' is the practical consequences of ideas Flux of processes, experiences and practices	Practical meaning of knowledge in specific contexts 'True' theories and knowledge are those that enable successful action Focus on problems, practices and relevance Problem solving and informed future practice as contribution	Value-driven research Research initiated and sustained by researcher's doubts and beliefs Researcher reflexive	Following research problem and research question Range of methods: mixed, multiple, qualitative, quantitative, action research Emphasis on practical solutions and outcomes

Figure 15: Comparative diagram of the five main research philosophies

Source: Saunders *et al.* (2009)

As outlined in Figure 15 above, five main research paradigms exist, with the positivist and the interpretivist being the most common stances. Positivism believes in investigating the world scientifically, through observing and experimenting human behaviour, in order to develop further knowledge and understanding (Saunders *et al.*, 2009). Therefore, the positivist paradigm adopts the deductive reasoning in formulating hypotheses, and then testing them with logical calculations to reach generalizable conclusions (Easterby-Smith *et al.*, 2008).

The interpretivist paradigm, on the other hand, is more concerned with the subjective side of human behaviour, and how individuals interpret the world and create meanings of their contexts (Guba and Lincoln, 1989). Under this paradigm, the reality is constructed socially (Bogdan and Biklen, 1998), placing an emphasis on the subjects under study and their ways of understanding the world. Therefore, the epistemology under this paradigm is subjectivism, allowing researchers to induce meaning from the data collected, based on their personal interactions with the participants, and on their prior experiences in the examined context (Punch, 2005). Within this spectrum, the integration of the social constructivism approach supports the researcher's belief that entrepreneurship is a concept that is defined and explained subjectively, constructing reality from entrepreneurial interpretations (Lindgren and Packendorff, 2009). Consequently, understanding the entrepreneurial experience (particularly failure) depends on the entrepreneurs' subjective formulation of reality and interpretation of actions and events (Cunliffe, 2008). Such adoption hence supports the adoption of narratives as a socially constructed tool of entrepreneurs' stories, in their process of reflecting on failure, in accordance with Gergen (1992) and Rae (2004). The associated ontology is hence relativism as the reality is constructed according to the researchers' experience with the participants, as well as their personal and professional backgrounds (Chalmers *et al.*, 2005). Consequently, the methodology adopted is qualitative in nature, where the researchers' observation contributes greatly to the data collection phase (Hara, 1995).

The researcher will adopt the interpretivist approach with an ontological belief in the socially constructed reality (of attributions of failure) and an epistemological aim to create new understanding and knowledge (Saunders *et al.*, 2007). In entrepreneurship, the interpretivist paradigm is crucial to reflect on the phenomenon under study, the subjects, and the research questions to be answered (Leitch *et al.*, 2009). More

specifically, for particular entrepreneurship questions to be best answered, the interpretivist qualitative approach is most suitable (Gartner and Birley, 2002), as in the case of this study. Through this stance, it is possible to understand and gain real insights on entrepreneurial learning from failure through attributions by:

“capturing the actual meanings and interpretations that actors subjectively ascribe to phenomena in order to describe and explain their behaviour through investigating how they experience, sustain, articulate and share with others these socially constituted everyday realities” (Johnson *et al.*, 2006, p. 132).

Through interpretivism, the researcher will be able to understand the social behaviour of attribution and learning from failure holistically (Shaw, 1999) and to examine in-depth how the perceived attributions affected their learning outcomes. As individuals understand various situations through their own individual experiences by expressing their thinking and expectations discursively, the interpretivist approach shall support the units of study (entrepreneurs) to share their stories, bringing the researcher closer to the insightful practices of failing entrepreneurs (Packard, 2017). Additionally, the interpretivist philosophy will allow the researcher to interpret data by closely interacting with interviewees to understand their perceptions on the phenomenon (attributions of failure) (Cassell and Nadin, 2008; Leitch *et al.*, 2009). Such interaction will assist in building knowledge from her personal experience, background, and prior involvement in the context under study (Chen *et al.*, 2011).

Therefore, the researcher’s prior engagement in Lebanon with various entrepreneurs, accelerators, and incubators supported adopting the interpretivist approach. Focusing on the rich and complex interpretations of various entrepreneurs, the interpretivist philosophy creates an axiological inference of the role exerted by the researcher’s beliefs and principles in analysing and interpreting the data (Saunders *et al.*, 2009). This knowledge involves indeed emphasising on the subjects of the study (the entrepreneurs) and their socially constructed beliefs and realities, supporting the suitability of interpretivism for researching entrepreneurship (Packard, 2017). Aiming to understand the fundamental meanings attached to their lived experiences of failure, this research will adopt the inductive approach, as explained next.

5.2 Approach to Theory Development

Following the adoption of the interpretivist paradigm, the researcher will incorporate the inductive approach for theory development (Saunders *et al.*, 2009). The inductive

approach essentially moves from the particularity to the generalisation, basing arguments on experience; whereas the deductive approach progresses contrarily, concluding the specific from the general, by relying more on uncontroversial principles (Trochim, 2006; Creswell and Clark, 2007). Therefore, under the inductive approach, researchers follow the qualitative analysis, and the quantitative applies for the deductive approach (Creswell and Clark, 2007). Viewing reality as measurable and valid reflects the quantitative theory, whereas the qualitative theory assumes relativity in interpreting reality. Relativity argues that individuals develop various meanings of reality that researchers will interpret subjectively (Onwuegbuzie and Leech, 2005).

Figure 16: Contrasting the deductive approach with the inductive approach

Source: Adapted from Woiceshyn and Daellenbach (2018)

For the sake of this study, the researcher will adopt induction as the most suitable research approach. This research is interested in the subjects of the study (entrepreneurs) and the perceived significance of their stories for reflecting on failure by developing cognitive attributions (Gill and Johnson, 2002). Henceforth, the qualitative approach is more suitable for answering the research questions and achieving the research objectives. Focusing on how reality is actually developed according to individual understanding and logic, the inductive approach will provide the most insightful validations of the formulated assumptions (Saunders *et al.*, 2009). Additionally, integrating the inductive approach with the researcher's professional

background in the designated context supports in developing the most out of the induction process. Stated otherwise, the researcher's involvement with the participants in the field contributes to the understanding of behavioural, personal, and other factors that, practically, cannot be evaluated quantitatively (Bell and Bryman, 2007). To conclude, entrepreneurial learning from failure is a phenomenon that requires in-depth exploration, which can be best achieved through the inductive qualitative approach, which will be more elaborated next.

5.3 Data Collection

This section outlines the adoption of the qualitative research approach, the research quality, and the data collection techniques to be implemented in this study. It is, however, imperative at this stage to discuss the constraints of the research that had to be considered while selecting the research instruments. The first constraint is financial, as this study is financially sponsored by the researcher herself, with no external funding sources. The second constraint relates to the time allocated for the data collection and analysis, which ranges between 6 and 9 months. The third constraint involves the access available to data and participants (as will be elaborated in Chapter 8, Section 8.4). Finally, this study is bounded by the word count as prescribed by the doctoral college guidelines, and hence, poses a fourth constraint in the selection of the data collection methods. These constraints influenced the selected research instruments as elaborated next.

5.3.1 Qualitative Approach

Following the interpretivist paradigm and the inductive approach, the researcher will adopt an exploratory qualitative technique in collecting and analysing the data. The researcher agrees with Fletcher (1997) that choosing the research methodology should stem from the adopted epistemological position. The techniques to be employed will impact the questions asked, the data obtained, and the answers found for the examined questions. In essence, the methods chosen for the data collection should be coherent and in harmony with the ontological and epistemological stances adopted, and most importantly with the subject under study (Hollinshead, 2004). Seeking a deeper understanding of the entrepreneurial learning process through entrepreneurs' attributions of failure that moves away from the quantitative investigation (Silverman, 2000) (e.g. Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015; Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015) and follows the objectives of the study (Haq, 2015), the exploratory qualitative approach is most

suitable. This study's emphasis on understanding the process with which cognitive attributions of failure are developed, the impact of its various dimensions on entrepreneurial learning, and the need to examine the emerging themes from the data collected and interpret the empirical evidence establish the justification for adopting an exploratory qualitative design (Cassell and Symon, 1994).

Issue	Qualitative methods	Quantitative methods	Mixed methods
1. Overall aim	Understanding and explanation of social phenomena	Generalization and conformation	Aims both explanation and generalization
2. Sample size	small	Large	Both small and large
3. Amount of data	Large amounts of textual raw data	Relatively small amount of numerical data	Both large and small amounts of data
4. Relationship with respondents	Close one-to-one relationship	Almost no direct relationship	Close one-to-one relationships with some but not with all respondents
5. Frequently used data collection techniques	Semi-structured interviews, easy but costly and time consuming	Large scale surveys, low response rates, less costly and less time consuming	Combines methods based on objectives, more costly and time consuming than the other two methods
6. Frequently used data analysis techniques	Thematic content analysis, tedious and time consuming	Statistical analysis using computer-aided programmes, relatively simple and quick	Combines methods from qualitative and quantitative approaches, takes longer time and costs more
7. Flexibility and standardization	Flexible	Less flexible than qualitative analysis	More flexible than both
8. Research process and data quality	Meticulous record keeping adds value to quality of process and data	Compromises quality of data for standardization	Quality of process and data is considered better than the other two methods
9. Interpretation of results	Lot of interpretation is required	Interpretation is concise due to use of statistics	Interpretation is harder and longer because of the use of both qualitative and quantitative methods
10. Generalizability	In general, generalizability is not an objective	Highly generalizable in general	Generalizability is stronger than in any of the other two methods
11. Triangulation	In general, no triangulation is done	In general, no triangulation is done	Triangulation is done
12. Overall usefulness, assuming cost, time and expertise are not issues	More useful than quantitative methods in understanding social phenomena	More useful than qualitative methods in replication	More useful than both qualitative and quantitative methods in all aspects
13. Term(s) used for quality of research	trustworthiness	rigour	Both trustworthiness and rigour

Figure 17: Comparative analysis of qualitative and quantitative research methods

Source: Haq (2015)

Moving away from the positivist approaches places a greater focus on the various dimensions of entrepreneurial research, as well as the interrelationship connecting

these dimensions (Anderson *et al.*, 2012). In other words, a traditional classical research method, such as the quantitative approach, is not sufficient to study the lived experiences of entrepreneurs. Stated differently, the qualitative theory believes that the researchers' involvement and development of value-based interpretations are crucial for the research findings (Soiferman, 2010). On the contrary, with the quantitative method, entrepreneurship is approached partially where its wholeness and context are abandoned. As a result, the essence of the lived experience vanishes. The quantitative method, thus, leads to the absurdity of entrepreneurship and diminishes its richness (Raco and Tanod, 2014).

Through the qualitative approach, the researcher will be able to build a comprehensive picture of the context of the study, words, and statements (Leitch *et al.*, 2009). More specifically, the exploratory qualitative approach assists in understanding a social phenomenon such as entrepreneurship, enabling the investigation of the various experiences and interpretations of individuals away from the rigid quantitative tools (Grill and Johnson, 2010). Subsequently, the academic (theoretical and empirical) progression of entrepreneurial research is suggested to be enhanced (Anderson *et al.*, 2012). Furthermore, entrepreneurial studies that involve investigating the perspectives of individuals who lived a certain experience and have hence attached meanings to these experiences require the adoption of a qualitative approach (Guba and Lincoln, 1994). In the same vein, Cope (2001) emphasised the contribution of qualitative research in supporting academics to make sense of the entrepreneurs' complex and personal world.

However, the qualitative approach is continuously criticized mainly for the small sample size, researchers' involvement, the threat to objectivity (Morse *et al.*, 2002), and the rare development of an idiosyncratic theory that applies to only one case or one individual (Eisenhardt and Graebner, 2007). In response to the critiques, Cope (2001) argued that the subjectivity and claimed unreliability of qualitative methods are in fact the result of the various ontological stances. Therefore, this type of studies serves best in studying human behaviour and personal experiences, allowing for the emergence of theory rather than imposing the theory on the issue under study. More specifically, the study will be giving the subjects space and voice to reflect on these experiences (Guthrie, 2007; Abebrese, 2014). As a result, the pursuit of objectivity and reliability are consequentially unattainable (Patton, 1990), as the researcher is

more interested in understanding the meanings and interpretations attached to the behaviour or event under study, rather than measuring them (Marschan *et al.*, 2004). Therefore, asking ‘how’ and ‘why’ questions in such qualitative designs assists the researcher in concentrating on the natural occurrence of events in their ordinary contexts, and in providing dense, rich, and comprehensive representations pertaining to specific contexts (Miles and Huberman, 1994). A further advantage for adopting the qualitative methodology is developing a clear picture of the context under study, flexibly, without the need to include a large sample (Sinkovics *et al.*, 2008). The data collection approaches that will be adopted for the qualitative study are discussed next.

5.3.2 Data Collection Techniques

In deciding on the research strategy, the selected approach has to be evaluated as to: its effectiveness in guiding the research to answer the study questions (Saunders *et al.*, 2009); and its association to data collection and analysis (Blaikie, 2007). This study will adopt the qualitative Multi-Methods Research (MMR)⁶, applying two qualitative data collection tools from two subsets of sample: experts and entrepreneurs (as will be elaborated in Section 5.4). The selected qualitative techniques include respectively: a) the in-depth semi-structured interviews, justified by the researcher’s interest in understanding the experts’ perspectives, backgrounds and experiences (Rowley, 2012); and b) the narrative inquiry (Elliot, 2005), justified by its focus on exploring the individual experiences of entrepreneurs as narrated in their stories, in relation with the interest of this study in exploring perceived attributions of failure (Creswell and Poth, 2016).

5.3.2.1 MMR Adoption

According to Deshpande (1983), the investigation of a specific phenomenon can be limited by the implementation of conventional and common techniques, thus bounding the scope of the study. This is particularly applicable in exploring phenomena involving social and personal behaviours, whether individually or collectively. Therefore, a single method cannot completely capture the individual phenomenon under study (Tellis *et al.*, 1999), whereas different techniques capture different visions, producing more robust findings (Stewart, 2007). Therefore, in line with the definition of MMR, this research will collect data from more than one

⁶ Employing a single source of data that is analysed using more than one tool does not classify as MMR. The same applies for applying a single analytical tool for different sources of data (Davis *et al.*, 2011).

qualitative source and hence apply more than one qualitative analytical tool (Creswell and Clark, 2017). The adoption of MMR provides great support for exploratory studies, allowing the researcher to gain a greater understanding of the topic under investigation (attributions of failures) (Davis *et al.*, 2011).

Purpose	Rationale	Weight	Reporting
Development	Use of one study to inform a subsequent study: Implemented sequentially to expand the insights generated about the research problem	Equal-weighted methods: the second method is used for the development of findings from the first study	Separate reporting of results of each phase of the study, followed by a general discussion that ties them together by comparing and contrasting findings
Initiation	Use of a preliminary study to launch the main study: Implemented sequentially for preliminary exploration of the phenomenon	Unequal weighted methods: The less heavily weighted method is employed to initiate the research and is secondary to the primary method that is used in the main study	Separate reporting of results, but the focus of the discussion is on the main study
Complementarity	Concurrent examination of various complementary facets of a phenomenon through two or more studies. The sequence of concurrence is irrelevant	Equally weighted methods in a one-phase design: results achieved using one method do not inform the design or implementation of subsequent methods	Merging the findings in a single report of results, as researchers analyse and interpret the data from multiple studies concurrently
Interpretation	Concurrent use of a second study to explain or confirm the results of the main study: the researcher anticipates the need to explain or confirm findings	Unequally weighted methods: a secondary method is employed to interpret or support results obtained from the primary method	Merging the findings in a single report of results, as the researcher analyses and interprets the data from multiple studies concurrently

Table 7: Detailed summary of the MMR design

Source: Adopted from Davis *et al.* (2011)

Adopting an MMR design serves one of four purposes (see Table 7) depending on the integrated weight assigned and implementation timing of each technique within the data collection (Tashakkori, 2009; Creswell and Clark, 2017). Among the four purposes of an MMR approach, the researcher's aim lies in the need to undertake an initial examination of the phenomenon, as the emerging context (Lebanon) and the focus of the study (perceived attributions of failure) impose a different exploration

that has a limited guiding framework to predict relationships and ascriptions (Tashakkori *et al.*, 1998; Creswell and Clark, 2017) (see Chapter 4). Therefore, the MMR design will be employed as an *initiation* supportive approach by conducting first interviews with industry experts (secondary method) to focus subsequently on the main study of entrepreneurs. The findings will be then reported separately as depicted in Chapter 6.

Adopting the MMR design with an initiation with the experts' interviews first will serve the primary purpose of providing the researcher with a preliminary, yet, insightful investigation of the most common attributions of entrepreneurial failure in the context under study (Tashakkori *et al.*, 1998). Lebanon, being the context of this research, suffers from the lack of recent academic studies on entrepreneurial failure in general and learning from failure in particular. Additionally, the focus of the study (attributions of failure) is already under-explored in the developed contexts but aggravatingly lacking in emerging and developing countries (Lattacher and Wdowiak, 2020). Therefore, the researcher needs an initiation stage through which more preliminary and recent insights on entrepreneurial failure can be revealed (Davis *et al.*, 2011).

While relying on the benefits of adopting an MMR design, the researcher recognises the challenges that may arise in such implementation, mostly in terms of resources needed (time) (Davis *et al.*, 2011). However, the researcher will manage to conduct the data collection over a period of 6 to 9 months, which is believable to be sufficient for the gathering and analysis of interviews and narratives. Another challenge that the researcher admits and realises is the expertise and knowledge needed to undertake an MMR design, with a good understanding of each method to be adopted (Davis *et al.*, 2011). In response to this, the researcher has improved her knowledge in the field by consulting published articles and books in relation to MMR (e.g., Deshpande, 1983; Tashakkori *et al.*, 1998; Davis *et al.*, 2011). The deep investigation of each approach in connection with the research problem, guided by the research aim and objectives will equip the researcher with the needed theoretical knowledge, to undertake the MMR design as elaborated next.

5.3.2.2 Semi-structured Interviews

In the field of entrepreneurial learning and in terms of methodological approaches, scholars (i.e., Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015; Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015) have called for

the future adoption of qualitative studies to understand the learning outcomes from failure and to investigate comprehensively the learning process (Lattacher and Wdowiak, 2020). Over years, the adoption of qualitative interviewing in entrepreneurial research has progressed especially when exploring individuals and environments (Javadian *et al.*, 2016). Such adoption highlights further the importance of qualitative interviewing in understanding the field of entrepreneurship. More specifically, adopting in-depth interviews will assist the researcher in investigating insightfully the personal and social dimensions of the phenomenon under study (DiCicco-Bloom and Crabtree, 2006).

Semi-structured interviews will grant the researcher the flexibility needed to collect the interpretations of participants, which is usually impractical in rigid quantitative studies. Developing the interviewing guide, improving the questions continuously, and interviewing selected candidates can be more flexible when using the semi-structured interview method, which leads to a richer data collection (Trochim, 2000). Therefore, this kind of interviews allows interviewees to elaborate on their experiences and backgrounds; and the researcher the chance to probe on particular statements (Horton *et al.*, 2004).

Despite its advantages, the semi-structured interviewing technique has been criticized mainly for its subjectivity and the close interaction of the researcher with the interviewees. However, the researcher recognises the issue of credibility and hence, will address it in designing, conducting, and analysing the interviews (Horton *et al.*, 2004). More specifically, once the plausible analysis and explanations are established inductively, the researcher will attempt to check for competing explanations through inductive and logical thinking. Looking for rival analysis implies reaching alternative logical explanations: by considering different possibilities which might be sustained by the data (logically), and alternative ways for organising the data which could lead to different outcomes (inductively). By thinking of alternative competing justifications, the researcher will attempt to accord more confidence in the research findings. This can be achieved by failing to find robust supporting evidence for alternate ways of representing the data or for opposing accounts (Patton, 1999).

5.3.2.3 Narrative Inquiry

As the main aim of this study is to understand the reflection of entrepreneurs on failure as explained by their perceived ascriptions of failure, the researcher has to choose between two techniques that serve best the main focus of this study and assist in answering the research questions most effectively: narrative inquiry and phenomenological interviewing. The section proceeds with contrasting the advantages of both techniques before justifying the adoption of the narrative inquiry. Narratives inform the researchers of the temporal unfolding of events (Elliot, 2005), but its adoption is still limited in entrepreneurial research, despite scholars' encouragement to apply it in empirical studies (Zahra *et al.*, 2014). Despite their criticised limitation in describing events, narratives offer an insightful opportunity into the thoughts, affections, and understanding of participants, by uncovering the meaning attached to these experiences (Thomas, 2012). Such an approach is best implemented when the researcher is interested in exploring an event that has either rare or perceptive data (Byrne and Shepherd, 2015). Henceforth, this technique fits well in this study on entrepreneurial failure, as entrepreneurs might be unwilling to discuss such adverse events (Dimov and Clercq, 2006; Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015). Additionally, such an approach is best adopted when exploring the 'how' questions (Larty and Hamilton, 2011; Mantere *et al.*, 2013), as in the case of this study ('how entrepreneurs ascribe failure while reflecting on their experience and how attribution affects their learning process and outcomes'). Through the narrative inquiry, the researcher will be able to collect the participants' perceived accounts of events and the assigned meanings to these events from their points of view (Flick, 2009).

The relevance of narratives emerges from being a tool that assists in studying individual experiences, building on Riessman's (2008) assumption that individuals tend to experience their lives through telling stories, which is an act of social action (Lal *et al.*, 2012). In criticising the narrative inquiry, opponents have devalued the contribution of narratives, claiming that it focuses on the plot of the stories rather than their content (Smith and Sparkes, 2006). Nonetheless, narrative researchers still adopt it believing in the relevance of human communication in forming experiences through narratives. Its epistemological stance provides a gateway "*portal through which experiences can be viewed and interpreted and then re-presented using storied forms*" (Lal *et al.*, 2012, p.7). This stance is supported by the ontological view that considers

narratives more than representations of individual experiences, but rather an aspect of these experiences (Bruner, 1991). As pointed out by Loseke (2007), people interpret their lived events by telling their stories, accentuating on the parts deemed important for them (Lal *et al.*, 2012), and socially constructed from their interaction with the researcher (Riessman, 2008).

In comparing it to the narrative inquiry, the phenomenological interviewing technique would also serve as a constructive and functional qualitative approach, despite its rare application in entrepreneurial research compared to psychology and education fields (Gartner and Birley, 2002). By implementing phenomenological interviewing (regardless of the stance: Husserl-transcending, or Heidegger-Existential) (Abebrese, 2014), the researcher may be more able to understand the subjective viewpoint of participants regarding their lived experiences, and what meanings are ascribed to these experiences (Cope, 2005). In essence, these personal interpretations of experiences constitute a major part of those experiences *per se* (Patton, 1990).

However, the phenomenological approach poses a great challenge to researchers at many levels: the first one is detaching the researcher's preconceptions about the phenomenon under the study. It is argued that such 'bracketing' allows for a greater and deeper understanding of the phenomenon, yet with a narrowed focus on its fundamental elements to avoid any theoretical bias (Chen *et al.*, 2011). However, this can be very hard to maintain, as the questions guiding any research need to have some preliminary answers to ensure a novel contribution into the field of the phenomenon under investigation (Cope, 2011). This challenge is supported by Eisenhardt and Graebner's (2007) statement that, it cannot be possible for the researcher to initiate interviewing with a clear mind of theoretical presuppositions, as the researcher conducts interviews with research objectives in mind, which consecutively emerge from reviewing the literature.

The second level of challenges with phenomenological interviews involves the level of freedom granted to participants during interviews. The researcher is supposed to relinquish her control over to participants, granting them more trust and relaxation to convey deeply their experiences (Cope, 2011). This level of control which allows the interference of the researcher only with questions that emerge from the dialogue

represents another challenge of this technique. Furthermore, discussions do not always result in focused interviews but might exhibit fluctuations in several instances. The researcher could then face occasions where the interviewee might take a complete turn in their discussion, bringing up a new issue or consideration. The resulting new direction of interviews may disrupt the chronology and coherence of events (Cope, 2011). A third challenge that may emerge from adopting phenomenological interviews is the complexity of translating the interpretive stories of participants and the risk of jeopardising their interpretations. Therefore, a fourth challenge surfaces with regards to the researcher's ability to remain objective and detached (though the existential form criticised the transcendental form for this point) (Cope, 2011), in line with the bracketing dimension (Raco and Tanod, 2014). The phenomenology (especially the Heideggerian-existential), despite its limitations, still holds much contribution to the entrepreneurial field, by deeply appreciating the complexities and uncertainties in the lives of entrepreneurs (Higgins *et al.*, 2015). In exploring its contribution, it is noted its epistemological similarity to the narrative research (Riessman, 1993; Lieblich *et al.*, 1998), as the narrative inquiry also aims into exploring how interviewees create order in their narration of experiences in order to make sense of these experiences (Cope, 2011).

Subsequent to presenting both approaches and taking into consideration the available (time) resources and word count restriction, as well as the researching experience of the researcher, the selection of the narrative inquiry was deemed the most relevant. The narrative approach exhibits relevance to the researcher's interpretivist-epistemology, constructivist-ontology, and axiological stance of narratives as a valuable source of knowledge, to interpret the meanings behind individual experiences (Nigar, 2019).

The narrative approach can be distinguished into two main theoretical stances: the experience-centred approach and the event-centred approach (Andrews *et al.*, 2013). The researcher will implement the former, as it goes "*beyond the past-tense first-person recountings [...] to include present and future stories about others*" and themselves (Squire, 2013, p. 4). An interesting contribution of this narrative approach is the representation of personal changes while addressing themes not clauses as in Labovian event-centred approach. Another noteworthy contribution of this approach

is allowing the researcher to look for fragments that are essentially difficult to transcribe, contradictions arising within narratives, tones, pauses and expressed emotions when saying some words (such as laughter) (Squire, 2013); all of which serve to achieve the aim of this study in exploring the cognitive and emotional reflection of entrepreneurs upon failure, and perceived attributions and explanations. In summary, through the experience-centred narrative approach, the researcher will focus on the process of telling the stories, as well as the meaning within these stories; and the way individuals reinterpret their experiences through social interaction (Clandinin, 2006).

The adoption of the narrative inquiry necessitates defining what is meant by narratives. According to Hinchman and Hinchman (1997), narratives are told discourses of events in a chronological (though not always) and sequential manner, while describing life events and connecting them meaningfully. As such, narratives provide insightful windows on individual experiences, as people attempt to give meaning to their experiences (Czarniawska, 2000), as well as to themselves, with the opportunity of revealing personal transformations and characters on a comprehensive narrative 'plot' (Lawler, 2002). Comparing it to the in-depth interviewing adopted with the experts' sample, the meaningful accounting of entrepreneurs' experiences and actions could be lost in answering semi-structured questions (Czarniawska, 2000). This will consequently hinder the interest of this research in the lived experiences of entrepreneurs. Another main advantage of the narrative inquiry resides in its consideration of the social context in which the experience occurred (Elliot, 2005). Therefore, a deeper inference on the impact of culture (stigma) on the reflection *per se* is provided. For the sake of this study, the researcher will adopt the episodic narratives focusing on specific events (in this case failure), rather than their life stories (Singh *et al.*, 2015).

Critiques have pointed out to the credibility aspect of narratives, judging the accuracy of a story. However, by distinguishing between the precision being reported and making the plot plausible, the researcher can mitigate any risks to credibility (Polkinghorne, 1995). In this research, the focus is placed on the attributions of failure as perceived by entrepreneurs. In other words, the researcher is interested in exploring how entrepreneurs ascribe and reflect on failure, rather than the actual reasons for it

(Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015). Therefore, such risks to the accuracy of the reflection are irrelevant, not jeopardising the quality of narratives.

The research design is developed into three main phases, as detailed in Figure 18. The first phase entails a theoretical background on the process of entrepreneurial learning from failure; the second phase defines the methodology adopted, as an interpretivist, qualitative approach that surveys consecutively two samples of participants using two interviewing techniques: in-depth interviews and narrative inquiry; and the last stage involves interpreting the findings with two appropriate analytical tools: thematic analysis and narrative analysis. An important consideration within the research design represents the consecutive interviewing that will start with experts and then follow-up with entrepreneurs. The interviews of experts will act as a preliminary analysis before conducting the narratives with entrepreneurs. This consecutive interviewing serves a primary purpose for the study: developing preliminary knowledge about the attributions of entrepreneurial failure in Lebanon (Section 5.3.2.1). Designing the research entails developing the design of data collection techniques as elaborated next.

Figure 18: Qualitative Research Design

Source: Adapted from Creswell (2007)

5.3.3 Data Collection Design

This subsection presents the development of the interview guide and the design for narrative inquiry. Due to the imposed lockdown by the COVID-19 pandemic and the restrictions on travelling, besides the constraints on the limited resources of time and money, the researcher's aim to complete the data collection stage in the context of Lebanon may not be achievable. Henceforth, interviews that will not be possible to attend physically will be held remotely via skype (or any other convenient online platform), at the most convenient time and availability of interviewees.

5.3.3.1 Semi-structured Interviews

In developing the interview questions, the researcher appropriately addressed them to be considered as a valid data collection technique (Berry, 2002). The interview guide was established according to the research objectives and the review of the literature (Chapters 2 and 3) (guided by the process in Figure 19) and involves asking fifteen questions (see sample in Appendix A).

Figure 19: Process of formulating the interview questions

Source: Bryman (2012)

The first question is general in scope, asking the experts about their attributions of the failure of Lebanese entrepreneurs, especially in the first few years of operations. The second question moves into inquiring about the Lebanese ecosystem particularly and another question about governmental support, followed by one question about the financing factor, two questions about the level of readiness and skills of entrepreneurs across several business functions, followed by four questions about business aspects, one about culture (such as the impact of stigmatization), and one about technology.

The questions asked to the experts emerged from an extensive review of the extant (limited) research on entrepreneurship in Lebanon. By understanding first the situation of entrepreneurship in Lebanon, referring to interviewing materials as well, and reviewing extensively the research on learning from failure and attributions of failure (Brinkmann, 2014), the researcher was more able to engage in the discussion with experts, and to gather more relevant and insightful data as to their perspectives on entrepreneurial failure in Lebanon.

For the sake of enhancing the validity and credibility of interviews, the researcher will follow Myers and Newman's (2007) model in conducting them. Interviews will start with a short introduction about the research and the researcher, then the questions will follow, until reaching finally the closing part, where the researcher will thank the interviewees for their time and shared opinions. Though the interview questions are developed in a particular order, the researcher will not follow them strictly and might need to move among them, depending on the flow of discussion with interviewees. The main aim of interviews will be to maximize the sharing of opinions and expertise of interviewees, which eventually impact the quality of findings (Myers and Newman, 2007). Unlike interviews, the design of narratives is more unstructured as elaborated next.

<p>Situating the researcher To identify the relationship between the researcher, the interviewees and their organization by providing a brief overview of the researcher, research and role of the interviewee.</p>	<p>Minimising social dissonance To reduce the social distance between the researcher and the interviewee and building rapport by providing a warm introduction and facilitating the conversations</p>
<p>Representing a variety of voices To overcome bias, researchers should include a variety of subjects by interviewing more than one stakeholder (entrepreneurs and experts)</p>	<p>Everyone is an interpreter To ensure that the researcher not only interprets the interviewee's answers, but also that the researcher's questions are subject to the interviewee's interpretation by asking questions in English or Arabic and clarifying unclear terms</p>
<p>Using models in questions and answers To minimise imposing the researcher's world-view on the interviewees, by adopting the mirroring technique and repeating the responses of the interviewees to ensure they are properly captured (whether in English or Arabic)</p>	<p>Maintaining flexibility To minimise the use of a script and to improvise whilst listening and constructing the next question based on the interviewee's response, by following the flow of discussion and emphasizing the points highlighted by the interviewees</p>
<p>Confidentiality of disclosures To report on security and confidentiality agreements, by providing the interviewees with the participant information sheet and the participant consent form to participate and record the interviews</p>	

Table 8: Guidelines for semi-structured interviews in qualitative studies

Source: Adapted from Myers and Newman (2007)

5.3.3.2 Narratives

The structure of narratives (explained in Chapter 6, Section 6.2) will be very loose and flexible, granting entrepreneurs more flexibility to narrate their stories. However, the interview guide will adopt roughly the structure of Maykut and Morehouse (1994) as follows (see Appendix B for details):

- a) Starting with an introduction about the researcher;
- b) A summary of the research aim and topic;
- c) Getting permissions for the audio recording of the interviews;
- d) Initiating the interview with sociodemographic and background inquiries (gender, age, company's name, company's profits, pre-entrepreneurial occupation, entrepreneurial compensation, business legal nature, launching and discontinuation dates);
- e) Asking the interviewees to narrate their stories about their business, with emphasis on their perceptions on the attributions of failure;
- f) Probing on further points that either were not raised at all during the narration or had to be explored further (as guided by the analysis of experts); and
- g) Concluding the interviews after giving the interviewees a final opportunity to add further points that were not mentioned (Iborra, 2007).

The main interest of the researcher will be the narrated reflection of entrepreneurs, rather than formulating questions and building a report about their entrepreneurial career and experience with the business. The follow-up questions will be prepared in advance, according to the preliminary analysis that will result from the experts' interviews, following the MMR design. However, the researcher has enough flexibility to change the order of the questions, avoiding some or reformulating others, according to the interviewees' statements. Prior to the actual collection of primary data, the researcher aims to conduct a pilot study and integrate its findings into the final version of the interview questions.

5.3.3.3 Pilot Study

Pilot studies usually assist researchers in testing their methodology and ideas, for possible implications and for developing inductive theories (Maxwell, 2012). Therefore, prior to going for the field data collection, the researcher will conduct a pilot study with 2 research fellows, 2 experts and 1 professor. Through the pilot study, the researcher will conduct an initial exploratory research to identify and improve

aspects of the data collection process (Light *et al.*, 1990). In qualitative research, pilot studies provide researchers with an opportunity to even develop an initial interpretation of the perspectives of people considered as data units for the study, their behaviours, and the meanings behind each one of them (Maxwell, 2012). Those meanings, being real, reflect a critical part of the contexts and situations under investigation, without which the formulated theories would mostly be incomplete or incorrect (Menzel, 1978; Maxwell, 2012). Eventually, through the pilot study, the researcher will be more confident that the interview questions will generate the data needed to investigate and understand the points raised by the research questions (Maxwell, 2012). Other techniques were adopted to ensure the quality of the research was maintained as elaborated in the next section.

5.3.3.4 Research Quality

This section presents the research standards for evaluating the quality of any research from two dimensions: reliability and validity. The quality of quantitative studies usually associates with four main factors: internal validity, external validity, measurability, and reliability (Yin, 1994). However, these standards shall not evaluate the quality of qualitative studies, given the ontological differences between both approaches (Patton, 1990). Henceforth, for the qualitative research, these four criteria are substituted by *credibility* (trustworthiness of data and data analysis); *dependability* (research findings depend on the researcher's skills deemed sufficient to retrieve meaningful and reflective results from the data collected given the lack of reliability); *confirmability* (minimising any bias in the qualitative analysis in confirming the findings by others); and finally *transferability* (providing sufficient circumstantial data to relate the findings to other contexts) (Guba, 1981); all of which are used interchangeably rather than distinctively in describing the quality of qualitative studies (Golafshani, 2003).

The quality of qualitative research thus relates to its ability to help explain a situation that would otherwise create confusion. Therefore, the quality in this sense, usually defined as reliability in quantitative studies, refers to the capacity of the qualitative research to generate understanding (Golafshani, 2003). The trustworthiness of a qualitative study hence defines its quality and is considered an attached criterion of validity. Therefore, proving the validity of a study is enough to prove its trustworthiness (Patton, 2001) and the quality of its findings (Lincoln and Guba,

1985). Therefore, the more credible and trustworthy a qualitative study is (by creating a research trail that documents the research process), the greater the claim for the generalisability of findings (Golafshani, 2003). As this study does not aim to generalise the findings, the aim is rather to create inter and intra-accounts of entrepreneurs' perceived attributions (Cope, 2011). However, and in line with Lincoln and Guba (1981), qualitative studies can be judged according to the degree to which the qualitative findings might be transferable to various contextual settings and participants. Ensuring a thick description of the entrepreneurs' behaviours, experiences and contexts will assist in promoting the degree of transferability of the findings (Sim and Sharp, 1998). The validity of any qualitative study represents the researchers' perspective of the concept *per se* and the selected research paradigm (Creswell and Miller, 2000), and can be defined as rigour and trustworthiness (Stenbacka, 2001). Therefore, the issue of validity for qualitative research is more judged by the degree of the researcher's rigour for collecting and analysing data, and by justifying the methods employed and the process of making significant decisions (Noble and Smith, 2015). Consequently, the criterion for dependability is related to the degree of consistency in adopting methods for the analytical process. The consistency in the decisions of selecting participants, collecting data, transcribing interviews, and analysing transcripts reflects the credibility of the study (Beal, 2013). Supporting the study with sufficient details and evidence, such as direct interviewees' quotes, patterns emerging and 'interpretive commentaries' (abstraction revealed from the meaning within stories) (Pak, 2013) grants the study greater credibility by keeping an audit trail (Lincoln and Guba, 1985). On the other hand, credibility in qualitative research refers to the degree to which the researcher succeeds in retrieving the interviewees' information and meanings, and how well these meanings are deduced (Saunders *et al.*, 2009). The study will manage to achieve this level of validity through the efforts of the researcher as the main instrument (Patton, 2001). These quality measures are supposed to be maintained along the process of data collection until the final stage of analysis and writing up the report, including the selection of participants as elaborated next.

5.4 Sampling

In this section, the sampling technique selected for this qualitative research is presented, along with an outline of the sample size and sample composition.

5.4.1 Sample composition

In qualitative studies, two main theoretical approaches can be applied: the emergent theory with the exploratory approach, and the cultural theory with the confirmatory approach. This study will adopt the exploratory approach that inductively explores a theory within the data collected, and therefore, will apply the saturation sampling model, as it is not possible to determine a valid, accurate and generalizable size of the study sample (Trotter, 2012).

Probabilistic Sampling	Non-Probabilistic Sampling
Simple random sampling (each unit has an equal chance of being chosen)	Convenience sampling (units will be selected according to the researcher's accessibility to them; cost-effective approach)
Stratified random sampling (each subgroup/stratum within the population has an equal chance of being chosen)	Purposive sampling (units will be selected purposively given their ability to provide information)
Systematic random sampling (only the first sampling point is randomly selected, and the units are then chosen at regular intervals)	Snowballing sampling (units relevant to the research are selected first and then refer the research to other units)
Cluster sampling (units are chosen from aggregated population geographically distributed)	Judgment sampling (units are selected according to the researcher's judgment; cost-effective)
Multi-stage sampling (a combination of cluster sampling first, stratified sampling second and third selecting relevant units to be included in the sample size)	Quota sampling (units are selected as quota from strata within population)

Table 9: Probabilistic versus non-probabilistic sampling

Source: Adopted from Rahi (2017)

Sampling techniques fall within one of two approaches: probabilistic and non-probabilistic, as shown in Table 9 above. The first category treats each unit to have the same probability of being chosen, whereas, under non-probability sampling, the probability of choosing one unit is completely unknown or unspecified (Rahi, 2017). Data collection is a critical step for answering any research questions. Consequently, deciding on the data collection method and the sample size should be made properly and accurately, given the impact of irrelevant data on the quality of research (Tongco, 2007).

For the data collection of this study, purposive sampling will be adopted for both sets of samples. The purposive sampling is of contributory importance to qualitative studies, as it allows researchers to select candidates who are able to provide rich information (Patton, 1990; Garcia and Welter, 2013). This sampling method consists of deliberately recruiting experts who have an enriching experience with the situation of entrepreneurship in Lebanon; and entrepreneurs who experienced failure (and perceived their ventures as failure) (Doern, 2016) and are willing to share their experiences and opinions reflectively (Etikan *et al.*, 2016). The purposive sampling technique will be complemented by the snowballing technique to reach entrepreneurs who are willing to participate and provide comprehensive narratives (Patton, 1990; Cope *et al.*, 2004; Cope, 2011; Singh *et al.*, 2015; Corner *et al.*, 2017). The purposive sampling involves various dimensions, among which the researcher will focus on the maximum variation sampling. In other terms, the maximum variation type of purposive sampling allows the researcher to look at the sampling units from various angles to gain further insights, while selecting the units from a broad continuum (Etikan *et al.*, 2016). The criteria adopted for selecting the participants of both samples for the data collection should be clearly explained, as will be shown in the next subsection.

The purposeful sampling serves the aim of this study, by achieving three significant goals that will improve the contribution of this research (Maxwell, 2012). The first one involves the representativeness of the population. One of the criticised issues associated with sampling in qualitative approaches is the narrow focus of these studies on investigating in-depth a specific phenomenon within very specific contexts. Therefore, the sample in these studies is essentially small in number, compared to larger sample sizes determined by the power analysis in quantitative studies, posing a challenge on their representativeness of the population. However, Weller and Romney (1988) argued in their consensus theory that small groups with particular behaviours and relevance to the greater group, as in qualitative studies, can be still representative of the population just like any larger group, as long as proper sampling measures are being applied. Consequently, purposely selecting cases and individuals considered to be typical within the context will generate more confident conclusions that represent the population of interest than a simple random sample size. This can be achieved by integrating the heterogeneity of the population rather than just the average cluster within this variation (as a second benefit) (Maxwell, 2012).

Finally, purposive sampling allows the researcher to thoughtfully choose participants or cases that are most relevant to the issue under study. However, deciding on the final selections necessitates appropriate knowledge and information about the settings of the research. Considering the risk of key informants' bias (Pelto and Pelto, 1975) where the small number of informants purposefully selected might provide perspectives that are not typical, the researcher will adopt the systematic sampling to argue confidently that the declarations given by the selected informants are indeed representative of the group. Subsequent discussion of the sample size will be elaborated on next.

5.4.2 Sample Size

Baker and Edwards (2012) argued that the current research on qualitative methodology is lacking a straightforward discussion on the criteria for a sufficient number of interviewees (Robinson, 2014). Such a credible and valid sample size is debatable (Baker and Edwards, 2012), given the relative judgment of qualitative researchers (Saunders and Townsend, 2016).

The sample under qualitative studies is a process rather than just a pre-determined number (Trotter, 2012). The research purpose and the research questions remain the main guidance, justification, and rationale for determining the number and the nature of participants, given the researcher's limited time and resources (Patton, 2015). Therefore, within this range, the researcher shall not decide on a pre-determined number of interviewees for each sample. However, the qualitative collection shall continuously interview participants until repeated themes start to emerge, also called data saturation (Saunders and Townsend, 2016). Even with a small purposive sample, qualitative researchers can still successfully investigate the topic (Weller and Romney, 1988; Trotter, 2012).

The researcher will address the issue of sample size by following the lead of qualitative studies undertaken in the field of entrepreneurial learning from failure. The majority of qualitative studies relevant to this field employed between one entrepreneur (for a qualitative case study) and 30 entrepreneurs (for in-depth interviews with thematic analysis), as depicted in Table 10. Therefore, the researcher has only set a minimum number of 10 entrepreneurs and 5 experts (for a minimum total of 15), following on Marshall *et al.*'s (2013) conclusion that qualitative studies

are usually embracing a sample size from 15 to 60 participants, in accordance with Adler and Adler's (2012) recommendation of 12 to 60 participants. Even one interview could be sufficient if it provides salient information that fulfils the research purpose. Henceforth, the researcher is responsible to take into consideration the implications of their sampling epistemology and ontology (Becker, 2012; Marshall *et al.*, 2013; Patton, 2015).

Author(s) & Year(s)	Research Focus	Research Approach	Sample Size
Cope (2003)	Reflection on failure and learning	Qualitative (multiple case studies)	2 entrepreneurs
Singh <i>et al.</i> (2007)	Learning outcomes	Qualitative (multiple case studies)	5 entrepreneurs
Huovinen and Tihula (2008)	Transformation process of experience into knowledge	Qualitative (single case study)	1 entrepreneur
Cope (2011)	Process of learning from failure	Qualitative (interpretative phenomenological analysis)	8 entrepreneurs
Pretorius and Le Roux (2011)	Active learning and reflection process	Qualitative (longitudinal case study)	1 entrepreneur
Heinze (2013)	Sense-making process of failure	Qualitative (hermeneutical phenomenological analysis)	6 entrepreneurs
Mantere <i>et al.</i> (2013)	Attributions of failure	Qualitative (cross-case narrative analysis and grounded theory)	18 stakeholders (including 5 entrepreneurs)
Byrne and Shepherd (2015)	Emotions and perceived learning	Qualitative (multiple-case studies and cross-cases analysis)	13 entrepreneurs
Singh <i>et al.</i> (2015)	Stigma and learning from failure	Qualitative (narrative analysis)	12 entrepreneurs
Corner <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Emotional resilience and learning from failure	Qualitative (narrative analysis)	11 entrepreneurs
Dias and Teixeira (2017)	Process of learning from failure	Qualitative (interpretative phenomenological analysis)	6 entrepreneurs
Walsh and Cunningham (2017)	Attributions of failure	Qualitative (thematic analysis of in-depth interviews)	30 entrepreneurs
Amankwah-Amoah <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Imprinting process from failure on subsequent venturing	Qualitative (multiple case studies and cross-cases analysis)	22 entrepreneurs
Dias and Martens (2019)	Reflection process on failure	Qualitative (content analysis of in-depth interviews)	3 entrepreneurs

Table 10: Summary of qualitative studies on entrepreneurial learning from failure
Source: Adapted from Wang and Chugh (2014) and Lattacher and Wdowiak (2020)

The sample chosen for the qualitative data collection is divided into two different subsets: the first set includes the industry experts that the researcher is interested in

their opinions and reflection on the situation of entrepreneurial failure in Lebanon; and the second set includes the entrepreneurs who viewed their ventures as failures and decided to exit or to discontinue. The experts' sample will thus include key decision-makers in financing organisations in Lebanon (such as banks, accelerators, governmental departments, incubators) and entrepreneurship mentors. The researcher will interview at least one individual from each of these groups in order to ensure diversity.

For the second set, the researcher will consider the various industries operating in the country, such as agriculture, tourism, manufacturing, and trading and services. At least one entrepreneur from each industry will be interviewed to support the study with a variant and heterogeneous sample. The focus within this sample on micro and small businesses is linked back to: the 'tight' relationship between entrepreneurs and their ventures; the dominance of small business in the majority of world economies; the high rate of failure among these businesses; and the heterogeneity of businesses and entrepreneurs (i.e. De Bruin *et al.*, 2007; Shepherd and Cardon, 2009). Therefore, the sample chosen will embrace a variety in size, industry, gender, age, time since the closure, and nature of failures (Byrne and Shepherd, 2015). The criteria for selecting candidates in both samples will be as outlined in Table 11. Each subset of the sample chosen will be interviewed separately and analysed differently, as discussed in the next section.

Criteria for selecting entrepreneurs

The entrepreneur exited the business upon a decisive choice (regardless of whether the business was sold or discontinued);

The business exit should have not been related to lawsuits or external legal enforcement;

The business should have been established in Lebanon and operate within the Lebanese or external market;

The nature of the business should not be a traditional micro-business, such as an off-license shop, pastry shop, haircut salon, etc. as these micro-businesses face extreme competition; and

The entrepreneur should have acted as the main decision-maker rather than being a silent partner.

Criteria for selecting experts

Being a decision-maker in the process of financing Lebanese entrepreneurs in a financing organization or an entrepreneurship mentor or holds (or held) a position that interacts with entrepreneurs; and

Possess the knowledge and experience relevant to be shared.

Table 11: Criteria for selecting participants of both samples

Source: Researcher

5.5 Qualitative Data analysis

Qualitative data analysis techniques vary in nature and process. Therefore, choosing the appropriate analytical technique depends on various interconnected factors: the research question investigated, the theoretical base of the research, and finally the relevance of the technique to the analysis of data collected. The chosen technique should assist the researcher in familiarising with the data, engaging within it, searching for patterns, and understanding the underlying relationships, to finally conclude with explicit findings (Kawulich, 2004). Data analysis involves interpreting certain pieces of information, by summarising the initial amounts of the data collected (LeCompte and Schensul, 1999). In analysing the data and following on the consecutive interviewing technique (interviews then narratives) of MMR, the researcher will implement two different analytical approaches pertaining to each data collection technique. The process will be initiated with the application of thematic analysis for the in-depth interviews of experts, followed by the narrative analysis of entrepreneurs' stories.

5.5.1 Thematic Analysis

The interviews with the industry experts, as in the case with the entrepreneurs, will be audio recorded whilst taking handwritten notes. The audio files will be then transcribed in detail, orthographically, depicting the pauses of the interviewees, laughter, hesitation, emphasis and talks cut-offs (Braun and Clarke, 2012). Detailed transcription is necessary to apply the thematic analysis (TA) to the qualitative responses of industry experts. TA is one of the most popular qualitative analysis tools that can be implemented in various ways and across various qualitative approaches (Braun and Clarke, 2012). The thematic analysis to be adopted involves six stages, as detailed in Table 12 below; the emerging themes will guide the entrepreneurs' interviews ought to be analysed through the narrative analysis, as to be elaborated next.

Stage	Process
Familiarising with the data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reading the transcripts over and over, as well as • Listening to the audio files several times • Immersing oneself within the data and making notes out of it • Spotting items that could of relevance to the research questions • No coding shall be developed at this stage, and the notes taken serve only as an assisting tool for the coding process later
Generating initial codes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analysing the data through coding. Codes are very critical as they provide the building blocks for developing the themes and concluding the analysis. The criticality of these codes resides in identifying important aspects in the data that are possibly relevant to the RQs (Braun and Clarke, 2012).
Looking for themes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engaging in an active process of searching for themes by constructing themes rather than just finding them • Reviewing the codes developed in the previous stage in order to recognise any overlapping areas among the various codes. The theme should be emerging from a collection of codes that have uniting feature in common and is representative of the meanings and patterns of the data
Reviewing themes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rechecking whether the themes that emerged from the previous stage actually represent the extracts of the data text. This quality check results in either discarding some codes or relocating them under other themes; in some cases, the researcher had to amend the theme for the sake of capturing the most relevant data
Defining themes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Qualifying each theme by its specificity and singular emphasis • Developing the connections among the themes without each theme overlapping the other and provide answers to the research questions
Writing up the analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A continuous process that starts from taking notes, and developing codes and themes • Representing the story from the data, according to the analysis conducted

Table 12: Process of Thematic Analysis

Source: Adopted from Braun and Clarke (2012)

5.5.2 Narrative Analysis

Narrative analysis is considered by researchers (e.g., Elliott, 2005) as a knowledge source in the entrepreneurship field, even though it was not adopted till recently (Larty and Hamilton, 2011). Adopting the narrative analysis expands and enriches the data collection stage in entrepreneurship, especially that researchers often overlooked entrepreneurs' stories (Johnson, 2004). However, in narrative analysis, the researcher shall be prudent in her role played in collecting the data and developing the research process (Bruni *et al.*, 2005). Henceforth, the relationship of the researcher and the

interviewee with the narrated material constitute a central issue in the narrative analysis (Fletcher, 2007).

Unlike other qualitative techniques, under the analytical methodology of narratives, no single technique that can be adopted across all studies exists (Czarniawska, 2004). Accordingly, researchers may rely on the work of their peers to develop their own method for their particular fieldwork. This accepted convention holds true, as long as the generated outcome of the narrative analysis provides meanings for subsequent research (Gill, 2015). In other words, contributions on narrative analysis have not provided specific guidance on the analytical or interpretative approach (Elliott, 2005; Whiffin *et al.*, 2014), whilst scarce accounts defining the various approaches of narrative analysis exist (Lieblich *et al.*, 1998; Elliott, 2005). Henceforth, the choice of the approach(es) from the work of others adds complexity to the work of narrative analysis (Edwards, 2016).

Holistic - Content	Holistic - Form
Categorical - Content	Categorical - Form
<p>Holistic Analysis – Each story is viewed as a whole and the parts within it interpreted in relation to other parts of the story</p> <p style="padding-left: 40px;">Holistic-Content – Focus is on what happened in each story</p> <p style="padding-left: 40px;">Holistic-Form – Focus is on the plot or overarching theme (e.g., a tragedy)</p> <p>Categorical Analysis – Units are abstracted from the complete stories</p> <p style="padding-left: 40px;">Categorical-Content – Categories related to the topic are identified</p> <p style="padding-left: 40px;">Categorical-Form – Focus is on linguistics or style (e.g., use of metaphor)</p>	

Figure 20: Classification of narrative analysis

Source: Beal (2013)

Conventionally, in narrative analysis, researchers may choose one of four central analytical approaches, according to the unit of analysis selected (categories versus whole) and the focus of analysis under interest (form versus content) (Lieblich *et al.*, 1998), as shown in Figure 20. In this study, the researcher will adopt the holistic content analysis (Lieblich *et al.*, 1998). In telling narratives, individuals employ narrative thinking as a cognitive form to naturally relate events (Bruner, 1986). As the function of the holistic-content analysis focuses on configuring the experiences and events holistically, this analysis is therefore coherent and in accordance with the

underlying cognition employed by entrepreneurs in making sense of their experiences through narratives (Beal, 2013). As a result, this analysis allows the researcher to capture the complexities of personal experiences and their progressive dimensions, while enabling her to induce findings beyond the individual cases (Sandelwoski, 1996) from the themes emerging from the narratives (Lieblich *et al.*, 1998). Additionally, the holistic analysis of each story allows for the investigation of the various associations across the various attributions developed. However, this process *per se* does not allow for a comparative analysis across the various accounts (Ayres *et al.*, 2003).

Analytical Stage	Analytical Type
Familiarisation	Familiarisation with the narratives (Iyengar, 2014) Reading the narratives while listening to the recordings (Kellie and Howie, 2007)
Immersion	Reading the stories as narrated (Beal, 2013) Obtaining a general overview (Koch, 1998; Elliott, 2005)
Holistic content analysis	Intra-stories: Categories and sub-categories emerging (Lieblich <i>et al.</i> 1998) Connections within categories (Lieblich <i>et al.</i> , 1998)
Categorical content analysis	Inter-stories: Comparative analysis across categories (Lieblich <i>et al.</i> , 1998) Commonalities and differences arising (Morse and Field, 1995)
Organising and presenting the findings	Reviewing all evidence collected, from the analyses of content and form Koch (1998), Lieblich <i>et al.</i> , (1998)

Table 13: Process of Narrative Analysis

Source: Adapted from Edwards (2016)

In response to the bounded selection of one of the distinct categories of narrative analysis (Lieblich *et al.*, 1998), narrative researchers may employ various approaches simultaneously and creatively. Combining techniques in exploring the experiences of their participants (Holloway and Freshwater, 2007; Keats, 2009) has become more common in narrative studies (i.e., Robichaux and Clark, 2006). Therefore, the researcher will complement the holistic content analysis with the categorical content analysis. This latter form of analysis involves retrieving references from each narrative account through the emerging themes, allowing for comparison across

multiple interviews (Lieblich *et al.*, 1998; Earthy and Cronin, 2008). This combined analysis will enable the researcher to understand the attributive process perceived by each entrepreneur holistically as presented in their stories, and to scan for commonalities and differences across the various attributions developed by various entrepreneurs. The analytical process adopted subsequent to transcribing the interviews, as summarised in Table 13, will be explained in more details in Chapter 6, Section 6.2, as to how the process was conducted on the collected narratives.

5.6 Ethics

Abiding by the requirements mandated by the University of the West of Scotland, the researcher sought ethical clearance from the doctoral college before commencing the actual data collection. The pilot study did not require such clearance. Such clearance aimed to mitigate the risks that could be imposed over the researcher and the participants, and to demonstrate that the researcher will adhere to the generally accepted principles of conducting research. The researcher will send for each participant two main documents: the consent form and the information sheet. The first one aims into collecting their written consent for participating in the data collection, and the second one provides summarised information as to the focus of the study, its purpose, and the confidentiality and anonymity standards with which data will be treated. Both sheets will be sent to each participant prior to the interview, and the participant consent form will be signed either with ink or digitally. Sheets are developed in English, and in case the participants asked for an Arabic version, the researcher prepared a translated version. The data to be collected will be only stored on the personal computer of the researcher and accessed by her as well as the director of studies. Subsequent to the study completion, the data shall not be kept longer than the provision prescribed within the university's ethical guidelines of research.

“Every adversity, every failure, every heartache carries with it the seed of an equal or greater benefit” – Napoleon Hill

6 Chapter Six: Findings

This Chapter examines the actual process of collecting and analysing the in-depth interviews of experts and the narratives of entrepreneurs. These sections help in problematizing and demystifying the fieldwork undertaken by the researcher, through an actual reflection on the occurrences happening all along the research journey (Sparkes, 2002). The details listed in this section comprise the experience of the researcher and reveals the process behind the work presented. Tensions or problematic dilemmas faced are presented as well, eventually disclosing the ability of the researcher to represent social research via disciplined decision-making (Coffey and Atkinson, 1996). While adhering to the main purpose of the qualitative analysis in retrieving patterns and meaningful themes, the researcher admits to facing initially few analytical challenges in summarising the in-depth interviews and narratives, in order to present strictly the reflective and relevant findings. However, this challenge was shortly resolved with dedication and enhanced knowledge by adhering to the processes outlined in Chapter 5.

The findings within this Chapter seek to achieve the research aim of this study by answering the last two research questions on how entrepreneurs develop attributions during their reflection on failure, in order to understand the impact of these attributions on learning outcomes. Therefore, this and the next Chapters will unveil how entrepreneurs determine an attribution as internal or external through the venture’s aspects. The findings presented herein are divided into two main parts, in line with the separate reporting of results of the ‘initiation’ purpose of MMR (see Chapter 5, Section 5.3.2.1 and Table 7). As a result, the report starts with the findings of the less heavily weighted approach, reporting the themes that emerged from the thematic analysis applied to the in-depth interviews with experts. These interviews served a primary purpose: providing the researcher with a preliminary, yet, insightful investigation of the most common attributions of entrepreneurial failure in the context under study, given the lack of recent academic studies on this subject in Lebanon.

The second part of this Chapter presents the analysis of entrepreneurs’ narratives (considered as the primary approach and the focus of this research), and how they reflected upon their failures, explaining the various attributions developed by each

participant (holistically) and, in comparison with others (categorically). In this part, the researcher will analyse how entrepreneurs developed attributions for failure and how each dimension of these attributions affected their learning process, as well as their cognitive, emotional, and behavioural responses. Whenever feasible, the researcher presented comparative perspectives between both sampled categories.

6.1 Experts' Interviews

The design of interview questions addressed to the industry experts emerged from the existing entrepreneurship studies (not only on failure) in Lebanon (i.e., El Nemar *et al.*, 2016), private (banks, accelerators, venture capitalists and other financing and credit organisations) and public reports, and governmental programmes. By skimming the situation of entrepreneurship in Lebanon, referring to interviewing materials, and extensively reviewing the existing research on learning from and attributions of failure (Brinkmann and Kvale, 2005; Brinkmann, 2014), the researcher was able to engage in discussion with the industry experts, and gather more relevant and insightful data. Experts were comfortable answering the interview questions based on their experiences; when a question seemed not to relate to their expertise, interviewees were reluctant to answer it (for instance, the technology level available and acquired by tech start-ups), which is suggested to add higher reliability in the answers given, minimising the risk of self-representation (Goffman, 1959).

To build rapport with interviewees, the researcher has explained in the correspondences the research context and aim and outlined the points to be discussed during the interviews (McGrath *et al.*, 2018). To earn their trust, the researcher collected a signed consent form from each interviewee and provided them with a written statement that guarantees the confidentiality and anonymity of their identities and responses. After conducting the first interview, questions were readjusted to integrate some points raised with the first interviewee, such as the availability of finance and the entrepreneurs' ability to earn and manage funds. Subsequently, in each interview, the order of questions was reassessed according to the flow of discussion and to the emphasis placed by each interviewee on some points more than others (Fox, 2009). All the interviewees contacted were very dedicated to participating and adjusted their schedules to fit the interviews, showing interest in the study and requesting a copy upon its finalization. The same interest was also revealed by entrepreneurs, who were very excited to share their experiences with the researcher,

expressing the need for such studies that may improve the future of entrepreneurial initiatives in Lebanon. This emphasised interest could be explained with Goffman's (1959) argument that interviewees attempt to enhance their image and the impressions developed in any physical or remote social interaction (in this case with the researcher) (Merunkova and Slerka, 2019).

Interviews lasted between 50 and 90 minutes, during which the researcher was taking notes to probe with additional questions about points raised by the interviewees and deemed relevant for them. Four interviews were conducted face to face when the researcher was in Lebanon in September 2019, and the rest (3) were conducted remotely in October, November, and December 2019. Interviews were audio-recorded subsequent to receiving the interviewees' consent on taping the discussion. Given the Arabic discourses in some of the interviews, the Arabic and English transcriptions were sent to a sworn translator for accuracy⁷. In this study, the researcher was concerned about losing valuable data that the participants might wish to delete if they read the transcripts after the interviews (Horton *et al.*, 2004). Therefore, the researcher did not send the transcripts back to the interviewees, after clarifying this issue with experts (and entrepreneurs) upon concluding the interviews. As the interviewees did not object it, the researcher agrees with Mero-Jaffe (2011) that the spoken language conveyed would be different from the written statements, because of the employment of different terminology. Therefore, when reading the spoken statements written by the researcher, interviewees might feel disappointed and/or embarrassed, perceiving unfounded judgment (Mero-Jaffe, 2011).

6.1.1 Demographics of Experts

This sample involved seven experts who held for a significant period of time either decision-making positions at private and semi-private institutions that provide financing for entrepreneurs or act as entrepreneurship mentors. The appointment of experts was based on the purposive sampling (see Chapter 5, Section 5.4.1), and the criteria involved: a) being a decision-maker in a financing organisation that supports Lebanese entrepreneurs or an entrepreneurship mentor; and b) possess the relevant knowledge and experience to be shared. These criteria have been assessed by referring

⁷ Entrepreneurs' narratives were also sent for a translator to double check the accuracy of translation, while conserving the anonymity of the personal information within, by removing the names of individuals and organisations.

to the researcher’s professional and weak networks. Data saturation was achieved with 7 participants, hence, the researcher decided to cease the interviews at this number.

Three of the industry experts occupied decision-making positions in private financing organisations (one commercial bank – Ex1 and two accelerators – Ex2 and Ex3); one expert worked for three years in the department of SMEs of a governmental institution (Ex4); another expert occupies a decision-making position in a reputable semi-public financing organisation (Ex5); and the last two experts act as private entrepreneurial mentors (Ex6 and Ex7). Therefore, interviewees were chosen according to their positions and ability to provide valuable and relevant information (Bernard, 2002). Including private and public organisations within the study would be more insightful as to the experience of each sector with entrepreneurs. All of the interviewed experts were male, in their middle age, with at least 3 years of experience in dealing with entrepreneurs.

Code	Position
Ex1	Head of SMEs financing in a famous Lebanese commercial bank
Ex2	Financing decision-maker for accelerator A
Ex3	Financing decision-maker for accelerator B
Ex4	Former senior employee at the Ministry of Economy and Trade
Ex5	Decision-maker in a private-public financing organisation for start-ups and SMEs
Ex6	Private entrepreneurship mentor A
Ex7	Private entrepreneurship mentor B

Table 14: An informative summary of the interviewed experts

Source: Researcher

6.1.2 Analytical Process of Interviews

In this section, the researcher reports the themes that emerged from the thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2012) applied to the in-depth interviews of experts, by following the process depicted in Chapter 5, Section 5.5.1, Table 12 (see Appendix C for a sample).

Interviews started with a general question about any possible reason that the interviewees might think of, stemming from their experiences and considered as an ascription to entrepreneurial failure. All responses to the first question gave emergence to the following common themes: finance (either in terms of access to finance or the sufficiency of funds), market (the size of the Lebanese market and/or their ability to access the local market along with competition), government (how far government is supporting and whether it is sufficient), and managerial knowledge (readiness of entrepreneurs to adopt an entrepreneurial career, ability to manage venture and entrepreneurial decision-making). With these patterns and concepts (already expected to arise from the results of the pilot study and consulting with the literature review), the researcher linked the responses to the study aspects for a deeper investigation, following with the interview questions. For instance, when the interviewee answered the first question that financing is considered a main contributory factor to the failure of entrepreneurs, the researcher probed further asking about the extent to which the entrepreneurial knowledge in managing these funds is relevant and existing. Additionally, when the experts mentioned entrepreneurial team conflicts, the researcher inquired about the quality of human capital and the entrepreneurs' leadership style. Figure 21 below summarises the main themes recurrent in the thematic analysis, while at the end of every subsection a summary of the key findings is identified in terms of the dimension of attribution.

Figure 21: Summary of the themes from the thematic analysis (I denotes internal, E denotes External)

These findings provided the researcher with a preliminary, deep investigation of the experts' attributions of entrepreneurs' failure. In summary, the selected candidates have explained the failure of start-ups and the exit decisions of entrepreneurs through a combined-hybrid approach, focusing the attribution as internal or external to the entrepreneur: macro-environment (external level) factors, including the access to finance, access to market, governmental support, national stability and security, and convenience and availability of infrastructure; whilst also evaluating the entrepreneurs' abilities to manage these ventures (individual-internal level).

6.1.2.1 Availability, Access, and Management of Funds

All participants recognised the lack of sufficient funds as a main factor that threatens the survival of entrepreneurs (Arasti, 2011; Mantere *et al.*, 2013; Eggers and Song, 2014; Mandl *et al.*, 2016). Reduced cash flows can critically jeopardise the sustainability of entrepreneurs and start-ups, especially at their early seed stage (Fort *et al.*, 2013). Though acquiring funds is majorly important for these ventures to be established, interviewees attributed failure only partially to it:

“The access to capital is considered the 4th survival factor, not the first, not the second, not the third [...] why did I decide to put it here? Because it doesn’t really create that much impact, if you as an entrepreneur, don’t possess a good idea, a good business model and understand your market. Yes, I wouldn’t say that financing is a problem. It’s important but it’s not critical in the Lebanese situation” – Ex6.

This attribution of failure to funds reflected an external dimension. The high criteria (credit history and collateral) requested by banks complicate the access of small ventures to funds (Poutziouris *et al.*, 2002; Fatoki, 2014). Access to financing was judged to be difficult in terms of admission criteria (Naimy, 2011), but good in terms of the number of financing initiatives available and amounts granted (GEM, 2018). According to all interviewees, the country, in its both sectors private and public, is performing much better than the Middle East region in financing SMEs and entrepreneurs, especially with the circular 331 in operation (OECD, 2019). However, for tech and early seed start-ups, the situation⁸ is not as encouraging as it is for traditional businesses, due to: the limited capacity of accelerators and incubators to finance these start-ups; the concentration of investments on ‘future unicorns’; and the limited availability of venture capitalists for early seed entrepreneurs (Rouhanna, 2018). As a result, entrepreneurs refer to informal sources of funds from peers and networks (Fatoki, 2014):

“Unfortunately, the Lebanese ecosystem still lacks a proper legal framework that supports venture capitalists. Moreover, this ecosystem is still financially immature, especially after the suspension of circular 331. So funds within Lebanon are not sufficient, and we don’t have financial markets” – Ex7.

“The funds available to entrepreneurs are limited nowadays to 5-10% of the total number of financing applications initially admitted to incubators” – Ex3.

“Financing is a problem for start-ups given the need for collateral and a proper business plan [...] established businesses are in a better position as they can prove their ability to repay” – Ex1.

The attribution of failure to funds also revealed an internal dimension. All interviewees have made it clear that the financing factor does not have much influence on failure, as the entrepreneurs’ ability to manage these funds plays a more overarching role (Mezher *et al.*, 2008; Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015):

⁸ ⁸ However, it’s important to relate the feasibility of funds to the economic stability of the country, where the shrinkage in banks’ lending capacity has affected prospective plans of early seed entrepreneurs to apply for or renew the financing. Proving their capability to repay their debts, early seed entrepreneurs have to submit the proper analysis and financial statements for such renewal, which is also a subject to their understandability of the requirements – as mentioned by Ex1.

“Entrepreneurs claim bankruptcy and lack of funds as the cause behind their failure, but if the management is not proper, even if they have tons of cash they will still fail” – Ex5.

“2015 marked a good year of financial support, then it decreased in 2018 [...] Entrepreneurs and business owners are used to easy money” – Ex4.

An interesting point raised during the interviews relates to the active engagement of entrepreneurs in looking for available funds, versus the initiatives of financing enterprises to reach out to entrepreneurs in marketing their dedicated programs. In probing further, four interviewees stated that Lebanon lacks a publicly accessible economic database (BLOM Bank, 2018) (as well as in any other field) that provides information about the entrepreneurial ecosystem and market insights. Therefore, the unavailable access needed to market information (Farsi and Toghraee, 2014) is costly through private organisations, because of the irregular and poor market intelligence provided by the research centres in Lebanon (such as the Central Administration of Statistics) (MET, 2014). However, three interviewees criticised the lack of initiatives taken by entrepreneurs (*internal ascription*) in seeking funds available for start-ups:

“Lebanon is lacking effective and systematic R&D [...] you can say that Lebanon is a data desert; though some platforms are being developed by the ministry of economy or the central bank, the data is still static and illusive” – Ex4.

“Entrepreneurs need to be a bit *sophistiqués* [implying they should be proactive and open-minded]” – Ex1.

“Our advertising is centralised in the capital [...] but after all if entrepreneurs are willing to find us, they can” – Ex2.

“[...] but on the other side, entrepreneurs are not taking enough initiatives whether to research the market, competitors and available financing competitions and programs” – Ex5.

While discussing the entrepreneurs’ financial management skills, interviewees assessed entrepreneurial competencies in managing these funds, as well as in preparing entrepreneurs for the career, as will be elaborated next.

Figure 22: Key findings of Section 6.1.2.1

6.1.2.2 Entrepreneurial Competencies

Entrepreneurs usually fall in love with their ideas and businesses and consider them to be their own babies (Cardon *et al.*, 2005). From such metaphoric lenses, entrepreneurs were argued to be blindfolded in their love for their businesses. Henceforth, novice entrepreneurs fail to scrutinise their ideas properly (Pretorius and Le Roux, 2011), and only begin to understand the responsibilities as they move through the early seed stage, outlining the experiential process in learning about entrepreneurial skills (Lippman and Rumelt, 1982). However, prior to such realisation, entrepreneurs may exhibit overoptimistic ambitions for their business (Hayward *et al.*, 2010) and personal overconfidence (Astebro *et al.*, 2014), giving themselves an improper balance between passion and confidence (Cardon *et al.*, 2005). This can be applied to the case of the majority of Lebanese entrepreneurs who, according to the statements of all experts, overly exaggerate the success of their ideas. These entrepreneurs believe that the idea *per se* guarantees their success, and hence, refrain from taking any further initiatives in improving the idea or their skills (*internal ascription*):

“They come to you and think they have a unique and innovative idea that will create thousands of dollars” – Ex1.

“They all think that they have a unique idea that will rock” – Ex6.

Lebanese entrepreneurs were judged for the lack of vision (Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015) and strategic planning (Dias and Martens, 2019), relying on: improvisation (Martinez, 2001) in deciding on the entrepreneurial pursuit as mentioned by Ex1; on the effectuation reasoning (Sarasvathy, 2001) in managing the ventures; and in some occasions, a total absence of strategy (Inkpen and Choudhury, 1995). The reasoning

process is therefore revealed starting with the decision to undertake an entrepreneurial career (Gabrielsson and Politis, 2011), which is often ‘spontaneous and immature’ (improvised), based on evaluating the success of other businesses:

“If his neighbour’s minimarket is operating properly and is having many customers, s/he would decide also to go into opening a grocery store, expecting that the variables and the results would be quite similar” – Ex1.

All seven interviewees stated that Lebanese entrepreneurs, in their request for funds or even subsequent to receiving funds, lack the proper visionary plan that explains the value of the business and its objectives, a contingency plan, a reflective study of the market, a thorough research and understanding of competition, the strategic options to raise funds and an exit strategy, all factors that decrease the survival probabilities of the venture (*internal ascription*) (Rogoff *et al.*, 2004; Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015; Ploum, *et al.*, 2017; Dias and Martens, 2019). As the decision to establish a business is usually emerging from an impulsive desire to generate money, it lacks in many instances the enablers of success. As a result, the lack of understanding the market, in terms of customers and competitors, weakens their chances to sustain in the market (Hayward *et al.*, 2006; Shepherd *et al.*, 2014; Camuffo *et al.*, 2019). The effectuation decision-making (Sarasvathy, 2001) in assigning weight to the ‘superficial’ assessment of other businesses (as stated by Ex1) and the belief in price-discrimination (Varian, 1989) as the sole competing strategy proved ineffective at a later stage (Yusuf, 2012). Regardless of the success potential of the idea (service or product), operating blindly from competition causes ineffective procedures and processes that might not result in a fair market share:

“Entrepreneurs who managed to get funds, fail later due to their lack of understanding the market” – Ex4.

“[...] but on the other side, entrepreneurs are not taking enough initiatives whether to research the market, competitors and available financing competitions and programs” – Ex5.

“Before joining our programs, the readiness level of entrepreneurs is low, but through the journey, they try to adopt more of a proactive mindset” – Ex3.

“[...] sometimes entrepreneurs are not aware of the problem they are solving with a slight understanding of the competition” – Ex2.

Another point agreed by all seven interviewees as to the failure of entrepreneurs relates to their improper managerial and entrepreneurial knowledge (Rogoff *et al.*, 2004; Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015; Dias and Teixeira, 2017). Apart from the lack of a business plan and a visionary mission, failure can be attributed to the immature level

in entrepreneurs' managerial skills and decisions (Minello *et al.*, 2014; Walsh and Cunningham, 2017), which are necessary to conduct a profitable business. According to all interviewees, Lebanese entrepreneurs run businesses solely on the basis of passion and intuition. However, operating based on passion and intuition (Mitchell *et al.*, 2002) cannot be judged to be totally detrimental or harmful to the business career. Passion on one side promotes entrepreneurial sustainability and persistence even in difficult occasions, but on the other side, it makes it difficult for the entrepreneur to quit the idea, or at least change it (Cardon *et al.*, 2005). Passion may encourage entrepreneurs to overcome obstacles (Cardon *et al.*, 2009) with skills such as assessing the situation proactively, making appropriately informed decisions, spotting opportunities, seeking active exploitation, and recognising the time to exit the market:

“I am coaching entrepreneurs, and I can tell you that most of them possess a weak business model and an improper business plan, that's if they had any” – Ex6.

“The readiness of entrepreneurs for their careers is a main issue [...] they don't prepare a reflective plan about their target segments, competitors, value provided by product or service offered, and projected profitability” – Ex1.

Among these managerial skills is a critical skill that was highlighted by Interviewee Ex1, which is the improper management of cash flow. In parallel, interviewee Ex6 commented that entrepreneurs, once have raised the funds, confuse the personal with the organisational accounts in terms of expenditures (Mezher *et al.*, 2008). This inappropriate management of organisational funds (Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015) reflects in a negative or inaccurate cash flow, leading to a shortage of cash in subsequent stages:

“Entrepreneurs confuse between the personal and the business use of the funds. If they have cash in their till, they will take it out and overspend, improperly managing their cash” – Ex4.

However, for the tech start-ups, the situation can be judged to be slightly better to a certain extent as explained by interviewees Ex2 and Ex3. In other words, accelerators and incubators provide further coordination, support, and education to their candidates (Goswami *et al.*, 2017). Such support encourages them to undertake more entrepreneurial initiatives, such as examining competitors and business models, engaging actively in the market and studying it correspondingly through pilot studies, developing networks and reaching out to experts (this point will be developed later) and expanding their business plan and vision. Nevertheless, even with external encouragement, minor improvement can occur if entrepreneurs lack the pro-active

soul (Priyanto and Sandjojo, 2005). Among other competencies, the emphasis by experts on networking skills is elaborated next.

“Some entrepreneurs come prepared with a great plan in their head on how to do things; yet, with some entrepreneurs, no matter how much you push them, they will be lacking behind. I mean they won’t do it unless you ask for it [...] but no we don’t just pick anyone. Apart from the idea, we judge their personality, mostly, their extent of flexibility, adaptability, and level of initiatives” – Ex3.

Figure 23: Key findings of Section 6.1.2.2

6.1.2.3 Emphasis on Strong Networks

Given the high risk associated with early seed ventures, financing organisations in Lebanon seem to act as advisors and consultants for entrepreneurs, advising them on red flags at a small scale, and connecting them with experts and mentors (as in the case of accelerators). According to all experts, this ‘forces’ entrepreneurs to adopt more thoughtful decisions, who feel pressured by the follow up of investors or creditors. For the majority of interviewees, most entrepreneurs usually do not exhibit sufficient pro-activeness and initiatives at several levels, including the intention to expand their networks (Priyanto and Sandjojo, 2005; Zhao *et al.*, 2010). This was deemed as a critical issue that leads eventually to business exit, discontinuation, or failure (*internal ascription*):

“[...] Entrepreneurs sometimes realise that they need assistance, but they don’t seek out to mentors, except when pushed by their investors, if they have any” – Ex6.

“Some entrepreneurs come with their own networks [...] accelerators provide them with access to bigger, national and global mentors, other accelerators and experts; entrepreneurs need to initiate the process of approaching those networks and take initiatives in this prospect; however, only few have it” – Ex2.

Therefore, in their very early seed stage, entrepreneurs rely usually on their strong networks composed of families and friends, due to the confidence and trust emerging from these bonding social structures (Jaafar *et al.*, 2009). Only at later stages, and

when pushed by their investors, entrepreneurs realise the relevance of developing and expanding weak networks over strong networks (Lans *et al.*, 2015). Interviewee Ex3 was more positive in judging entrepreneurs from this perspective and preferred to praise those few entrepreneurs who take the initiative and connect with these mentors proactively (Zhao *et al.*, 2010), ahead of the accelerators' advice. Nevertheless, this does not reject the fact that the majority of entrepreneurs needs constant and regular follow-up to expand their networks. When inquired about the reason behind the lack of such initiatives, interviewee Ex2 raised the controversial thinking of entrepreneurs: on one level, entrepreneurs recognise the relevance of these networks for the success of their businesses as social resources (Rooks *et al.*, 2016), but on the other hand, initiatives taken tend to be very limited (Zhao *et al.*, 2010):

“They know how important networks are for them, however, they hesitate to take initiatives. [It] could be out of negligence, I say” – Ex2.

On another level, entrepreneurs not falling under the umbrella of accelerators or financial organisations exhibited fewer efforts to merge with third parties of interest and benefit to their businesses, as stated by the majority of interviewees. This reluctance to expand networks has been thus explained by entrepreneurs' introversion (in relation to the concept of expressiveness by Lans *et al.*, 2015), as described by interviewee Ex6; relating to the 'egoistic' culture as described by interviewee Ex1; or even the lack of trust within the Lebanese culture as per interviewee Ex5 (in relation to the concept of social perception by Lans *et al.*, 2015), respectively:

“[...] some believe they know it all; others feel shy to ask for help and reach out to mentors; others simply have no idea and some are very good” – Ex6.

“They think they know all about the entrepreneurial journey, and believe in the success of their idea, therefore they think they don't need to reach out for others' assistance or advice” – Ex1.

“Entrepreneurs are aware of the relevance of networks for their businesses, but the lack of trust among us as a culture is imposing more negative influence on such networking initiatives” – Ex5.

Being overwhelmed with an exaggerated estimation of the probability of success of their business idea (overoptimism) and the claim of 'knowing it all' (overconfidence), Lebanese entrepreneurs in most cases refrain from seeking advice and help from various types of networks, including other entrepreneurs. This relates to a certain extent to the case of narcissist entrepreneurs: Lebanese entrepreneurs disregard objective signals provided about the venture and select only the information that defends their state (Liu *et al.*, 2019). More introvert entrepreneurs prefer to stick with

their strong networks (friends and family), given the higher feeling of security and trust that these networks usually provide (Hallam *et al.*, 2018). On the other hand, developing weak networks necessitates a certain degree of flexibility, labelled as social adaptability which embraces the entrepreneurs' ability to willingly accept others' ideas and integrate them into the personal business (Baron and Markman 2000; Baron and Tang, 2009); a concept that Lebanese entrepreneurs are not ready to integrate yet in their majority according to five interviewees:

“They don't develop networks unless pressured by their VCs, or whatever investor they have. Some of them think they know it all and they don't need assistance; others feel shy to approach; some have no consideration at all for networking; and some are very good” – Ex6.

As reflected, the evaluation of entrepreneurs' networking initiatives necessitates a linkage to the lack of databases in Lebanon, according to interviewees Ex1, Ex6, and Ex5. Networking with mentors and investors assume in the first place the accessibility to these networks through a certain platform, which is convenient for entrepreneurs to find and access. However, such dedicated networking platforms are not available yet in Lebanon, according to interviewee Ex3. Therefore, further questions may arise as such: do entrepreneurs quit the idea of networking because they cannot find relevant data about these networks? Or even if these platforms were readily available and accessible, would entrepreneurs refrain from taking the initiative to expand on their networks? Interviewee Ex3 believed that entrepreneurs may find other means to expand their networks, such as conferences, seminars, and workshops (Lans *et al.*, 2015). However, the extent to which the participating entrepreneurs are actually networking in these events also poses another concern, as only a few approaches and engages with attendees:

“[...] we don't have a proper infrastructure to assist entrepreneurs in building networking and raising the funds” – Ex1.

“Some entrepreneurs are so introvert. They don't mingle with others and don't approach anyone. Others are very good and proactive” – Ex3.

Networks, therefore, play a significant role for entrepreneurs mostly at the marketing level as elaborated next on the marketing skills.

Figure 24: Key findings of Section 6.1.2.3

6.1.2.4 Ineffective and Insufficient Marketing

The marketing factor is considered a critical tool for the survival and sustainability of businesses (Tsai and Eisingerich, 2010; Ren *et al.*, 2015). When asked about the weight of this factor in contributing to failure, all interviewees apart from interviewee Ex5, stated that entrepreneurs are not sufficiently implementing this function either due to the lack of funds (*external ascription*) or to their improper understanding of the marketing function and of its relevance to their business (*internal ascription*):

“[...] the advertising conducted by businesses should be planned and executed according to the service or product offered [...] however, entrepreneurs may not fully understand it or apply it” – Ex6.

“Entrepreneurs I would say may lack the knowledge on how to properly advertise for their service or product [...] Even the process of going to market, they still undertake it in an ineffective and/or improper way” – Ex3.

“The marketing efforts of the entrepreneurs are still shy- they are using heavily the social media but it’s being well managed and monitored” – Ex1.

“Entrepreneurs are totally aware I would say about the marketing function and its relevance; and I think they are doing a proper and a good job [...] I think entrepreneurs are good in advertising for their business- I believe this is something that we Lebanese are good at” – Ex5.

Entrepreneurs refer to social media as their most affordable marketing channel, given its contribution to amplifying brand equity, develop the product more effectively, build relations with customers, and enhance the business’ reputation (Hubspot, 2012; Schaupp and Belanger, 2014). Interviewees did not agree collectively on the level of entrepreneurs’ recognition and understanding of the marketing function. For some interviewees, the way this function is being executed is not satisfactory for survival (Nwankwo and Gbadamosi, 2010), even within the financial constraints imposed on

entrepreneurs (O'Donnell, 2014). The situation is deemed similar for tech start-ups, who can only expose their products through social media (Hubspot, 2012):

“[...] another important factor is the access to market which means how they are advertising for their products. Social media ads used heavily by entrepreneurs don't always work for any idea [...] for some ideas you need to have salespeople on the street to get you sales; you need to understand the distributive channels that work best for you. Entrepreneurs in Lebanon must think about the go-to-market strategy, but this lacks a lot in the country even for mature and big companies” – Ex6.

Under the patronage of accelerators and investors, tech start-ups operate slightly better in this function, but, other entrepreneurs still lack the commitment to purposefully dedicate and engage in collecting and understanding customers' feedback. In the opinion of interviewee Ex2, this lack of understanding and commitment to the function of marketing is probably related to the little knowledge possessed on how to do it effectively (Nikfarjam and Zarifi, 2015) despite recognising its importance. For the majority of interviewees, entrepreneurs in their majority fail to exploit the marketing factor since the formation stage, and consecutively refrain from taking proper initiatives to invest time and funds in this function:

“Entrepreneurs are exhibiting little knowledge about the macro-market and what is holding for them [...] entrepreneurs in many instances do not realise the difference between building the product according to users' needs and design-thinking then checking whether this product or service fits within the market” – Ex3.

“As their investors, we push them to understand their market segment and the channels to these customers” – Ex3.

A good marketing function necessitates dedicated salespeople and teams, highlighting the relevance of human capital to the survival of entrepreneurs as elaborated next.

Figure 25: Key findings of Section 6.1.2.4

6.1.2.5 Availability and Ability of Human Capital

The robust attachment to the strong networks raises the concern of whether entrepreneurs hire friends and peers or recruit more professionally qualified people, outside their circle of strong networks. Unexpectedly, all seven interviewees stated that the hiring process does not occur out of social pressure. The strong attachment expressed to their businesses accompanied with a possession feeling (Cardon *et al.*, 2009) creates for entrepreneurs the reluctance to delegate functions to ‘outsiders’, preferring to undertake all functions personally (Churchill and Lewis, 1983). This comes in line with the shocking statistic of GEM (2016) that more than 40% of Lebanese entrepreneurs expect to not recruit any employee in a five-year time. However, this tendency raises the concern as to the sufficient skills of recruited human capital to execute business functions:

“I wouldn’t say any entrepreneur would hire someone just because he or she is a relative or a friend. They won’t risk their precious business that easily” – Ex1.

When deciding to recruit, entrepreneurs rely on their strong networks for referencing, yet, recruit only the personnel perceived to have the most relevant skills to the job description and the business (Bontis *et al.*, 2000), away from the strong networks’ pressure as expressed by five interviewees:

“Recruitment is mostly initiated through families and friends, but for sponsored start-ups by investors and venture capitalists, the process is more formal given their follow-up and pressure” – Ex6.

The only problem associated with the recruitment process is the compensation scheme offered to partners and/or employees, due to the entrepreneurs’ limited resources (Salgado *et al.*, 2020). Constrained by a limited budget during the early seed phase that restrain the ability of new ventures to compete with bigger companies (Powell and Baker, 2014), entrepreneurs usually offer either an equity reward or lower-than-market salary, justified by the lower productivity of small business ventures compared to more mature companies (Burton *et al.*, 2018). The desired skilled people, hence, will be rarely motivated to join, which leaves entrepreneurs on many occasions with less educated and less experienced staff (Nystrom and Elvung, 2014; Ouimet and Zarutskie, 2014). The financial constraints (Powell and Baker, 2014) hence force entrepreneurs to compromise the talents needed with the most convenient and affordable options, a problem that escalates even more for tech start-ups (in terms of the availability of technical expertise). Therefore, the unsatisfying quality of human

capital recruited negatively affects start-ups' innovation and, possibly their survival (De Winne and Sels, 2010). In connection with recruitment, interviewees had conflicting perspectives as to the level of technical expertise and talent available within the Lebanese market. For technology start-ups, the actual shortage in the technical skilled workforce, and a proper human capital platform creates another challenge for entrepreneurs (Rogoff *et al.*, 2004). Subsequently, a performance gap surfaces between what entrepreneurs expect their staff to achieve and their actual achievement, level of commitment, and enthusiasm:

“Lebanon lacks technical talents which is still in its infancy stage, in terms of quantity and quality. What shall they do then? Bring from abroad when they cannot pay? They will have to select whichever is locally” – Ex2

“Entrepreneurs find it difficult to hire the needed skills, for two main reasons: first, there is no proper platform to find these talents, and second, the budget constraints of early seed entrepreneurs make the advertised salaries less appealing to talented personnel” – Ex1

“Technical skills available in the market are in fact few [...] and whoever is there is not motivated to join a risky start-up at a low salary compared to more mature companies” – Ex3.

According to all interviewees, the problem does not solely lie within the level of skills actually recruited, but also with the level of harmony within the team. Disagreements between partners threaten not only the growth of the business but also its survival (Stam and Schutjens, 2005). As interviewees Ex2 and Ex3 stated, many entrepreneurial teams withdrew from the admission process or cancelled their business projects due to internal conflicts between partners. The initial selection of partners seems to be grounded on similarity and likeness rather than skills (Forbes *et al.*, 2006). Conflicts among team members can be considered a major threat to entrepreneurs that leads in many instances to the discontinuation of the business:

“Many of our candidates simply withdrew and abandoned the business idea due to their conflict with partners; though their business could have been a successful project” – Ex3.

Such threats might be related to the capacity of entrepreneurs to manage people effectively and efficiently while keeping them motivated, by developing motivational approaches and restructuring the adopted compensation schemes (Lyons *et al.*, 2005). From the very early stage, entrepreneurs should properly manage their human capital, given the impactful role played more significantly in the early stage than the later stage (Daou *et al.*, 2014). Otherwise, the end result will be arising internal conflicts that escalate at the expense of teamwork, leading members to either quit or withdraw, as stated by interviewee Ex3. Furthermore, entrepreneurs do not seem to take

initiatives to reassess and evaluate their own skills and capacities as well as their employees’, or provide training and development within the boundaries of the financial constraints:

“We had many incidents where the co-founders fought with each other or disagree over some operational perspectives, and then abandon the idea because of that. And some of them had really good ideas that ended up unrealised” – Ex3.

“Effective recruitment means that entrepreneurs must assess their staffs continuously, and not only the personnel but also themselves if they wanted to grow and expand. But I wouldn’t say they do that” – Ex1.

In connection with discussing human capital comes the issue of the assistance provided by the entrepreneurial ecosystem and its impact on entrepreneurs’ failure as discussed next.

Figure 26: Key findings of Section 6.1.2.5

6.1.2.6 Unsupportive Ecosystem

Experts have emphasised, throughout the interviews, the impact of the Lebanese ecosystem on entrepreneurial survival (and failure). All interviewees criticised the improper infrastructure, the political instability of the region and its impact on the Lebanese market, the costly and unsupportive legal regulations in terms of registering and deregistering business especially for tech start-ups⁹, and the complications of exporting to regional and international markets (Mezher *et al.*, 2008; MET, 2014; GEM, 2016).

“Lebanon is detrimental for entrepreneurs [...] any conflict in the region reflects back on Lebanon” – Ex4.

⁹ This drives entrepreneurs to transfer their business from an active state to a dormant state in order to avoid the high exit fees, as mentioned by each of the six interviewees. This has in fact posed greater difficulty to the researcher to find the proper sampling candidates through official platforms.

“The economy was boosting in 2016 and 2017 but since then, it is going down, affecting the purchasing capability of people. You know when there is recession, people will refrain from spending their money” – Ex1.

As a part of this ecosystem, culture has been examined and investigated significantly in entrepreneurial research as to its impact on promoting entrepreneurial careers in the first place (Gupta *et al.*, 2010). Interestingly, culture also impacts the exit decision of entrepreneurs, not only the entry attempts. The Lebanese culture was described by all interviewees as very supportive for self-employment (emphasised for the autonomous jobs) (GEM, 2017) and for the pursuit of entrepreneurial careers (GEM, 2016). However, this cultural perception of entrepreneurial careers provides low tolerance towards failure and associates the failing and discontinuing entrepreneurs with shame and stigma (Bacon, 2016):

“Our culture supports the ambition of having your own business and being self-employed rather than employed by others” – Ex1.

“The Lebanese culture has a high stigma for failure and doesn’t tolerate failing entrepreneurs. At the same time, almost every Lebanese person wants to be a boss of their own [...] For your info, one of the reasons why women entrepreneurs are more successful in Lebanon is because they tend to exhibit their best in the face of the cultural disbelief in their ability to succeed [...] For entrepreneurs, failure has a bigger noise in culture than it has in their heads; so yeah, the fear failure because of society’s criticism is there” – Ex4.

Therefore, even when entrepreneurs struggle financially at a certain stage and realise the dead-end of their business, hesitance from actually adopting the exit decision relates to avoiding stigmatisation (Vaillant and Lafuente, 2007). Fearing this association of names with failure in the society’s mind starts hence even before failure (Singh *et al.*, 2015). At this stage, entrepreneurs face the denial state, refusing to accept the reality that the business cannot survive anymore. This psychological pressure in some instances contributes to the failure *per se* (Singh *et al.*, 2015). Following up on the culture’s impact, two interviewees mentioned the low level of cooperation within the Lebanese culture, especially at the entrepreneurs-to-entrepreneurs level and entrepreneurs-to-advisors level, linking the discussion back to the issue of overconfidence (Navis and Ozbek, 2016):

“I cannot say that there is cooperation in our culture, even accelerators among each other instead of joining efforts and boosting the level of admissions for tech start-ups compete rather than cooperate [...] even entrepreneurs... they don’t like to learn from others and hear other entrepreneurs’ stories; they will always tell you ‘*yeah I know*’ and they end up not appreciating the learning experience of their ancestors” – Ex3.

This degree of cooperation actually raises concern as to the impact of failure stigmatisation on encouraging entrepreneurs to seek out external assistance. In other

instances, it may be the result of fear of judgment rather than overconfidence, which will be explored in the narrative analysis of entrepreneurs.

Figure 27: Key findings of Section 6.1.2.6

In summary, the selected candidates have explained the failure of start-ups and the exit decisions of entrepreneurs through a combined-hybrid approach, focusing the attribution as internal or external to the entrepreneur: macro-environment (external level) factors, including the access and availability to finance, access to market, governmental support, national stability and security, and convenience and availability of infrastructure; whilst also evaluating the entrepreneurs' abilities to manage these ventures (individual-internal level). Table 15 below represents a summary of the key findings from this section.

It is important to re-emphasise at this stage that the purpose of interviewing experts was to establish a recent, strong, and sound background of perceived attributions of failure, given the scarce resources available in the particular cultural and developing context of the study. The themes that emerged were therefore helpful in developing follow-up questions for the interviews with entrepreneurs. The follow-up questions represented notes on the themes raised by the experts to understand the entrepreneurs' perspectives and reflection upon them. This does not contradict with the concept of narratives, as people do not always tell long stories and in some instances might forget some details and then bring them out later (as witnessed by the researcher during some interviews) (Riessman, 2008). By concluding with the analysis of experts, the Chapter proceeds with the presentation and analysis of entrepreneurs' narratives.

Internal Dimensions	External Dimensions
Networks Insufficient efforts undertaken Reliance on strong and close networks	Networks No platform exists to find networks
Finance Management of funds is not satisfactory	Finance Access to finance is difficult and unsatisfactory Availability of funds is good but not sufficient
Human Capital Recruitment process is not very professional	Human Capital No proper market for finding talented people Compensation paid to HC is a major obstacle
Marketing Marketing is usually executed with less planning The function is executed at the social media and traditional levels	
Skills and Competencies Level of preparedness and skills is unsatisfactory Intuitive decision-making is mostly dominating Over-confidence optimism are main drivers for failure	
	Ecosystem Institutional level of support is low Culture tolerance to failure is low despite supporting independent employment

Table 15: Summary of findings from experts' interviews

6.2 Entrepreneurs' Narratives

In narrating their stories, not all interviewees would tell long narratives with determined structures. Therefore, the researcher had to interfere with some entrepreneurs more than others, whilst recognising that the quality of stories is not compromised by their length (Georgakapoulou, 2006; Riessman, 2008). Narratives told by interviewees represent personal opinions, experiences, and behaviours that supply the entrepreneurship research with a rich database, the fact that made narrative analysis popular in this field (Gartner, 2007). Unfortunately, narratives of failure have not received as much attention as the success stories, which stems from the bias that learning occurs mostly from success (Gong *et al.*, 2009). However, in researching failure, these discourses represent a tool of interpretation that entrepreneurs employ to make sense of their entrepreneurial experiences, as well as of their identities, with

the possibility of revealing transformative accounts (Lawler, 2002). Following Elliot's (2005) work, the researcher, instead of accounting for the whole life of entrepreneurs, focused the data collection on the episodic event of the entrepreneurial experience. Narratives may encompass the explanation and attributions of failure as perceived by entrepreneurs, rather than being mere descriptions of prior experiences. Henceforth, the search and emphasis are not on finding accurate explanations of failure, but rather on the entrepreneurs' personal attributions of failure (Mantere *et al.*, 2013).

Following on the work of Corner *et al.* (2017), the narratives had a flexible, loose structure that was initiated first with an open-ended question that induces their stories: 'Would you please convey to me the story of your venture and how did it fail? What went wrong with the business?'. For some issues raised (or missed), entrepreneurs needed some follow-up questions by asking 'How did you handle it then? Or what was the consequence of that decision?'. The second part of collecting narratives involved questioning interviewees purposefully, where the researcher engaged actively with entrepreneurs through purposeful questioning. Such probing aimed at clarifying the points that were implied or raising issues that were missed (Kelly and Howie, 2007).

The interviewees shared much rich information about their experience with the venture and the resulting failure, including their emotional and behavioural reactions. Interviews lasted between 70 and 90 minutes, during which entrepreneurs provided vivid and valuable descriptions of their experiences with failure, which was much appreciated but unexpected due to the sensitivity of such topic (Mantere *et al.*, 2013). The recorded interviews, as in the case with the experts, were transcribed in detail before applying the combined holistic/categorical-content narrative analyses (Lieblich *et al.*, 1998) (for details see Chapter 5, Section 5.5.2).

The holistic content analysis involved re-storying the story of each entrepreneur (Ollerenshaw and Creswell, 2002), outlining how elements were connected and accumulated towards the end of the narrative (Polkinghorne, 2007). The analysis could not be initiated before the researcher's familiarisation with the data. To obtain a general overview of the stories, the researcher had to go over each narrative several times, immersing herself within each story. The researcher relied on Polkinghorne's (1995) step of identifying the plot for each story (even when the analysis focused on

the content of stories rather than their form). Reading the narratives made it obvious that entrepreneurs narrated their stories according to the life stage of the business: a) (pre)launching the venture, b) managing the venture and c) exiting the venture. The plot was identified through the temporal interconnection of actions and/or events, with emphasis on the ones that accumulated to contribute to the end of the narrative (failure) (Polkinghorne, 2007). After identifying the plot within the transcripts, the researcher initiated the analysis of the content to understand the ‘what’, ‘how’ and ‘who’ elements (Beal, 2013).

As the analysis aims into investigating each narrative holistically, a visual representation of the codes (actions/decisions/events) was developed rather than simply sequencing events (as attached in Appendix D). The codes represented categories within the story (Edwards, 2016) which referred to decisions made, actions undertaken and events occurring during the venture’s life, along with the personal responses subsequent to failure using colour coding (Iyengar, 2014). Therefore, these categories represented the attributions developed for failure (along with their justifications), and the learning outcomes that resulted. Subsequently, a re-storied transcript of these codes was developed for each entrepreneur to: mirror the structure of each story; show the interrelatedness between the various codes or data; and uncover the meaning of the narratives (Polkinghorne, 2007).

Unlike the holistic-content analysis, the categorical content analysis encompassed retrieving the themes emerging from the raw, untouched stories of entrepreneurs. Henceforth, the first step comprised breaking the stories of interviewees into smaller extracts or units of content. This process, labelled as dissection by Lieblich *et al.* (1998), implies that “*the narrative story is dissected, and sections or single words belonging to a defined category are collected from the entire story, or from several texts belonging to a number of narrators*” (p.12). Such analytical anatomy of the texts and extracts provided a platform that enabled the researcher to examine the discrepancies, as well as the similarities between the various themes arising from the narratives of different entrepreneurs (Beal, 2013). The researcher invested considerable time and effort in developing knowledge out of the themes that shape entrepreneurs’ stories, reading over and over the transcripts (Ollerenshaw and Creswell, 2002).

The categorical process adopted for each interview was divided into three main stages (Iborra, 2007). The first stage included retrieving extracts from texts and then, relating those extracts to categories created across the discourses of interviewees. The second stage moved into visually modelling the analysis, by highlighting the main categories and the relationships among them. The final stage involved writing a summary (or a memo) about the analysis of each interview, describing the key categories that emerged from the analysis, and the relationships among these categories, along with the different particularities and similarities among the interviewees' stories (Earthy and Cornin, 2008). The last step assisted in preserving the individuality of each entrepreneur's experience, as the main categories were selected for the purpose of situating each entrepreneur accordingly.

Considering the criticism that such categorical analysis might break the data from the comprehensive experience of individuals (Conrad, 1990), the researcher has ensured to categorise the extracts without isolating them from the personal contexts in which they were stated, preserving the linkage between the meaning and the story. Accordingly, the researcher wrote theoretic notes about each entrepreneur to maintain the peculiarities of each that were reflected upon later by the emerging categories (Iborra, 2007). Consequently, a context was established in order to construct the different patterns between categories, after comparing them and their uniqueness for every entrepreneur. Moreover, the combination of the categorical analysis with the holistic analysis helps in preserving the context of each, as the holistic content analysis aims into maintaining the peculiarities of each (Beal, 2013). In the process of selecting the pertinent categories, the researcher selected the categories that represented actions, occurrences, and decisions (Kelly and Howie, 2007). These categories were, then, classified as most relevant in understanding the attributions developed by entrepreneurs and their responses to failure. A peculiarity about the narrative analysis is highlighting a category as relevant even when mentioned only by one interviewee if this category helps in understanding the entrepreneurs' experience and decision-making process (Iborra, 2007).

The process of storytelling, being loaded with emotions, reveals a more insightful comprehension of entrepreneurial exit decisions from the lenses of entrepreneurs' themselves (Gartner, 2010), which can be extensively used for future learning (Rae and Carswell, 2000). This process of reflecting upon the event of failure (in a

retrospective form) allowed entrepreneurs to re-think how associations of actions can be understood. This re-imagination of the past event enables an insightful and thoughtful process of sense-making (Boje, 2008 as cited in Keeble-Ramsay and Keeble, 2018). The emerging categories and themes were analysed holistically within each story then across multiple interviews, integrating the initial analysis of experts within this analysis. Within each form of analysis, the researcher has grouped the emerging categories according to the nature of attributions developed, which gave rise to four types as will be elaborated next.

Following on Pitt's (1998) emphasis on the significance of narratives to explore the sense-making process of failure by entrepreneurs, the researcher borrowed the concept of practice-based theories of Rae (2004), originally applied to study learning from success stories (see Chapter 2, Section 2.3.2). The concept was adopted to develop practice-based attributions of failure as ascribed by entrepreneurs during their reflection process on this episodic event. Implied within the attributions developed, the practice-based theories highlighted what did not work according to entrepreneurs, and how these pitfalls can be avoided to enhance the survival opportunities of business ventures. Starting first with a reflective summary of interviewed entrepreneurs, the analysis follows afterwards.

6.2.1 Demographics of Entrepreneurs

The candidates were chosen based on the purposive sampling method, allowing for a fair representation of the varying industries operating in Lebanon, and the different geographical areas within the country (see Chapter 5, Section 5.4.2). Starting with the demographics, only two of the fourteen interviewees were female. The ages of the interviewees ranged between 25 and 55, operating across several fields (technology products and services; food and catering; clothing and design; graphic design; and computer hardware and software). The entrepreneurs selected were all based in Lebanon and operated either in the national (11 businesses) or in the international markets (3 businesses). In terms of their backgrounds, only two of the interviewees were partially unemployed before launching their businesses, and the rest were either employed (9) or serial entrepreneurs (3). Education-wise, all interviewees (apart from one serial entrepreneur) had at least one university qualification (Bachelors) before pursuing entrepreneurial careers.

The process of reaching to interviewees was more complicated, difficult, and challenging than expected (as will be elaborated in Chapter 8, Section 8.4). Indeed, the government, specifically the Ministry of Economy and Trade, does not retain any updated proper records on the names of businesses that have discontinued their operations, from which the selection can occur¹⁰. The lack of an accurate national database (BLOM Bank, 2018) on the status of businesses in Lebanon, whether active, dormant, or discontinued, has forced the researcher to look for alternative ways. Therefore, the researcher had to rely on her professional and weak networks as well as informal references, spreading the word about the study (personally and through social media posts), and the need for interviewing entrepreneurs. The researcher has also surfed many regional crowdfunding websites to find out the contact details of Lebanese entrepreneurs. Given the difficulty to reach out to the intended participants, the purposive approach was supported with snowball sampling. However, the researcher made sure that the interviewees suggested by others and selected for the analysis do not present obvious homogeneity with their references (Penrod *et al.*, 2003). Candidates were then contacted for an online interview through Zoom or Skype, as per their convenience, and the interviewees were spread over the period of 3 months (March-May 2020).

The researcher initiated the recruitment of the sample with the names and companies of 42 entrepreneurs, either found online or referred to by the researcher's networks. With the responses received, the researcher filtered the profiles of the potential candidates according to the criteria listed in Chapter 5, Section 5.4.2., removing 11 entrepreneurs who did not qualify. Moreover, the contact details (phone numbers and emails) of 9 entrepreneurs were outdated, and another 8 entrepreneurs either refused or ignored the request to participate. Table 16 below represents an informative summary of entrepreneurs and their ventures. Names were not used, and instead, codes were assigned for each entrepreneur, preserving the confidentiality and anonymity of each participant. Before proceeding with the analysis, it is important at this stage to emphasise the definition of failure adopted for this study, as the termination of a business venture that either did not achieve the initial goals of its

¹⁰ The official gazette would list discontinuing businesses by date; however, the contact details of the founders were either unavailable or outdated.

main shareholders (entrepreneurs) or has not been economically viable (Cope, 2011; Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015; Jenkins and McKelvie, 2016).

Code	Prior Employment	Business Area	Formal Venture	Date of Foundation	Date of exit	Profitability	Personal Compensation	Initial Funds ¹¹	Size of the Venture ¹²	Location
En1	No	Services	No	2017	2019	Unprofitable	None	Personal	Micro - Less than 10	North Lebanon
En2	Yes	Services (digital)	Yes	2011	2012	Breakeven	Salary	Personal	Micro - Less than 10	Capital
En3	Yes	Production	No	2017	2019	Profitable	Share of the profits	Personal	Small- Less than 50	Capital
En4	Yes	Production (tech)	Yes	2015	2019	Unprofitable	None	Investors	Small- Less than 50	Capital
En5	Yes	Services (digital)	No	2013	2016	Breakeven	Salary	Personal	Micro- Less than 10	Capital
En6	Yes	Trading	Yes	2009	2020	Profits declined after the first 2 years	Salary	Personal and commercial	Micro-Less than 10	South Lebanon
En7	No	Production	No	2015	2017	Unprofitable	Expense's coverage	Personal	Micro- Less than 10 (6 are seasonal workers)	North Lebanon
En8	Yes	Hospitality	Yes	2016	2019	Unprofitable	None	Personal	Medium- Less than 100	Capital
En9	Yes	Services (digital)	Yes	2005	2011	Profitable	None	Investors	Medium- Less than 100	Capital
En10	Yes	Services	Yes	2018	2019	Unprofitable	Share of profit	Crowdfunding (small amount)	Micro- less than 10	Capital

¹¹ Personal capital can be either savings or borrowings from family and friends. The researcher did not find any relevance to the analysis in differentiating between these two. Commercial capital implies loans from banks.

¹² Business venture cannot be defined the same way as in developed countries. In fact, the “Micro Enterprise” earns “less than \$300 thousand” and employs “less than 10 employees”; “Small Enterprise” earns “less than \$3 million” and employs “less than 50 employees”; and “Medium Enterprise” earns “less than \$30 million” and employs “less than 100 employees” (Hamdar *et al.*, 2017, p. 334). Under this notion, more than 93% of the Lebanese companies registered as operating companies are classified as MSMEs (Mezher *et al.*, 2008; Hamdar *et al.*, 2017). For the sake of this study, the definition will be rather dependent on the number of employees.

En11	Yes	Services	Yes	2015	2017	Unprofitable	Salary	Investors	Small-Less than 50	Capital
En12	Yes	Hospitality	Yes	2015	2018	Unprofitable	Share of profit	Personal	Micro-Less than 10	Bekaa
En13	Yes	Production	Yes	2014	2016	Unprofitable	Share of profit	Personal	Micro-Less than 10	Bekaa
En14	Yes	Services	Yes	2012	2016	Profits declined after the first 2 years	Salary	Personal	Micro-Less than 10	Capital

Table 16: An informative summary of the demographics of entrepreneurs interviewed

Source: Researcher

Figure 28: Scheme outlining the heterogeneity of entrepreneurs interviewed

Source: Researcher

6.2.2 Reflection Process on Failure

In analysing the reflective narratives of entrepreneurs, the plot of each story revealed three main timeframes that structured the narratives: the first stage, which involved the establishment of ventures; the second stage, the management of ventures; and the third stage, the exit event of entrepreneurs. The reflective/assessment process of entrepreneurs was clearly stated in every stage, as interviewees articulated weaknesses, strengths, and wrongdoings in each timeframe. A great emphasis was placed on the second stage during which entrepreneurs evaluated their behavioural decision-making for the life of the venture. Failure ascriptions were developed significantly in this stage to explain, reflect, and elaborate on the experience and the eventual failure.

The relevance of these stages mirrors the researcher's argument that the failure was not the result of an overnight decision, but rather an accumulated outcome of a series of events and/or decisions-behaviours (Delmar *et al.*, 2003). Henceforth, analysing the reflective process and the learning outcomes generated from the exit decision necessitates elaborating on each stage while emphasising the resulting ascriptions in each, as perceived by entrepreneurs. Building on the general categorisation of

attributions as internal-unstable-controllable and external-stable-uncontrollable (Weiner, 1985), and the weight of the locus of causality dimension in critically influencing the degree of entrepreneurial learning from failure (Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015), the researcher noted the emergence of four attributive categorisations. These four distinct, yet, interrelated groups encompass: *individual (internal)*: failure is the result of entrepreneurial decisions and behaviours (controllable) (Walsh and Cunningham, 2017); *ecosystematic (external)*: failure was caused by the entrepreneurial ecosystem in which the business operated (uncontrollable) (including institutions, society, and market) (Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015); *fated*: entrepreneurs had already invested every effort that could be provided and nothing was left to be done (Mantere *et al.*, 2013); and *mistaken judgment of opportunities*: entrepreneurs realised at a later stage that the opportunity perceived at the beginning (service or product) turned out to not solve an actual problem in the market (Dempster, 2020).

Code (Name)	Previous Entrepreneurial Experience	Initial Motivation	Next venturing activity	Time gap
En1	Novice	Lack of employment opportunities (EO)	Entrepreneur	9 months
En2	Serial	Scalable business	Entrepreneur (angel investor)	24 months
En3	Serial	Health problems	Entrepreneur	20 months
En4	Novice	Settlement and lack of EO	Entrepreneur	18 months
En5	Novice	Lack of interest in EO	Freelancer	2-3 months
En6	Novice	Lack of interest in EO	Freelancer	2-3 months
En7	Novice	Social initiative and lack of interest in EO	Entrepreneur	9 months
En8	Serial	Scalable business	Entrepreneur	9 months
En9	Serial	Scalable business	Entrepreneur	7 months
En10	Novice	Social initiative and lack of interest in EO	Entrepreneur	8 months
En11	Novice	Scalable business	Entrepreneur	24 months
En12	Novice	Lack of EO	Entrepreneur	7 months
En13	Novice	Settlement and lack of EO	Entrepreneur	6 months
En14	Novice	Lack of EO	Entrepreneur	27 months

Table 17: An informative summary of entrepreneurs

Source: Researcher

The reflection process involved exploring the attribution of entrepreneurs at each business aspect and how each led to the failure. The purpose behind analysing these attributions involved understanding the process with which entrepreneurs develop attributions and categorise an attribution as internal or external. These dimensions unveiled the learning outcomes from failure, by highlighting the minor and major attributions as perceived by entrepreneurs rather than the primary attributions concluded by Yamakawa and Cardon (2015) and Walsh and Cunningham (2017) among others. Consequently, such deep exploration revealed diverging findings; more specifically, as entrepreneurs were elaborating on each attribution, ascriptions classified as purely internal in other studies had also external roots in this study and vice-versa.

As a result, the researcher has classified the ascriptions and attributions as internal if these involved deliberate actions and decisions made by the entrepreneur (as will be elaborated next). For instance, Walsh and Cunningham (2017) have classified the lack of proper market research as an external attribution to the individual, when the entrepreneur explicitly stated not researching the market properly (for details see Walsh and Cunningham, 2017, page 696). On the contrary, in this study, interviewees blamed themselves for overlooking such a step, or understating the relevance of conducting market research; hence, the attribution was eventually internal rather than external. Therefore, exploring internal and external attributions through business aspects, events, decisions, and behaviours assists in understanding more deeply and comprehensively the attribution, reflection, and learning processes from failure. Within this reflective process, entrepreneurs implied their learning outcomes associated with each business aspect correspondingly, emerging from the identification of wrong decisions and behaviours (Cope, 2011). Subsequent to the analysis of all stages, the entrepreneurs' emotional responses were analysed separately.

6.2.2.1 Stage 1: Establishing the Venture

During this stage, the reflection gave rise to three main issues: the differentiated initial motivations, the availability, access and management of funds, and the level of planning and preparedness for the entrepreneurial career.

6.2.2.1.1 Initial Entrepreneurial Motivations

All entrepreneurs, upon storytelling their experiences, initiated their narratives by highlighting the motivational factors that induced the venturing pursuit. The reflection on the initial motivations is of high importance for the reflection process on the entrepreneurial experience, as these factors impacted the persistence of entrepreneurs (DeTienne *et al.*, 2008); their nature and type of exit (DeTienne, 2010); and the process of making sense from failure (Heinze, 2013).

Entrepreneurs usually have different motivations behind pursuing entrepreneurial careers and the degree and authenticity of this motive determine their persistence and devotion (DeTienne *et al.*, 2008). The level of knowledge acquired and developed (Wennberg *et al.*, 2010), the readiness to fit within the entrepreneurial career, and the personal drive and motivation of each interviewee (DeTienne *et al.*, 2008) regulated their persistence or decision to exit. For novice entrepreneurs, which compose the majority of the sample size, the lack of suitable employment opportunities in terms of salary and position was the main drive to pursue the entrepreneurial career (MET, 2014; GEM, 2016), with two entrepreneurs exhibiting social motivation:

“At the same time, I was offered to do some freelancing projects with the UN, IRO, so at some point, I realised that I cannot keep up with both types of work, and I started losing interest in my full-time job” – En5.

In contrast, serial entrepreneurs, given their previous experiences, were mostly driven by the ambition of growing a scalable business, satisfying their need for a substantial achievement (Gabrielsson and Politis, 2011):

“The main motive for behind going for the business was the lack of employment opportunities. I was looking for a job but couldn’t find my desired one so I thought to take a social initiative that will give us a return for me and my friends. So yeah my passion for going into this was my passion for social work [...]” – En7.

“My main concern is that I established the venture to scale the idea globally or at least regionally and to be acquired by big companies” – En8.

Interestingly, both classes of entrepreneurs (novice and serial) showed on average a similar timespan of their ventures (between 2 years and 4 years). Therefore, the initial motivations did not create much impact on the persistence of entrepreneurs in the market, challenging DeTienne *et al.* (2008). However, these motivations impacted the direction of funds sought, where serial entrepreneurs sought external funding more than the novice entrepreneurs, and hence managed to raise significant investments for their ventures (Cosh *et al.*, 2009; Garg and Shivam, 2017).

6.2.2.1.2 Availability, Access, and Management of Funds

The lack of funds was considered by the experts as one of the main obstacles for entrepreneurs to sustain and/or to succeed, but not a reason for failure (see Subsection 6.1.2.1). On the contrary, interviewed entrepreneurs had different perspectives as to the lack of funds, therefore, the attribution of failure to the lack of funds took several angles. Some entrepreneurs attributed the failure partially to the lack of funds, considering it an obstacle for paying proper compensation to recruit and retain the necessary talents (Salgado *et al.*, 2020); others viewed it as a challenge for implementing the planned marketing strategy (O'Donnell, 2014). Interestingly, some entrepreneurs exploited the lack of funds as an opportunity to learn and insource some of the venture's functions, for the purpose of reducing costs associated with hiring and delegating:

“Maybe if I had the funds as my peers, I would have spent it unwisely, and wouldn't have probably learnt as much as I did without these initial funds” – En1.

Given the heterogeneity of the sample, the notion of funds had to be analysed from two different perspectives: venturing either with limited funds (personal borrowings) (Witt, 2004) or after raising substantive amounts of equity funds (Beck and Demircuk-Kunt, 2006). The researcher will refer to the first group as the unfunded entrepreneurs and the second group as the funded entrepreneurs. During this stage, entrepreneurs mostly emphasised the availability and access to funds, and hence, the amount of capital available throughout the venture's life. Novice entrepreneurs in majority relied on personal networks for funds (Witt, 2004) and personal savings (Fatoki, 2014), while serial entrepreneurs in majority managed to raise substantial funds:

“All of our funds were personal loans from friends and family; I avoided banks due to the lack of collateral and the fact that we are a newly established start-up” – En1.

“What I felt is going to be easy and straightforward probably around 3 months took me indeed 10 months. But eventually I managed to raise 1.1 million USD to kick off our venture” – En4.

Additionally, all entrepreneurs believed that the shortage in liquidity was an issue not only for launching the ventures but also throughout the whole lifecycle of the venture (Fort *et al.*, 2013; Jere *et al.*, 2015). However, its impact was intense in the beginning:

“Everyone advises and says yeah do this and do that, reach the stars, but the ugly truth is that without funds you can't actually do anything [with laughter]” – En5.

“Again, I started with zero capital, even my dad didn't have the funds to provide me with. I even had to sell my car when I decided to grow the shop to a printing centre as I had some lack of funds” – En6.

Therefore, the attribution of failure to lack of funds differed among both groups depending on their initial financial status. According to two of the funded entrepreneurs, the lack of funds was contributory to the exit decision, even after raising millions of dollars that were completely invested in the business (En4 and En8). Henceforth, the exit decision came subsequent to ‘failing’ to raise more funds that were needed for further expansion (En8) or product development (En4):

“I couldn’t raise any further funds. I needed the funds for regional expansion and for pushing the company really high. But I couldn’t secure these funds. So yes, my decision to exit is majorly attributed to this lack of funds” – En8.

An interesting attribution raised by these entrepreneurs was related to their perceptions of the role of investors and venture capitalists in the failure. These entrepreneurs accused the improper level of sophistication and diversified knowledge and background of investors in the Arab region, and their understanding of the value of service or product pitched. Such accusation relates to the Nemesis narrative, in which investors are blamed greatly for the failure (*external ascription*) (Mantere *et al.*, 2013):

“The venture capitalists in the Arab world have little experience and understanding of the hardware investment, and thus, they were praising the product and the idea, but they would feel more comfortable with software because this is where their experience lies [...] I met with 82 investors but couldn’t convince anyone of them to invest” – En4.

As for the unfunded entrepreneurs, external financing (equity and debt) was highly difficult to receive, given the limited available supply of debt financing (Abdesamed and Abd Wahab, 2014) and venture capitalism (Shane, 2012) for new ventures. Probing further about the sources of funds within the unfunded category, all seven entrepreneurs agreed on the problematic access to debt financing due to the high criteria of banks for credit history and collateral to qualify for debt financing (Naimy, 2011; Fatoki, 2014) and on the low availability of venture capitalism (Blumberg and Letterie, 2008; Jeger *et al.*, 2016). Perceiving the impossibility of borrowing loans from banks (Xiang *et al.*, 2014), entrepreneurs referred to their close networks seeking additional support of funds (Witt, 2004; Fatoki, 2014). By inquiring further into the reason for the unsuccessful pursuit of raising funds and its implications on the entrepreneurial journey, entrepreneurs reflected on their experiences with local funding competitions. On the individual level, entrepreneurs considered the level of preparedness for these competitions as dedicated, by investing substantial effort and time to pitch:

“[...] they [the jury] were really happy with my business idea. They used to praise me for it (laughs). But still I didn't manage to even raise a penny. And I was preparing nice presentations and really look forward to it but all in vain” – En7

However, this issue brought up an interesting attribution by one entrepreneur, which could be probably experienced by other entrepreneurs not included in the study. Given the small size of the country, some members of the jury in funding competitions used to attend and judge for almost every pitching competition. Henceforth, and according to the entrepreneur, this reflected negatively on their pitching, as the jury was judging the entrepreneur for having a lack of life purpose (if he keeps submitting the same idea), or with a lack of dedication and focus (if he decided to change aspects of his idea, partially or totally) (*external ascription*):

“You know in Lebanon, as a small country, you will see almost the same jurors in every competition you attend. And then they will think that you have nothing in life but to go to these competitions. Also, sometimes, the jury judges you for switching entrepreneurial ideas, in case you didn't foresee yourself in one particular idea. But in their opinions, you are not dedicated or strategic in reaching one goal; this is also a problem” – En7.

When faced with a shortage of external funds, entrepreneurs tend to rely on the internally generated cash flows to sustain themselves (Sampagnaro, 2013). This was not possible to achieve for the unfunded entrepreneurs due to two main reasons: unprofitability of their businesses (GEM, 2016) and their skills in managing the funds (Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015) (*internal ascription*). More specifically, two entrepreneurs have attributed this lack of liquidity to their improper follow up with collecting outstanding debts, which, if occurred, would have deferred the liquidity crisis (Majkova and Kljucnikov, 2017):

“[...] back then they [the sales] were small, but now when I think about it, it wasn't actually small returns. It was just maybe me, I was impatient, because the 3000 we had in a month as break-even is actually good... it wasn't bad... but my deficiency in collecting this money was actually the bad thing and it was my fault. So that was the problem” – En2.

On the contrary, three other entrepreneurs sought effortfully to collect their receivables but were unable to do so (Kestens *et al.*, 2012). For these entrepreneurs, sufficient but unsuccessful efforts and time were invested in their attempt to collect outstanding debts (*fated ascription*):

“[...] because you know, in Lebanon clients drag in settling their outstanding debts. And it happened. This is why I was refraining from operating heavily in the Lebanese market. So, I was targeting more GCC countries and the US, as well as Europe. I didn't want to take any risk in Lebanon” – En9.

“We did our best to collect the outstanding debts, but we just couldn't. especially with our dealers in Saudi Arabia. They simply didn't pay us our full fees” – En14.

Another *internal attribution* for managing funds and liquidity was also revealed with one funded entrepreneur for overspending on product development (Arasti, 2011) and an unfunded entrepreneur for overspending the company’s cash, without properly segregating between personal and business expenditures (in line with experts’ statements) (Mezher *et al.*, 2008), respectively:

“I spent all of the funds raised on product development. This is definitely one of my mistakes” – En4.

“I was overly withdrawing money. Whenever I needed anything to buy, for my personal or family use, I used to simply withdraw cash or use the cards to purchase it” – En6.

The exploration of the entrepreneurs’ struggle with funds seems to be guided by the purpose behind raising these funds and the number of rounds for raising funds. Funded entrepreneurs perceived investors as the main contributor to the exit decision (Mantere *et al.*, 2013), as the purpose for the second round of funds aimed at scaling up the business and building an international name (Gabrielsson and Politis, 2011; Garg and Shivam, 2017). Henceforth, the early ambitions of the ventures that were not realised due to the inability to raise further funds led to the exit (though En4 blamed himself for the mismanagement of funds in developing the product) (Politis and Gabrielsson, 2009; Cope, 2011). On the other hand, unfunded entrepreneurs who sought debt financing struggled with meeting the requirements and hence, believed that the lack of profits and absence of collateral challenged their access to this level of financing (Sampagnaro, 2013). In parallel, financing competitions sought were perceived as unfair, given the dominance of a single jury. Figure 29 below highlights the nature of attribution of the lack of funds and its impact on various business levels.

Figure 29: Nature of attributions of the lack of funds and their impact on the venture

6.2.2.1.3 Level of Preparedness and Failure

In this section, the reflection of entrepreneurs took place over their level of preparedness and planning for their ventures, including the formality of plans and market research. Half of the entrepreneurs revealed a full immersion and understanding of the market with a proper and formal planning (mostly funded and serial entrepreneurs). The other half had an informal, incomplete plan (Arasti, 2011; Pretorius and Le Roux, 2011; Eggers and Song, 2014; Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015) and a preliminary, shallow study about competitors, target segments, and prices (Hooley *et al.*, 1999) (unfunded entrepreneurs), which were ascribed as attributions of failure (Rasmussen *et al.*, 2011). The decision behind adopting this step was mostly affected by the pressuring existence of investors in the big picture. More specifically, the entrepreneurs' efforts to study the market aimed either to maintain the flow of funds or to attempt raising financial funds (pitching and raising funds) (Yusuf, 2012):

“Honestly if it was up to us we wouldn't have done any reports, but we had to do them as the NGO was following up with us, always asking us for updates and our achievements, and what is our next step” – En7.

“From a business perspective, it is a failure. Also, from a startup perspective it is still a failure. The goal of the startup is not to generate revenue in the first 2 years but to develop a successful business plan replicable business model and I did not. I had a partially successful business model, but I couldn't find a way to execute it” – En2.

Therefore, this finding raises the concern to the actual awareness of entrepreneurs of market research. In other words, speculating a context where entrepreneurs already had their initial funds secured would they still study the market? Subsequent to the shallow market research (Walsh and Cunningham, 2017) and the lack of planning (Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015), the resulting improper pricing of services or products, and the late recognition of strong competitors contributed to the death of the venture of unfunded entrepreneurs (Mezher *et al.*, 2008) (*internal ascription*). An interesting contradiction was therefore revealed between the entrepreneurs' acknowledgement of the need for conducting a proper study and their lack of executing such study. The plans developed were either informal or incomplete in terms of analysing the market and the rivalry (Walsh and Cunningham, 2017), which is supposed to efficiently determine the appropriate pricing, segmenting, and marketing strategies. The decisions were therefore adopted through improvisation (Martinez, 2001) or effectuation (Sarasvathy, 2001), relying on their interactions with customers as the main source for information (Resnick *et al.*, 2016):

“[...] we then realised that we had a strong competitor that we were not aware of [...] our competitor was very strong and so we didn’t have a chance against him. They produce in big quantities and cheaper price and they claim as well to be organic. I think I disregarded it thinking that it is in another city and is less probable for farmers to deal with it” – En7.

“In terms of competition, there are only few small individuals with whom we compete. We did a preliminary study that includes the names of the competitors, their prices, their targeted areas, their services provided so that we can decide on which services and areas we can focus and which ones to forego as they have already invested money in this and we don’t want to compete on such levels. Before deciding on the price, we did a breakdown of the costs that we need to cover first. Also, we categorised our customers like clusters” – En1.

In reflecting upon the market, three of the funded entrepreneurs (two of which are serial) attributed the failure completely to the market (and ecosystem) (*external ascription*). On the contrary, novice and unfunded entrepreneurs were more understanding of the market, though not completely satisfied with it, praising the small size and flexibility of the market as a learning platform for trial-and-error:

“Also the Lebanese market shouldn’t be the aim for any business, but it is a good start and a privilege as it is very flexible and forgiving (trying and learning with mistakes), more than any other market where there are whales would have probably vanished me” – En1.

Therefore, entrepreneurs attributed the failure partially to the lack of market research and planning, and correspondingly attributed this lack of market study *internally* to personal inconsideration (Arasti, 2011). When inquired further to elaborate, entrepreneurs acknowledged overlooking the competition in relation to their exaggerated belief in their capacity to lead the venture to success and to raise funds in the future (overconfidence and underestimation of the efforts needed) (*internal attribution*) (Astebro *et al.*, 2014; Navis and Ozbek, 2016). This factor has been weighed only by unfunded entrepreneurs as a partial contributor to failure.

Figure 30: Nature of attributions of the market study and their impact on the venture

In summary, unfunded entrepreneurs attributed the failure majorly to the lack of funds, which was attributed in return intensely to the difficulty in raising funds (*ecosystematic ascription*), and nominally to the ability of entrepreneurs in managing funds and liquidity (*internal ascription*). In parallel, funded entrepreneurs attributed the lack of funds solely to external factors (*ecosystematic ascription*). Another pure *internal attribution* of failure related to the entrepreneurs' level of preparedness and planning exhibited by novice-unfunded entrepreneurs. The improper pricing and unawareness of competition caused by the lack of planning (*internal ascription*) were considered attributions of failure. The impact of initial motivations on the exit decision and learning from failure will be elaborated later. By concluding with the main themes in the first stage, the analysis moves into the next timeframe.

6.2.2.2 Stage 2: Managing the Venture

In this second time plot, entrepreneurs reflected differently on the various patterns of entrepreneurial decision-making, according to their prior experience, optimism, and determination motivation (Gabrielsson and Politis, 2011). In their reflection on behavioural decision-making, entrepreneurs focused on assessing their decisions and actions (Cope, 2011) with respect to the main managerial functions such as planning, budgeting, managing, advertising, networking, and recruiting.

While reflecting on their managerial approach, entrepreneurs mostly revealed two main patterns that were more correlated than distinctive: intuitive (or effectual) and rational (or causal) (Sarasvathy, 2001). The correlation in employing both processes was exhibited through many behaviours, such as intuitively advertising for the company but rationally seeking finance. In other words, when entrepreneurs face an uncertain event, the information that should be supposedly relied upon stems either from their external environment or from their evaluation of past decisions in similar contexts (Achtziger and Alos-Ferrer, 2014). In this study, serial entrepreneurs with linear and expert minds seemed to adopt more the rational approach, given their entrepreneurial experience and initial motivations (Gabrielsson and Politis, 2011). On the contrary, novice entrepreneurs, composing the majority of the sample, adopted less planning, structure and information (Sarasvathy, 2001), relying more on the effectuation reasoning following their spiral and transitory minds (Gabrielsson and Politis, 2011).

Throughout the reflection, entrepreneurs highlighted their actions and decisions across various business aspects. More specifically, entrepreneurs reflected on their social networks and initiatives in networking, the extent of planning and executing the marketing function, the recruitment and management of human capital, and the proper market research. Other points raised by entrepreneurs necessitated further probing and analysis by the researcher, such as the impact of cultural stigmatisation and governmental support.

6.2.2.2.1 Social Skills and Networks

Networks compose an integral part of entrepreneurs' success and have been considered as one of the critical sustainability factors for early start-ups (Lans *et al.*, 2015; Boso *et al.*, 2019). The reflection of entrepreneurs on business networks involved an evaluation of the nature of these networks and their past impact on survival, by assessing the aspects of the social capital mostly relied upon. The reflection assessed the nature of entrepreneurs' networks (who are they connected to) and the ways of building these networks (how did they reach them) (Burt, 1997; Nahapiet and Ghoshal, 1998). Networking skills of entrepreneurs were then elaborated through the five characteristics of their social competence (Baron and Markman, 2000; Baron and Tang, 2009): *social adaptability*, which describes the ability of entrepreneurs to adjust their business idea, according to others' suggestions; *social perception*, which describes their ability to form accurate perceptions about other people; *personal expressiveness*, which determines their ability to express emotions and enthusiasm visibly; *ingratiation*, which relates to their ability to flatter socially and compromise with others; and *self-promotion*, which reveals the entrepreneurs' ability to present their own skills and achievements positively.

As part of understanding the perceived attribution of failure to networks, it is critical to reflect on the entrepreneurs' awareness and recognition of the role of networks. Almost all interviewees expressed the significant role played by their strong, frequent, and bonding networks in their very early stage. More specifically, these networks assisted in spreading the word about the business and acted as an informal marketing team that also served as a small piloting test (Jaafar *et al.*, 2009). For 11 entrepreneurs (including En11, who raised substantial amounts of money), strong networks played a significant role in increasing the brand's equity and exposure, and in improving the product or service to a certain extent through opinions and feedback (in relation with

the entrepreneurs' social adaptability) (Lans *et al.*, 2015). Interestingly, this support was preceded with negative perception:

“[...] Then I realised that I have to tell them (friends and family) [about the business] as I needed their help to grow the business and so I told them. Otherwise I would have needed lots more funds in order to grow the business; so, I told them hey guys, I have this business and I really need your feedback and evaluation, if you see anything wrong with it, please let me know. And this is what actually made me grow and get recognised and known by the people on the ground. So, my friends' feedback was very helpful, telling me don't do this, don't do that, so we were actually upgrading and updating according to their evaluation and this is where we started to grow a bit” – En1.

Despite the high cultural support for autonomous professions (GEM, 2016:2017), there seems to be a lack of support by family and friends towards the choice of the entrepreneurial career. Almost half of the unfunded entrepreneurs explained how their close networks were not supportive of the entrepreneurial idea at first and advised the entrepreneurs to seek 'stable' employment instead. This level of support is closely connected to the culture's understanding and perception of risk, which turned out to be less encouraging for risk-taking (GEM, 2018):

“In my whole family, only one person was supportive, but the rest was so against my pursuit of self-employment” – En6.

The weak networks on the other hand, though recognized for their relevance to the businesses (White and Houseman, 2002), were assessed according to the entrepreneurs' active approach in expanding and developing these networks (Zhao *et al.*, 2010) (*internal ascription*). Taking new initiatives to develop further networks was difficult to achieve in the entrepreneurs' opinions, attributing the cause either internally to their “introvert” personalities (the ingratiation):

“[...] but all three of us are introvert, so we didn't engage with anyone (with laughter). I used to help other candidates there with some design requests, but we never asked anything from anyone, anyway we are not the kind of people who would ask for anything” – En5.

“In terms of networks, the NGO that helped us, I was a good volunteer and member at. I witnessed many people seeking finance for their ideas, but I was too shy to go on stage and pitch my idea. I dreamt about this. Then, after attending such pitching events, I started having some talks with those guys who pitched, who were feeling proud for people to come and ask them. This is how I started to increase my networks” – En7.

Or to their perception of the effectiveness and nature of these networks (social perception):

“[...] they would speak down to you, I didn't appreciate these people and I didn't want to waste time with them. My ego wouldn't allow me at this age” – En4.

Among novice entrepreneurs, entrepreneur En1 raised an interesting initiative to approach a network of entrepreneurs, sought for the purpose of learning from their entrepreneurial stories (Welter and Kautonen, 2005). This network, as explained, provided a massive emotional and learning support (Soetanto, 2017) that encouraged the sustainability of the business for two years and maintained the entrepreneurial motivation, in contrast to the experts' argument that the level of mutual support among entrepreneurs is almost inexistent:

“One of my very strongest networks was actually an NGO that I co-founded before the business but I didn't actually make use of it properly [...] so through this NGO, I was actually exposed to businesses whom I can provide services for. What was also very helpful for me was actually the network of the other entrepreneurs that I know because they had similar challenges and they've been through similar experiences, so they have helped me a lot. Essentially, they have provided me with emotional support that I was in huge need of, and also definitely giving me advice and recommendations, like you can do this you can do that” – En1.

On the contrary, funded and serial entrepreneurs were more comfortable expanding their networks in seminars and conferences (Lans *et al.*, 2015). In parallel, serial entrepreneurs did not attribute failure to their networks, perceiving their networking approach to be very sufficient, effective, and enriching. Exploring more specifically the reflection on the role of these networks on survival, the provision of financial resources through weak networks (Connelly *et al.*, 2011) reveals the contribution of these networks to the funded entrepreneurs:

“When we first get the big contracts, the main ones that would cover the costs. I got them from one of my contacts in Silicon Valley” – En9.

“Lebanon is tiny, and my networks helped me especially to raise money [...] I wouldn't say my networks helped me in getting customers but I would definitely say that my networks, the conferences roundtables and seminars I was attending allowed me to connect to investors and raise money” – En11.

Therefore, the background and experience of entrepreneurs (Baptista and Karaöz, 2006) determined to a certain extent the willingness and the level of initiatives taken to expand weak networks. The three types of networks developed (clients, potential investors, and prior work/volunteering) (Birley, 1985) assisted either, in increasing the clients' base (in many instances getting clients through clients) or connecting them with potential investors (Barons and Tang, 2009). In most cases, entrepreneurs referred to these priorly developed weak networks, with insufficient initiatives to strengthen these networks (Soetanto, 2017):

“In Lebanon, it’s all about networking but it wasn’t like us at all, we used to attend networking events after lots of hesitation to actually attend, but we didn’t know how to approach others/ even with the help of accelerators we weren’t doing much” – En5.

In summary, the majority of entrepreneurs, funded and unfunded, relied on their trust in the power of their strong networks (Hallam *et al.*, 2018) in building brand awareness about their businesses, and in enhancing the quality of the product or service offered, by providing constant feedback and recommendations (Jaafar *et al.*, 2009). Five of the novice entrepreneurs assigned a partial attribution of failure to ineffectively managing or approaching influential weak networks (*internal ascription*). The approaching process was perceived as limited and bounded (Soetanto, 2017). This assessment of their own networking skills provided entrepreneurs with the opportunity to learn. On the contrary, entrepreneurs with more solid professional (or entrepreneurial) experience, exhibited more initiatives in developing weak ties. However, funded entrepreneurs believed in the strength and sufficiency of their networking skills and approach and hence, did not attribute failure to it. Networks acted for both groups as a marketing tool that influenced the survival of the business as elaborated next.

Figure 31: Nature of attributions of the networking skills and their impact on the venture

6.2.2.2.2 Marketing: Planning and Execution

The reflection on the effectiveness of the marketing function and its contribution to failure by each entrepreneur had a different level of attribution. The process revealed that, given the variance in the financial capital earned by interviewees, the marketing function was adopted at one of six layers: by relying on the strong networks (Reijonen, 2010; Resnik *et al.*, 2011); by applying innovation in cheaper alternatives to compensate for the small budget (Nikfarjam and Zarifi, 2015); by overlooking the function under the excuse of funds (Musso and Francioni, 2014); by exercising individual efforts in the market (traditional marketing) (Kumar *et al.*, 2017); by relying on social media (Schaupp and Belanger, 2014); or by assigning dedicated department and staff for the function (as in the case of funded entrepreneurs). Interestingly, unfunded entrepreneurs, in their majority, either did not set up a marketing plan or developed a very basic one, attributing failure to the lack of planning (*internal ascription*) (Rogoff *et al.*, 2004; Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015).

Almost all entrepreneurs significantly highlighted the advertising contribution of their strong networks, such as families and friends (Reijonen, 2010; Resnik *et al.*, 2016), who supplied the business with the first few customers and raised brand awareness in the market:

“[...] so my family would tell in every store they go into about my business and helped me spread the word of mouth about it” – En2.

The role of these informal marketing teams (O’Donnell, 2014) did not bear similar weight by funded entrepreneurs, given their financial ability to allocate a marketing department with devoted salespeople and campaign. Funded entrepreneurs reflected a satisfactory perspective on the development and the proper execution of a comprehensive marketing plan (West and Noel, 2009):

“Our marketing was a success. We worked geographically, and we focused the marketing within each area. We focused on areas to make sure the KPIs are growing. And we were doing as well as door to door marketing. We had a sales team and they were doing really good. We had a devoted marketing plan and personnel” – En8.

Reflecting further on the efforts placed for executing the marketing function, ‘unfunded’ entrepreneurs connected this execution with the financial constraints. Unsurprisingly, to compensate for the limited funds, these entrepreneurs diverted their efforts to the heavy reliance on social media in creating brand awareness and increasing their customer base (Hubspot, 2012; Schaupp and Belanger, 2014).

However, the effectiveness of social media as a marketing tool was not satisfactory for entrepreneurs, as the challenge resided in driving the desired human traffic to the company's page and in making actual orders (Hubspot, 2012). Such follow-up that also required collecting data from customers' feedback (Keh *et al.*, 2007) was judged by entrepreneurs as improper, given the limited efforts directed towards these tasks. In ascribing this lack of efforts within the marketing function, entrepreneurs attributed three main (perceived) reasons: the stress resulting from the constant search for funds and potential investors (*the first-degree cause is ecosystematic and the second-degree cause is internal*)¹³, loss of hope in the future success of the business (low level of optimism), and lack of personnel to handle these tasks (attributed to ecosystematic factors, as will be elaborated in the next subheading):

“In the last few years, I relied heavily on social media; I developed further the website and went for google ads etc. I also marketed my business through mass media websites. And yeah...they were actually very helpful. At some time in the past, my marketing strategy wasn't very effective” – En6.

“We had the marketing plan in the beginning. And we decided to start with a prototype that will help us raise funds, and also the environmental experts' advice would guide us” – En7.

The ineffectiveness of social media as a marketing tool was an alarming signal for some entrepreneurs, who quickly converted the marketing execution to offline traditional implementation¹⁴ (Kumar *et al.*, 2017). Realizing the urgent need to build market share, entrepreneurs referred to door-to-door and personally directed marketing methods, to develop the intended market segment. This was justified as the only possible channel to reach out to the actual clients (*fated ascription*). Surprisingly, both classes of entrepreneurs (serial and novice) applied in essence similar strategic advertising techniques, but the process of execution was different. The variance in both executions related to the personal contribution of the entrepreneurs (and his/her partners), also known as self-marketing (Shepherd, 2005), more heavily adopted by unfunded entrepreneurs. Therefore, the availability of funds acted as a facilitator for the execution of a proper advertising campaign, whereas it posed some challenges for unfunded entrepreneurs:

¹³ Overlooking the effective execution of the marketing function was attributed to the lack of funds (external); the constant search for these funds caused a confusion and a lack of focus on the function (internal); which resulted in less customer base, and eventually failure.

¹⁴ Defined in this study as the offline method of marketing for the company's products and image (Kumar *et al.*, 2017) and involves doing personal and door-to-door marketing.

“The marketing was actually done by me as I had a marketing background. And I have the knowhow. So, I was doing everything myself. The marketing I was doing was very satisfactory for the strategy I had in mind, which is to build awareness rather than growth, so I wasn’t doing trade shows, direct mail, etc.” – En9.

“[...] this ad that I just told you about is useless. It got us a lot of PR [public relations], and everyone downloaded the application, but this kind of ads doesn’t get us real users [...] when you have such product and you do such ad, you end up with a mismatch. This is what went wrong. You should learn this [...] but, this is wrong to do such ad for this kind of product and services, as it gives you brand equity, but it does not give you actual orders [...] hard work does. We used to have a proper marketing plan and what we used to do is the pull effect marketing; we checked all the possible channels to reach users and we knock each one by one. This actually worked [...] we used to go visit the neighbourhoods and speak to the concierge of the building [...] and also we did partnership with communities [...] so this hard-work and physical efforts works, but the social media ads helped only in building brand equity” – En11.

However, the lack of these funds did not seem to be a major obstacle when compensated with innovativeness and creativity to create new marketing strategies (Nikfarjam and Zarifi, 2015):

“[...] on another level, I did not have the funds to do with marketing and you know the marketing costs money. So, even Facebook ads I was reluctant to pay for them and so, I thought about something that is cheaper doesn't cost me money and at the same time is smart marketing so what I did is that I made like an alliance with restaurants with whom I was working. So, I asked those restaurants to give me free sandwiches per day or croissants or any other item, and so basically I was posting a question on the social media like a competition and whoever answers the question correctly will actually get the free sandwich [...] people were actually participating on this competition questions. My main purpose was to create awareness about our brand in people’s minds” – En1.

To summarise, entrepreneurs, across the various industries in which the ventures were developed and the levels of funding raised, reflected an understanding of the relevance of a viable marketing function. Nevertheless, for the majority of novice entrepreneurs, the efforts dedicated to developing a formal and comprehensive marketing plan were very modest in nature and in application (Rogoff *et al.*, 2004; Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015). This lack of effective marketing planning and subsequent execution was attributed partially to an *internal* inconsideration (overlooking) in line with Gamble *et al.*'s (2011) argument that entrepreneurs may constitute the major obstacle against the effective execution of the marketing function (Reijonen, 2008). The major attribution of ineffective marketing was linked back to the lack of funds (*external ascription*). Through the reflection, entrepreneurs realised the enhanced performance that could have been achieved if a proper marketing function (in terms of planning and implementation) has been adopted (Ren *et al.*, 2015), adopting the counterfactual thinking (Baron, 2004). On the other hand, serial and/or funded entrepreneurs expressed their satisfaction with the marketing plans developed and the approaches

adopted in the market. Henceforth, for them, the marketing function did not contribute to the failure. Understanding the reflection on the marketing function involves understanding the entrepreneurial approaches in recruiting the needed capital to execute the function as will be analysed next.

Figure 32: Nature of attributions of the marketing function and their impact on the venture

6.2.2.2.3 Capacity of Recruiting and Managing Human Capital

Entrepreneurs attributed the failure partially to improper marketing and subsequently referred either to self-marketing (Shepherd, 2005) or to joint efforts with the sales team to collect most of the market data (Keh *et al.*, 2007). This behaviour has been probed consequently to the extent of trust exhibited by entrepreneurs in their human capital, and how would entrepreneurs judge its contribution to failure. At this stage, the reflection of entrepreneurs on human capital should marry the issue raised by the experts earlier, as to the availability and quality of talent within the Lebanese market. Three entrepreneurs were not satisfied with their human capital, specifically the level of professional ethics (rather than skills), such as unfaithfulness and lack of transparency (*external ascription*). This attribution resembles what Mantere *et al.* (2013) referred to as the betrayal of internal players. In some instances, the staff hired were not exhibiting the proper professional behaviour, despite the entrepreneurs' adoption of participative or bureaucratic leadership:

“However, the quality of our drivers wasn’t always good. Some drivers were corrupted, stealing our customers for personal interests, though we paid attention to the age risk and we hired from 40 to 60 years old people. They were denying it until faced with pictures and cameras from within the car showing their behaviour. And that was shocking for me as I was giving them the car and getting paid on a fixed salary per month” – En8.

In elaborating on their human resource management skills, entrepreneurs perceived themselves as transformative leaders, who engaged their employees in the decision-making (apart from one novice entrepreneur, En6, who centralised the decision-making process), and implemented a bureaucratic approach. Entrepreneurs reflected on this perception believing that their professional previous experience and/or education degrees have moved them away from the traditional autocratic perspective of business owners (including En6):

“My HR approach was much customised, according to the individuals. Usually I follow the participative approach where I engage more my staff. But with the drivers, I moved from democratic to a bit autocratic. With every set of people, you need to apply a different set of behaviour. So, sometimes we need to put some rules like their safety and the reputation of the company in being fully legally compliant” – En1.

Subsequent probing about the relation between the recruitment process and the quality hired (Rogoff *et al.*, 2004) revealed that four entrepreneurs ascribed the outcome of failure partially for not adopting formal recruiting procedures, with occasional recruitment from a social drive perspective (Tajfel, 1974), in line with the self-concept (Stewart and Hoell, 2016) of entrepreneurs as a social contributor:

“If I met someone occasionally through my networks, and I found out he is unemployed, I would ask him to come and learn at my company” – En6.

“If I was looking for distribution people, and I met someone who says they can do it, I would be like yeah let’s try it out” – En2.

This reflection revealed that such recruitment behaviour exhausted the time and financial resources of entrepreneurs (Powell and Baker, 2014). The retention of employees at this stage was a major challenge (Salgado *et al.*, 2020), given the limited financial resources acquired by the business and the shortage in liquidity (Quaye *et al.*, 2014). Henceforth, the turnover rate at the majority of the businesses interviewed was considered really high, despite the attempts of entrepreneurs to provide continuous training and development (Rasmussen *et al.*, 2011). Even with the adoption of a strict recruitment process that included risk assessment and background checks (as in the case of funded entrepreneurs), the quality of the staff was still reflected as implausible, mostly due to deception and lack of transparency (Betrayal feeling) (*fated ascription*) (*external*) (Mantere *et al.*, 2013):

“I would say some were controllable, but others were not. For that purpose, I was conducting training for the staff on our off days, I even brought coaches and trainers to train them about customer service” – En1.

“But it's all about who are your people that can make a difference....and what I learned through my entrepreneurial journey is that it's not about who you are recruiting it's about recruiting superstars! And this is my focus now; sometimes it takes me months to find people but I'm willing to wait for those superstars to find” – En2.

When rationalising the non-adoption of a professional recruitment basis, entrepreneurs' ascriptions generated four main themes: a) lack of funds: due to the comparably low salaries offered, the skilful and worthy employees would not be tempted to join start-ups (*external ascription*) (in line with the experts' statement) (Salgado *et al.*, 2020); b) riskiness of start-ups: much skilled human capital, even graduates, avoid joining start-ups, as the risk of failure is high (inherent risk):

“One or two weeks after being recruited they would quit. They would tell me sorry I don't see myself as a salesman. So I need to recruit someone quickly instead” – En2

c) non-fitness of career: after passing the recruitment process, employees would not perceive their career within this particular business (maturity of staff) (*external ascription*); and d) nothing else can be done: even when the recruitment process was formalised and the staff are trained and coached regularly, their unethical behaviour could not be controlled, and therefore, the business could not have done anything to prevent such occurrences (*fated ascription*):

“I was recruiting very professionally. I told you we were an established company, doing background checks, reference letters, interviews, and probation. But still, we couldn't prevent unethicity among our staff” – En8.

As a responsive mechanism to decrease the turnover rate, entrepreneurs recognised the need for upgrading their compensation scheme to offer proper incentives for desired candidates (Lyons *et al.*, 2005). The majority of entrepreneurs believed that the existing talents require a high amount of compensation that start-ups cannot afford without appropriate funds (Salgado *et al.*, 2020). Therefore, whenever feasible, the initiative was implemented (some have even taken loans just to raise their compensation), upgrading the rewards scheme for few times, before reaching the most affordable satisfying compensation system:

“I changed my compensation system several times, trying to understand what can motivate them [employees] the most to sustain in the company rather than losing them for bigger competitors” – En9.

Another outcome attached to the quality of people hired is the level of delegation assigned thereafter, which also reflects a part of the entrepreneurs' personal traits, as

well as their approach for managing their human capital. The level of delegation connects significantly with the level of skills hired, as well as the belief in their staffs' contribution and ability to handle the workload (Bontis *et al.*, 2000). This was not always the case for 'unfunded' entrepreneurs, as three entrepreneurs centralised the majority of the functions in their hands, sometimes justifying it by the 'unsatisfying' quality of the human capital (*external ascription*). On the contrary, entrepreneurs who were financially supported (En4, En8, En9 and En11) were more dedicated to conducting frequent orientation sessions, technical training, dedicated succession plan, and staff development process:

“Honestly, one of my main weaknesses is that I used and still working as a one-man show [...] the business was centralised around me. I had 2 employees who were responsible only for few tasks, according to their office schedule, but I was the one actually doing everything. I don't trust to delegate some tasks. And if I did, and the work isn't as expected, I would be very upset and blame myself for not doing it personally” – En6.

“I sent them to attend courses and get them in touch with specific individuals who had expertise with the things we were working on. I wanted to develop their abilities, but I couldn't do it myself; so, I dedicated a budget and was referring to third parties to help us out, in Spain, and China” – En4.

In alignment with the previously mentioned rationalisations of the recruitment process and the level of delegation, the majority of entrepreneurs took the blame for their unsuccessful entrepreneurial journey, rather than blaming their human capital (Mantere *et al.*, 2013). The sense of self-responsibility was explicitly stated for the majority of entrepreneurs (Mussak, 2003; Minello *et al.*, 2014), apart from four entrepreneurs (out which 3 were funded) who attributed the exit decision to the operating environment context:

“If something goes wrong, it's the responsibility of the CEO-entrepreneur, he decided to hire them. He knows them, even if it's the employees' mistake, he hired them.” – En2.

Another point raised under the notion of human capital is the quality of partners and the nature of partnership developed. Surprisingly, out of the eight entrepreneurs who had partners, only one entrepreneur En7 expressed his discomfort and dissatisfaction with his partner, raising his concern for future partnership subsequent to this distrust feeling (Huntsinger, 2011; Heinze, 2013). The equivalent value of contributions by each partner in terms of dedication and commitment seem to influence the possibility of conflicts among partners, pushing entrepreneurs to learn about the nature of partnerships (Amankwah-Amoah *et al.*, 2018). The selection of mind-matching partners that stems from a social psychology approach combined with an assessment

of the potential contributions (Forbes *et al.*, 2006) seems engaging and successful in terms of business relations, as in the cases of En11, En5, En4. Partners in their majority emerged from the weak networks rather than the strong networks, unexpectedly for the Lebanese culture with a high tendency for family-run businesses (GEM, 2017:2018):

“When we used to meet during our previous employment as freelancers, I got to know his personality, thinking pattern and his previous background as a research engineer. This is what actually encouraged me to go into a partnership with him [...] all of these skills with team spirit provided me with an encouraging mix to go for partnership with him. In a team, we expect things from others, so the clearer these expectations are and the more informed we are about each other the better the partnership will be. I also judged him for his ability to develop and his adaptability” – En10.

An interesting observation noted during the narratives and raised by the funded entrepreneurs was that three of them refrained from taking a salary or any kind of monetary compensation apart from their equity share. The aspiration, ambitions, and optimism that these entrepreneurs held for their ventures (Gabrielsson and Politis, 2011) is most probable to explain this behaviour:

“I didn’t use to take any compensation. I was really aspiring its growth” – En9.

“I didn’t use to take any salary. I was contributing with the efforts, know-how, new ideas, design and all the other stuffs” – En8.

In summary, entrepreneurs believed in the relevance of adopting a professional recruitment process in order to acquire and retain skilled human capital. However, this recognition was often theoretical with less practice in place, as professional recruitment was not always followed (*internal ascription*). The financial constraints (*external ascription*) limited the compensation scheme that was offered, and hence, compromised to a certain extent the quality of the skills hired. On the contrary, funded entrepreneurs managed to hire dedicated personnel (local and international). In unexpected occurrences, like the unexpected leave of one personnel, the recruitment was therefore quick and immediate to cover the human gap. Entrepreneurs apart from (En2) believed that their approach for managing the human resources was satisfying, engaging, motivating, and transformational, yet the turnover rate exhibited by the staff was high in nature. Eventually, the quality of the human capital was not always satisfying (*external ascription*) but had only a limited contribution to the unsuccessful journey. An interesting point raised during the analysis referred to the professional ethics of employees in connection with the local culture. The impact of culture is hence discussed in the next section.

Figure 33: Nature of attributions of the human capital and their impact on the venture

6.2.2.2.4 Role of Culture and Ecosystem on Persistence

As for the culture, entrepreneurs had different perceptions as to the societal tolerance towards failure. Reflecting on the support experienced for pursuing entrepreneurial careers, entrepreneurs expressed their experiences with stigma and shame (Singh *et al.*, 2015). For three novice entrepreneurs, the support was almost negligible upon pursuing the entrepreneurial career in contrast to GEM's (2016:2017) report, and the society was very judgmental towards the exit decision (Canon and Edmondson, 2005). One novice entrepreneur exhibited the impact of failure on his familial support (Singh *et al.*, 2007), including his wife, stating how her confidence in his entrepreneurial skills fell dramatically after failure. The pressure to switch to a 'more secure and less risky job' reveals the internal struggle lived between both worlds (Heinze, 2013):

"So I thought a lot about closing my business but I never went for this actually before because I was always scared of being labelled as a failure. Though I was struggling financially with the company and with the number of clients that I was receiving but I still didn't take the decision to close the business and to exit the business just because of the stigma of the failure" – En1.

"I was reluctant to cease my business because I wanted to avoid people's criticism and labelling my experience with failure. It hurt me and made me feel weak in such terms" – En6.

Stigma, as a social cost, was a concern for the majority of novice entrepreneurs (Ucbasaran *et al.*, 2013; Nielsen and Sarasvathy, 2016), upon deciding to exit the unprofitable venture; an issue that affected the timing of the decision. These entrepreneurs postponed implementing the exit decision, worrying about society's perception towards them as 'failing entrepreneurs who couldn't sustain their

businesses' (Singh *et al.*, 2015). Positively, this anticipation of failure had balanced their experience with the actual negative emotions resulting from failure, but increased their financial costs (Shepherd *et al.*, 2009):

“[...] when the business wasn't profitable everyone around me was advising me to quit the idea but only very few were encouraging me. I was so ready to close down the business but because of the image that will be perceived as a failure, I was reluctant, fearing people to label me as an entrepreneur with failing business rather than them thinking that quitting will be a release and an assistance for me. So, when the revolution started, I took it as an excuse to close the business and this didn't create much pressure by the people as many businesses were closing down afterwards” – En1.

Cultural support was improved as the businesses survived, but it was not sufficient to be labelled as support. Serial and funded entrepreneurs exhibited higher confidence in challenging society and shame, openly sharing their stories with others (Singh *et al.*, 2015). However, a common point raised by all entrepreneurs regarding the culture's judgment on entrepreneurship was the underestimation of entrepreneurial careers. For the Lebanese society, the notion of entrepreneurs is simplified to business owners, and regardless of how innovative the entrepreneurial idea is, the society will still undermine it, not giving it the expected respect and understanding (as mentioned by En1, En7, En8 and En9).

“My clients were always trying to bargain with me telling me ‘oh com'on you're not company X [mentioning a big competitor's name], why don't you sell cheaper’” – En9.

“You know whenever I used to tell everyone about my idea of recycling rotten vegetables they used to laugh and say that I basically work with garbage [laughs]” – En7.

Culture is only one component of a larger entrepreneurial ecosystem that was recurrently stated by interviewees as influencing the survival of business ventures (Isenberg, 2011; Stam, 2015). The extent of governmental support was heavily researched as to its extent in promoting entrepreneurial initiatives and affecting the success of early start-ups (Isenberg, 2011; Rodriguez-Pose, 2013; Audretsch *et al.*, 2015). Nevertheless, interviewees upon launching their businesses did not look forward for any governmental intervention, but rather regard it as “inexistent”. Henceforth, entrepreneurs considered the lack of governmental support as a catalyst rather than a direct factor of failure. In other words, if the government provided the minimum viable services and organised an embracing ecosystem (Isenberg, 2011), entrepreneurs would have probably sustained longer (Mezher *et al.*, 2008). Consequently, in terms of attribution, the lack of governmental support is considered

within this study as an ecosystematic catalyst for failure, rather than a causal ascription.

All entrepreneurs attributed failure partially to more macro-levelled factors, such as the unsupportive ecosystem and the lack of governmental support, repeatedly mentioning the contribution of government to survival or failure (Mezher *et al.*, 2008; Naimy, 2011). Only one entrepreneur (En11) benefited from the injection of funds that were supplied by the central bank of Lebanon (BDL) through circular 331, which was previously highlighted by the experts as a major booster of entrepreneurship. The rest either did not qualify for that support or did not look forward to it (Xiang *et al.*, 2015), following their perceptions of the lack of governmental transparency:

“I am myself an unorthodox entrepreneur [a description of what’s not generally accepted as an entrepreneur], liberalist, and I don’t believe in governments; I don’t look forward to receiving anything from it” – En2.

“I didn’t go for it because I wouldn’t get it so why should I bother? Everything is corrupted here and they have already their people to give the grants for” – En7.

As reflected by all entrepreneurs, the case of governmental support in Lebanon is of a different perspective from other emerging countries. All entrepreneurs were not seeking complementary support such as funds, subsidies, or tax reforms, but rather needed the public supply for the most basic and essential infrastructure (electricity, water, internet, telephone, fuel, transportation) (Mezher *et al.*, 2008; GEM 2016:2017:2018). Due to the shortage in these services, the private supply (in a monopolistic market) significantly increased the fixed costs for entrepreneurs. The result reflected on reducing profitability and negatively affecting the operations of services or the manufacturing of products in case of service interruption (Naimy, 2011):

“There was no governmental support at all. It was negligible and even less than zero. I would say that the infrastructure itself increases our fixed costs greatly, otherwise it would have been much less. All of those costs we are paying them double” – En9.

Entrepreneurs operated with the inconsideration of governmental support in mind, believing in a corrupted state of affairs and non-transparent governance. Henceforth, entrepreneurs on many occasions traded in the informal economy¹⁵, avoiding the

¹⁵ The informal operating of the businesses has constrained entrepreneurs further, as it limited their ability in certain occasions to apply for official tenders and projects.

costly and complex procedure of registering (or even deregistering) a business (Mezher *et al.*, 2008):

“The government not only does not support start-ups but is also against them” – En12.

“It's because our government and politics do not help at all. We had luxury cars and we had regular cars, so, on top of the luxury cars, we had screen Ads. These screens were connected to geo-targeted locations [...] but the police used to stop us, though legally, no existing law is prohibiting us from doing it. Still, we had to pay fines and bribes to the police to let us go without confining the cars, which had cost us a lot each month” – En8.

This statement reveals the ironic implication by the majority of entrepreneurs, who laughed when talking about governmental support. On infrequent occasions, the central bank seminars and workshops were helpful to a certain extent and accessible to entrepreneurs but were not sufficiently supportive:

“As for governmental support, there was only training and seminars offered by BDL [central bank of Lebanon]” – En10.

This section provided the various levels and dimensions of failure attributions as perceived by entrepreneurs. In summary, the failure was attributed partially by novice and unfunded entrepreneurs to the lack of influential networks, due to the lack of social skills adopted and efforts undertaken in reaching these networks (*internal ascription*). Another attribution of failure was linked to the small customer base caused by improper planning (*internal ascription*) and execution of marketing (constrained by the lack of funds) (*external ascription*). A final attribution of failure was related nominally to the unsatisfying quality of human capital recruited, which was constrained by financial resources (*external ascription*), the recruitment process adopted (*internal ascription*) and the availability of moral and skilled talents in the market (*external ascription*). The ecosystem being an external catalyst for failure impacted the level of persistence of entrepreneurs, delaying failure because of the arising social costs (i.e., stigma) and the low social tolerance towards failure. On the other hand, serial entrepreneurs (apart from En2 and En11) did not hold any personal liability for the failure and attributed the failure to external factors completely. By concluding on the second stage which reflected the process of managing the ventures, the Chapter proceeds with analysing the third stage as reflected by entrepreneurs.

6.2.2.3 Stage Three: Exiting the Venture

In this stage, the reflection on the exit decision and the learning outcomes is analysed. The learning outcomes emerged subsequent to the realisation of previous

wrongdoings, and hence represent learning from mistakes (Cope, 2011). Strategically, the failure experience induces learning on the effectiveness of strategies adopted, and the need in the future to change the implemented options (Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015). This change stems from the entrepreneurs' transformation in their understanding and perceptions of the environment and existing opportunities (Lin *et al.*, 2019). More specifically, by experiencing failure, entrepreneurs shake their usually embraced assumptions, mental models, extant beliefs, and frames of references that normally direct their behaviours (Cope, 2011).

6.2.2.3.1 Motivation and Exit Decision

The sample consisted of serial and novice, funded and unfunded entrepreneurs, who exhibited different entrepreneurial behaviours and patterns of decision-making. As argued in the analysis of the first stage, the initial motivations of entrepreneurs to engage in entrepreneurial pursuits impacted the nature and timing of their persistence decisions (DeTienne *et al.*, 2008; DeTienne, 2010; Shepherd and Patzelt, 2017). Moreover, these motivations were referred to by entrepreneurs to elucidate their sense-making of failure, cognitively and emotionally (Heinze, 2013). Henceforth, the exit decision between these groups was subsequently different, though common in essence (discontinuation rather than stewardship) (DeTienne *et al.*, 2015) within the same group despite the particularity of each. This difference was also exhibited on the level of making sense of failure and developing attributions. More specifically, aspiring entrepreneurs with great ambitions undertook a different timing of exit decision, and had different criteria for that decision, the connection of which was not previously proven by Parastuty *et al.* (2016). Funded entrepreneurs reached the exit decision immediately after realising the impossibility of scaling up the business as initially planned and aspired, and therefore, quit the business (En8), sold their shares (leaving the business in a 'good' state of operations) (En9), or discontinued it (En11) (DeTienne *et al.*, 2015):

“It was a tough decision, and that was at the end of 2017, because our dream was not to build a small cute business, the dream was to build a scalable business that goes beyond Lebanon and even beyond the GCC” – En11.

“But the reason why I decided to quit is because the business is scalable in Lebanon, which was my aim since I founded the company [...] My concern is that I joined to scale the idea globally or at least regionally and to be acquired by big companies [...] When I felt the project wasn't scalable and my partner, who is the main investor didn't want to invest money anymore I felt that I am wasting my time. And this wasn't my plan [...] He invested all of his money in the business, so, I decided to lose all the efforts and time that

I contributed to this business for one year or one year and a half; and then I quit, leaving the company operating” – En8.

In contrast, unfunded and/or novice entrepreneurs (in addition to one serial entrepreneur, En2) sustained in the business until the liquidity dropped to an extremely low level (DeTienne, 2010), making it difficult to survive (Muhammad *et al.*, 2010):

“[...] but it was difficult to keep up with a fixed cost, at a time when we did not have revenues nor raised funds. We tried to go to neighbouring areas [...]; we went for fundraising in the capital city in many competitions, as I mentioned and in several exhibitions. But everything went in vain (he laughs)” – En7.

“At later stages, the financial condition was deteriorating, to the point that we were struggling with paying the rent [...] In many instances, we didn’t have any work to do, we were just occupying the office” – En5.

Entrepreneurs are argued to prepare exit plans before finally executing the exit decision of their failing ventures (Wennberg *et al.*, 2010). Serial entrepreneurs, given their experience, have developed alternative exit plans to be pursued subsequent to exiting their current ventures, and had decisive and quick closure (Dias and Teixeira, 2017). Novice-unfunded entrepreneurs did not prepare such plans but managed to get involved with freelancing or partial employment opportunities before embarking in another venture:

“When I felt the project wasn't scalable and my partner who is the main investor didn't want to invest money anymore, I felt that I am wasting my time. And this wasn't my plan [...] so, I decided to lose all the efforts and time that I contributed to this business for one year or one year and a half, and I quit” – En8.

Very interestingly, all interviewees (apart from two novice entrepreneurs who, though still within the self-employment field, have engaged in freelancing activities) re-embarked in subsequent venturing activities. However, this re-engagement for novice entrepreneurs passed through a transitory phase first. Novice entrepreneurs embarked first in freelancing or temporary employment opportunities as a coping mechanism (for both emotions and financial costs) after failure (Singh *et al.*, 2007). Nonetheless, interestingly, these transitions were outlined as a preparatory stage for planning and launching their current ventures. In other words, these entrepreneurs built upon the failure experience and attempted to employ effectively the knowledge acquired by investing the time after failure in developing stronger and sounder business plans. This finding is interesting on the level of behavioural outcome, as other studies (i.e.

Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015; Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015) highlighted failure time passage as simply the time in months between failure and regeneration. Such behavioural outcome supports the argument on the impact of entrepreneurial failure on encouraging subsequent venturing (i.e., Shepherd, 2003; Ucbasaran *et al.*, 2003; Stam *et al.*, 2008; Singh *et al.*, 2015).

On the attribution level, motivations not only impacted the process of reflection and sense-making of failure (Heinze, 2013) but, interestingly, revealed an association with the direction and dimension of attributions developed by entrepreneurs. Interestingly, entrepreneurs who initially raised high ambitions for their ventures (linear and expert-minded) (Gabrielsson and Politis, 2011) attributed failure majorly to external factors. However, entrepreneurs with more spiral and transitory minds have attributed the failure to a hybrid combination of internal and external ascriptions, with a domination of the internal blame. Taking into consideration how the majority (12) of these entrepreneurs re-embarked in venturing activities, this finding challenges the argument that internal attributions (Engel *et al.*, 2014) or even partial external attributions (Mandl *et al.*, 2016) might discourage novice and serial entrepreneurs from re-embarking in another venture.

In terms of failure time passage, this study supports the argument that a shorter period to re-embark in entrepreneurship is argued to optimise perceived learning outcomes from failure (Fang He *et al.*, 2018), especially when accompanied by internal attributions (Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015). Re-entrepreneurs revealed short periods between failure and re-engagement in entrepreneurship, with superiority for serial entrepreneurs. More specifically, novice entrepreneurs had their own time digesting the failure, reflecting on it, and learning from it (Walsh and Cunningham, 2017). These entrepreneurs thought about the failure, embraced their emotions, challenged their society, and learned from the experience to move on and forward into their lives (Haynie and Shepherd, 2011). Such emotion-focused coping (Singh *et al.*, 2007) was not adopted by serial entrepreneurs who were faster in moving forward and re-embarking in venturing activities. Their behaviour may be rationalised by either:

- a) The dominating nature of the external attribution of failure (En3, En8 and En9) (Eggers and Song, 2014), which inherently prevents reflection over failure (Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015; Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015). These entrepreneurs did not believe in their personal responsibility to the failure and rather blamed

the external factors of the ecosystem (Engel *et al.*, 2014; Walsh and Cunningham, 2017). More specifically, these entrepreneurs considered that the Lebanese ecosystem *per se* is neither helpful, nor embracing, or encouraging for entrepreneurship (Mezher *et al.*, 2008). In their opinions, the managerial aspects of the venture were above a satisfying level, and therefore, no personal blame should be held for the failure. Their only mistake, as clearly stated by them, related to their ‘mistaken overestimated’ belief in the Lebanese market’s ability to cultivate and promote businesses with internationalisation potential. Therefore, the reflection process of these three entrepreneurs exhibited little learning on the personal level, in line with the literature (i.e. Mantere *et al.*, 2013; Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015; Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015; Walsh and Cunningham, 2017). This finding hence provides evidence to the theoretical simulation of Mandl *et al.* (2016) of the impact of external attributions and the tendency to re-engage in entrepreneurial activities. Interestingly, all three entrepreneurs established their subsequent ventures in a different ecosystem, hence, establishing a greater confidence level in the performance of their businesses; or

- b) The deep internal attribution of failure in an insightful reflection and learning process, which created high-level perceived learning that was tested in subsequent venturing (Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015). En2, in contrast to other serial entrepreneurs, attributed the failure holistically and primarily to himself. In other words, this entrepreneur held himself responsible for the improper management of human resources and cash flow of outstanding receivables (Rogoff *et al.*, 2004). Such attribution allowed for a deep, personal, thoughtful, and deliberate reflection process that assisted the entrepreneur in learning more about himself and the business (Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015; Walsh and Cunningham, 2017).

As another interesting finding in line with the literature (Cardon *et al.*, 2009; Mantere *et al.*, 2013), all entrepreneurs (apart from En3, En8 and En9), in describing their entrepreneurial journeys, used the word passion to reflect on the attachment created with the business career and to describe their goals from the entrepreneurial pursuit (Clarke and Halte, 2010). In the same vein, all entrepreneurs (apart from the four entrepreneurs with external attributions) have perceived great levels of generated learning from the venture’s failure, describing it as a ‘learning’ experience that

sharpened their skills properly for their next ventures (i.e. Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015; Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015; Walsh and Cunningham, 2017). Entrepreneurs mentioned recurrently learning from failure (Politis and Gabrielsson, 2009), and considered failure as the best event that happened in their entrepreneurial journey, revealing a strong readiness to look at failure positively (Heinze, 2013). This learning has developed principally from their belief in their own contribution to the failure (as elaborated next):

“Well we are talking about a failure here and I would say that you are taking the word failure in a different way, but for me, I accept it as a failure and accept it as the lesson. It wasn't a successful business, so I don't take it personally and I don't feel like ashamed to say it was failure. It taught me a lot. My behaviour was a failure and I accept my past and I accept it as a lesson. After all, if you're not failing you're not learning” – En2.

“We learned a lot from it [...] This project was a suffering for me, I learned from it [...] I worked on this project for 2 years and learned from it a lot [...] I really widened my knowledge [...] I am 100% satisfied with the business and the experience, as it made me way stronger and prepared to my current business, and therefore, it was an absolute learning experience” – En7.

“When you have your own business basically you will need to pay all of those things [...] And unfortunately only after opening the business I realised all of these difficult things and I went through this hardship and it was really tough on I was literally learning everything from scratch” – En1.

6.2.2.3.2 Ascriptions of Failure

Almost every novice entrepreneur took personal responsibility for the failure (*internal ascription*) in managing the venture in terms of networks, marketing, market research and the funds available (raised or borrowed). On the contrary, three serial and one novice entrepreneurs blamed failure entirely on the Lebanese entrepreneurial ecosystem – *external ascription*. The most common areas of *internal attribution* (individual-level) as reflected by entrepreneurs fell under five main themes:

- a) Overestimation of the idea's success and underestimating the efforts needed for success (Hayward *et al.*, 2006);
- b) Personality traits that prohibited networking or dealing with human capital efficiently (introversion or timidity) (Baron and Tang, 2009);
- c) Centralisation of the workload which increased the pressure (GEM, 2016);
- d) Huge ambitions rather than the minimum viable business (Hayward *et al.*, 2010);
and
- e) Lack of a comprehensive business and market plan beforehand, accompanied by the lack of proper execution and follow-up (Rogoff *et al.*, 2004; Mezher *et al.*, 2008; Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015; Umar *et al.*, 2018; Dias and Martens, 2019).

Though different initial motivational factors impacted the exit decision of entrepreneurs (DeTienne, 2010), these factors did not have the same impact on the pro-activeness of entrepreneurs (Priyanto and Sandjojo, 2005) to address their knowledge gap and improve their readiness for the entrepreneurial career. Upon realising the shortage in particular competencies and skills, entrepreneurs in their majority initiated the process of improving their managerial behaviour which reflects the persistence of entrepreneurs to learning as they progress with the venture (Kolb, 1984; Petkova, 2008). This study hence provides further evidence that the learning process is actually initiated throughout the life of the venture, not only after failure (Costello, 1996; Abatecola and Uli, 2016). However, the extent and the degree of these initiatives differed among entrepreneurs (in terms of the combination adopted from the following):

- a) Attending seminars, workshops, training (En1, En2, En11, En6, En7, En4);
- b) Registering for courses (En11, En10; En4, En5, En6);
- c) Sharing knowledge with partners (En11, En2, En10);
- d) Reading relevant books and articles (En11, En2, En10); and
- e) Seeking experts' advice (En7, En1, En3)

Exploring further on the internal attributions of failure, the controllable and internal dimensions of failure were traced back to the constraints as well as the resources that affected the degree and extent of self-improvement initiatives taken by each. The limitations differed among both groups of entrepreneurs (funded and unfunded), but linked back to one of three categories:

- a) Lack of funds to get access to the proper resources (Quaye *et al.*, 2014) (*external ascription*);
- b) Underestimating the need to develop skills (overconfidence) (Hayward *et al.*, 2006) (*internal ascription*); and
- c) Losing hope in the business' ability to persist due to low profits (GEM, 2016), as five unfunded entrepreneurs admitted that their lack of dedication, interest, and persistence (*internal ascription*) (Petkova, 2008; Arasti, 2011; Mantere *et al.*, 2013) has contributed to a great extent to the exit decision:

“I labelled it [the business] as unprofitable because I simply couldn't collect my outstanding receivables [which composed a huge part of the cash flow]. I should have sustained a bit longer” – En2.

“I worked on it for less than 2 years but then I gave up” – En14.

“Once the business started to go down, I just wanted to quit and travel abroad” – En6.

Table 18 below summarises the various dimensions of attributions as developed by entrepreneurs throughout the three stages of their ventures. In conjunction with the attributions developed, the Chapter moves into elaborating on the entrepreneurs' responses in reaction to failure.

Code (Name)	Internal attribution	External attribution	Fated attribution	Mistaken opportunity
En1	Lack of proper and sufficient market research Lack of proper planning and execution of marketing Lack of preparedness for the career Underestimation of the efforts (combined with overconfidence to cope) Overestimation of the idea's success (overoptimism)	High criteria for debt financing Fierce funding competitions Limited governmental support Quality of talents hired (linked back to lack of funds) Inexistent database to rely on Costly and complicated procedures of registration Cultural intolerance to failure Constant economic pressure	Implied (the entrepreneur persisted for two years, did his best in applying for funds, but couldn't do more)	N/A
En2	Lack of determination in collecting outstanding debts Overestimation of the idea's success (overoptimism) Improper recruitment and human capital management Irrelevant reliance on market signals	Low morality of staff and supply chain Cultural misunderstanding of entrepreneurial career (at some point underestimation) Lack of talents in the Lebanese market	N/A	N/A
En3	N/A	Political and economic instability within the country (inability to collect receivables and reduction in orders) Inexistent governmental support Costly and complicated procedures of registration	Implied (the entrepreneur persisted for two years, did his best, but couldn't do more)	N/A

En4	Improper time management Perfectionism	Inability to raise further funds (linked to improper time management and lack of knowledge of VCs) The perception of Western VCs about the Middle East	N/A	Developing a solution for a problem that was mistakenly thought to exist (despite thorough market research)
En5	Introversion Improper planning Overlooking the marketing Lack of proper initiatives in raising funds Spontaneity of decision (intuitive in majority) Lack of proper initiatives in networking Lack of market research Underestimation of the efforts needed (overconfidence in future coping) Lack of visionary planning	Inexistent governmental support Costly and complicated procedures of registration Economic instability Cultural misunderstanding of entrepreneurial career (at some point underestimation)	N/A	N/A
En6	Improper management of cash flow (overspending) Lack of pitching skills (and self-promotion) Improper management of the venture Unorganised and undetermined self Improper choice of office location Improper market research Improper planning and implementation of marketing Centralisation (one-man show)	High criteria for debt financing (lack of funds) Lack of database to rely on Inexistent governmental support Cultural intolerance to failure Cultural misunderstanding of entrepreneurial career Constant economic pressure Inability to retain good employees (the entrepreneur wondered whether it is caused by his HRM skills or the lack of funds)	Time changed as well as people's approach to technology	N/A

Inability to retain good employees

En7	<p>Improper market research Overestimation of the idea's success Lack of managerial insights Lack of dedication</p>	<p>Inexistent governmental support High criteria for debt financing Strong funding competitions Cultural intolerance to failure Cultural misunderstanding of entrepreneurial career Costly and complicated procedures of registration</p>	N/A	Developing a solution for a problem that was mistakenly thought to exist
En8	<p>Blaming oneself for operating in the Lebanese market</p>	<p>Insufficiency of equity financing Inexistent governmental support Low morality of the staff Political and economic instability Cultural misunderstanding of entrepreneurial career Corrupted state of affairs</p>	<p>Implied (the entrepreneur persisted for less than two years, did his best, but couldn't do more)</p>	N/A
En9	<p>Network capabilities (according to the Lebanese culture)</p>	<p>Political and economic instability Low ethics of Lebanese businesses Lack of skilled talents in the Lebanese market Costly and complicated procedures of registration Inexistent governmental support Cultural misunderstanding of entrepreneurial career Corrupted state of affairs</p>	N/A	N/A
En10	<p>Overestimation of the idea's ability to raise funds</p>	<p>High criteria for debt financing Limited governmental support</p>	N/A	Developing a solution for a problem that was mistakenly thought to exist

En11	Improper time management Improper understanding of the market needs Improper execution of marketing Being loaded with easy money Fast recruitment compromising the quality of talents Poor prioritisation Unfocused strategy	Costly and complicated procedures of (de)registration Immaturity of the ecosystem to embrace start-ups Cultural intolerance of failure Unsuitability of the Lebanese ecosystem (for testing or launching)	N/A	N/A
En12	Improper planning Overlooking the marketing Lack of proper initiatives in raising funds Lack of market research Reliance on strong networks Underestimation of the efforts needed	Inexistent governmental support Costly and complicated procedures of registration Economic instability Cultural misunderstanding of entrepreneurial career (at some point underestimation)	N/A	N/A
En13	Improper planning Overlooking the marketing function Improper recruitment and management of human capital Underestimating the efforts needed Overestimating the idea's success (overoptimism)	Political and economic instability Low ethics of businesses and clients High criteria for debt financing Inexistent governmental support	N/A	N/A
En14	N/A	Political and economic instability Corrupted state of affairs	Inability to collect receivables Implied (the entrepreneur persisted for less than two years, did his best, but couldn't do more)	N/A

Table 18: Attributions of failure by each entrepreneur

6.2.2.4 Entrepreneurs' Responses to Failure

If exploited effectively, business failure can result in three levels of learning outcomes: emotional, behavioural, and cognitive (Ucbasaran *et al.*, 2013). However, delineating these responses cannot be achieved easily, as entrepreneurs move forward by understanding (emotionally), processing (cognitively) and reacting (behaviourally) to entrepreneurial failure (Shepherd and Cardon, 2009; Ucbasaran *et al.*, 2013; Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015). Through their narratives, entrepreneurs (so-called auteurs of the stories told) addressed the experience with failure cognitively as a psychological processing, and emotionally through its social construction (Mantere *et al.*, 2013). Therefore, these responses are best discussed aggregately rather than separately.

The reflection and the attribution processes of failure are argued to be accompanied by various negative emotions which might inhibit learning outcomes (Cope, 2011). Though entrepreneurs have exhibited facing negative emotions, such as grief, subsequent to failure, these emotions did not hinder the learning process (Byrne and Shepherd, 2015). The self-awareness of grief as a negative emotion that resulted from failure assisted in moderating the level of stress experienced (Shepherd, 2003). Additionally, as reflected in Table 16, the narration of failure (and the corresponding reflection process) exhibits varying time periods between failure and narratives. Therefore, entrepreneurs who have recently exited the businesses demonstrated more intense and stronger emotions (En8, En9, En4 and En6) than their peers with longer gap periods.

The emotions revealed through the narratives were not necessarily entirely negative (Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015), moderated in most cases by the anticipation of failure and the balancing of grief that might result (Shepherd *et al.*, 2009). More specifically, recently failing entrepreneurs revealed more negative emotions such as frustration, grief and despair when narrating their failures (Amankwah-Amoah *et al.*, 2018). Though the recovery has not been achieved completely for the newly 'failed' entrepreneurs (as negative emotions still emerged during the narration), the learning process was initiated for the novice entrepreneur and completed by partial re-emergence (Shepherd, 2003) in line with Corner *et al.* (2017).

Other entrepreneurs (apart from the four with external attributions) exhibited very positive emotions as to how meaningful, enriching, and profound the failure experience turned out to be (Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015). In agreement with Byrne

and Shepherd (2015), the study found that, though the negative emotions were fervent, the learning process was not hindered, in contrast to Shepherd's (2003) argument. The cognitive internal attributions developed have outweighed the negative emotions to speed up the emergence of the positive ones, avoiding the thought of loss (Shepherd, 2003) and focusing on the sources of stress arising from failure (Singh *et al.*, 2007). Stated otherwise, the aftermath of failure seemed to be focussed more on reflecting and understanding the causes for failure, than on processing the emotions resulting from the negative event of failure (Singh *et al.*, 2007).

It is necessary to re-emphasise at this stage that this study did not consider the performance of the subsequent venturing activities of re-entrepreneurs. Instead, the behavioural response was limited to either re-engagement in ventures or abandonment of entrepreneurship. Therefore, the researcher does not claim to judge the effectiveness of the learning process of entrepreneurs. Such evaluation of learning can be only achieved by assessing the performance of subsequent ventures (Lin *et al.*, 2019), though this criterion seems controversial (Ucbasaran *et al.*, 2013). However, interestingly, re-entrepreneurs seemed confident to express how the learning from the previous ventures improved their satisfaction and expectations with their current ventures, whom they perceived as sustainable and 'going really well'.

Emotionally, this study unveiled four main types of emotional responses, disclosed by entrepreneurs whilst narrating their failure and reflecting on the aftermath of exit:

- a) Laughter: three of the novice entrepreneurs (En1, En5, and En7) laughed quite a few times while narrating their stories, especially on the parts that felt very personal. These parts mostly included the 'silly' decisions made or actions taken by these entrepreneurs. These emotions represent very interesting findings of positive emotions, as other studies have revealed relief and excitement (Singh *et al.*, 2007; Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015; Walsh and Cunningham, 2017). More specifically, entrepreneurs laughed when pointing out their behavioural mistakes, naivety in proceeding with the venture (Mantere *et al.*, 2013), or inability to raise funds:

"But we didn't collect any money (laughs again) [...] So, we didn't raise any funds, and we just did one episode of our animation which took us around 6 months (laughs a lot when mentioned the period) [...] Everyone advises and says yeah do this and do that, reach the stars, but the ugly truth is that without funds you can't actually do anything (laughs again)" – En5.

“We went for fundraising in the capital city in many competitions as I mentioned and in several exhibitions. But everything went in vain (he laughs) [...] sometimes, you probably have an average idea which is not as great as you think. My surrounding was uneducated and they judged me as working in the garbage; that was their perspective of the project (he laughs)” – En7.

A plausible explanation of such ironic self-criticism can be possibly explained by the entrepreneurs’ embarrassment of their old self, and how that identity approached the entrepreneurial journey. Such an explanation can, thus, be linked significantly to the rare discussion of the entrepreneurs’ explicit comparison between their old and current selves (Mantere *et al.*, 2013). In the process of reflecting upon failure, novice entrepreneurs made this clear comparison between their old identities (that established and managed the failing venture) and their current identities (that learned from the failure experience) (Mantere *et al.*, 2013), in line with their internal attributions of failure. In parallel, this comparison was not revealed by serial entrepreneurs (apart from Entrepreneur En2), given their attribution of failure essentially to external ascriptions, and the little transformation at the individual level (Cope, 2011). These entrepreneurs explained the gap between both types of identities by underlining the ‘low skills’, ‘immaturity’, ‘simple-mindedness’, ‘naivety’, ‘carelessness’, and ‘impulsivity’ of the old personality in managing the venture:

“From a communication perspective, it was different, my younger self from my current self. So, now I ask why are you lying to me, but back then, if someone is lying to me I would just move away [...] but what I’m saying is back then I would have, no, I should have acted in a different way and probably the same way I think now” – En2.

Among the three entrepreneurs who ironically criticised themselves with laughter, two entrepreneurs re-embarked in entrepreneurial pursuits, while the third one is currently working as a freelancer. Re-entrepreneurs have highly asserted their appreciation of the failure journey as a strong learning episode in their lives (Politis and Gabrielsson, 2009; Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015). The event of failure has equipped, enlightened, and supported these entrepreneurs with enhanced entrepreneurial skills that are being used effectively and successfully in their current ventures¹⁶ (Stam *et al.*, 2008;

¹⁶ According to the entrepreneurs’ self-declaration

Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015; Corner *et al.*, 2017; Walsh and Cunningham, 2017). Interestingly, these three entrepreneurs have attributed failure, majorly, to the lack of funds (*external-ecosystematic*) and improper managerial skills (*internal-individual*). Therefore, this study has provided further evidence on the transformative level of learning generated (Cope, 2011) on the individual and venture levels, subsequent to hybrid attributions of failure (i.e., Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015; Walsh and Cunningham, 2017). Relating to these attributions, all three entrepreneurs (among others) stated feeling relieved from worrying about the financial costs and burdens that were stressful before the failure (Walsh and Cunningham, 2017), as will be explained later.

- b) Grief and frustration (associated with relief): two entrepreneurs, one serial (En8) and one novice (En6), exhibited intense negative emotions of grief and frustration when reflecting on failure (Hayward *et al.*, 2010; Cope, 2011; Pittaway and Thorpe, 2012; Walsh and Cunningham, 2017). The tonality of their voices, the sad attitude towards failure, and the frustration in storytelling the failure (Byrne and Shepherd, 2015) reflected an incomplete emotional recovery process from the failure. This can be possibly explained by the recency of their failures at the time of the interview, as the shorter the time between the interviews and the reflective narrative process, the stronger the negative emotions resulting from failure (Eggers and Song, 2014). These negative emotions were also experienced by other entrepreneurs, aftermath the failure (Shepherd, 2003). However, the valence and activation of these emotions were considered moderate (Weiss and Beal, 2005), revealing an emotional resilience (Corner *et al.*, 2017) of Lebanese entrepreneurs. This finding challenges further Shepherd's (2003) and Shepherd and Cardon's (2009) arguments that negative emotions can act as an obstacle for re-engagement in entrepreneurial venturing and learning from failure.

On another level, this feeling was quite interesting for the serial entrepreneur who attributed the failure completely to external factors, in contradiction to the argument of the association of such negative emotions with internal attributions (Walsh and Cunningham, 2017). Though the recovery process *per se* cannot be considered to be completed (as it still raises negative emotions)

(Shepherd, 2003), the serial entrepreneur (with a dominating external-ecosystemic attribution of failure) managed to re-embark in another entrepreneurial venture. Engaging in another venture that he established before exiting the failing venture represents a mechanism for avoiding continuous yearning over the venture and pro-action towards moving forward (Shepherd, 2009). This entrepreneur expressed deep satisfaction and happiness with the current venture's success, in contradiction to the literature's argument that such outcomes usually accompany internal attributions (Ucbasaran *et al.*, 2013; Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015; Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015; Mandl *et al.*, 2016). On the other hand, the novice entrepreneur (with a deep internal attribution of failure) avoided re-engaging straight away in another business venture fearing another failure (Nielsen and Sarasvathy, 2016). However, by diverting the focus from the emotional loss and failure to other aspects of life (loss orientation) (Shepherd, 2003), the learning from failure during this stage is risked being wasted if the failure time recovery extends extensively (Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015; Fang He *et al.*, 2018).

- c) Inconsideration: this attitude was very interesting for the researcher when revealed by two entrepreneurs, one serial (En9) and one novice (En11). This feeling was exhibited by the 'short memory' of entrepreneurs when narrating their failure. In many instances, both entrepreneurs explicitly stated forgetting some details about the ventures as to the various services offered, number of employees hired, the exact duration of the business, the exit date, and the timeline of the venture. This finding was more surprising from the side of the novice entrepreneur (who developed an intense internal attribution of failure), given the argument of the emotional attachment usually established between the entrepreneur and his/her first venture (Cardon *et al.*, 2005), which supposedly makes it a memorable experience. Both entrepreneurs re-embarked in subsequent venturing activities and, as in the previous two categories, explicitly revealed their complete satisfaction with their current pursuit. Learning-wise, the novice entrepreneur revealed a perceived high form of learning based upon the developed skills and enhanced approaches (D'Amelio, 2011; Dias and Martens, 2019).

d) Positivity: the rest of the entrepreneurs (excluding the ones with pure external attributions) demonstrated positive feelings when reflecting on failure (regardless of their attributions), by emphasising the learning that resulted from this experience (Politis and Gabrielsson, 2009; Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015). Entrepreneurs within this category considered the failure experience as a negative event that occurred in their lives but had to move forward (Shepherd, 2003). By re-embarking in new venturing activities, the recovery process of these entrepreneurs is considered to be moderate (Fang He *et al.*, 2018), exhibiting emotional resilience (Corner *et al.*, 2017). Almost all entrepreneurs expressed the relief feeling for finishing off with the venture (Shepherd, 2003; Dias and Teixeira, 2017; Walsh and Cunningham, 2017), given the stressful frames of mind encountered prior to the failure mainly associated with organisational costs.

6.3 Summary

This Chapter presented separately (in line with the MMR design) the findings of the in-depth interviews with experts, followed by the narrative analysis of entrepreneurs' stories. As for the first part, the findings revealed two main dimensions of attributions developed by experts, depending on their perceptions of the locus of causality and controllability with respect to entrepreneurs (Weiner, 1985). Henceforth, failure was attributed majorly to the lack of funds (Fatoki, 2014) (*external ascription*) and the competencies of entrepreneurs (Dias and Martens, 2019) (*internal ascription*). This study, therefore, provided more recent evidence and a deeper understanding of the perceptions of experts' attributions of entrepreneurial failure. The attributions thus involved an assessment of entrepreneurial competencies and decisions: the ability to manage and raise funds (Mezher *et al.*, 2008), developing a vision and a strategy for the business (Dias and Martens, 2019), networking skills (Watson, 2012), ineffective execution of marketing and overreliance on social media (Nakara *et al.*, 2012), improper research of the market (Nwankwo and Gbadamosi, 2010), overconfidence (Navis and Ozbek, 2016) and overoptimism (Hayward *et al.*, 2010). However, these attributions were not clear-cut internal and external, but rather entangled, highlighting the influence of the operational environment on entrepreneurial competencies (see Section 6.1.2 for details).

The second part involving the narrative analysis revealed also intertwined attributions in perceiving which internal and external factors were contributory to failure. The focus on internal attribution by the majority of entrepreneurs provide further evidence to Mantere *et al.*'s (2013) refutation of the self-serving bias associated with the attribution theory. The process of attributing failure was allocated to business dimensions, behaviours, and actions, and revealed hybrid attributions (Walsh and Cunningham, 2017) by the majority of entrepreneurs, which suggests the possibility of multiple causes for failure (Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015). The exclusion applies to single-nature (external) attributions developed by three serial entrepreneurs and one novice entrepreneur, who detached themselves from failure and avoided any responsibility for it (Engel *et al.*, 2014). Table 19 below outlines the differences between the perceptions of experts in explaining entrepreneurial failure and the rationalisation of entrepreneurs for their failures.

Internal Attribution		External Attribution	
Experts' Perceptions	Entrepreneurs' Perceptions	Experts' Perceptions	Entrepreneurs' Perceptions
Low ability to manage and raise funds	Mismanagement of funds	Lack of available funds	Low availability of funds (debt and equity)
Not developing a vision and a strategy for the business	Improper planning		
Lack of networking skills	Low networking skills	Lack of networking platform	
Ineffective execution of marketing and overreliance on social media	Improper planning for marketing function		Lack of funds to conduct proper marketing
Improper research of the market	Insufficient market research		Unsatisfying quality of talents existing
Overconfidence and overoptimism	Overconfidence and underestimation of efforts		

Lack of institutional support	Absence of governmental support
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Table 19: Comparative summary of experts’ and entrepreneurs’ attributions of failure

The findings of the study provided original evidence on the detailed process with which entrepreneurs explain the causes of failure whilst integrating the business dimensions. In other words, the study revealed how failure may be attributed to various minor and major dimensions for each attribution (i.e., Rogoff *et al.*, 2004), attempting to unveil in more depth the resulting learning outcomes, rather than the common identification of primary attributions (i.e., Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015; Walsh and Cunningham, 2017). Henceforth, the internal attributions of failure by novice entrepreneurs were related to the lack of initiatives in expanding and approaching weak networks (Wang *et al.*, 2015), improper reliance on social media (Nakara *et al.*, 2012), lack of dedicated proper planning (for marketing and business) (Dias and Martens, 2019), overconfidence (Hayward *et al.*, 2010) and improper management of funds (Mezher *et al.*, 2008). The external attributions embraced the difficulty in raising funds (Sampagnaro, 2013; Fatoki, 2014), legal framework and procedures (GEM, 2016), lack of needed talents (Rogoff *et al.*, 2004) and societal responses to entrepreneurial ideas which, though motivates entrepreneurship (GEM, 2016), underestimates small businesses (as explained in Section 6.2.2.2.4).

Though negative emotions were commonly highlighted as accompanying the reflective process on failure with grief mostly surfacing (Shepherd, 2003; Cope, 2011), the positive emotions revealed by novice entrepreneurs were very interesting (see details in Section 6.2.2.4). These emotions stemming plausibly from their ironic reflection on their immature self and irrational decision-making undertaken in their previous ventures revealed the higher transformative (Cope, 2011) level of learning. Interestingly, the negative emotions were not very frequent or intense and hence did not interfere in the learning process, revealing emotional resilience (Corner *et al.*, 2017). Learning outcomes were implied within the reflection, and represented learning from mistakes (Cope, 2011) on the effectiveness of strategies adopted, the need in the future to change the implemented options, and the amended understanding

and perceptions of the environment and opportunities (Lin *et al.*, 2019). Individual-level learning was found to be connected majorly to internal attributions (Walsh and Cunningham, 2017). Finally, this study concludes that the highest levels of transformative and double-loop learning occur through the internal attributions, combined with external attributions as reflected in Figures 34 and 35 below. A further insightful discussion of the findings will be provided in the next Chapter.

Figure 34: Comprehensive scheme of perceived internal attributions

Figure 35: Comprehensive scheme of perceived external attributions

"The difference between average people and achieving people is their perception of and response to failure" – John C. Maxwell

7 Chapter Seven: Discussion

This research aimed to enhance the understanding of the sense-making process of failure by deeply exploring how entrepreneurs develop failure attributions. The purpose behind such exploration was to understand the impact of these attributions and their dimensions on perceived learning outcomes. Prior to initiating the study with entrepreneurs, the researcher analysed the perspectives of industry experts on failure. The main purpose of this analysis was to acquire a preliminary, yet insightful investigation of the most common attributions of entrepreneurial failure in the context under study, given the shortage in recent academic studies on entrepreneurial failure in Lebanon. Therefore, this Chapter (and Chapter 6) aimed into answering the last two research question as to ‘How entrepreneurs ascribe failure to internal and external factors by employing the cognitive attribution?’ and ‘How can the understanding of entrepreneurial learning (outcomes) be enhanced by insightfully expanding on the dimensions of the attribution approach (process)?’.

7.1 Introduction

The failure of a business venture is a clear indication that something wrong happened, and therefore, reflecting on this experience allows for the development of causal relationships. The resulting causal attributions assist entrepreneurs in dealing with the so-perceived negative experience (Cardon *et al.*, 2011; Cope, 2011). Despite the extant investigation on entrepreneurial failure through the attribution theory (i.e., Shepherd *et al.*, 2011; Mantere *et al.*, 2013; Eggers and Song, 2015; Walsh and Cunningham, 2017), the mechanism with which entrepreneurs develop attributions (Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015) still needs to be investigated. Henceforth, this study partially addresses the gap of exploring the process with which entrepreneurs attribute failure and ascribe responsibilities, by providing narrative evidence as to their perceived attributions and perceived learning outcomes.

The attribution theory as adopted in this study was concluded to yield findings that expand beyond the contribution of the extant literature (e.g., Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015; Mandl *et al.*, 2016) and enhance the understanding of the attribution mechanism adopted by entrepreneurs. In other words, the common internal, external (Weiner, 1985; Pittaway and Thorpe, 2012; Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015; Yamakawa *et al.*,

2015; Mandl *et al.*, 2016) and hybrid attributions of failure (Walsh and Cunningham, 2017) were more insightfully explored to understand three main issues: how entrepreneurs perceive failure and, hence, develop ascriptions; how is failure explained with minor and major attributions developed over the business aspects; and the impact of these attributions and dimensions on the perceived learning outcomes.

The reflection involved assessing the entrepreneurs' controllability over each business aspect and event, and the extent to which their decisions within each contributed to the failure. This reasoning for attribution allowed a deeper exploration and understanding of the process (the 'how' element) (Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015) with which entrepreneurs identify mistakes that should not be replicated (Minniti and Bygrave, 2001; Politis, 2005). Henceforth, this study concludes that failure attributions developed by entrepreneurs are not distinct categories that can be simply classified as internal or external. More specifically, this research unveils how attributions may have several dimensions within each aspect, resulting in an interrelated hybrid nature (Walsh and Cunningham, 2017). These perceived attributions represent practice-based attributions, building on Rae's (2004) concept of practice-based theories of learning (see Chapter 2, Section 2.3.2). These attributions, therefore, represent findings that were developed based on practice rather than individual cases. A more detailed explanation of individual attributions is provided in Table 19, Figures 34 and 35 in Chapter 6, summarising how the attributions of entrepreneurs differed in nature and scope for each aspect of the entrepreneurial journey.

The reflection process on failure was revealed to take place over three main stages that correspond to the venture's life (forming the plot of the stories told). Entrepreneurs elaborated in each stage on their evaluation of the previous events, decisions and behaviours, and their perceived learning from the failure experience. Unsurprisingly, the learning outcomes of entrepreneurs were implied throughout their stories rather than accounting separately for these outcomes (i.e., Singh *et al.*, 2007; Walsh and Cunningham, 2017). Learning outcomes emerged subsequent to the realisation of the wrongdoings (Cope, 2011). Henceforth, these outcomes represented the effectiveness of strategies adopted, the need in the future to change the implemented options, and entrepreneurs' understanding and perceptions of the environment and opportunities (Lin *et al.*, 2019).

The process of making sense from failure via narratives revealed the emotional states experienced by entrepreneurs and the interconnection between these emotions and the nature of each attribution. As highlighted continuously, the decision for subsequent venturing as a behavioural outcome of learning from failure was restrained to the decision of engagement or abandonment of entrepreneurial activity, rather than an evaluation of the performance of subsequent ventures to assess the effectiveness of learning. However, in this aspect, entrepreneurs have expressed their ultimate satisfaction with their current ventures as an outcast comparison with the failing ventures.

7.2 Reflection on Foundation Stage

In analysing the reflection on the first stage of establishing the venture, this study revealed that the lack of funds cannot be simply considered an external attribution of failure. More specifically, the research concluded with a) a major external attribution of failure to the lack of available and accessible funds and b) a minor internal attribution to the improper management of available funds and the lack of influential networks. The lack of funds was rationalised over the availability of funds and the access of entrepreneurs to these funds. Access to finance is considered a massive challenge for entrepreneurs (Lekhanya and Mason, 2014; Jere *et al.*, 2015). Businesses, especially in their early stage, are rarely able to secure loans from commercial banks (Abdesamed and Abd Wahab, 2014), or raise funds from venture capitalists (Beck and Demirguc-Kunt, 2006). This fact builds further constraints in their plans to create rewarding projects (Gimmon and Levie, 2010). Most of the issues reflected upon the financial constraints involved the inability of start-ups to provide collateral in their quest to secure funds (Abdesamed and Abd Wahab, 2014), and therefore, found as a recourse to borrow from family and friends instead of banks (Fatoki, 2014).

In this study, the shortage in funds was attributed partially to the lack of connections that, if entrepreneurs possessed them, would have been in a better position to secure the needed amounts (mostly emphasised by experts) (Connelly *et al.*, 2011). Another attribution of the lack of funds related to the high lending (or investing) criteria that makes it difficult for entrepreneurs to qualify for debt (or equity) financing (mostly emphasised by the entrepreneurs under the finance gap theory) (Naimy, 2011). According to experts, the shortage of funds is a contributory factor to the exit decision

(failure) of entrepreneurs, yet, not responsible for the failure. In contrast, entrepreneurs considered the lack of liquidity a major burden to proceed with operations, due to the lack of profits (GEM, 2016), lack of funds at reasonable costs (Schmidt *et al.*, 2015) (external attribution) and ineffective management of the available funds (Mezher *et al.*, 2008) (internal attribution), including the exaggerated spending and the collection of outstanding debts, as agreed by both samples. Therefore, this study has provided further justification as to the need to explore deeper the attributions of failure as perceived by entrepreneurs from several angles.

Exploring entrepreneurs' motivations emerged from the impact of these motivations on the sense-making process of failure (Heinze, 2013) and the entrepreneurial attitude subsequent to failure in terms of future endeavours (Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015). Interestingly, the study revealed the impact of these ambitions on the nature of attributions developed. More specifically, entrepreneurs with initially high ambitious motivations attributed failure either to a mistaken judgment of opportunity or an ecosystematic-external attribution. In earlier studies (i.e., Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015), motivation was investigated to its impact on the success of future venturing. Therefore, this study has expanded the comprehension of the role of motivations not only on subsequent endeavours but also in developing attributions and reflecting on failure. Entrepreneurs with initially big ambitions and achievement goals (Gabrielsson and Politis, 2011) tend to attribute failure to external factors; a plausible explanation might relate to their tendency to protect their ego and self-esteem (Ucbasaran *et al.*, 2010; Engel *et al.*, 2014), previously attached to the big dreams.

7.3 Reflection on Survival Stage

The findings from the second stage of reflecting deeply on entrepreneurial decision-making (Rae, 2004) and business aspects revealed how the various dimensions of perceived attributions explained the various levels of perceived learning (Cope, 2011; Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015).

7.3.1 Reflection on Individual Level

The internal attributions of failure developed through this process expanded the work of scholars (i.e., Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015; Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015; Walsh and Cunningham, 2017) in understanding how entrepreneurs reflect on failure and evaluate the contribution of their skills and competencies to failure. These competencies usually define the sets of skills, knowledge and attitude exhibited by

entrepreneurs. Making the appropriate decisions defines the survival of the business and its ability to sustain in the market (Gans *et al.*, 2017). This depends greatly on the ability of entrepreneurs to reach these decisions properly and then implement them effectively (Minello *et al.*, 2014).

Novice entrepreneurs reflected with an internal attribution of failure and share of the blame, recognising their lack of entrepreneurial skills (Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015; Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015). However, the emphasis on their pro-activeness undertaken to address the gaps in knowledge and entrepreneurial skills can be explained as an ego-protective mechanism (Shepherd and Patzelt, 2017). The findings thus, provided further evidence on the initiation of entrepreneurial learning, especially when anticipating failure (before the actual failure) (Hines and Thorpe, 1995; Costello, 1996). However, the extent of initiatives assumed by entrepreneurs to expand on their skills was limited in efforts, and in some instances constrained by: the lack of financial resources (Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015) (*external ascription*); the underestimation of the need for expanding skills - overconfidence (Eggers and Song, 2014) (*internal ascription*); and the decline in ambition and belief in the future sustainability of the business (Petkova, 2008; Arasti, 2011) (*internal ascription*). The common underestimation of the complexities of an entrepreneurial career and of the efforts needed for a successful business as an attribute for failure corroborates the argument on the contribution of overconfidence (and hence overoptimism) to failure (Hayward *et al.*, 2010; Invernizzi *et al.*, 2017). This is considered an interesting finding as earlier studies (i.e., Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015) focused on the lack of commitment, which has not been found to be an attribution to failure in this study.

In line with the Catharsis finding of Mantere *et al.* (2013), the findings within this study refuted the self-serving bias of the attribution theory (Petkova, 2008), yet proved the adoption of self-justification as a process in reflecting on failure. Protecting and sustaining their self-esteem (Aronson, 2011), novice entrepreneurs labelled their old identities as immature, naïve, overconfident, optimistic, impulsive, and irrational. The emphasis on the current, developed, and mature entrepreneurial identity confirms the transformative learning (Cope, 2011) achieved by entrepreneurs on the individual level while reflecting on failure (Walsh and Cunningham, 2017).

7.3.2 Reflection on Business Level

The reflection on entrepreneurial skills and competencies in relation to business aspects proved once again that attributions of failure necessitate a further exploration of its various dimensions, before defining it as internal or external. This exploration reasserted the conclusion that attributions carry intertwined ascriptions rather than a single straightforward categorisation. Henceforth, reflecting on the business level, different attributions emerged according to two main levels of failure ascription that consequently impacted the learning generated: *planning* for the function and *executing* the function (Menon *et al.*, 1999), as exemplified in Figures 34 and 35. Interestingly, all entrepreneurs revealed their recognition and full awareness of the relevance of each function on their business performance. However, the reflection exhibited varying levels as to the planning and execution, allowing for the development of various internal and external attributions. However, the lack of planning for the venture (and for each business aspect) was perceived as a major internal attribution to failure (Rogoff *et al.*, 2004; Arasti, 2011; Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015; Walsh and Cunningham, 2017), such as the lack of researching the market and competition (Michelmores and Rowley, 2013).

First, the attribution of failure to the marketing function did not develop a single direction (internal) as advised by scholars (Rogoff *et al.*, 2004; Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015; Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015). The marketing concept and application differs in the entrepreneurial context from the organisational context (Nikfarjam and Zarifi, 2015). The focus on a limited base of clients, with a restricted knowledge in marketing, reflects with unplanned and flexible efforts (West and Noel, 2009). The findings of this study revealed that the attribution of failure to the marketing function holds both: an internal and an external attribution, and therefore cannot be simply classified as an internal attribution (e.g., Rogoff *et al.*, 2004; Atsan, 2016). The novice unfunded entrepreneurs' awareness and recognition of the relevance of the marketing function led to the development of improper marketing plans (Musso and Francioni, 2014). However, the low extent to which this planning was executed was deemed by these entrepreneurs as contributory to failure. Funded entrepreneurs were more confident in executing the marketing function, while unfunded entrepreneurs relied more on their networks (strong, weak and clients) to achieve the advertising function (Reijonen, 2010), and on innovativeness in rare occasions. Therefore, the internal

attribution of ineffective or improper marketing (planning level) is directly linked to the shortage of funds, which has an external-ecosystematic attribution for failure (execution level). Additionally, two minor sub-attributions emerged: loss of hope in the future success of the business (low level of optimism and hence dedication – *internal attribution*) (Arasti, 2011), and lack of personnel to handle this task due to financial constraints (Rogoff *et al.*, 2004) (*ecosystematic attribution*). On the contrary, funded serial entrepreneurs did not attribute failure to marketing, claiming sufficient, effective, and dedicated marketing planning and execution. Such differentiation highlights and reveals more in-depth the learning outcomes associated with each level of attribution as will be elaborated in Section 7.6.

Second, the attribution of failure to the absence of influential networks revealed an internal dimension. Novice (unfunded) entrepreneurs related this attribution to the lack of social competencies, mostly ingratiation, social perception, and self-promotion (Lans *et al.*, 2015). Entrepreneurs, in their majority, built their trust (Hallam *et al.*, 2018) on the assistance provided by their strong networks in building brand awareness, and enhancing the quality of the product or service offered (Jaafar *et al.*, 2009). On the contrary, funded-serial entrepreneurs did not attribute failure to networking, arguing on their sufficient, effective, and beneficial networks. Therefore, the reflection over networking revealed two internal dimensions: the personal proactiveness in expanding networks (Zhao *et al.*, 2010) and the social skills required for developing these networks (Lans *et al.*, 2015). The findings under this aspect revealed an absolute internal attribution for failing in developing beneficial networks (Jansen, 2012), despite the entrepreneurs' recognition of its impact on business performance (Wang *et al.*, 2015).

Third, the findings of this study uncovered several angles as to the perceived contribution of the recruited human capital to failure, given the significant role played by the first few employees to entrepreneurial survival (Wright *et al.*, 2005; Powell and Baker, 2014). Henceforth, the aspect of human capital as raised by entrepreneurs involved reflecting upon the effective recruitment, management, and compensation of a sufficient reserve of skilled human capital. Interestingly, and in line with Mantere *et al.* (2013), the majority of entrepreneurs blamed themselves more than their employees. However, minor attributions were developed as to: the unavailability of

the required tech talents in the Lebanese markets (GEM, 2018) (*external ascription*); the limited financial compensation (Salgado *et al.*, 2020) (*external ascription*); and the informal recruitment process (Rogoff *et al.*, 2004; Arasti, 2011) (*internal ascription*). Interestingly, serial entrepreneurs who exhibited an absolute external attribution for failure also showed a fated attribution for the recruitment process. In other words, the lack of moral and professional ethics in the recruited talents could have not been uncovered even with a proper and formal recruitment process.

Fourth, throughout the reflection process, serial entrepreneurs (in majority) attributed failure purely to ecosystematic-external factors. Attributing failure to external factors is argued to hinder learning from failure (Engel *et al.*, 2014), as the lack of shame or responsibility (Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015) rarely motivates entrepreneurs to learn from failure by reflecting on its causes (Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015). Such attribution motivates entrepreneurs for subsequent venturing as the reasons for failure are not internal (Engel *et al.*, 2014). Though the findings of this study agree on the quick re-engagement of these serial entrepreneurs in subsequent ventures, it does not seem to agree with Lin *et al.* (2019) argument of the probable lower chances of success given the lack of learning. A plausible explanation that necessitates further research could be related to changing ecosystems. These entrepreneurs with external attributions reported absolute satisfaction with their current ventures, after moving out of the Lebanese ecosystem, officially blamed for their failure (Mezher *et al.*, 2008; Naimy, 2011).

7.4 Reflection on Exit Stage

The nature of the exit decision and the initial motivations of entrepreneurship were further confirmed within this study as to their impact on the reflection process on failure (Heinze, 2013). However, a further contribution in connection with motivations revealed their impact on the nature of attributions developed. Funded entrepreneurs with initial big ambitious motivations reached the exit decision immediately after realising the impossibility of scaling up the business as initially planned and aspired. Therefore, the quick decision of exit (DeTienne *et al.*, 2015) led to the perceived attribution of failure to external factors. In contrast, the decision to exit was sustained longer for novice-unfunded entrepreneurs until the extreme shortage in liquidity (DeTienne, 2010). This decision was impacted by the perceived

cultural stigmatisation (Vaillant and Lafuente, 2007; Pretorius, 2009) and concluded with bearing personal blame and responsibility for the failure. Therefore, the findings have provided further evidence on the impact of stigma in developing contexts as an expensive social cost for novice entrepreneurs, forcing them to delay the exit decision and causing higher financial costs (Singh *et al.*, 2015) but less emotional costs (Shepherd *et al.*, 2009). The interesting finding related to the reengagement of the majority of entrepreneurs in subsequent venturing activities supports the argument of the literature on the impact of entrepreneurial failure on subsequent venturing (i.e., Stam *et al.*, 2008; Singh *et al.*, 2015; Mandl *et al.*, 2016; Boso *et al.*, 2019).

Figure 36: Representation of the sequential process of Lebanese entrepreneurs' learning from failure

7.5 Emotional Reflection

On the emotional level, this study provides further evidence as to the impact of failure anticipation on the regulation of negative emotions generated from failure (Shepherd *et al.*, 2009; Dias and Teixeira, 2017). The moderate activation level of negative

emotions (Wolfe and Shepherd, 2015) as experienced by the majority of entrepreneurs subsequent to failure supports the concept of emotional resilience by Corner *et al.*, (2017), in agreement with Eggers and Song (2014). This moderate activation of emotions founded motivational and informational attitudes to learning from failure (Fang He *et al.*, 2018). A plausible explanation of this finding is probably associated with the high level of regulation over emotions (Weiss and Beal, 2005; Wolfe and Shepherd, 2015) and the effective emotion-focused coping adopted by entrepreneurs subsequent to failure, especially reframing and re-examination (Singh *et al.*, 2007).

In parallel, the valence of emotions, known as the influence of the situation on the entrepreneurs' well-being (Weiss and Beal, 2005), was found to be very low, as entrepreneurs did not report any impactful outcome on their health subsequent to failure (Wolfe and Shepherd, 2015). Another possible explanation appealing for future research relates to the impact (or pressure) of cultural context on the quick emotional recovery of entrepreneurs from failure, especially in developing contexts. In the same vein, the interesting finding of laughter, among other positive emotions, reveals not only the evolved identity from failure (Mantere *et al.*, 2013), but also proves further the high level of emotional resilience of Lebanese entrepreneurs. In parallel, the intense negative emotions exhibited by a serial entrepreneur who attributed failure holistically to external factors challenge the argument that such emotions are usually accompanied by the personal blame attached with internal attributions (Shepherd, 2003; Cope, 2011; Ucbasaran *et al.*, 2013; Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015; Walsh and Cunningham, 2017). This finding reveals that more is to be explored about the affective outcomes of serial entrepreneurs subsequent to failure. A plausible explanation might relate to the resources (belief, time, and efforts) already injected into the business which could have created such deep emotional attachment (Cardon *et al.*, 2005).

7.6 Learning Generated

The learning outcomes generated from the sense-making of failure depended on the dimensions of perceived failure attributions (i.e., Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015; Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015; Singh *et al.*, 2015; Corner *et al.*, 2017). As explained throughout this Chapter, and as summarised in Table 19, the attributions of failure had varying intertwined internal and external roots, developing minor and major

ascriptions of failure. Therefore, the resulting learning levels also revealed entangled and overlapping associations, ranging over three main dimensions: individual level (skills, weaknesses, areas for improvement); venture level (business operations and management); and ecosystem level (nature of market and customers, legal structure, financial support available) (Cope, 2005; Walsh and Cunningham, 2017). For instance, the major internal attributions of failure combined with minor external attributions (as in the case of marketing) provided a deep reflection on the experience and resulted in learning outcomes at the individual, ecosystem, and venture levels. At the individual level (transformative learning) (Cope, 2011), entrepreneurs learned about their personal weaknesses, misbeliefs, levels of optimism and confidence, and knowledge and skills (D'Amelio, 2011). Under the venture level, the venture and the venture management levels suggested by Cope (2005) were combined, integrating both dimensions: understanding the nature of the business and its weaknesses, as well as the weaknesses in past decision-making, entrepreneurial behaviours, and the skills needed for managing the venture. The ecosystem-level learning outcomes involved learning about the market dynamics in which the business operates, the levels of competition, financing options, availability of talents, networks and connections, the legal system, and the nature of consumers (Cope, 2005).

The study concluded that even when the failure was attributed internally for most of the venture's managerial process, the learning outcomes span over individual and venture levels (Cope, 2005; Cope, 2011). The findings, therefore, expand on the work of Yamakawa and Cardon (2015) and Yamakawa *et al.* (2015), arguing that higher levels of learning (transformative and double loop) are achieved with a major internal attribution of failure combined with a minor external attribution. In parallel, these findings challenge Mandl *et al.* (2016) argument that internal attributions drive entrepreneurs out of the entrepreneurial career. Interestingly, none of the entrepreneurs treated the business as an outstanding unit or developed any mechanistic ascription of failure (as in Mantere *et al.*, 2013; Walsh and Cunningham, 2017). On the contrary, the business was considered as the outcomes of the entrepreneurs' previous managerial decisions, being the final decision-makers of their ventures (Delmar *et al.*, 2003). The findings of this study are hence summarised in: Figure 36 above that summarises the process undertaken by the participants of this study; Figures 34 and 35 that schematise the interrelationships of attributions across the

business aspects; and Figure 37 that represents the Comprehensive Learning Process (CLP).

Figure 37: Comprehensive Learning Process from failure (CLP)

8 Chapter Eight: Conclusion

8.1 Introduction

This Chapter presents the study contributions pertaining to answering the research questions and meeting the research aim and objectives. Acknowledgement of the limitations and constraints of the study and their impact on the pursuit of the research is then discussed, before concluding with the areas for future research suggested to enhance academic understanding of entrepreneurial learning from failure, especially in developing contexts. The last section of this research represents the researcher’s personal reflection on the doctorate journey.

8.2 Revisiting the Research Aim and Objectives

In this section, the researcher reviews the study aim and objectives (see Sections 1.5), for the purpose of validating that they have been attained. The research aim was:

- To insightfully explore how causal attributions of failure are developed by entrepreneurs (Homsma *et al.*, 2007) during the process of reflecting on failure, in order to understand the impact of these attributions and their dimensions on the expected learning outcomes.

Following on this aim, the study was guided by the following research objectives:

- To examine the nature of entrepreneurial failure and exit decisions of entrepreneurs;
- To understand the relationship between the reflection process on failure and entrepreneurial learning;
- To examine the role of attribution in the reflection process from entrepreneurial failure;
- To explore the mechanism with which entrepreneurs develop failure ascriptions with respect to internal and external factors by employing the cognitive attribution; and
- To investigate the impact of expanding the dimensions of attributions on the process of reflecting on failure and on the outcomes of learning generated.

Achieving these objectives required an insightful review of the extant research on how learning is generated from entrepreneurial failure, the various learning outcomes, the

role of cognitive attribution within this reflection process, and the influence of its dimensions on the nature of learning generated. Consequently, the study concluded with a comprehensive learning process (CLP) that takes into consideration the various interrelationships between attribution and business aspects, emphasising the relevance of such deep investigation of failure attributions in understanding how learning is generated from failure. These objectives have been achieved by examining the academic literature in Chapters 2 and 3 thoroughly on the extant contributions on entrepreneurial learning from failure and reviewing the significance of the attribution theory into the field, allowing for a sound theoretical foundation for the research. The literature gap emphasised separately in Chapter 4 accentuated the need for a comprehensive and insightful reflection study that explores in-depth the mechanism with which failure attributions are developed. Next, the contributions of the study are discussed.

8.3 Contributions to Knowledge

The study has contributed to the field of entrepreneurial learning theoretically and practically. The researcher hence elaborates on how the findings of this study contribute to the knowledge and the practice of the field, enhancing the understanding on entrepreneurial learning from failure.

8.3.1 Theoretical Implications

The first contribution of this study involves moving beyond the common examination of the actual causes of entrepreneurial failure, to emphasise on more insightful dimensions such as the learning dynamics. Therefore, this study contributes to the field of entrepreneurial failure by accentuating the relevance of failure as a learning experience, eventually challenging the extant anti-failure bias within entrepreneurial research. Additionally, this study provides empirical evidence to the field of entrepreneurial learning from failure by moving away from the theoretical contributions (i.e., Ucbasaran *et al.*, 2013; Jenkins and McKelvie, 2016; Wei *et al.*, 2019), to support the more recent, yet, limited empirical studies (i.e., Byrne and Shepherd, 2015; Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015; Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015; Mueller and Shepherd, 2016; Corner *et al.*, 2017; Fang He *et al.*, 2018; Boso *et al.*, 2019).

Focusing strictly on the outcomes of entrepreneurial learning is not much contributory to entrepreneurial research, without the integration of theories that assist in exploring the “*entrepreneurial learning as an experiential process, and how this process evolves*

throughout the entrepreneurial career” (Politis, 2005, p. 418). Within the field, this study has provided a theoretical contribution to the adoption of the attribution theory as a cognitive mechanism to reflect on failure. Building on previous scholars’ work (i.e., Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015; Walsh and Cunningham, 2017), this research has expanded the scope of investigating the causal attributions developed by entrepreneurs in making sense of their failure. This study concluded that failure attributions developed by entrepreneurs are not distinct categories that can be simply classified into primary internal or external. As a result, this study has responded to the various calls (Ucbasaran *et al.*, 2013; Eggers and Song, 2014; Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015; Walsh and Cunningham, 2017) in understanding the process of developing attributions for failure, mostly on the individual level and the impact of these attributions on learning outcomes.

Additionally, the insightful exploration of attribution through business aspects, decisions, and behaviours stipulates an enhanced understanding of three main issues: how entrepreneurs perceive failure and hence develop ascriptions; how is failure explained with minor and major attributions perceived over the business aspects; and the impact of these attributions and dimensions on the perceived learning outcomes. This study then supports the significance of internal attributions in generating higher-level (transformative and double loop) learning. More specifically, the major internal attributions of failure combined with minor external attributions resulted in higher learning outcomes at the individual, ecosystem, and venture level. Henceforth, a detailed explanation of the direct and indirect associations within the internal attribution *per se* assists in understanding further its content, outcome, and impact on learning. The enhanced skills, knowledge, and capabilities to manage business venture are thus suggested to enhance the metrics and performance of subsequent ventures, allowing for the effective and rewarding implementation of the learning outcomes.

8.3.2 Practical Implications

Built upon the various contributions of earlier scholars (i.e., Rae, 2004; Cope, 2011; Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015; Walsh and Cunningham, 2017) and the findings of this study, the CLP model (see Figure 37 supported by Figures 34 and 35) revealed how entrepreneurs essentially perceive and attribute failure, directly and indirectly, developing minor and major attributions that eventually impact their learning outcomes. Therefore, the practical contributions of the study, as summarised within

this process, are potentially numerous. First, this process is suggested to assist failing entrepreneurs in making insightful sense from failure, by undertaking a structured, yet, flexible reflection. The relevance of the process for these entrepreneurs is mostly concentrated within the attribution process that can be applied according to two main levels: *planning* for the function and *executing* the function. Implementing this aspect assists entrepreneurs in evaluating entrepreneurial behaviour and in identifying perceived constraints, strengths, and weaknesses. Subsequent to understanding the dimensions of their attributions of failure, entrepreneurs may be in a better position to evaluate their coping mechanism with the arising negative emotions and the conditions for the positive emotions (if any). A parallel implication for current entrepreneurs struggling with their business survival suggests using the model as an anticipatory mechanism of failure. Considering failure seriously (Dias and Teixeira, 2017) is argued to balance emotional costs (Shepherd *et al.*, 2009). Therefore, the anticipation of failure through this model is proposed to enhance the reflection process, moderate the emotional responses, and improve the cognitive sense-making of failure.

A second practical contribution of this study as depicted within the process resides in its significance to nascent entrepreneurs through vicarious learning (Bandura, 1977). Moreover, these entrepreneurs may rely on the CLP model to understand the weaknesses and errors committed by ‘failing’ entrepreneurs. As a result, the model may act as a guidance tool for future/nascent entrepreneurs to anticipate the business aspects with possible mistakes, and the personal capabilities with areas for improvement or development. Such type of learning usually equips people with general knowledge on how to approach new conditions and situations (Wood and Bandura, 1989). The ultimate outcome is proposed to be a higher probability of ventures’ survival. On another level, current (as well as nascent) entrepreneurs are recommended through the model to limit the extent of (or avoid) external attributions of future failure, and rather configure personal responsibility towards it to enable a superior level of learning.

Another contribution of this research to the practice resides in its implications for a) policymakers and educators, and b) accelerators and financiers. Nahata (2019) suggested that countries aim to promote entrepreneurship mostly for potential and novice entrepreneurs. However, little support is being offered to failed entrepreneurs.

Therefore, more (private and institutional) support may be offered to failing entrepreneurs in facilitating the recovery process, and in encouraging them to share their stories as a support for challenging social stigmatisation. In the same vein, practice-based attributions resulting from the reflection process over entrepreneurs' experiences are not bounded or limited to individual entrepreneurs, but rather become a social, knowledgeable resource that emerges from the socially negotiated structures and the practices of a business venture (Rae, 2004). Therefore, in promoting the quasi-equivalence concept of learning from success stories and the mistakes of previous discontinuing entrepreneurs, policymakers, as well as educators, are recommended to provide support programmes and entrepreneurial education for nascent entrepreneurs, by adopting the CLP model and the practice-based attributions. On another level, finance providers and entrepreneurial accelerators are proposed to enhance the level of advisory support provided to entrepreneurs. More specifically, by attempting to comprehend how entrepreneurs think, behave, reflect, and learn, venture's stakeholders, e.g., finance providers, mentors, and investors, are suggested to develop more effective strategies in supporting entrepreneurs.

A final major contribution of this study to the practice of entrepreneurial learning from failure relates to the context of the study. The majority of influential studies on entrepreneurial learning from failure were conducted in developed contexts, such as UK, Europe, and North America, with very limited contributory studies in less developed contexts such as Africa and Asia (Lattacher and Wdowiak, 2020). Therefore, this study is adding to the limited research on learning from entrepreneurial failure conducted in developing and emerging contexts and is the first of its kind in Lebanon in particular and the Middle East in general. Subsequently, the evidence provided by entrepreneurs in a developing context is suggested to be influenced by the local cultural (stigma before and after failure), especially at the levels of the exit decision and the regulation of emotions that resulted from failure. Henceforth, it is suggested that the low cultural tolerance towards entrepreneurial failure and the resulting high cost of stigma over discontinuing entrepreneurs (especially the novice entrepreneurs) motivated entrepreneurs to undertake a quick recovery (mostly emotional) to avoid further stigma or sympathy. This can provide a promising window for future research.

8.4 Limitations of the Research

Under this section, the researcher acknowledges the limitations of the research, bounded by the available resources; the accessibility to information and to participants; and the methodological approach of the study. Exploring these limitations sheds the light on their impact on the validity of findings and the steps taken by the researcher to address them in order to preserve the implications of the research.

Retrospectivity of narratives: This research relied strictly on retrospective narratives. Though the narratives would have probably matured with time passage since the failure was experienced, capturing the narratives right at the time of failure is particularly impossible, especially in the context of this study. In Lebanon, the legal announcement of discontinuation takes a considerable time because of the formal and legal process (if the venture operated in the formal economy); the reluctance of entrepreneurs to announce the closure of their ventures to their networks; and the understandable hesitation to share experiences straight after failure.

Recall bias: An inherent limitation in any retrospective research is recall bias. This limitation is argued to affect the process of recalling events as they occurred. However, the recall process of critical events and situations within 15 years of the incident's occurrence remains valuable with a high degree of accuracy (Berney and Blane, 1997), and thus, does not impose any fundamental threat on the analysis.

Limited size of the sample: The size of the sample was bounded by the available access to data, as the researcher faced few challenges in collecting the data. Lebanon lacks an official and public comprehensive database of discontinuing ventures. Henceforth, the researcher's second recourse was to contact financing companies, accelerators, banks, Ministry of Economy and Trade, Commercial Register, Chamber of Agriculture and Commerce, Chamber of Manufacturing, and private entrepreneurial research centres to ask for the needed data. All the publicly sought attempts were unsuccessful, either because some public institutions rejected the request even for academic purposes, or due to the unavailability of these data. Private requests from accelerators and credit companies were rejected as well, under the excuse of confidentiality and protecting private information. Therefore, the last resort of the researcher was to refer to her strong and weak networks, asking informally for participants who match the sampling criteria, posting interviews' requests on social

media, and sending email requests to third parties who could be of help (such as world bank branch in Lebanon). In parallel, the researcher adopted the snowball sampling technique to reach out to more interviewees as entrepreneurs usually connect with entrepreneurs, while taking into consideration the resulting risk of homogeneity from such snowball referrals. However, the sample size shall not pose any validity threat, as the researcher followed the lead of the most recent studies investigating entrepreneurial learning from failure (see Table 10 in Chapter 5, Section 5.4.2).

Heterogeneity of the sample: Given the two definitions of failure adopted for the sake of this research, the resulting sample was heterogeneous, lacking homogeneity that simplifies the comparison of results (Byrne and Shepherd, 2015; Lattacher and Wdowiak, 2020), as recommended by Smith *et al.* (2009). However, this heterogeneity allowed for interesting findings in the reflection process on failure (Heinze, 2013), especially on the level of comparison between novice and serial, funded and unfunded, technology and traditional entrepreneurs.

Sensitivity of the topic: It was a daunting and difficult process to find entrepreneurs who have been socially referred to as failing, and yet, ready to share their experiences openly (Cope, 2011).

Generalisation: The adoption of qualitative approaches with small samples do not usually allow for generalizability. However, this thesis originally aimed into creating local, rather than generalizable knowledge, by examining inter and intra accounts of entrepreneurs “*that provides fine-grained pro-casual accounts [...] examining intra- and inter-case processes and dynamics*” (Cope, 2011, p.15). Nevertheless, to allow these findings to be applicable beyond the individual cases presented, borrowing Rae’s (2004) concept of practice-based theories allows the attributions to be not based on personal narratives or practice, but rather on the reflection process on the practice as implied within these narratives.

Subjectivity of narratives: The study relied on the subjective assessment of entrepreneurs for the probable causes behind their ventures’ failure, which is criticised for bearing a potential bias. However, as the research questions focus on understanding the entrepreneurs’ personal attributions and interpretations of failure, the basis for this bias is thus removed (Jenkins, 2012). The aim of the study is not to reveal the actual causes for entrepreneurial failure in Lebanon, but rather the personal

perceptions of failure of two main samples (entrepreneurs and experts), and the learning generated from entrepreneurs' attributions (Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015). Additionally, the sense-making process as an interpretive mechanism of failure displays an outstanding emphasis on plausibility rather than accuracy. In other words, the process is not considered an unbiased, objective process, but is rather a personal identity and beliefs-based mechanism. Henceforth, the accuracy in their perceptions and reflections should not be an issue, as the new data generated will assess causal attitudes, leading to changes in behaviours and beliefs (Ucbasaran *et al.*, 2013).

Researcher's bias: A possible limitation for this research could relate to the researcher's bias. However, the strict implementation of methodological guidelines during the design and conduct of the research ought to remove any bias from her side, even when the processes of data collection, analysis, and writing were conducted solely by the researcher. Additionally, continuous reviews from the Director of Studies assisted in incorporating further perspectives throughout the analytical process. In parallel, reviews from third parties, such as conference presentations, provided further independent perspectives that were taken into consideration.

Pandemic: the data collection was undertaken over two stages. The first one involved being physically in the context of study and aimed for completing the data collection before returning to the UK. However, due to limited time and resources, the data collection was not accomplished through a single visit, especially with the MMR design. Nevertheless, the diffusion of the pandemic and the restricted travel, movement, and resources resulting from prolonged lockdowns in Lebanon and the UK have forced the researcher to switch to remote data collection. Though face-to-face interaction would have been more beneficial in understanding the emotions attached to the reflective storytelling of entrepreneurs, online interviews were still completed successfully, following up with interviewees whenever needed.

8.5 Potential Areas for Future Research

This study has investigated in-depth the cognitive reflection process on entrepreneurial failure through perceived attributions, to understand how the attributive mechanism is undertaken and how the outcomes are affected. For that purpose, the researcher emphasised the relevance of the nature and dimensions of attributions in influencing the reflection and learning from failure. By offering

practice-based ascriptions, the researcher developed a comprehensive learning model that outlines the interrelationships between ascriptions, emotions, business aspects and learning outcomes. However, as made clear throughout the study, the performance of subsequent venturing was out of the scope of this research. Henceforth, future research may consider assessing the relationships of these ascriptions as outlined in the schemes with the performance of new ventures.

The relationships outlined in the model stemmed from the narrative analysis of 14 entrepreneurs who discontinued their businesses. Future longitudinal research might assess the validity of the ascriptions depicted within this model or explore further attributions that were not included within this research given the constraining time and financial resources, such as managing the supply chain. Another window for future research might verify the presumed comprehensive learning process by surveying more homogeneous entrepreneurs (e.g., novice entrepreneurs) and examine whether the nature of attributions within each business dimension changes or not. Similarly, a more insightful and deeper exploration is suggested on the interrelationship among these attributions and how these reflect in more effective learning and implementation.

Future researchers may also investigate the impact of the time gap between the occurrence of failure and the reflection process on the nature of attributions and eventually on the learning outcomes. For that purpose, researchers are recommended to spot entrepreneurs shortly after failure to collect their narratives. After some time (6 months to one year), researchers may re-institute the narratives of the same entrepreneurs, in order to understand the activation and maturity of emotions and therefore, the impact on the learning process from failure, as well as any change in the nature of attributions developed.

Future research shall also aim to investigate more empirically the various attributions developed over time whether in this study or in earlier inquiries. Empirical support is needed to verify the various conceptual contributions into the attribution research territory, recommending the adoption of more narrative-based analysis, such as the

interpretative phenomenological analysis¹⁷ developed by Smith *et al.* (1999) and applied first by Cope (2011). A parallel methodological recommendation for future research involves the integration of narrative inquiry within phenomenology. These approaches are suggested to provide a further insightful understanding on the attributions of failure as perceived by entrepreneurs. The researcher could not have adopted such a contributory approach, due to the study constraints.

This study has added to the field of entrepreneurial learning from failure empirical data from a developing context. Existing differences among cultures and entrepreneurial ecosystems, especially between developing and developed economies, are suggested to play a great role in shaping and determining the level of attributions perceived by entrepreneurs and the resulting emotional responses. The emotions exhibited by entrepreneurs differed greatly from the literature (e.g., Shepherd, 2003; Cope, 2011; Walsh and Cunningham, 2017), implying a causal connection with the cultural context (e.g., nature of culture in emerging economies) (see Chapter 6, Section 6.2.2.2.4). The high perception of stigmatisation in the Lebanese context is suggested to have pushed (negatively or positively) entrepreneurs to regulate their emotions and overcome failure quickly. Therefore, recommendations for future research involve conducting more empirical studies over the impact of culture on the direction (positive or negative) and speed of recovering from (or overcoming) the emotional responses that resulted from failure. Another related recommendation might involve investigating the level of emotional responses resulting from external attributions in developing contexts. The intense grief feelings of one serial entrepreneur who attributed the failure completely to external ascriptions recommend further investigation on the causal linkage behind such reactions (e.g. self-esteem, passion, ambitions).

8.6 Reflection on the Doctorate Journey

Self-reflection on the three-year doctoral journey provides an insightful understanding with which the researcher retrieves the meaning of her experience and the change that she witnessed (Jarvis, 2009). In reflecting on the journey, the researcher followed the methodology of Louie *et al.* (2003), known as the three-phase self-study. The

¹⁷ Interpretative phenomenological analysis is the analytical tool of phenomenological interviews, where the researcher should not have any pre-determined questions about the topic under study apart from an opening question. The interviews are thus loose structured, and questions only stem from the context of the interviews (Thompson *et al.*, 1989 as cited in Cope, 2011).

reflection starts with an assessment of her own behaviour and thoughts at the beginning of the doctoral journey, as her previous experience and knowledge impacted the doctoral experience (Jarvis, 2009). The second stage of implementation reveals personal information about the researcher, whilst questioning her personal beliefs. The third stage involves disseminating the reflection while identifying the contribution of the reflection outcomes on the journey, represented by this section of the dissertation.

Being admitted for the doctoral degree under a full scholarship was an intrinsically motivating behaviour that the researcher worked for, for two years, prior to her successful admission. Henceforth, the enthusiasm with which the researcher started her degree was the main drive that was re-energising her regular low flames throughout the three-years. Equipped with 5 years of senior auditing experience, the researcher believed in her potential to achieve her doctor title within the original time span of three years, setting her future career path for a strategy consultant position. Though the researcher did not write a journal to document her progress during the three years, her draft documents that she updated several times represent a trail of the academic and cognitive progress that she witnessed during the journey. The many-times Eureka that she faced, inducing her to make structural and essential changes to her research, assert her constant dedication to complete her degree. Understanding the process of selecting a methodology that best answers the research was only achieved by changing the methodology three times. Similarly, updating the literature review twice does not seem now a negative by-product of a confused research mind felt back then. On the contrary, these transformative stages composed important steps that highlighted the commitment to improve the work consistently and contribute significantly to the field under study.

However, if more resources were available (time and financial), the researcher would have surveyed more entrepreneurs increasing the sample size and providing a more heterogeneous composition. Nevertheless, the delightful (though stressful) journey of such a prestigious academic degree has changed her on the cognitive, intellectual, and emotional levels. Hardworking nights combined with a switch in the professional domain (from auditing to customer service) had had their negative affective impact for the first two years but also revealed her unforeseen potential of emotional and cognitive endurance. The researcher's ability to work on several projects

simultaneously while still completing her degree without seeking (external or internal) support has shaped further her capacity to work academically and professionally under pressure. The insights gained from the field investigation enriched her reservoir of knowledge needed to act as an entrepreneur herself in the near future.

The initial aim of the journey to earn the title turned out to be the knowledge capacity behind that title.

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Appendix A: Experts' Interview Guide

Greeting and Introduction

- Explaining the role of the interviewee as a research student and introduce her professional and academic background

Aim of the Interview

- As outlined in the participant information sheet that I've sent you previously [via phone/via email], the reason behind my interest in interviewing you is related to my doctoral research on how Lebanese entrepreneurs reflect on failure and perceive their previous entrepreneurial experiences and how this would impact their perceived learning outcomes. The first stage of my research involves getting insights on the situation of entrepreneurial failure from experienced individuals like yourself. Since you are a professional expert [mention position] with a sound experience with entrepreneurs [name of the organisation] (if any), your perspectives on the field would be very contributory to this research.

Interview Ethics

- Before we begin, I would like to ask for your permission to audiotape the interview. If that's okay with you, I would then like to ask you to sign the consent form, to approve your willingness for participating in this study and for being recorded. However, I would like to re-assure you that all the opinions, perspectives and information given during this interview will remain confidential and anonymous. If you feel uncomfortable with any of the questions to be asked, please feel free to inform me and then we can skip it.
- I would like also to notify you that if you wanted to add any answers after the interview, please feel free to contact me [email or phone depending on the initial way of communication]. To preserve the spontaneity of answers, I will not send a summary of the narratives to you, unless you request for it. Would this be okay with you?
- Would you like to ask me any questions before we start the interview?

Interview Questions

- In your opinion and according to your experience, why Lebanese entrepreneurs are failing?
- How would you judge the **level of governmental support** in contributing to failure or to persistence of entrepreneurs in Lebanon?
- To which extent do you believe the **Lebanese ecosystem** has led to the failure of entrepreneurs?
- To what extent do you believe the **financing factor** was a contributing factor to the failure of these businesses?
- To what extent do you believe Lebanese entrepreneurs are **planning** to their entrepreneurial career? In terms of *perceiving the opportunity*, deciding *on the product or service*, and initiating *a plan and budget*?
- How would you judge the **managerial** and **entrepreneurial** knowledge and skills of Lebanese Entrepreneurs? And how would you judge **their efforts in expanding this knowledge**?
- How would you judge the role of **networks** for Lebanese entrepreneurs' persistence? And on the individual level, how would you judge their

awareness and **efforts** in expanding and seeking the help of networks of the Lebanese Entrepreneurs?

- To which extent do you believe Lebanese Entrepreneurs are **able, recognize** the relevance of and **execute** advertising for the sustainability of early seed businesses? (planning, budgeting, and running advertising)
- How contributory **is the human capital** recruited by Lebanese Entrepreneurs to their failure?
- How well entrepreneurs **plan** for their ventures and **understand the market** in which they will be operating?
- How would you judge the **level of technology** in contributing to failure or persistence of entrepreneurs?
- How would you judge the **level of support** (encouragement or discouragement) of the Lebanese culture (family and friends) to early entrepreneurs and serial entrepreneurs?

Exit of Interview

- Would you like to add any further points before we conclude the interview?
- Would it be okay for you if I contacted you later in case further clarification was needed?
- Would you like me to send you a copy of the transcripts or you don't mind me not doing so?
- Finally, would you recommend someone else who in your opinion might provide possess sound experience with entrepreneurs and can thus provide rich information for this research?
- Thank you so much for your valuable cooperation, time, and information.

Appendix B: Narrative Inquiry Guide

Greeting and Introduction

- Explaining the role of the interviewee as a research student and introduce her professional and academic background

Aim of the Interview

- As outlined in the participant information sheet that I have sent you previously [via phone/via email], the reason behind my interest in interviewing you is related to my doctoral research on how Lebanese entrepreneurs reflect on failure and perceive their previous entrepreneurial experiences and how this would impact their perceived learning outcomes. Since you are a founder and an entrepreneur of a prior business venture [name of the organisation] (if known previously) that you decided to exit, your reflection and story would be very contributory to this research.

Interview Ethics

- Before we begin, I would like to ask for your permission to audiotape the interview. If that's okay with you, I would then like to ask you to sign the consent form, to approve your willingness for participating in this study and for being recorded. However, I would like to re-assure you that all the opinions, perspectives and information given during this interview will remain confidential and anonymous. If you feel uncomfortable with any of the questions to be asked, please feel free to inform me and then we can skip it.
- I would like also to notify you that if you wanted to add any answers later, please feel free to contact me [email or phone depending on the initial way of communication]. To preserve the spontaneity of answers, I will not send a summary of the narratives to you, unless you specially request it. Would this be okay with you?
- Would you like to ask me any questions before we start the interview?

Interview Questions

- Sociodemographic details
 - Gender
 - Age
 - Educational background
 - Company's name
 - Organisation legal nature
 - Starting date
 - Discontinuation date
 - Year 1 Profit
 - Year 2 Profit
 - Before exit Profit
 - Compensation
 - Previous experience/occupation
 - Vision of the business
 - Nature of operations- industry
 - Perception of opportunity
- 'Would you please convey to me the story of your venture and how did it fail? What went wrong with the business?'

- For some issues raised (or missed), some follow-up questions by asking ‘How did you handle it then? Or what was the consequence of that decision?’
- ‘What did you learn from the experience’ and how would you describe your emotional status aftermath failure? How did you cope with it? [in case these points were not implied throughout the narratives]

Exit of Interview

- Would you like to add any further points before we conclude the interview?
- Would it be okay for you if I contacted you later in case further clarification was needed?
- Would you like me to send you a copy of the transcripts or you don’t mind me not doing so?
- Finally, would you recommend someone else who in your opinion might provide possess sound entrepreneurial experience and is willing to share their story with this research?
- Thank you so much for your valuable trust, time, and information.

Appendix C: Sample Thematic Analysis

Extracts	First-order Coding	Second-order Coding	Emerging Theme
<p>“Unfortunately, the Lebanese ecosystem still lacks a proper legal framework that supports venture capitalists. Moreover, this ecosystem is still financially immature, especially after the suspension of circular 331. So funds within Lebanon are not sufficient, and we don’t have financial markets” – Ex7.</p>	<p>Low level of venture capitalism Immature Ecosystem Insufficient debt funding</p>	<p>Limited availability of Debt Funding</p>	<p>Access and Availability of Funds</p>
<p>“The funds available to entrepreneurs are limited nowadays to 5-10% of the total number of financing applications initially admitted to incubators” – Ex3.</p>	<p>Limited capacity of accelerators</p>	<p>Limited Availability of Equity Funding</p>	
<p>“Financing is a problem for start-ups given the need for collateral and a proper business plan [...] established businesses are in a better position as they can prove their ability to repay” – Ex1.</p>	<p>Difficult Admission criteria for debt financing Insufficient Business Planning</p>		

The table above represents a sample of the thematic analysis applied to the interviews of industry experts.

Appendix D: Sample Narrative Analysis

Step 1: Identifying categories (Edwards, 2016) through colour coding (Iyengar, 2014)

I graduated in 2012 and started immediately a full-time position as a junior designer at ██████ in Beirut. At the same time, I was offered to do some freelancing projects with the ██████ at some point, I realised that I cannot keep up with both types of work, and I started losing interest in my full-time job. I worked there for 1 year and 11 months, until I decided to quit my job and work as a freelancer. ██████ at the same time was helping me with some animation features given that he likes animation. He graduated as well from the same university as an engineer, but he couldn't manage to find a job, so he decided to re-major with an animation course online. And so, we were working together on few projects jointly, having one every few months. Then, as the workload increased gradually, and while ██████ mastered the animations part, we asked another friend of us, ██████, to join us given his background in music, as this was a requirement for some of the ██████. ██████ later developed an interest in the animations' part, and he started learning from ██████. Then, we decided to present ourselves officially as ██████, but you know how expensive it is in Lebanon to register a company, so we never claimed to be a company as we didn't have the money to even register it. When we first thought about the idea, we decided to see a lawyer that we actually went to, in order to form a legally registered company. But we realised that it costs a fortune and am glad that we didn't register because it was a bad idea anyway. Then, we were doing few animations projects for some NGOs, before engaging in advertising projects. (to the researcher: I don't know whether you had a look at our projects). In fact before engaging with projects other than ██████, we developed ██████ and we submitted it to ██████ for few months who offered us a workspace and assistance, but all three of us are introvert, so we didn't engage with anyone (laughs a lot). I used to help the guys there with some design requests, but we never asked anything from anyone, anyway we are not the kind of people who would ask for anything, so we didn't ask for financing, or anything else. Word started to spread about our animations, and this how others were recognising us; then, we put it on Zoomal (a crowdfunding platform), but we didn't collect any money (laughs again). We didn't know how to advertise for ourselves, we didn't know how to do many things properly. The accelerator surely provided us with some help but we still lacked a lot. So, we didn't raise any funds, and we just did one episode ██████ which took us around 6 months (laughs a lot when mentioned the period). We were actually occupying my room with a table in the middle. It was a really nice idea that I would have loved to keep working on it if that was feasible. Everyone advises and says yeah do this and do that, reach the stars, but the ugly truth is that without funds you can't actually do anything (laughs again). So, this ██████ reflects how we try to fix things ourselves (as Lebanese), and so when we submitted the trailer to Beirut Design Week. a decision maker there offered us her

Step 2: Holistic Content Analysis – Re-storying the narratives to create narrative accounts (Beal, 2013)

Original Extract – Raw Story	Re-storied Excerpt – Narrative Account
<p>Honestly, one of my main weaknesses is that I used and am still working as a one man show. And I didn't have funds to manage the structure of my business. It was a big pressure the work and the life troubles in Lebanon. So it's like running continuously without stop. So I needed to manage myself properly before managing my business. And always my excuse was always the lack of funds, blaming the lack of money and the continuous thinking about money for the lack in proper self-management and business management</p>	<p>He attributed failure to his mistake in centralising the workload. He made the connection clear between the lack of funds and its negative impact on his intention to structure his business. Additionally, he explained how the lack of funds was used as a self-justification for the lack of management and organisation.</p>

The table represents a comparison of an extract from the original story of one entrepreneur (En6) and the narrative account that was developed from the re-story created by the research

The figure above depicts a sample scheme from En6 that represents the various relationships revealed among the different categories emerging within a single story holistically.

Step 3: Categorical Content Analysis – identifying categories from the raw stories to identify similarities and differences across accounts (Earthy and Cronin, 2008).

En6 (unfunded – novice)	En4 – (funded – novice)	En8 – (funded – serial)
Centralisation of decisions – lack of delegation – not enough trusting quality of work of staff	Decentralisation of ideas and decisions – engaging others in decision-making	Decentralisation of decision – appropriate delegation of staff
No formal marketing plan – overreliance on social media and social networks (weak and strong)	Formal Marketing plan was developed but not executed due to the lack of funds	Marketing was executed properly according to a formal plan with dedicated staff
Started with strong networks but then expanded to weak networks developed from earlier experience	Weak networks were developed personally through earlier experience and were assistive	Weak networks were much helpful and developed from previous experience
Recruitment executed from a social assistance perspective	Recruitment was very formal and strict	Recruitment was done very professionally

Appendix E: Ethical Clearance

12/08/2019

Dear Ms. Ghiwa Dandach,

Your application 8065: Investigating the discontinuation of early seed SMEs in Lebanon, submission 6945, has been approved by the Business and Enterprise SEC .
You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Mr D McFadzean

Appendix F: Evaluation of Learning Frameworks

Rae and Carswell (2000)

Rae and Carswell (2000) developed a framework of entrepreneurial learning composed of five main themes (personal theory, known capabilities, personal values, social relations, and active learning), which emerged from analysing the narratives of thirteen “exceptional performers”. As outlined in the picture below, the framework focused on the learning episodes (periods of their lives) that were deemed mostly significant by the entrepreneurs. The model reflected the connections among these themes and how they reflect on entrepreneurial learning, revealing how individuals learn by creating senses from each theme and resources associated within each:

- Personal values, self-efficacy, and goal achievement: the motivation of entrepreneurs to achieve the ambitious goals that they set for themselves encouraged their learning behaviour, in consistence with McClelland (1961). This ‘teleological’ process of self-efficacy supported Bird’s (1988) argument of self-belief in realising the goal setting.
- Personal theory: under this theme, entrepreneurs developed four main subthemes that emerged as important principles to accomplish goals: human capital management, business growth by keeping an eye on the market, vision and planning accompanied by decision-making, and finally the balance between keeping control and loosening control. This theme is found significant for entrepreneurial learning, because when entrepreneurs understand their own decision-making process and develop it as a basis for their results, the outcome may tend to be more effective.
- Known capabilities: entrepreneurs tended to develop and expand the skills they are mostly confident with, as well as the ones judged as relevant to their aspired careers. In this process of self-growth and skills’ enhancement, entrepreneurs became more aware of their own weaknesses and areas for improvement.
- Active learning: the entrepreneurs’ ability to learn in an active approach represented a critical part of the whole learning process, taking into consideration the speed of active learning and implementation of this learning.
- Social learning: social connections provided a learning opportunity for entrepreneurs that they have exploited properly and hence learned from their relationships: family ties, mentors, educational ties, successful entrepreneurs, etc.

The model proposed by Rae and Carswell (2000) has important implications for knowledge, as well as for the practice. Through this model, the process of entrepreneurial learning is revealed as an interaction between the personal theory and the known capabilities, along with the social learning from individual relationships and willingness to actively learn, and to energise the personal values leading eventually to the achievement of goals. An interesting point about this framework is the equal weight of each theme, rather than the dominance of one theme over others. Entrepreneurs might refer to the themes explored as an initiating step to reflect on their own experience, in a structured rather than a random way. The result would be a greater comprehension of their own processes and experiences as well as resources. However, given the peculiarity of the experience of failure and its strong impact on entrepreneurs, emotionally, behaviourally, and cognitively (Shepherd and Cardon, 2009; Ucbasaran *et al.*, 2013), not all steps can be adopted in the same structure. More specifically, the model enhances the entrepreneurs' ability of reaching venture goals (Rae and Carswell, 2000) rather than recovering from failure, such as the grief recovery developed by Cope (2011) and reflecting on the experience insightfully. Nonetheless, from this model, the themes of active learning, given its necessity for an effective learning to occur (Stam *et al.*, 2006), social learning, given the assistance provided by the networks in reflecting on learning (Amankwah-Amoah *et al.*, 2018), and the personal theory which constitutes the main mode upon which the reflection

process occurs (Minniti and Bygrave, 2001; Sarasvathy, 2001) will be adopted for the current study.

Rae (2005)

By investigating a series of life-stories narratives over two years for three emerging entrepreneurs, Rae (2005) developed a tridiac entrepreneurial learning framework that reveals the various aspects affecting entrepreneurial learning. The findings came up with three key themes, according to the participants' accounts. The first theme identified was the 'personal and social emergence' which relates to the entrepreneurs' attempt to develop their identity and self-sense, as well as future goals, from and within their social context (families and social connections, academic and professional). The second theme is the relevance of context to the entrepreneurial process; individuals learn by participating in social, professional, and other types of contexts. Through this immersion, learning occurs as individuals relate, compare, and share their experiences to construct meanings. The last theme relates to the notion of the negotiated enterprise. According to Rae (2005), entrepreneurial formation occurs through negotiated connections with others, rather than by a single person. By engaging in interactive relations with others, individuals may be more able to realise their ambitions, and these social connections may include any stakeholder of the venture. For the learning to successfully happen in this case, the ability of entrepreneurs to engage with people is highly significant (Wenger, 1998).

Despite establishing the connection between the context and the entrepreneur for the sake of learning from entrepreneurial experiences, the lack of the consideration of cognition makes the model incomparable to the cognitive theory (Mitchell *et al.*, 2002; Shepherd and Krueger, 2002), which suggests a rational exploration of entrepreneurial learning. This framework was rather built on Wenger's (1998) social theory of learning (as well as other social constructionists such as Shotter, 1993, and Gergen, 1999). The contribution of this model from a socially constructivist perspective shall not be ignored or undervalued, as up till the date of this framework, theories that investigated the entrepreneurial learning overlooked the social constructivism ground, and focused on the cognitive explanation (Rae, 2005). However, this model was developed based on the entrepreneurial experience with no special consideration to the failure experience, which necessitates more of a combined approach of cognition and social constructivism, to allow for the embracing of the rational, as well as the emotional reflection on failure (Ucbasaran *et al.*, 2013; Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015).

Politis (2005)

In their discussion of entrepreneurial learning, Reuber *et al.* (1990) differentiated between two main concepts: entrepreneurial knowledge and entrepreneurial experience. The entrepreneurial experience is the participation of entrepreneurs in creating a new business, whereas entrepreneurial knowledge is the pragmatic understanding that emerges from the encounters within the experience. In investigating how the entrepreneurial experience generates knowledge, Politis (2005) suggested that scholars need to understand the mode of transformation employed by entrepreneurs, and which factors influence this mode of processing. As the learning process is not acquired automatically as a consequence for having entrepreneurial experience, the transformation process holds the weight for the whole process, by generating the knowledge from that experience (Kolb, 1984). This transformation process can be integrated with the notion of experiential learning that suggests first, developing a representation of the experience, before transforming this representation later into knowledge (Kolb, 1984). Based on this notion, the learning process is consequently a continuous process that is created and recreated (Holmqvist, 2000).

Despite the relevance of this model to the current study, especially in its two dimensions the development of entrepreneurial knowledge and the transformation process leading to the development of this knowledge, this model is, first, built on the basis of the experiential learning theory and second, lacks the integration of emotions resulting from the experience of failure in particular. In spite of its influential contribution to the field of entrepreneurial learning, the experiential theory of learning reflects only on few factors that led to the failure, besides decontextualizing the learning process (Kayes, 2002). Furthermore, the sequential process of the experiential learning ignores the intuitive capacity of entrepreneurs, usually developed over many concrete experiences, and adopted when faced with critical occurrences (Baron, 1998). Hence, the experiential learning process is not deemed very relevant to embrace the complexity of uncertainties faced by entrepreneurs (Politis, 2005).

Petkova (2008)

By developing a conceptual model of entrepreneurial learning from performance errors, Petkova (2008) outlined how errors detected in performance can be a significant source of learning for entrepreneurs. The model adopts the cognitive theory and hence proposes three processes that generate the learning: outcome generation, error detection and error correction. By correcting their errors, entrepreneurs either specialise their general knowledge structures or refine these specialisations.

Despite its comprehensiveness and contribution into understanding the process with which entrepreneurs learn from their errors, this model is essentially conceptual, focusing on the performance errors resulting from the knowledge possessed by the entrepreneurs, and limited the discussion and integration of attribution to the biases generated by individuals: self-serving bias and attributional style.

Cope (2011)

Cope provided a comprehensive explanatory model of the failure, outlining how the learning is processed. It started with handling the costs resulting from failure, recovering from grief, and then reflecting over the failure to generate higher levels of learning.

Despite the comprehensiveness of this framework, the attribution in its various dimensions during the reflective process associated with the loss orientation was not explored. Therefore, this process, despite its influential contribution into the field, cannot be wholly adopted in this study. However, the levels of learning, the learning outcomes, and the processes of reflecting on failure will be borrowed from this model.

Heinze (2013)

The process developed by Heinze (2013) cultivates from the need to understand the process of making sense from failure. The model suggests that entrepreneurs do not only experience failure economically, but also in every aspect of their lives. By interviewing five entrepreneurs, the research concluded that social interactions trigger strong emotions, some of them last disappear after a while (e.g. grief, confusion, worrying about financial costs), whereas more long-lasting emotions persist (e.g. distrust and betrayal).

Despite its contribution into understanding the sense-making of the failure experience, this process mainly concentrated on the emotional dimension of the failure, and the resulting coping mechanism with these emotions. Therefore, such bounded focus of the emotions may not be relevant to the current study, investigating the attributions and their impact on the learning process.

Yamakawa *et al.* (2015)

The authors developed a model that reveals the impact of the internal attributions for failure, as a learning mechanism that leads to subsequent venturing pursuit. Though concluding that the internal attribution generates greater learning, which ultimately

enhances the performance of subsequent entrepreneurial endeavours, this benefit is dependent on the motivation of entrepreneurs positively, and on the number of previous failures negatively. In other words, the greater the motivation and/or the

Theoretical Model

lower the number of previous failures, the higher the knowledge to be created from the previous experiences (Yamakawa *et al.*, 2015).

Despite the contribution of this model in understanding the impact of internal attribution into the effectiveness of learning cognitively, and specifically subsequent venturing, it categorises the internal attribution as a statistical variable, without further exploration on what factors fall under this attribution. Therefore, the statistical approach of the internal attribution within this model without deep exploration of what is considered as internal, its focus on serial entrepreneurs and subsequent venturing, and the major cultural variance within both study contexts (Japan vs. Lebanon) make this model less relevant to explore the attribution of entrepreneurs in Lebanon.

Yamakawa and Cardon (2015)

Yamakawa and Cardon (2015) developed a learning model that outlines the impact of internal and external ascriptions of failure, as perceived by entrepreneurs, on the learning outcomes. Two moderators were considered impactful on the learning process: time taken by entrepreneurs to restart; and abandoning the domain of prior business. The authors focused on the second stage of critical reflection, in the three-step process suggested by Cope (2011), arguing that this stage holds the most weight for improving entrepreneurial learning, more than the first stage of separating the oneself from the failure and the third stage of taking reflective actions. When

entrepreneurs engage in a reflective process on their mistakes, people focus on attributing causes for these wrongdoings, which will eventually prevent repeating them again as a form of learning. This model suggests that the attributing the failure to internal and unstable dimensions, combined with shorter time to re-embark in future venturing, improves entrepreneurial learning. On the other hand, the external ascriptions alone, attached to changing the domain hinder the effective form of learning (Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015).

Though contributing to the gap of understanding how entrepreneurs ascribe failure and the impact of these ascriptions to the learning outcomes, the developed model did not consider the hybrid attribution that can be perceived by entrepreneurs and explained the internal attribution statistically, without exploration into its components and dimensions. Additionally, the cultural variance of the context (Japan) make this model less explanatory of the dimensions of attributions in a less emerging context.

Walsh and Cunningham (2017)

The authors developed a model that outlines the process of learning from failure, which eventually leads to the regeneration step, defined as reengagement in entrepreneurial activities. The model emerged from investigating the linkage between attribution and learning on three levels: internal, external and hybrid; the responses associated with each level leading to the learning dimensions and resulting from each agree with to Cope's (2011) model.

Despite its contribution to the field in scrutinising the learning from failure, especially by highlighting the impact of failure attributions on emotional, cognitive, and behavioural responses, this study overlooked the interaction and interconnection among the various levels of resulted learning. In other words, the learning dimensions may not possess clear-cut boundaries across the learning dimensions; for instance, external attributions are linked strictly to learning about networks and relationships, while the reflection on the market may also result in better understanding of the market operations, which will lead to better management of the marketing, sales and growth functions, hence venture management. Furthermore, and more importantly, the nature of attributions applied for this model does not agree with the direction of this research. In other words, the inadequate market research was ascribed externally, whereas an internal attribution would have been more appropriate if this improper market research is the result of a lack in marketing skills and appreciation. However, this study provided the justification for future studies to emphasise on the individual experiences of entrepreneurs with failure, to understand further the complex shades connecting attributions and learning.

Amankwah-Amoah *et al.* (2018)

In investigating how the learning and imprinting processes of entrepreneurs from failure impact the nature of subsequent ventures, Amankwah-Amoah *et al.* (2018) contributed to the field by developing the evolutionary phase framework that outlines

the transitional mechanisms of failure on the processes, behaviours and routines of business ventures.

Amankwah-Amoah *et al.* (2018) concluded that four phases exist, subsequent to the failure imprinting influence:

- Grief and despair: in this phase, entrepreneurs undergo a reflective process to make sense of the failure, loaded with grief and loss of hope. Throughout this phase, and despite the negative emotions' impact on individuals' decisions (Shepherd, 2003), entrepreneurs learned more about the nature of partnership relations, as well as the resources and skills required to undertake a new venture.
- Transition: following on the grief and despair exhibited in the first phase, this stage focuses on conceptualising new ideas and reconfiguring resources for new ventures (Yamakawa and Cardon, 2015). For instance, the networks developed from the failure boosted the imprinting influence on the entrepreneurial abilities to identify new business opportunities.
- Formation: the previously developed knowledge, emotions and cognitions are integrated into the new venture and its operating environment. The window of 'imprintability' (Marquis and Tilcsik, 2013) was mostly established within this phase, exhibited by the extreme determination of entrepreneurs to surmount the stigmatisation resulting from failure.
- Legacy: in this stage, emerge the failure-inspired processes and strategies, by avoiding the factors that contributed to the initial failure. Entrepreneurs' perceptions of prior failures, as well as their beliefs and values, are therefore imprinted within the new business culture, strategy and values (Zheng, 2012).

Despite its relevance, this model focuses on the imprinting processes in subsequent venturing and therefore, is less relevant to this study that focuses on the second phase more thoroughly. However, in this stage, the model did not take into consideration the role of attribution during the transition, and its impact in conceptualising and learning.

Wei *et al.* (2019)

By examining twenty-four factors that were suggested to influence the entrepreneurial learning process from failure, Wei *et al.* (2019) developed a structural, hierarchical model of the most fifteen impactful factors. According to this model, entrepreneurial learning seems to be directly impacted by the self-efficacy of entrepreneurs and their regulatory process of emotions. Social capital and psychological capital impact the process in an indirect way, by improving the self-efficacy factor, while the psychological capital can be enhanced, through prior failure experience and entrepreneurial education. The regulation of emotions is directly impacted by personality traits, entrepreneurial expectations of failure and their sense of failure. The conditions of the environment seem to impact the entrepreneurs' forecasting of failure, similarly as the influence of the cultural sense-making on the sense of failure. The macro-environment of business ventures seems to be less impactful on entrepreneurial learning, including the economic conditions, the familial and institutional support, and the characteristics of the industry.

Though this study identified the key factors affecting directly or indirectly the learning from failure, it cannot be employed in this study as it does not reflect the process with which the individual factors are elaborated, connected and integrated into the learning process.